

Best Sequence	Prec MW	Prec m/z	Theor MW	Theor m/z	Prec m/z
NPKFPELN	974.4433	488.2289	974.4709	974.4709	974.4709
SVGLRGYGQLNPL	1388.6615	695.338	1388.7412	1388.7412	1388.7412
NQPVVQLPE	1024.5543	513.2844	1024.5077	1024.5077	1024.5077
VQEPQIPV	925.4859	463.7502	925.4756	925.4756	925.4756
MEDPLPLYP	1105.5393	553.7769	1105.5001	1105.5001	1105.5001
KSELVLPQ	913.4099	457.7122	913.512	913.512	913.512
PTDPILQILP	1137.6305	569.8225	1137.6282	1137.6282	1137.6282
MEDPLPLYP	1105.5363	553.7754	1105.5001	1105.5001	1105.5001
AVPGPSQPAAPKPGQSGL	1675.7379	838.8762	1675.8417	1675.8417	1675.8417
EDPIQAQPVLP	1237.7114	619.863	1237.619	1237.619	1237.619
MPPLKPLPT	1024.5543	513.2844	1024.5627	1024.5627	1024.5627
MEDPLPLYP	1105.5363	553.7754	1105.5001	1105.5001	1105.5001
SVGLPGLSVERN	1388.66	695.3373	1388.7147	1388.7147	1388.7147
QVLPPSQNPVP	1191.6791	596.8468	1191.6135	1191.6135	1191.6135
NQPVVQLPE	1024.5543	513.2844	1024.5077	1024.5077	1024.5077
ATLDGLSNGRAQVML	1561.7661	781.8903	1561.777	1561.777	1561.777
QVLPPSQNPVP	1191.6791	596.8468	1191.6135	1191.6135	1191.6135
AVDRIGIPGSNF	1276.6337	639.3241	1276.6411	1276.6411	1276.6411
NELPGLPQYDVL	1388.66	695.3373	1388.6824	1388.6824	1388.6824
AVAPNIEPVPN	1135.6571	568.8358	1135.5873	1135.5873	1135.5873
MPSGPIPP	826.4037	414.2091	826.3895	826.3895	826.3895
LISEPPLQVLP	1236.7039	619.3592	1236.6965	1236.6965	1236.6965
PLLTAPQPGV	991.5059	496.7602	991.5703	991.5703	991.5703
QDEVPLPKHLPQ	1432.7474	717.381	1432.7198	1432.7198	1432.7198
NTPYP	0	747.3634	746.3599	746.3599	746.3599
RAVLPTVQPV	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.6499	1078.6499	1078.6499
LGLGNIGPAGGLP	1132.5463	567.2804	1134.6396	1134.6396	1134.6396
GSSIMPGKINPV	1198.6255	600.32	1198.6379	1198.6379	1198.6379
RVLDVIPPIGG	1135.6571	568.8358	1135.6602	1135.6602	1135.6602
SIGVILIVIPL	1135.6571	568.8358	1135.7581	1135.7581	1135.7581
DMILMPII	946.5385	474.2765	944.5075	944.5075	944.5075
VGGVIIDA	0	743.388	742.4225	742.4225	742.4225
GNGQGKGIEEI	1102.5146	552.2646	1102.5143	1102.5143	1102.5143
IAVIPLLP	0	439.2881	876.5684	876.5684	876.5684
IQMIVLPVV	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.7039	1123.7039	1123.7039
NPASNLPYLP	1086.613	544.3138	1086.5233	1086.5233	1086.5233
VSVGLPGL	0	757.4025	756.4382	756.4382	756.4382
VRGILADGV	898.4835	450.249	898.5236	898.5236	898.5236
GPFIPT	0	631.3415	630.3377	630.3377	630.3377
GPAGPT	0	499.2426	498.2438	498.2438	498.2438
SVGLRGYGQLNPL	1388.6615	695.338	1388.7412	1388.7412	1388.7412
QEPVIGVP	0	821.4327	820.433	820.433	820.433
QNLMEIL	972.5011	487.2578	972.5314	972.5314	972.5314
LLAVRVVKPID	1222.6869	612.3507	1222.7649	1222.7649	1222.7649
LGAGAVGALLLSAN	1433.7515	717.883	1433.7643	1433.7643	1433.7643
HLPLIP	0	689.4285	688.4272	688.4272	688.4272

VTADLPEV	858.4435	430.229	858.4335	858.4335	858.4335
DIYVIGIPI	1001.5475	501.781	1001.5797	1001.5797	1001.5797
LDAVPLDFA	959.5069	480.7607	959.4964	959.4964	959.4964
GEGPLIQAMSRTN	1388.6615	695.338	1388.6718	1388.6718	1388.6718
ALAIAPDTAMGLGR	1372.6417	687.3281	1372.702	1372.702	1372.702
IDMLDL	718.3923	360.2034	718.3571	718.3571	718.3571
LISEPPLQVLP	1220.6841	611.3493	1220.7017	1220.7017	1220.7017
AILPKNVLDIDLPVP	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
FTGIPQ	0	662.3212	661.3435	661.3435	661.3435
PGATTPGNWLIG	1199.5377	600.7761	1199.5823	1199.5823	1199.5823
AILPKNVLDIDLPVP	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
ATAGAAVLA	0	744.3466	743.4177	743.4177	743.4177
TNQPVVQLPE	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.5873	1123.5873	1123.5873
IFISHALQNPQL	1379.7363	460.9194	1379.7561	1379.7561	1379.7561
ATLDGLSNGRAQVML	1561.7661	781.8903	1561.777	1561.777	1561.777
NTPYP	0	747.3657	746.3599	746.3599	746.3599
GVVGLIGPNG	898.4835	450.249	898.476	898.476	898.476
KRGLKNIPVV	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.7078	1123.7078	1123.7078
GAVPKIQ	0	713.4139	712.4119	712.4119	712.4119
GGANAP	0	528.2203	527.2339	527.2339	527.2339
FAPNFLAI	891.4463	446.7304	891.4854	891.4854	891.4854
IDAVE	0	546.2748	545.2697	545.2697	545.2697
VFPADIP	1514.8088	758.4117	757.4011	757.4011	757.4011
QVPAEPIP	977.55	489.7823	977.5182	977.5182	977.5182
GLAKAVVAVAGGVLP	1433.7515	717.883	1433.8606	1433.8606	1433.8606
GLAKAVVAVAGGVLPVAV	1561.8145	781.9145	1561.9556	1561.9556	1561.9556
ATAPAAV	0	616.285	615.3228	615.3228	615.3228
DIGTTTMVDQ	1079.4193	540.7169	1079.4805	1079.4805	1079.4805
MLTDILP	801.5057	401.7601	801.4306	801.4306	801.4306
VALGPA	0	527.2801	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
PTQPAVAVKP	1006.5083	504.2614	1006.5811	1006.5811	1006.5811
NTPYP	0	747.3617	746.3599	746.3599	746.3599
SGIDGA	0	519.2358	518.2336	518.2336	518.2336
FCDVEP	0	675.2765	674.2911	674.2911	674.2911
IGELAVQEGEQILQ	1526.6888	764.3517	1526.7828	1526.7828	1526.7828
LDPNPLV	0	767.4228	766.4225	766.4225	766.4225
IVGGP	0	442.2647	441.2587	441.2587	441.2587
NPDILAMTATPIPR	0	755.3907	1508.8021	1508.8021	1508.8021
ASLPVPQ	0	753.4456	752.4069	752.4069	752.4069
NPDILAMTATPIPR	0	755.3888	1508.8021	1508.8021	1508.8021
FIDELFLP	992.4518	497.2332	992.5219	992.5219	992.5219
DVPQGLPNVV	1036.5359	519.2752	1036.5553	1036.5553	1036.5553
GAVPKIQ	0	713.4128	712.4119	712.4119	712.4119
MVPKVLPLP	1024.5543	513.2844	1024.5991	1024.5991	1024.5991
LGLPQITENVLQLL	1550.8182	776.4164	1550.892	1550.892	1550.892
DEKDAAAQQ	974.3331	488.1738	974.4305	974.4305	974.4305
QGGSFLEFPYQ	0	555.2437	1108.4713	1108.4713	1108.4713

ISAGIPQ	0	685.4194	684.3806	684.3806	684.3806
LLMLIVVPNLN	1237.7114	619.863	1237.7468	1237.7468	1237.7468
GVGVPQ	0	556.3035	555.3016	555.3016	555.3016
AKTIRVPKPV	1135.6571	568.8358	1135.7078	1135.7078	1135.7078
FIDELFLP	992.4518	497.2332	992.5219	992.5219	992.5219
QEPVIGVP	0	821.4354	820.433	820.433	820.433
RVGPQ	0	556.3049	555.3129	555.3129	555.3129
VALGI	0	472.2744	471.3057	471.3057	471.3057
LDGVLRP	768.4725	385.2435	768.4494	768.4494	768.4494
LLDAATTAIPGPL	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7074	1251.7074	1251.7074
DVRDMFLIP	1104.5513	553.2829	1104.5637	1104.5637	1104.5637
NLSVMPSGPIPP	1224.6771	613.3458	1224.6061	1224.6061	1224.6061
NLPYP	0	747.3632	746.3599	746.3599	746.3599
GIAPAV	0	527.2776	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
SEPLAEIK	885.4695	443.742	885.4808	885.4808	885.4808
LPQIPNG	737.4419	369.7282	737.4072	737.4072	737.4072
EDPIQAQPVLP LN	1432.7474	717.381	1432.7562	1432.7562	1432.7562
AELEKLLPE	1040.5349	521.2747	1040.5753	1040.5753	1040.5753
DYLPNLKDE	1105.5393	553.7769	1105.5292	1105.5292	1105.5292
PVPAVPQKGV	991.5059	496.7602	991.5703	991.5703	991.5703
TIGGVNFFTQ	1082.6029	542.3087	1082.5397	1082.5397	1082.5397
TPDQPELPEV	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.5397	1123.5397	1123.5397
ILQVLNNLIP	1136.6395	569.327	1136.6805	1136.6805	1136.6805
AGSQPR	614.3465	308.1805	614.3136	614.3136	614.3136
APAYK	548.4001	275.2073	548.2958	548.2958	548.2958
MMGTGAGVLA	906.4879	303.1699	906.4303	906.4303	906.4303
AHGALV	566.3137	284.1641	566.3176	566.3176	566.3176
KSGKPV	614.3465	308.1805	614.3752	614.3752	614.3752
HVAH	462.2532	232.1339	462.2339	462.2339	462.2339
AGGTVS	490.2939	246.1542	490.2387	490.2387	490.2387
GHPGGA	494.304	248.1593	494.2238	494.2238	494.2238
GGSGSGK	548.4001	275.2073	548.2554	548.2554	548.2554
FGAEK	550.3031	276.1588	550.2751	550.2751	550.2751
CHPKRAVP	906.4879	303.1699	906.4858	906.4858	906.4858
NCAK	434.2834	218.149	434.1948	434.1948	434.1948
AFAGP	461.2303	231.6224	461.2274	461.2274	461.2274
AGPSR	486.313	244.1638	486.255	486.255	486.255
AGSGLGR	616.3383	309.1764	616.3293	616.3293	616.3293
EGTGK	490.2939	246.1542	490.2387	490.2387	490.2387
LAACGSK	614.3465	308.1805	614.3387	614.3387	614.3387
ETGH	424.1342	213.0744	424.1707	424.1707	424.1707
VNVLWTFGDAAKVADVG	0	459.0965	1831.9469	1831.9469	1831.9469
PDGH	424.134	213.0743	424.1707	424.1707	424.1707
PHSE	468.2213	235.1179	468.1969	468.1969	468.1969
IACIR	574.3911	288.2028	574.3261	574.3261	574.3261
EFGV	450.293	226.1538	450.2115	450.2115	450.2115
AGIMK	518.3791	260.1968	518.2886	518.2886	518.2886

GALIYMRIH	0	269.1586	1072.5852	1072.5852	1072.5852
GAQNGV	544.1309	273.0727	544.2605	544.2605	544.2605
AESGV	0	462.2346	461.2122	461.2122	461.2122
VIKALAIQP	0	525.3364	1048.6644	1048.6644	1048.6644
FSSE	468.2213	235.1179	468.1856	468.1856	468.1856
NRAF	506.3091	254.1618	506.2601	506.2601	506.2601
EYGF	514.2041	258.1093	514.2064	514.2064	514.2064
IACIR	574.3911	288.2028	574.3261	574.3261	574.3261
AGTNP	0	294.1811	586.3075	586.3075	586.3075
TLGTHAFIHP	0	365.1036	1092.5717	1092.5717	1092.5717
HLDTVF	0	366.2138	730.365	730.365	730.365
ATSHKLH	0	397.217	792.4243	792.4243	792.4243
ATKIGIGPGK	0	471.29	940.5706	940.5706	940.5706
QIKDKPLK	0	485.3056	968.6019	968.6019	968.6019
AFIS	436.2506	219.1326	436.2322	436.2322	436.2322
PHSE	468.3148	235.1647	468.1969	468.1969	468.1969
KMIK	518.3788	260.1967	518.325	518.325	518.325
ATGGIRTPADVIKS	0	347.1918	1384.7675	1384.7675	1384.7675
KTMVDQ	720.3557	361.1851	720.3476	720.3476	720.3476
IAWGILGLVAV	0	371.241	1110.6802	1110.6802	1110.6802
GASIFGGPG	761.4105	381.7125	761.3708	761.3708	761.3708
IHDESEVH	964.4659	483.2402	964.425	964.425	964.425
LAPQP	0	525.3386	524.2958	524.2958	524.2958
PSNCS	506.3091	254.1618	506.1795	506.1795	506.1795
FINQ	520.2737	261.1441	520.2645	520.2645	520.2645
AGFRV	548.3281	275.1713	548.3071	548.3071	548.3071
DPMEQ	0	310.1119	618.2319	618.2319	618.2319
HPEISF	728.3823	365.1984	728.3494	728.3494	728.3494
FCLIHP	728.3823	365.1984	728.368	728.368	728.368
AGDVV	0	460.2004	459.2329	459.2329	459.2329
LGEN	0	489.2292	488.2231	488.2231	488.2231
GNGLP	456.222	229.1183	456.2332	456.2332	456.2332
FSCI	468.3148	235.1647	468.2043	468.2043	468.2043
DMID	492.2448	247.1297	492.189	492.189	492.189
GASMISK	692.3509	347.1827	692.3527	692.3527	692.3527
DLDYAF	742.3961	372.2053	742.3174	742.3174	742.3174
GDGNVSGGV	761.4105	381.7125	761.3192	761.3192	761.3192
DSAVV	0	490.2124	489.2435	489.2435	489.2435
QSEVV	0	561.2478	560.2806	560.2806	560.2806
VAVGGV	500.2892	251.1519	500.2958	500.2958	500.2958
AGEAPA	514.2041	258.1093	514.2387	514.2387	514.2387
AGFRV	548.3281	275.1713	548.3071	548.3071	548.3071
AVGLCGV	583.3359	292.6752	583.3329	583.3329	583.3329
YEVAH	617.3197	309.6671	617.2809	617.2809	617.2809
PEFNEK	778.4097	390.2121	778.3497	778.3497	778.3497
AGDVV	0	460.202	459.2329	459.2329	459.2329
DFSP	0	465.2	464.1907	464.1907	464.1907

DVNE	0	476.1605	475.1914	475.1914	475.1914
CLVEN	0	577.2405	576.2578	576.2578	576.2578
QCVF	428.2621	215.1383	428.1729	428.1729	428.1729
GPGVQ	456.222	229.1183	456.2332	456.2332	456.2332
VFID	492.2448	247.1297	492.2584	492.2584	492.2584
FIEI	520.2737	261.1441	520.2897	520.2897	520.2897
VYNQ	522.2603	262.1374	522.2438	522.2438	522.2438
VGSVVV	558.2583	280.1364	558.3377	558.3377	558.3377
EKTPELE	0	423.1944	844.4178	844.4178	844.4178
ESAAI	0	490.213	489.2435	489.2435	489.2435
DGNLQELATIERSKSFES	0	675.327	2022.9858	2022.9858	2022.9858
CLVV	432.2953	217.1549	432.2406	432.2406	432.2406
GNPSY	536.196	269.1053	536.2231	536.2231	536.2231
GIAPAVG	583.3359	292.6752	583.3329	583.3329	583.3329
QDVLAVDINEEPV	0	361.1712	1440.6984	1440.6984	1440.6984
GSLAIGDF	778.4097	390.2121	778.3861	778.3861	778.3861
RSFRSQ	780.3689	391.1917	780.3879	780.3879	780.3879
DNVE	0	476.1575	475.1914	475.1914	475.1914
ILIPGSKPPK	0	525.3337	1048.6644	1048.6644	1048.6644
AGEVAP	0	543.239	542.27	542.27	542.27
TDVEN	0	577.2454	576.2391	576.2391	576.2391
DVVP	428.2632	215.1389	428.2271	428.2271	428.2271
FGNGV	492.2448	247.1297	492.2332	492.2332	492.2332
IFDE	522.2603	262.1374	522.2326	522.2326	522.2326
AGDVVV	558.2583	280.1364	558.3013	558.3013	558.3013
SSKGKV	0	303.1662	604.3544	604.3544	604.3544
AQTLGE	617.3197	309.6671	617.3021	617.3021	617.3021
AGSTIGK	0	317.1822	632.3494	632.3494	632.3494
IQLNGAP	711.4105	356.7125	711.3915	711.3915	711.3915
QSGNIDVMQYL	0	423.1957	1266.5914	1266.5914	1266.5914
EEIRE	0	675.3268	674.3235	674.3235	674.3235
CIVV	432.2953	217.1549	432.2406	432.2406	432.2406
GAVGSS	476.1873	239.1009	476.2231	476.2231	476.2231
FIEI	520.2737	261.1441	520.2897	520.2897	520.2897
NAPPND	0	314.0912	626.266	626.266	626.266
NFVIDN	0	361.1697	720.3442	720.3442	720.3442
IDTYNEVP	0	476.1966	950.4233	950.4233	950.4233
AIPPK	0	525.3352	524.3322	524.3322	524.3322
MRVTTDTRPAYVGYTGITAC	0	573.1419	2288.1294	2288.1294	2288.1294
DTVEN	0	577.2444	576.2391	576.2391	576.2391
DVVP	428.2632	215.1389	428.2271	428.2271	428.2271
AFAEK	0	283.1296	564.2908	564.2908	564.2908
GLGGPGIILELGN	0	303.1659	1208.6765	1208.6765	1208.6765
LSSVGLKIYIK	0	306.0488	1219.754	1219.754	1219.754
AGSTIGK	0	317.1808	632.3494	632.3494	632.3494
PQNPLQ	712.4039	357.2092	712.3392	712.3392	712.3392
NEEEYYDDANE	0	377.1288	1504.5114	1504.5114	1504.5114

NDPMEIDISPH	0	423.1952	1266.5551	1266.5551	1266.5551
AGVCGGIAEHFGWDKSLTRIALV	0	629.0962	2512.3259	2512.3259	2512.3259
GGERP	0	644.3326	643.2925	643.2925	643.2925
VVDAHS	0	314.09	626.3024	626.3024	626.3024
MPDN	0	476.1995	475.1737	475.1737	475.1737
AIQGH	0	525.2293	524.2707	524.2707	524.2707
LAGVIIGIALPAAIGPK	0	525.3361	1572.9967	1572.9967	1572.9967
AGSEPA	0	531.2345	530.2336	530.2336	530.2336
GLPAVQ	0	584.3339	583.3329	583.3329	583.3329
GLLATIVLGVVASLMPVDFAMPVA	0	611.0866	2440.3474	2440.3474	2440.3474
PLSNKFILKLPVGLSTILLAIA	0	613.1562	2448.5447	2448.5447	2448.5447
GALPFYDQDIE	0	423.1948	1266.5768	1266.5768	1266.5768
AGAIP	0	428.2283	427.2431	427.2431	427.2431
AGNEATLEISTCM	0	447.2052	1338.5796	1338.5796	1338.5796
TSMMLGVY	0	451.2099	900.4085	900.4085	900.4085
GPGLPA	0	511.2452	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
INNALEQLH	0	526.2559	1050.5458	1050.5458	1050.5458
GGSAIM	534.1929	268.1037	534.2472	534.2472	534.2472
AGAVEQITMANAL	0	430.2269	1287.6493	1287.6493	1287.6493
KTSDWGWSIDP	0	431.2162	1290.588	1290.588	1290.588
DISE	0	463.1989	462.1962	462.1962	462.1962
AVPAKITPH	0	467.255	932.5444	932.5444	932.5444
QTNMNVNE	0	476.1911	950.3651	950.3651	950.3651
EGSFSS	0	613.1552	612.2391	612.2391	612.2391
AAGFIKS	0	347.1903	692.3857	692.3857	692.3857
AGIPGA	0	485.2275	484.2646	484.2646	484.2646
GAGVHA	0	511.2461	510.255	510.255	510.255
ADIAH	0	526.2568	525.2547	525.2547	525.2547
ADGMY	0	556.1319	555.1999	555.1999	555.1999
VAAGAVSAHEGDGAAG	0	447.2035	1338.6165	1338.6165	1338.6165
ADQFVSEE	0	463.1984	924.3713	924.3713	924.3713
HTEE	0	515.1349	514.2023	514.2023	514.2023
AIPPK	0	525.3358	524.3322	524.3322	524.3322
EYGSTG	0	613.1552	612.2391	612.2391	612.2391
DYPY	0	279.1333	556.2169	556.2169	556.2169
EVTNETLPSAIES	0	348.176	1388.6671	1388.6671	1388.6671
AGSVPTAANA	0	430.2257	858.4083	858.4083	858.4083
EPSPNVPDVPT	1297.6222	433.548	1297.5674	1297.5674	1297.5674
DADGI	0	490.2248	489.2071	489.2071	489.2071
GPGLPA	0	511.2472	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
KDLFDSLLTASRQTADASY	0	526.2605	2101.0327	2101.0327	2101.0327
AVDAGINYIDSADL	0	718.8658	1435.6831	1435.6831	1435.6831
AFSI	436.2516	219.1331	436.2322	436.2322	436.2322
ATVTLGVS	746.3839	374.1992	746.4174	746.4174	746.4174
EYTIEE	782.4277	392.2211	782.3334	782.3334	782.3334
DIVQKGAGTFQVKVAKVLR	0	515.1324	2056.2156	2056.2156	2056.2156
NIIALGAGALH	0	525.3336	1048.6029	1048.6029	1048.6029

EQELKPITGH	1150.5829	576.2987	1150.5983	1150.5983	1150.5983
EKEPF	0	631.2725	630.3013	630.3013	630.3013
HIGQPQ	0	679.3494	678.3449	678.3449	678.3449
GAFDAA	550.2729	276.1437	550.2387	550.2387	550.2387
SFGVIGYV	0	281.1481	840.4382	840.4382	840.4382
AADVVL	586.2947	294.1546	586.3326	586.3326	586.3326
GADIANE	688.3499	345.1822	688.3028	688.3028	688.3028
DGGNLVD	688.3499	345.1822	688.3028	688.3028	688.3028
INNALEQLH	0	526.2599	1050.5458	1050.5458	1050.5458
ATAGEIG	0	618.3221	617.3021	617.3021	617.3021
GSGKAPQ	0	644.3044	643.3289	643.3289	643.3289
GDAPVMSLFDLAK	1378.6107	690.3126	1378.6803	1378.6803	1378.6803
DCSL	436.2516	219.1331	436.1628	436.1628	436.1628
GGMNI	490.2742	246.1444	490.221	490.221	490.221
FDGDN	0	284.0979	566.1973	566.1973	566.1973
AAETSV	0	289.1523	576.2755	576.2755	576.2755
EVTNETLPSAIES	0	348.1755	1388.6671	1388.6671	1388.6671
AGVMVAGI	0	359.2628	716.3891	716.3891	716.3891
DPTKPPPWPT	1150.5829	576.2987	1150.5659	1150.5659	1150.5659
AGIKTFFSGNAGVLFQDWADVEP	0	600.2953	2397.1641	2397.1641	2397.1641
EKEPF	0	631.2717	630.3013	630.3013	630.3013
GKLGPAH	0	679.3487	678.3813	678.3813	678.3813
SSTGVT	550.2729	276.1437	550.2598	550.2598	550.2598
IVGSVL	586.2947	294.1546	586.369	586.369	586.369
ETDVEP	688.3499	345.1822	688.2916	688.2916	688.2916
AINPS	0	501.2631	500.2595	500.2595	500.2595
GSGKAPQ	0	644.3018	643.3289	643.3289	643.3289
GGNNP	458.2124	230.1135	458.1761	458.1761	458.1761
ETLV	460.3262	231.1704	460.2533	460.2533	460.2533
KPKI	484.2496	243.1321	484.3373	484.3373	484.3373
GNTQQ	546.1687	274.0916	546.2398	546.2398	546.2398
ISMISL	0	332.1823	662.3673	662.3673	662.3673
ALATSFQVLE	0	360.2104	1077.5707	1077.5707	1077.5707
AKEAVAPN	0	400.2167	798.4236	798.4236	798.4236
EQELKPITGH	1150.5829	576.2987	1150.5983	1150.5983	1150.5983
GSSGGATASVAANE	1177.576	589.7953	1177.5211	1177.5211	1177.5211
ITQEE	0	620.2756	619.2701	619.2701	619.2701
GGNPI	456.2928	229.1537	456.2332	456.2332	456.2332
QAVGV	472.1604	237.0875	472.2646	472.2646	472.2646
GCDSGL	550.2729	276.1437	550.2057	550.2057	550.2057
GGPLMI	586.2947	294.1546	586.3149	586.3149	586.3149
CMISKN	0	348.0686	694.3142	694.3142	694.3142
LDDDFTVTYEIV	0	477.2153	1428.666	1428.666	1428.666
AIPSDNSIKG	0	501.2641	1000.5189	1000.5189	1000.5189
GQIDPNITVAA	1097.5315	549.773	1097.5717	1097.5717	1097.5717
MVIV	460.3262	231.1704	460.2719	460.2719	460.2719
AGGLAS	474.1263	238.0704	474.2438	474.2438	474.2438

ENVAVKAP	0	414.2336	826.4549	826.4549	826.4549
LQPMIKPE	0	486.2525	970.5157	970.5157	970.5157
HEQAG	0	542.1815	541.2133	541.2133	541.2133
QVSEGYRKQT	1177.576	589.7953	1177.5728	1177.5728	1177.5728
ITQEE	0	620.2735	619.2701	619.2701	619.2701
DILP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
GCDSTGL	550.2729	276.1437	550.2057	550.2057	550.2057
AADVVL	586.2947	294.1546	586.3326	586.3326	586.3326
DLEVGASQH	954.4869	478.2507	954.4407	954.4407	954.4407
GIDAGNGDGAH	1097.5315	549.773	1097.4374	1097.4374	1097.4374
HGRDVLVALAI	1162.5845	582.2995	1162.6823	1162.6823	1162.6823
ETIV	460.3262	231.1704	460.2533	460.2533	460.2533
PGGPVL	538.3703	270.1924	538.3115	538.3115	538.3115
AAGNIAGILGMIL	0	304.1755	1212.6901	1212.6901	1212.6901
EVNVEV	688.3499	345.1822	688.3279	688.3279	688.3279
GAAGIGNSH	782.4277	392.2211	782.3671	782.3671	782.3671
GEIHVDAP	836.4219	419.2182	836.4028	836.4028	836.4028
GSSTGGDGAGGA	892.4373	447.2259	892.3522	892.3522	892.3522
LQPMIKPE	0	486.2542	970.5157	970.5157	970.5157
DTPLLVDYTD	1150.5829	576.2987	1150.5394	1150.5394	1150.5394
DLIP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
LMEP	488.1371	245.0758	488.2305	488.2305	488.2305
NIASL	516.1725	259.0935	516.2908	516.2908	516.2908
GAFSGL	550.2729	276.1437	550.2751	550.2751	550.2751
LTPGSL	586.2906	294.1526	586.3326	586.3326	586.3326
AGKGAPQFFQL	1162.5845	582.2995	1162.6135	1162.6135	1162.6135
GANFL	520.2771	261.1458	520.2645	520.2645	520.2645
LDDLVD	688.3499	345.1822	688.3279	688.3279	688.3279
AGEIEKV	744.4099	373.2122	744.4018	744.4018	744.4018
GTALALGPQ	826.4509	414.2327	826.4549	826.4549	826.4549
ASFFTGVTEPLE	1296.6189	433.2136	1296.6238	1296.6238	1296.6238
GSSTGGDGAGGA	892.4373	447.2259	892.3522	892.3522	892.3522
LTEKPVNHLT	0	584.3266	1166.6295	1166.6295	1166.6295
GGSGAGAVFATIPA	0	588.296	1174.5983	1174.5983	1174.5983
DILP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
ETVI	460.328	231.1713	460.2533	460.2533	460.2533
AGDNI	488.1371	245.0758	488.2231	488.2231	488.2231
PMEK	0	504.2401	503.2414	503.2414	503.2414
LTVTTHAPKPV	1162.5845	582.2995	1162.671	1162.671	1162.671
ASEMATLALTLHAKQLAVGRPQCQ	0	635.0964	2536.3254	2536.3254	2536.3254
VMVI	460.328	231.1713	460.2719	460.2719	460.2719
SACGAL	520.2771	261.1458	520.2315	520.2315	520.2315
GKWQAR	744.4099	373.2122	744.4031	744.4031	744.4031
ITIVGGGPA	783.4317	392.7231	783.449	783.449	783.449
LSQLLVPN	0	442.263	882.5175	882.5175	882.5175
AVNDDGVAVLG	0	515.2432	1028.5138	1028.5138	1028.5138
DASQVSAGASAVL	0	588.2962	1174.583	1174.583	1174.583

DILP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
MVIV	460.328	231.1713	460.2719	460.2719	460.2719
AGAPDS	516.17	259.0923	516.218	516.218	516.218
DYYP	556.2499	279.1322	556.2169	556.2169	556.2169
AGLLIAEP	782.4277	392.2211	782.4538	782.4538	782.4538
GIQLGIRP	852.4438	427.2292	852.5181	852.5181	852.5181
VGQGKTSDAEN	1104.5667	553.2906	1104.5048	1104.5048	1104.5048
LGNIGPAGGLPVV	1162.5845	582.2995	1162.671	1162.671	1162.671
MVIV	460.328	231.1713	460.2719	460.2719	460.2719
KEAVIPQ	783.4317	392.7231	783.449	783.449	783.449
IVGGP	0	442.2649	441.2587	441.2587	441.2587
NAMIGEAEH	970.4647	486.2396	970.4178	970.4178	970.4178
GRPGE	0	515.2434	514.2499	514.2499	514.2499
TPDLHQSRTP	1150.5857	576.3001	1150.5731	1150.5731	1150.5731
MVIV	460.328	231.1713	460.2719	460.2719	460.2719
GGSAP	516.17	259.0923	516.218	516.218	516.218
CIGGVV	546.3363	274.1754	546.2836	546.2836	546.2836
AGVDPV	556.2513	279.1329	556.2857	556.2857	556.2857
ATVQPRI	800.4139	401.2142	800.4392	800.4392	800.4392
IGAGIGNHV	852.4438	427.2292	852.4454	852.4454	852.4454
IPLLTAPQPGV	1104.5667	553.2906	1104.6543	1104.6543	1104.6543
GLTGQGP	0	629.2862	628.3181	628.3181	628.3181
DIIP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
SASSASGSADL	0	318.1289	951.4145	951.4145	951.4145
SLGAHAASA	783.4317	392.7231	783.3875	783.3875	783.3875
IVGGP	0	442.2654	441.2587	441.2587	441.2587
YQGGDNAGH	917.1794	459.597	917.3627	917.3627	917.3627
EGIAH	0	526.2589	525.2547	525.2547	525.2547
LTEGTLIKILTSKGAGNQGVI	0	529.1241	2112.2153	2112.2153	2112.2153
ETIV	460.328	231.1713	460.2533	460.2533	460.2533
GAAADL	516.17	259.0923	516.2544	516.2544	516.2544
EAIGAV	558.2455	280.13	558.3013	558.3013	558.3013
LPSTSSLP	800.4293	401.2219	800.428	800.428	800.428
ATALSAKPE	0	444.2434	886.476	886.476	886.476
AKGDVFPLLTKILDASE	0	455.0878	1815.9982	1815.9982	1815.9982
IYLQQL	1036.4429	519.2287	1036.4965	1036.4965	1036.4965
LGNGDAHVVH	1104.5667	553.2906	1104.5101	1104.5101	1104.5101
DIIP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
DHSF	504.2195	253.117	504.1969	504.1969	504.1969
CHAAGV	556.2535	279.134	556.2427	556.2427	556.2427
ELGSDD	0	318.1295	634.2446	634.2446	634.2446
GADLITLASMRLIPV	0	393.2209	1568.896	1568.896	1568.896
DLSDLALD	860.4106	431.2126	860.4127	860.4127	860.4127
FAAAM	0	526.2595	525.2257	525.2257	525.2257
GHAAAGENLAKL	1150.5857	576.3001	1150.6095	1150.6095	1150.6095
PAVVGQLL	796.3711	399.1928	796.4695	796.4695	796.4695
LDQDENF	879.1639	440.5892	879.361	879.361	879.361

ATALSAKPE	0	444.2435	886.476	886.476	886.476
EELFEHFS	1036.4429	519.2287	1036.4502	1036.4502	1036.4502
ILIPGSKPPK	0	525.335	1048.6644	1048.6644	1048.6644
VDVGAPYDPSNPDDPDVPTDP	0	546.2378	2180.9385	2180.9385	2180.9385
AGGVGMFISPVA	1104.5667	553.2906	1104.5637	1104.5637	1104.5637
DVTRWKIRRFKFRFDPLNAP	0	659.1039	2632.4502	2632.4502	2632.4502
DIIP	456.2935	229.154	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
TQYALPEVSGL	0	393.2225	1176.6027	1176.6027	1176.6027
GIFLGQGGGL	860.4106	431.2126	860.4756	860.4756	860.4756
ADGVAP	0	529.2616	528.2544	528.2544	528.2544
MAGAITNDTPV	0	545.2898	1088.5172	1088.5172	1088.5172
GAPGPAAQV	0	767.365	766.3973	766.3973	766.3973
YDYP	556.2535	279.134	556.2169	556.2169	556.2169
HGTFFT	658.1069	330.0607	658.3075	658.3075	658.3075
AISPPLPQ	853.4518	427.7332	853.4545	853.4545	853.4545
LDNPLPPL	878.4601	440.2373	878.4749	878.4749	878.4749
ATALSAKPE	0	444.2447	886.476	886.476	886.476
IYLQQLLEE	1036.4429	519.2287	1036.4965	1036.4965	1036.4965
AIPPK	0	525.3383	524.3322	524.3322	524.3322
VDVGAPYDPSNPDDPDVPTDP	0	546.2409	2180.9385	2180.9385	2180.9385
HRIFELVTKDGYLKEFSQQPPT	0	659.1071	2632.365	2632.365	2632.365
DIIP	456.2957	229.1551	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
FFIY	0	295.1648	588.2948	588.2948	588.2948
LMNNATMEIP	1132.5792	378.5337	1132.5256	1132.5256	1132.5256
FPTMPAEFRPT	0	437.2131	1308.6173	1308.6173	1308.6173
ADGVAP	0	529.2602	528.2544	528.2544	528.2544
SNEPV	0	545.2918	544.2493	544.2493	544.2493
AGLGIAG	0	558.2852	557.3173	557.3173	557.3173
QVAPVAQ	0	712.36	711.3915	711.3915	711.3915
AGDPK	0	244.1286	486.2438	486.2438	486.2438
PLVLGHEFSGKVV	0	346.1953	1380.7765	1380.7765	1380.7765
ISFEEA	0	348.0701	694.3174	694.3174	694.3174
ALPGLGLNV	852.4438	427.2292	852.5069	852.5069	852.5069
LIVNPIDP	879.4647	440.7396	879.5066	879.5066	879.5066
ATALSAKPE	0	444.2445	886.476	886.476	886.476
EIEE	1036.4429	519.2287	518.2224	518.2224	518.2224
ESEELTEAL	0	546.239	1090.5031	1090.5031	1090.5031
DIIP	456.2957	229.1551	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
VHAF	472.2304	237.1225	472.2434	472.2434	472.2434
HEFT	532.2525	267.1335	532.2281	532.2281	532.2281
TPDMVP	658.1069	330.0607	658.2996	658.2996	658.2996
GSADWQMIPE	1132.5825	378.5348	1132.486	1132.486	1132.486
GQMDGQII	860.4106	431.2126	860.4062	860.4062	860.4062
TLLDMKGNP	0	545.2922	1088.5536	1088.5536	1088.5536
DAAIAAGAP	0	756.3461	755.3813	755.3813	755.3813
EVVVETVYV	0	346.1957	1035.5488	1035.5488	1035.5488
RAQAALQP	854.4927	428.2536	854.461	854.461	854.461

DGDRSLPK	0	444.2432	886.4509	886.4509	886.4509
TYSE	0	499.1123	498.1962	498.1962	498.1962
AGLLTTLMAL	1002.4995	502.257	1002.5784	1002.5784	1002.5784
KGVLEP	0	642.3781	641.3748	641.3748	641.3748
MVIV	460.3258	231.1702	460.2719	460.2719	460.2719
TTAGIA	532.2525	267.1335	532.2857	532.2857	532.2857
AVFEGP	0	318.165	634.2963	634.2963	634.2963
FFTLEP	752.3301	377.1723	752.3745	752.3745	752.3745
LMMLIGAI	860.4106	431.2126	860.4864	860.4864	860.4864
GADSPV	0	545.2879	544.2493	544.2493	544.2493
DYIF	556.2525	279.1335	556.2533	556.2533	556.2533
AIQDAPKP	854.4927	428.2536	854.4498	854.4498	854.4498
EPAESPQAG	884.4759	443.2452	884.3876	884.3876	884.3876
EFEEEADE	0	499.1147	996.356	996.356	996.356
IGAGVGSAMGLA	1002.4995	502.257	1002.5168	1002.5168	1002.5168
DLIP	456.2957	229.1551	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
ETVI	460.3258	231.1702	460.2533	460.2533	460.2533
FVDI	492.2426	247.1286	492.2584	492.2584	492.2584
NEFVF	654.2579	328.1362	654.3013	654.3013	654.3013
DYVDEL	752.3301	377.1723	752.3229	752.3229	752.3229
AQHPQLENVV	1150.5885	576.3015	1150.5619	1150.5619	1150.5619
GAAFADEIGHRGP	1296.614	649.3143	1296.6211	1296.6211	1296.6211
LVPSGF	618.2421	310.1283	618.3377	618.3377	618.3377
ADIKPAPQ	854.4927	428.2536	854.4498	854.4498	854.4498
GIPHGGNGIG	878.4597	440.2371	878.4246	878.4246	878.4246
ECSE	0	499.1159	498.1268	498.1268	498.1268
AVIAFNIGAK	1002.4995	502.257	1002.5862	1002.5862	1002.5862
DAGGAEAA	0	661.2836	660.2715	660.2715	660.2715
EVIP	456.2957	229.1551	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
GGSSGGSF	654.2579	328.1362	654.2609	654.2609	654.2609
NNEVCH	0	358.1599	714.2755	714.2755	714.2755
DYVDEL	752.3301	377.1723	752.3229	752.3229	752.3229
AHDPRQTGGRG	1150.5885	576.3015	1150.5592	1150.5592	1150.5592
PSKPGEPGTTEPSQPGE	0	603.2768	1806.8271	1806.8271	1806.8271
DPNLRQEVEK	1226.6417	614.3281	1226.6255	1226.6255	1226.6255
HVSM	472.156	237.0853	472.2104	472.2104	472.2104
DYLF	0	279.133	556.2533	556.2533	556.2533
LGGEPP	618.2421	310.1283	618.3013	618.3013	618.3013
GGWLGGAI	0	414.2334	826.4337	826.4337	826.4337
PLPGNLTTVKVWLF	0	462.1009	1844.0601	1844.0601	1844.0601
FDDC	0	499.1133	498.1421	498.1421	498.1421
DILP	456.294	229.1543	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
GSASYGN	654.2579	328.1362	654.2609	654.2609	654.2609
AGTAGMAH	0	358.1594	714.3119	714.3119	714.3119
DYVDEL	752.3301	377.1723	752.3229	752.3229	752.3229
GLNHREPG	878.4597	440.2371	878.4359	878.4359	878.4359
GVSLDPSFVTT	1121.5045	561.7595	1121.5604	1121.5604	1121.5604

IRHLVANEAA	1150.5885	576.3015	1150.6095	1150.6095	1150.6095
NTGVMGTGADGEP	0	603.2774	1204.5031	1204.5031	1204.5031
DPNLRQEVEK	1226.6417	614.3281	1226.6255	1226.6255	1226.6255
DMDI	492.2426	247.1286	492.189	492.189	492.189
FFIY	0	295.164	588.2948	588.2948	588.2948
LGGKNM	618.2421	310.1283	618.3159	618.3159	618.3159
ISFCIL	0	348.1765	694.3724	694.3724	694.3724
LGIMLG PQ	828.4389	415.2267	828.4415	828.4415	828.4415
LGPEDAH LA	921.4156	461.7151	921.4556	921.4556	921.4556
IIHP	0	479.2962	478.2904	478.2904	478.2904
KDAVND	0	661.2815	660.3079	660.3079	660.3079
DLIP	456.294	229.1543	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
AGAKPVL	654.2579	328.1362	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
DYVDEL	752.3301	377.1723	752.3229	752.3229	752.3229
AMIPN	0	545.2545	544.2679	544.2679	544.2679
ANGFYANSIPC	1121.5045	561.7595	1121.5142	1121.5142	1121.5142
PAVVLPDANKQ	1150.5835	576.299	1150.6346	1150.6346	1150.6346
IMGDSEVGRLE	0	603.2786	1204.5758	1204.5758	1204.5758
EASDPNTFAYL	1226.6417	614.3281	1226.5455	1226.5455	1226.5455
FFIY	0	295.1626	588.2948	588.2948	588.2948
AGVYLP	618.2421	310.1283	618.3377	618.3377	618.3377
DTIHPI	0	348.1744	694.365	694.365	694.365
GISVEAEV	0	402.2326	802.4072	802.4072	802.4072
DAGATGPAGP	828.4405	415.2275	828.3614	828.3614	828.3614
SRGLPMET	921.4156	461.7151	921.4226	921.4226	921.4226
APASAASTTREKLRN	0	530.2891	1587.8329	1587.8329	1587.8329
SEKLASEIKGFIEKSEHQEANL	0	651.089	2600.3081	2600.3081	2600.3081
DIIP	456.294	229.1543	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
GKHDP	0	277.1168	552.2656	552.2656	552.2656
AGAKPVL	654.2579	328.1362	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
DYVDEL	752.3301	377.1723	752.3229	752.3229	752.3229
EDEFPK	763.3577	382.6861	763.3388	763.3388	763.3388
ASGVISSGI	789.472	395.7433	789.4232	789.4232	789.4232
YKAVLNAKDE	1150.5831	576.2988	1150.587	1150.587	1150.587
AATFPL	618.2421	310.1283	618.3377	618.3377	618.3377
ACINRLN	0	402.2341	802.412	802.412	802.412
AMIVGIPQ	828.4389	415.2267	828.4415	828.4415	828.4415
GNSEA	0	477.1617	476.1867	476.1867	476.1867
ADTEAVALGE	0	488.2323	974.4556	974.4556	974.4556
IGVGGAG	0	530.2902	529.286	529.286	529.286
AEMTGAGQNLDDLAVE	0	545.2505	1632.7301	1632.7301	1632.7301
SEVMGQLAPSPKPVVQRYKGLGEM	0	651.0868	2600.3455	2600.3455	2600.3455
LTEDVN	0	690.3263	689.3232	689.3232	689.3232
DILP	456.2924	229.1535	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
DFPF	524.2641	263.1393	524.2271	524.2271	524.2271
AQQATH	654.2579	328.1362	654.3085	654.3085	654.3085
NLDFGVV	763.3577	382.6861	763.3752	763.3752	763.3752

EDEFPK	763.3577	382.6861	763.3388	763.3388	763.3388
ASVVLGGT	789.4719	395.7432	789.4232	789.4232	789.4232
DGAHNLPV	878.4597	440.2371	878.4246	878.4246	878.4246
GMLMIT	0	665.2959	664.3288	664.3288	664.3288
VVHQV	0	291.1529	580.3333	580.3333	580.3333
AGMNNL	618.2421	310.1283	618.2795	618.2795	618.2795
ACKSKGRAVDIG	0	402.2336	1203.6394	1203.6394	1203.6394
GADGLLFH	828.4389	415.2267	828.413	828.413	828.413
AVVFNKR	0	417.2428	832.4919	832.4919	832.4919
GNSAE	0	477.1622	476.1867	476.1867	476.1867
GANQERIGE	0	488.2337	974.4305	974.4305	974.4305
ETFC	0	499.1129	498.1784	498.1784	498.1784
DILP	456.2924	229.1535	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
DFFP	524.2641	263.1393	524.2271	524.2271	524.2271
INYMD	654.2579	328.1362	654.2683	654.2683	654.2683
AVSSQAVS	747.3473	374.6809	747.3763	747.3763	747.3763
GAPTKGGWVYP	1131.5775	378.1998	1131.5713	1131.5713	1131.5713
ENFPEE	763.3577	382.6861	763.3024	763.3024	763.3024
ELNMIDED	0	490.2128	978.3852	978.3852	978.3852
RPDPLMEPAE	1153.5521	577.7833	1153.5437	1153.5437	1153.5437
LGGEPP	618.2421	310.1283	618.3013	618.3013	618.3013
ANADNIK	745.3447	373.6796	745.3607	745.3607	745.3607
LSALDFVGIRN	0	402.2343	1203.6611	1203.6611	1203.6611
ATLLGTVLKEKHSR	0	417.2446	1664.9938	1664.9938	1664.9938
ENARNMLP	944.4626	473.2386	944.4385	944.4385	944.4385
AVLGE	0	488.2826	487.2642	487.2642	487.2642
ASQMDWME	0	499.1162	996.3681	996.3681	996.3681
SEPEPLFEPPLSEPEP	0	507.2251	2024.9103	2024.9103	2024.9103
ADVADV	0	589.2803	588.2755	588.2755	588.2755
VYPF	524.2641	263.1393	524.2635	524.2635	524.2635
GALSSAWG	747.3473	374.6809	747.3552	747.3552	747.3552
DDPVLSKYVP	1131.575	378.1989	1131.5812	1131.5812	1131.5812
QMLFPK	763.3577	382.6861	763.3939	763.3939	763.3939
SDGGLLLQ	0	430.2278	858.4447	858.4447	858.4447
DEIGG	0	490.2119	489.2071	489.2071	489.2071
ASIVGCLGVAGD	0	531.2751	1060.5223	1060.5223	1060.5223
TPPMSLPWIL	1153.5521	577.7833	1153.6206	1153.6206	1153.6206
QDPE	488.1754	245.095	488.1754	488.1754	488.1754
EEDIK	745.3447	373.6796	745.3858	745.3858	745.3858
ENARNMLP	944.4626	473.2386	944.4385	944.4385	944.4385
PFAGP	0	488.2831	487.2431	487.2431	487.2431
GAAGFHTLPVVTAACLGLAK	0	499.1152	1992.152	1992.152	1992.152
LASSISEVTAP	0	589.2792	1176.5874	1176.5874	1176.5874
GEGISCL	0	678.3169	677.3054	677.3054	677.3054
VYPF	524.2641	263.1393	524.2635	524.2635	524.2635
ADNGFKITFVDV	0	332.1779	1324.6663	1324.6663	1324.6663
LDVNNIRNPVEV	0	346.1937	1380.7361	1380.7361	1380.7361

DDPVLSKYVP	1131.575	378.1989	1131.5812	1131.5812	1131.5812
ENFPEE	763.3577	382.6861	763.3024	763.3024	763.3024
QLWVVPP	820.4549	411.2347	820.4483	820.4483	820.4483
GIGDAV	0	531.276	530.27	530.27	530.27
GLIPTLDEPTV	1153.5521	577.7833	1153.623	1153.623	1153.623
AIAGPV	526.2689	264.1417	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
LLHDDD	0	364.0638	726.3184	726.3184	726.3184
NEEVQQ	745.3447	373.6796	745.3242	745.3242	745.3242
GEGPFPTEQ	974.433	488.2238	974.4345	974.4345	974.4345
ETFC	0	499.1136	498.1784	498.1784	498.1784
ADYIA	0	552.2292	551.2592	551.2592	551.2592
EDGHIDQDIL	1153.5521	577.7833	1153.5251	1153.5251	1153.5251
SFSLPQ	0	678.3162	677.3384	677.3384	677.3384
ENGANGATGMLQKPDFDKIEGKIPIY	0	727.1202	2904.4692	2904.4692	2904.4692
GGNIP	456.2943	229.1544	456.2332	456.2332	456.2332
LFAVDV	0	332.1798	662.364	662.364	662.364
LDVNNIRNPVEV	0	346.195	1380.7361	1380.7361	1380.7361
GLAERLDNFP	1131.575	378.1989	1131.556	1131.556	1131.556
ENFPEE	763.3577	382.6861	763.3024	763.3024	763.3024
QLWVVPP	820.4549	411.2347	820.4483	820.4483	820.4483
AEIGAEAIL	885.4695	443.742	885.4808	885.4808	885.4808
GIATAV	0	531.2742	530.3064	530.3064	530.3064
GLIPTLDEPTV	1153.5521	577.7833	1153.623	1153.623	1153.623
MAPVEP	0	675.277	674.2946	674.2946	674.2946
IYLGWLSI	0	322.1749	963.543	963.543	963.543
DQENLQ	745.3447	373.6796	745.3242	745.3242	745.3242
AEHLALIM	896.4272	449.2209	896.479	896.479	896.479
EFNDLLPK	974.4327	488.2236	974.5073	974.5073	974.5073
ECSE	0	499.1118	498.1268	498.1268	498.1268
ADYIA	0	552.2278	551.2592	551.2592	551.2592
DDVEE	0	606.205	605.2181	605.2181	605.2181
SFSLPQ	0	678.3165	677.3384	677.3384	677.3384
DEIDDEPDLIAE	1388.6647	695.3396	1388.5831	1388.5831	1388.5831
GGNIP	456.2943	229.1544	456.2332	456.2332	456.2332
IMII	488.3564	245.1855	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
GAEIDRLDDE	1131.575	378.1989	1131.5044	1131.5044	1131.5044
DKEDDE	763.3577	382.6861	763.2872	763.2872	763.2872
DVPGAPKIIKPP	0	411.2589	1230.7336	1230.7336	1230.7336
LSIQSLPK	885.4695	443.742	885.5172	885.5172	885.5172
GPTGPK	0	556.3042	555.3016	555.3016	555.3016
RPDPLMEPAE	1153.5521	577.7833	1153.5437	1153.5437	1153.5437
EDPVSE	0	675.2814	674.2759	674.2759	674.2759
FGGNAALLM	0	322.1751	963.4848	963.4848	963.4848
EEDIK	745.3447	373.6796	745.3858	745.3858	745.3858
LIGHTPLM	896.4245	449.2195	896.479	896.479	896.479
DIPN	0	458.2227	457.2173	457.2173	457.2173
DPDMLQDLV	1044.5103	523.2624	1044.4797	1044.4797	1044.4797

ADYIA	0	552.2287	551.2592	551.2592	551.2592
EEAEQ	0	606.2043	605.2181	605.2181	605.2181
LYGLEFVAEEAQQFIFIGGSLRN	0	651.092	2600.3274	2600.3274	2600.3274
TNNANDSQAVP	1131.575	378.1989	1131.468	1131.468	1131.468
ENFPPEE	763.3577	382.6861	763.3024	763.3024	763.3024
QGPLVRKEKPP	0	411.2586	1230.7085	1230.7085	1230.7085
GAVTLSIPK	884.4777	443.2461	884.5331	884.5331	884.5331
DFKPNLIK	0	488.2845	974.5437	974.5437	974.5437
GPTGPK	0	556.3072	555.3016	555.3016	555.3016
MPPVSE	0	675.2825	674.2946	674.2946	674.2946
AILDPE	656.2651	329.1398	656.3381	656.3381	656.3381
FGGGGGFE	0	364.0636	726.2973	726.2973	726.2973
DAGENQI	745.3447	373.6796	745.3242	745.3242	745.3242
DIMSAPIF	0	447.2238	892.4365	892.4365	892.4365
DPDMLQDLV	1044.5103	523.2624	1044.4797	1044.4797	1044.4797
SDYPA	0	552.2292	551.2227	551.2227	551.2227
EEAEQ	0	606.203	605.2181	605.2181	605.2181
SAFHEDFVHLASSGVVGKFIQTPK	0	651.0912	2600.3386	2600.3386	2600.3386
SPESELEFLSSE	0	677.2844	1352.5984	1352.5984	1352.5984
DIIP	456.294	229.1543	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
IMII	488.3564	245.1855	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
DKEDEE	763.3577	382.6861	763.2872	763.2872	763.2872
QLWVVPP	0	411.2558	820.4483	820.4483	820.4483
LSIQSLPK	884.4777	443.2461	884.5331	884.5331	884.5331
GPKPFYQT	936.3951	469.2048	936.4705	936.4705	936.4705
DEPDE	0	604.2005	603.2024	603.2024	603.2024
DEVSPPE	0	675.2804	674.2759	674.2759	674.2759
DLPSPE	656.2651	329.1398	656.3017	656.3017	656.3017
LDDPSE	674.2759	338.1452	674.2759	674.2759	674.2759
ADADVQQ	745.3447	373.6796	745.3242	745.3242	745.3242
AIPF	0	447.2236	446.2529	446.2529	446.2529
ATGET	0	478.2193	477.2071	477.2071	477.2071
GAAGADIARIADEPTQ	0	519.2456	1554.7638	1554.7638	1554.7638
ADYIA	0	552.2267	551.2592	551.2592	551.2592
WPTDEVTAKIESLDVDPGNADTA	0	612.0632	2444.123	2444.123	2444.123
RTIYEAKAWKDEAQNEIIFEF	0	651.0908	2600.291	2600.291	2600.291
EDPVSE	674.2759	338.1452	674.2759	674.2759	674.2759
ENFPPEE	763.3577	382.6861	763.3024	763.3024	763.3024
DLAIPVPP	0	411.2581	820.4695	820.4695	820.4695
KALEEAPK	884.4773	443.2459	884.4967	884.4967	884.4967
AGEPI	0	486.2503	485.2486	485.2486	485.2486
EGVQLVYKP	1013.5269	507.7707	1013.5546	1013.5546	1013.5546
LGADAVG	0	602.2774	601.3071	601.3071	601.3071
DEVSPPE	0	675.2804	674.2759	674.2759	674.2759
DIIP	456.294	229.1543	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
DAGLPQL	0	357.2092	712.3755	712.3755	712.3755
AGELNEL	745.3445	373.6795	745.3494	745.3494	745.3494

ENFKAR	745.3445	373.6795	745.3871	745.3871	745.3871
ALLMGMIAYIPF	0	447.2286	1338.708	1338.708	1338.708
EHLPEVVM	0	477.2347	952.4688	952.4688	952.4688
DEIQD	0	619.2545	618.2497	618.2497	618.2497
QTVQEPVKFEMDAVWMALLDPNG	0	651.0923	2600.229	2600.229	2600.229
EDEFPK	763.3578	382.6862	763.3388	763.3388	763.3388
DVPGAPKIIKPP	0	411.2589	1230.7336	1230.7336	1230.7336
DELDWRGAINQQTDE	0	448.2014	1788.7915	1788.7915	1788.7915
VGPSANTSGKP	1013.5209	507.7677	1013.5142	1013.5142	1013.5142
MDESL	0	594.2411	593.2367	593.2367	593.2367
ARATVIGHVQRGGVPSAKDRVLAS	0	612.0701	2444.3723	2444.3723	2444.3723
DIIP	456.294	229.1543	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
NAGGYDIPG	0	432.206	862.3821	862.3821	862.3821
IPTFFNFSEPVM	0	477.2364	1428.6636	1428.6636	1428.6636
GAGKSTLLNRIDPDLNIQ	0	486.2557	1941.0167	1941.0167	1941.0167
DEIQD	0	619.2538	618.2497	618.2497	618.2497
RMKVADEDAVIQSRLISRQVESA	0	651.0933	2600.3704	2600.3704	2600.3704
FNGSV	0	262.1183	522.2438	522.2438	522.2438
VVPP	0	411.2582	410.2529	410.2529	410.2529
AADFYHPGH	1013.5209	507.7677	1013.4355	1013.4355	1013.4355
AFENL	0	594.2422	593.2697	593.2697	593.2697
KLLSLSMLSPTGSEFSISFDDNG	0	612.0712	2444.1782	2444.1782	2444.1782
IGV NKQ	0	659.3325	658.365	658.365	658.365
DIIP	456.2918	229.1532	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
EPEEPE	0	356.1428	710.2759	710.2759	710.2759
CIGCGATLQ	864.4057	433.2101	864.3834	864.3834	864.3834
IAATHPVMN	0	477.2373	952.48	952.48	952.48
IIAEGDE	745.3447	373.6796	745.3494	745.3494	745.3494
DLAIPVPP	0	411.2594	820.4695	820.4695	820.4695
RHPDDLDF	1013.5209	507.7677	1013.4567	1013.4567	1013.4567
QSTGFDYPREAQPT	0	527.2434	1578.6951	1578.6951	1578.6951
AFEDL	0	594.2431	593.2697	593.2697	593.2697
KRLLVRNNGQVTFNNASGNGGGDG	0	612.0716	2444.2268	2444.2268	2444.2268
IGNGGNGAKINIKVQDVFM	0	659.333	1975.0197	1975.0197	1975.0197
DIIP	456.2918	229.1532	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
SLPVYVVQLPK	0	415.2528	1242.7224	1242.7224	1242.7224
IGGEV	0	474.2532	473.2486	473.2486	473.2486
INFTPLYPLNSAPNNVM	0	477.2372	1904.9342	1904.9342	1904.9342
GVAAFSGFVGYMVM	0	479.235	1434.6676	1434.6676	1434.6676
EPEEPE	0	356.145	710.2759	710.2759	710.2759
VVPP	0	411.2586	410.2529	410.2529	410.2529
AQGAAEQSHRTMIPSVSYAT	0	527.2414	2104.9849	2104.9849	2104.9849
AFEDL	0	594.242	593.2697	593.2697	593.2697
TGFNFLSGSTASSSETIK	0	612.0723	1832.8793	1832.8793	1832.8793
IGVNQE	0	659.3325	658.3286	658.3286	658.3286
AIFIVP	658.3273	330.1709	658.4054	658.4054	658.4054
IGGEV	0	474.2524	473.2486	473.2486	473.2486

LAAIQGGNHIYSGFSQDAG	0	477.2367	1904.9017	1904.9017	1904.9017
GSGLPGGIFLP	1013.5209	507.7677	1013.5546	1013.5546	1013.5546
GELLDNPRAA	0	528.2986	1054.5408	1054.5408	1054.5408
EDAPE	0	560.2328	559.2126	559.2126	559.2126
RLVTGSLIGVP	0	371.2282	1110.6761	1110.6761	1110.6761
VVPP	0	411.2584	410.2529	410.2529	410.2529
ISPVCLSLVIVT	0	415.254	1242.7257	1242.7257	1242.7257
CYTRILP	864.4057	433.2101	864.4528	864.4528	864.4528
TGFRAIGILIGVLVLSLLW	0	511.1198	2040.25	2040.25	2040.25
PIYFHITSPKHGSYYVYANGD	0	612.0722	2444.1438	2444.1438	2444.1438
GLVNGAE	0	659.3324	658.3286	658.3286	658.3286
ETVIP	658.3273	330.1709	658.3538	658.3538	658.3538
KDGEQFTQSSV	0	409.1859	1224.5623	1224.5623	1224.5623
IGGEV	0	474.2525	473.2486	473.2486	473.2486
EVET	0	477.2355	476.2119	476.2119	476.2119
DVISLPLQVA	0	528.2999	1054.5911	1054.5911	1054.5911
AATMYLEMLIDFGARTVIAVGSCGAL	0	669.0995	2672.3376	2672.3376	2672.3376
NELPGLPQYDVL	1388.66	695.3373	1388.6824	1388.6824	1388.6824
TDNGAQVIDSKDWSKRRFAYEIGGFN	0	816.1591	3260.5486	3260.5486	3260.5486
FFYI	0	295.1649	588.2948	588.2948	588.2948
DGANVYI	0	376.1703	750.3548	750.3548	750.3548
VPTPVHR	0	411.2571	820.4556	820.4556	820.4556
ISPVCLSLVIVT	0	415.2511	1242.7257	1242.7257	1242.7257
ASYIEPSV	864.4057	433.2101	864.4229	864.4229	864.4229
GAPKNVVLWNDDE	0	486.2537	1455.6995	1455.6995	1455.6995
GKKASIDGSTIISRNDG	0	612.0708	1832.9229	1832.9229	1832.9229
LTGVLTGIPAGL	0	371.2297	1110.6649	1110.6649	1110.6649
ADSVKSGSDSVS	0	409.1841	1224.547	1224.547	1224.547
EGGVIPTFQ	0	474.2474	946.476	946.476	946.476
IPTFFNFSEPVM	0	477.2308	1428.6636	1428.6636	1428.6636
GINLEIPIVS	0	528.2985	1054.5911	1054.5911	1054.5911
ADGRYGENPN	1092.5159	547.2652	1092.4473	1092.4473	1092.4473
ITDVE	0	576.2829	575.2803	575.2803	575.2803
IVNVIP	0	328.2216	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
DLVDDD	0	346.0541	690.2708	690.2708	690.2708
ENLNVY	0	376.1724	750.3548	750.3548	750.3548
FAGIGLVT	0	389.2311	776.4432	776.4432	776.4432
LSNVPVLS	0	415.2518	828.4593	828.4593	828.4593
HAPQPESV	864.3993	433.2069	864.3978	864.3978	864.3978
IAGDVGGGGLLSTNAANVIADVTK	0	669.1009	2672.3691	2672.3691	2672.3691
DFSNPDF	0	281.112	840.329	840.329	840.329
NSHID	0	293.159	584.2554	584.2554	584.2554
GVPVGATILILDGEK	0	371.2274	1480.8501	1480.8501	1480.8501
VGQLNGIP	0	399.2344	796.4443	796.4443	796.4443
VPTPVHR	0	411.2591	820.4556	820.4556	820.4556
LNNDKIK	0	459.2448	916.4866	916.4866	916.4866
EIDVIEIEQFTGY	0	562.2639	1683.788	1683.788	1683.788

QESDQ	0	847.2808	846.2879	846.2879	846.2879
IVNVIP	0	328.221	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
DEPDDADYDIVD	0	346.0539	1380.5205	1380.5205	1380.5205
IGTTVLLEPQLRIT	0	389.2379	1552.9188	1552.9188	1552.9188
VPLPVDDVSA	0	506.2942	1010.5284	1010.5284	1010.5284
ASEVE	0	534.2569	533.2333	533.2333	533.2333
DFPLT	0	592.2597	591.2904	591.2904	591.2904
TVSPEV	0	631.2904	630.3224	630.3224	630.3224
PWFIPTALAAGHIGFLWVIDTLLIP	0	691.0983	2760.5408	2760.5408	2760.5408
DTESEPEVDT	0	281.1128	1120.4408	1120.4408	1120.4408
LSNVPVLS	0	415.2539	828.4593	828.4593	828.4593
EIDVIEIEQFTGY	0	562.2684	1683.788	1683.788	1683.788
YGEPIG	0	635.3045	634.2963	634.2963	634.2963
GLSDAADNLVFQMM	1526.6891	764.3518	1526.6746	1526.6746	1526.6746
QESDQ	0	847.2841	846.2879	846.2879	846.2879
DIIP	0	229.1538	456.2584	456.2584	456.2584
DMITGLLD	0	293.1596	876.4263	876.4263	876.4263
IVNVIP	0	328.2223	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
FDPLT	0	592.2602	591.2904	591.2904	591.2904
TVSPEV	0	631.2885	630.3224	630.3224	630.3224
HGQMASGILSSLKIIYGESDQVEALD	0	691.0997	2760.364	2760.364	2760.364
SDDEIDQ	0	849.3405	848.3036	848.3036	848.3036
LSTLVSIP	0	415.2484	828.4957	828.4957	828.4957
ASLVYMPASE	0	534.256	1066.5005	1066.5005	1066.5005
EDAIAEHNKP	0	562.2677	1122.5305	1122.5305	1122.5305
GEGPLIQAMSRTN	1388.6621	695.3383	1388.6718	1388.6718	1388.6718
HSVIRSMGNTAIALG	1526.6888	764.3517	1526.7875	1526.7875	1526.7875
QESDQ	0	847.28	846.2879	846.2879	846.2879
IVNVIP	0	328.2224	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
GAVGAPIE	712.4106	357.2126	712.3755	712.3755	712.3755
GAFLIMASAILL	0	407.2353	1218.7046	1218.7046	1218.7046
VVPP	0	411.2549	410.2529	410.2529	410.2529
FDPLT	0	592.2596	591.2904	591.2904	591.2904
EALSKYEADLEDDSPDI	0	631.2886	1890.837	1890.837	1890.837
EDGGQMPPK	974.3331	488.1738	974.4015	974.4015	974.4015
GLIGAP	0	527.2774	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
SILSDELITVDSRRGIYHGAS	0	630.0799	2516.2871	2516.2871	2516.2871
NELRRNNQSMQ	1388.6621	695.3383	1388.6578	1388.6578	1388.6578
IGELAVQEGEQILQ	1526.6888	764.3517	1526.7828	1526.7828	1526.7828
AGEFSFSC	0	847.2828	846.3218	846.3218	846.3218
DPDMLQD	0	849.3389	848.3222	848.3222	848.3222
VLDVIP	0	328.2235	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
EKITPII	0	407.2379	812.5007	812.5007	812.5007
QDAVVPTV	0	415.2193	828.4229	828.4229	828.4229
GAQEEANEQ	974.3331	488.1738	974.3941	974.3941	974.3941
NADHGGSGKNH	1092.5128	547.2637	1092.4697	1092.4697	1092.4697
ALEPY	0	592.2598	591.2904	591.2904	591.2904

KDNFGAATNVANQGTMAADVLLIED 0		691.097	2760.3276	2760.3276	2760.3276
GAVPKIQ	712.4106	357.2126	712.4119	712.4119	712.4119
AVGFVTGSLNVDQL	0	474.2543	1419.7246	1419.7246	1419.7246
GLGPLA	0	527.2802	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
ALGVGPGNVPCFIE	1388.6621	695.3383	1388.6646	1388.6646	1388.6646
DQDAAINPAGCVIQI	1526.6888	764.3517	1526.7399	1526.7399	1526.7399
YDEEYEQ	0	975.3365	974.3505	974.3505	974.3505
LVNVLP	0	328.2214	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
SIGLISGRMGGTA	0	407.2365	1218.639	1218.639	1218.639
ADDLAVLL	828.4365	415.2255	828.4593	828.4593	828.4593
KNVFNHFLTGEAVGAREAIERTG	0	630.0791	2516.2771	2516.2771	2516.2771
LEAQHQGEGILV	0	647.3189	1292.6725	1292.6725	1292.6725
TYVF	528.2949	265.1547	528.2584	528.2584	528.2584
GAVPKIQ	712.4106	357.2126	712.4119	712.4119	712.4119
VDAGI	0	474.254	473.2486	473.2486	473.2486
GLIGAP	0	527.2796	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
AVPAGE	0	543.2759	542.27	542.27	542.27
IAELLP	0	328.2214	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
EQTPRWVINLLRT	0	407.2362	1624.9049	1624.9049	1624.9049
GGNAFVMMPAV	1092.5128	547.2637	1092.5096	1092.5096	1092.5096
AGPGGYVAAIRAAELGQKVTVVEKE	0	629.1439	2512.365	2512.365	2512.365
SVDIAKAVDGISLLSESA	0	630.0817	1887.02	1887.02	1887.02
NELRRNNQSMQ	1388.6621	695.3383	1388.6578	1388.6578	1388.6578
IMII	488.3576	245.1861	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
GEPLFSST	0	427.2062	852.3865	852.3865	852.3865
QHPAGVDQI	0	474.2545	946.4509	946.4509	946.4509
DEKAAAQQ	974.3331	488.1738	974.4305	974.4305	974.4305
GIAVPA	0	527.2785	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
VAEESY	0	826.3092	825.3392	825.3392	825.3392
INNVIP	0	328.2223	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
AGRGGGNPN	913.4155	457.715	913.4002	913.4002	913.4002
EIDDDPQAVYDDMPGVA	0	463.2024	1848.7723	1848.7723	1848.7723
ELANQLKIPQ	1153.5532	577.7839	1153.6343	1153.6343	1153.6343
IVRLGALHALQTAVSGVGGAGNIILL	0	629.1384	2512.4854	2512.4854	2512.4854
AGFTGGVMSRNEARAKIGLPPTDDG	0	630.0803	2516.2441	2516.2441	2516.2441
IMIL	488.3576	245.1861	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
TYVF	528.2949	265.1547	528.2584	528.2584	528.2584
SKEERQLQDF	0	427.2056	1278.6205	1278.6205	1278.6205
VDAGI	0	474.2528	473.2486	473.2486	473.2486
DEQQAAADK	974.3331	488.1738	974.4305	974.4305	974.4305
QENAEQAGQ	1102.3918	552.2032	1102.4526	1102.4526	1102.4526
DLVVLP	0	328.2233	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
ISVELLPS	0	429.2692	856.4906	856.4906	856.4906
AGVIGGVMPGG	913.4155	457.715	913.4691	913.4691	913.4691
DEIS	0	463.2008	462.1962	462.1962	462.1962
DKGETAYPN	993.4541	497.7343	993.4404	993.4404	993.4404
LGLVSQGAALPE	1153.5559	577.7852	1153.6343	1153.6343	1153.6343

AQNDRRLPDAA	1182.5688	592.2917	1182.5992	1182.5992	1182.5992
LDGAGP	528.2949	265.1547	528.2544	528.2544	528.2544
RDAPNASYGY	850.3484	426.1815	1275.552	1275.552	1275.552
AGNEE	0	519.2262	518.1973	518.1973	518.1973
AVAVPA	0	527.279	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
TASPQAEQQQ	1102.3918	552.2032	1102.4891	1102.4891	1102.4891
ENASGGQ	0	662.3225	661.2667	661.2667	661.2667
IVNVIP	0	328.2229	654.3952	654.3952	654.3952
GYGSGTW	0	364.0643	726.2973	726.2973	726.2973
HRYQRMME	0	384.1137	1149.5172	1149.5172	1149.5172
IIMMALLAISIP	0	429.2699	1284.7549	1284.7549	1284.7549
NGGSFMILS	0	463.203	924.4375	924.4375	924.4375
SDFPIMDVET	1152.5471	577.2808	1152.5009	1152.5009	1152.5009
TAGNGGANAPAYEF	0	670.3011	1338.584	1338.584	1338.584
FVDI	492.2422	247.1284	492.2584	492.2584	492.2584
EDQAAHLPN	993.4523	497.7334	993.4516	993.4516	993.4516
QENAEQAGQ	1102.3918	552.2032	1102.4526	1102.4526	1102.4526
GLVAKSVVIP	0	328.2227	981.6223	981.6223	981.6223
HNHSQQALSE	0	384.1144	1149.5164	1149.5164	1149.5164
LALGLYLISLIP	0	429.2675	1284.8057	1284.8057	1284.8057
PAPSKVQDR	996.4477	499.2311	996.5352	996.5352	996.5352
MAPVE	0	546.2737	545.252	545.252	545.252
SDFPIMDVET	1152.5471	577.2808	1152.5009	1152.5009	1152.5009
HNGSIALLPLDAKLNLNKLAQN	0	590.1221	2356.3228	2356.3228	2356.3228
HAMIQA	0	670.3017	669.3268	669.3268	669.3268
GTAHF	531.2735	266.644	531.2441	531.2441	531.2441
EYGPL	577.2801	289.6473	577.2748	577.2748	577.2748
IDAPPVNTVT	1026.4939	343.1719	1026.5233	1026.5233	1026.5233
LVVGNNIPGG	996.4477	499.2311	996.524	996.524	996.524
GIALPG	0	527.2789	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
KMAAMSE	0	384.114	766.3353	766.3353	766.3353
IIAI	0	429.2681	428.2999	428.2999	428.2999
IAIDGLGGAGIAGA	1154.5632	578.2889	1154.6295	1154.6295	1154.6295
HLADIEALIDGSDLSDTVKHHA	0	590.1216	2356.166	2356.166	2356.166
QMQQIDKSPDSGEEIAH	0	670.3006	2007.8844	2007.8844	2007.8844
EDLTEKD	0	849.344	848.3763	848.3763	848.3763
NAVVVPLG	0	385.2413	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
IGQNIAPGF	931.4501	466.7323	931.4763	931.4763	931.4763
PGLDRAPNLAPGTPGG	0	497.2654	1488.7684	1488.7684	1488.7684
LDAIAIANNL	1026.4851	514.2498	1026.5709	1026.5709	1026.5709
AVGLAP	0	527.2794	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
EMVSP	0	562.2507	561.2468	561.2468	561.2468
FKHT	531.2735	266.644	531.2805	531.2805	531.2805
EAVVYCEAPVA	0	384.1143	1149.5376	1149.5376	1149.5376
DNDIVLPE	913.4099	457.7122	913.4393	913.4393	913.4393
ADIVE	0	546.2705	545.2697	545.2697	545.2697
IPTGDNPCIPE	1154.5632	578.2889	1154.5278	1154.5278	1154.5278

MVDIE	0	606.2598	605.2731	605.2731	605.2731
ATDGPMPQTREH	0	670.2992	1338.5986	1338.5986	1338.5986
DEVDEQD	0	849.3432	848.3036	848.3036	848.3036
NAVVVPLG	0	385.2433	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
LTHGDTGIGTLDGLNGE	0	418.1446	1668.7955	1668.7955	1668.7955
GDKPALGAGF	931.4501	466.7323	931.4763	931.4763	931.4763
AVAVPA	0	527.2783	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
GTTNRAASKAADEAFAT	1680.7611	561.261	1680.8068	1680.8068	1680.8068
DIPERTRTQAESLTRFRVPPYV	0	675.1015	2696.4036	2696.4036	2696.4036
IMII	488.3568	245.1857	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
IGVLSS	574.3703	288.1924	574.3326	574.3326	574.3326
EAVVYCEAPVA	0	384.1146	1149.5376	1149.5376	1149.5376
SVDRLVPQ	913.4099	457.7122	913.4869	913.4869	913.4869
GAFVAA	0	535.2446	534.2802	534.2802	534.2802
ELITNARLPE	1154.5632	578.2889	1154.6295	1154.6295	1154.6295
TEDEI	0	606.2571	605.2545	605.2545	605.2545
VMDQLEN	0	849.3427	848.3586	848.3586	848.3586
GTILVPLG	0	385.2425	768.4745	768.4745	768.4745
DHSEQLGF	931.4501	466.7323	931.4036	931.4036	931.4036
AVAVPA	0	527.278	526.3115	526.3115	526.3115
DEELQQNVRPSGFY	1680.7611	561.261	1680.7744	1680.7744	1680.7744
DEPKS	0	575.2751	574.2598	574.2598	574.2598
AHANGGSG	0	670.2999	669.2831	669.2831	669.2831
DAANALAV	0	744.3449	743.3813	743.3813	743.3813
IMII	488.3568	245.1857	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
GMVLGV	574.3703	288.1924	574.3149	574.3149	574.3149
PQLPHDE	0	418.1432	834.3872	834.3872	834.3872
IINSQIPE	913.4099	457.7122	913.4756	913.4756	913.4756
ELITNARLPE	1154.5632	578.2889	1154.6295	1154.6295	1154.6295
TEDEI	0	606.2585	605.2545	605.2545	605.2545
EVDQVLIMSVNPGFGGQKFLESSIS	0	675.1031	2696.3367	2696.3367	2696.3367
DPDMLQD	0	849.3426	848.3222	848.3222	848.3222
GTILVPLG	0	385.2437	768.4745	768.4745	768.4745
VEAFSPIAH	1012.5127	507.2636	1012.4978	1012.4978	1012.4978
GLNAGLLKMPQSRH	0	527.2794	1578.8301	1578.8301	1578.8301
NNTNVSNGDWVLFSG	1680.7611	561.261	1680.738	1680.738	1680.738
IMPNT	0	575.2761	574.2785	574.2785	574.2785
DNNLSYLKTKKQKMHHLLTE	0	611.1671	2440.2896	2440.2896	2440.2896
IMII	488.3568	245.1857	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
CLVAAV	574.3703	288.1924	574.3149	574.3149	574.3149
QNMADEQ	0	418.1434	834.3178	834.3178	834.3178
GAFVAA	0	535.2493	534.2802	534.2802	534.2802
GMQTLGV	0	705.3239	704.3527	704.3527	704.3527
DPDMLQD	0	849.3386	848.3222	848.3222	848.3222
SLAIVPIG	0	385.2422	768.4745	768.4745	768.4745
SLAFVFFGLVDYA	1518.7032	507.2417	1518.7759	1518.7759	1518.7759
DTAYAFGIGE	0	522.2154	1042.4607	1042.4607	1042.4607

TVLNPEDHVDVICVAG	1680.7611	561.261	1680.8029	1680.8029	1680.8029
EDAAAV	0	575.2776	574.2598	574.2598	574.2598
MINVV	0	575.3706	574.3149	574.3149	574.3149
GAENGLLA	0	744.346	743.3813	743.3813	743.3813
GMVLGV	574.3703	288.1924	574.3149	574.3149	574.3149
LEIASYDADLVGEFG	0	418.1432	1668.7883	1668.7883	1668.7883
GFYGLGGSAAVAA	0	535.2467	1068.524	1068.524	1068.524
GLDNIRNDYQEIIDHRLPE	0	578.2836	2309.1401	2309.1401	2309.1401
SKSPLTVALGVDFGQPQVTDLR	0	611.1651	2440.3325	2440.3325	2440.3325
VSTPKLIEPGI	0	385.2427	1152.6754	1152.6754	1152.6754
LIPALNGPHSPVTGF	1518.7032	507.2417	1518.8195	1518.8195	1518.8195
EAVED	0	562.2549	561.2282	561.2282	561.2282
MEDVI	0	606.2601	605.2731	605.2731	605.2731
GLDYHWDTSPQ	1334.5349	668.2747	1334.5415	1334.5415	1334.5415
AMGALQPG	0	744.3465	743.3636	743.3636	743.3636
VGMVAV	574.3703	288.1924	574.3149	574.3149	574.3149
GGLNLPE	740.4413	371.2279	740.3705	740.3705	740.3705
LEIASYDADLVGEFG	0	418.143	1668.7883	1668.7883	1668.7883
DTAYAFGIGE	0	522.2136	1042.4607	1042.4607	1042.4607
MGLGAA	0	535.2466	534.2472	534.2472	534.2472
GLDNIRNDYQEIIDHRLPE	0	578.2813	2309.1401	2309.1401	2309.1401
NAVVVPLG	0	385.2427	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
FLDEAGGD	0	412.0807	822.3395	822.3395	822.3395
AIAAYMKNIAPKQT	1518.7026	507.2415	1518.8229	1518.8229	1518.8229
ITDVD	0	562.2628	561.2646	561.2646	561.2646
DDDEI	0	606.2567	605.2181	605.2181	605.2181
ANGIHMAYIAIENDPVPVGVYNAI	0	636.0797	2540.2734	2540.2734	2540.2734
GVMATP	574.3703	288.1924	574.2785	574.2785	574.2785
DPSGWVGFVGCE	0	418.1431	1251.5231	1251.5231	1251.5231
GAMASV	0	535.2466	534.2472	534.2472	534.2472
DEVIAHLEET	0	578.2805	1154.5455	1154.5455	1154.5455
VAGSYFVTALQTVISRRIDPFDTG	0	654.0906	2612.3599	2612.3599	2612.3599
TPGIVPIG	0	385.2425	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
ITDVISLP	0	429.2674	856.4906	856.4906	856.4906
AKVTVTAAQATAGIAF	1518.7026	507.2415	1518.8406	1518.8406	1518.8406
AAMETYQAH	1020.4503	511.2324	1020.4335	1020.4335	1020.4335
IISDD	0	562.266	561.2646	561.2646	561.2646
MEDVI	0	606.2585	605.2731	605.2731	605.2731
PEKELTMSTKPKYQQALSAYVE	0	636.0793	2540.2832	2540.2832	2540.2832
GGPTVFEE	0	418.1437	834.376	834.376	834.376
GIPGL	0	456.2406	455.2744	455.2744	455.2744
FVDIVMPI	0	475.2383	948.499	948.499	948.499
VETPMNFNQ	1079.4193	540.7169	1079.4594	1079.4594	1079.4594
ATSKIQAQEQIDPTTLGQVRDIGNTG	0	654.0886	2612.3406	2612.3406	2612.3406
AGVFQDL	0	375.1842	748.3755	748.3755	748.3755
GTILVPLG	0	385.2431	768.4745	768.4745	768.4745
FLDEAGGD	0	412.0817	822.3395	822.3395	822.3395

SATDDAINQAQDAVT	1518.6934	507.2384	1518.6798	1518.6798	1518.6798
DEAIDAVTVSDLLTAQNQLDD	0	562.2644	2245.0598	2245.0598	2245.0598
MEDVI	0	606.2585	605.2731	605.2731	605.2731
PEKELTMSTKPKYQQALSAVYE	0	636.0807	2540.2832	2540.2832	2540.2832
SLSGLNV	0	345.2121	688.3755	688.3755	688.3755
NTDPQ	0	575.2775	574.2234	574.2234	574.2234
ASAPNVKLIENVVSCPNVKEGGIAFG	0	654.0878	2612.3633	2612.3633	2612.3633
KAGEHAMNALEEY	0	740.3285	1478.6348	1478.6348	1478.6348
GTILVPLG	0	385.2412	768.4745	768.4745	768.4745
AIGGTIGTGLFLGAGQS	1518.6934	507.2384	1518.8042	1518.8042	1518.8042
ITEIS	0	562.262	561.301	561.301	561.301
PENPTEPTPE	0	606.2558	1210.5354	1210.5354	1210.5354
GGLLPGFMPVWAYGWNALGKNPVF	0	636.0801	2540.304	2540.304	2540.304
AKVVDHAKVVGPT	0	345.2133	1376.7776	1376.7776	1376.7776
AGFEIATT	0	405.21	808.3967	808.3967	808.3967
IDLGSDKVYVYNV	1483.7202	495.5807	1483.7559	1483.7559	1483.7559
KPNSIPDYNT	0	575.2766	1148.5349	1148.5349	1148.5349
ENIGMVFQHFNLFPHLSVLQNI	0	654.0873	2612.321	2612.321	2612.321
GPADP	0	456.2388	455.2016	455.2016	455.2016
ADEWLTIR	0	502.2458	1002.5134	1002.5134	1002.5134
RVQDFANAQEGHF	1518.6934	507.2384	1518.6852	1518.6852	1518.6852
PEKELTMSTKPKYQQALSAVYE	0	636.0774	2540.2832	2540.2832	2540.2832
LDLDDLIM	0	981.4163	980.4525	980.4525	980.4525
FAHGGS	0	575.2767	574.2499	574.2499	574.2499
DGQVVAPVD	898.5091	450.2618	898.4396	898.4396	898.4396
GVIDKE	0	660.3145	659.349	659.349	659.349
ESGGFNAF	0	828.3661	827.345	827.345	827.345
EDNNPIPF	0	473.208	944.424	944.424	944.424
DEDN	0	492.1818	491.15	491.15	491.15
MMLFTPDM	0	493.2138	984.4119	984.4119	984.4119
ADVLQLVED	1000.4971	501.2558	1000.5077	1000.5077	1000.5077
FDFDNLPP	0	981.4102	980.4127	980.4127	980.4127
FISGELAY	898.5091	450.2618	898.4437	898.4437	898.4437
DFPI	0	491.2152	490.2427	490.2427	490.2427
DAQSVTDNSSPASS	0	494.2149	1479.5961	1479.5961	1479.5961
LDGEGYTYP	1045.4895	523.752	1045.4241	1045.4241	1045.4241
AQQAHA	0	554.2529	553.2609	553.2609	553.2609
DEPKS	0	575.2795	574.2598	574.2598	574.2598
PENLDQVFGQTHLLGPGK	0	488.2461	1949.0007	1949.0007	1949.0007
EAENDEE	0	418.1423	834.2879	834.2879	834.2879
DNQITFDE	0	491.215	980.4087	980.4087	980.4087
AGDSII	0	575.2738	574.2963	574.2963	574.2963
AADTATTFI	0	304.1617	909.4443	909.4443	909.4443
EAEVPD	0	330.1649	658.281	658.281	658.281
DKISFF	755.3597	378.6871	755.3854	755.3854	755.3854
VGFLVGQI	0	417.2318	832.4695	832.4695	832.4695
GLASLGATPI	898.5091	450.2618	898.5124	898.5124	898.5124

KLGPAMALV	898.5091	450.2618	898.531	898.531	898.531
DVNKFDQQFPPK	0	488.2474	1461.7252	1461.7252	1461.7252
DIMMPEMD	0	491.2137	980.3653	980.3653	980.3653
NEDIIEYVT	1094.504	548.2593	1094.5132	1094.5132	1094.5132
QPDTVQAPTPP	1150.5576	576.2861	1150.5507	1150.5507	1150.5507
IGLMPHMTIRE	1296.6102	649.3124	1296.6682	1296.6682	1296.6682
FGVNTFII	0	304.1629	909.496	909.496	909.496
DVPHGV	0	312.1517	622.3075	622.3075	622.3075
TEVQNTPTVT	0	330.1635	987.4873	987.4873	987.4873
EEVFGKE	836.4145	419.2145	836.3916	836.3916	836.3916
LSGRVSALP	898.5091	450.2618	898.5236	898.5236	898.5236
APDAFVVPK	942.5015	472.258	942.5175	942.5175	942.5175
LTLVLP	654.3365	328.1755	654.4316	654.4316	654.4316
GAVMDNL	718.3571	360.1858	718.332	718.332	718.332
QAAAPAMMIP	982.4711	492.2428	982.4616	982.4616	982.4616
AGVLGPGYTVAV	1102.5195	552.267	1102.6023	1102.6023	1102.6023
AENLFQSNEV	1150.5576	576.2861	1150.5143	1150.5143	1150.5143
VASNQKPDEPVP	1296.6102	649.3124	1296.6198	1296.6198	1296.6198
CIDKVEE	834.4075	418.211	834.3793	834.3793	834.3793
VAMGLGQQLP	942.5015	472.258	942.4844	942.4844	942.4844
DADTLAEIAI	1030.4983	516.2564	1030.5183	1030.5183	1030.5183
GLQLDEILNPVT	1311.6074	656.811	1311.6921	1311.6921	1311.6921
TMGALAGV	718.3571	360.1858	718.3683	718.3683	718.3683
DVVESLII	886.4719	444.2432	886.5012	886.5012	886.5012
EAVNIGESY	980.4065	491.2105	980.4451	980.4451	980.4451
SVVASPAFNL	1020.4485	511.2315	1020.5128	1020.5128	1020.5128
IGEGSRGVSSGGQ	1102.5197	552.2671	1102.5367	1102.5367	1102.5367
EAMQEMALII	1147.5024	574.7585	1147.5618	1147.5618	1147.5618
GIKPLGA	654.3365	328.1755	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
GRNMAGAH	812.4559	407.2352	812.3712	812.3712	812.3712
DLMPVPIQ	912.4391	457.2268	912.4626	912.4626	912.4626
SLDISEGDVP	1030.4983	516.2564	1030.4818	1030.4818	1030.4818
SKNVKSQP	886.4719	444.2432	886.4872	886.4872	886.4872
ETPYFIPD	980.4065	491.2105	980.4491	980.4491	980.4491
QDKVQPKKA	1040.5349	521.2747	1040.5979	1040.5979	1040.5979
VSYIAAQAPIA	1102.5197	552.2671	1102.6023	1102.6023	1102.6023
PTPNPSHSPQS	1147.5024	574.7585	1147.5258	1147.5258	1147.5258
LRIYQNPQF	1178.5741	590.2943	1178.6084	1178.6084	1178.6084
SPATDALTYQLK	1307.6324	654.8235	1307.6609	1307.6609	1307.6609
GAPGIIQ	654.3365	328.1755	654.3701	654.3701	654.3701
AGFLYGW	812.4559	407.2352	812.3857	812.3857	812.3857
ITGSMIPVI	929.4877	465.7511	929.5256	929.5256	929.5256
TVQTLYRANGAQVKYHGGLYTNQC	0	856.1379	3420.6487	3420.6487	3420.6487
AQKLEKAPE	1125.5557	376.1925	1125.6394	1125.6394	1125.6394
PIDAPFSVGC	1020.4487	511.2316	1020.4586	1020.4586	1020.4586
EPESGAPILL	1040.5349	521.2747	1040.5389	1040.5389	1040.5389
IGEGSRGVSSGGQ	1102.5244	552.2695	1102.5367	1102.5367	1102.5367

PQSPTNYDPI	1147.5002	574.7574	1147.5033	1147.5033	1147.5033
VEGARAEVPLGA	1168.5858	585.3002	1168.6088	1168.6088	1168.6088
ATLGANAGPLPVV	1178.5741	590.2943	1178.6659	1178.6659	1178.6659
AANAVIP	654.3365	328.1755	654.3701	654.3701	654.3701
GAVAVVPSP	795.3909	398.7027	795.449	795.449	795.449
AAPNNLLT	812.4559	407.2352	812.4392	812.4392	812.4392
DFQVLIVP	929.4877	465.7511	929.5222	929.5222	929.5222
SAANNADGSVANVIQQTNQ	1900.8616	634.6278	1900.8875	1900.8875	1900.8875
FTGMILNNRGAM	1324.6023	663.3084	1324.6268	1324.6268	1324.6268
ATAEAAE	661.3188	331.6667	661.2919	661.2919	661.2919
IVRNDLVVVV	1125.5557	376.1925	1125.6758	1125.6758	1125.6758
EPKEAQVP	896.4831	449.2488	896.4603	896.4603	896.4603
KPNSIPDYNT	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.5349	1148.5349	1148.5349
PGTSLFGLAYGS	1168.5858	585.3002	1168.5764	1168.5764	1168.5764
VTIIDGAFSGLS	1178.5741	590.2943	1178.6183	1178.6183	1178.6183
AGKAVPL	654.3365	328.1755	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
NIIQLPIQ	938.4547	470.2346	938.5437	938.5437	938.5437
TLQAEPVNFHGIEAYR	1900.8545	634.6254	1900.9431	1900.9431	1900.9431
QSADKEVGLVKY	1318.6373	660.3259	1318.6769	1318.6769	1318.6769
DAGFDYSVVKPAG	1324.6023	663.3084	1324.6299	1324.6299	1324.6299
IMII	488.3576	245.1861	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
GLLANGFSA	0	284.2061	849.4232	849.4232	849.4232
DVAAGMV	661.3188	331.6667	661.3105	661.3105	661.3105
DLTVLPTV	856.4455	429.23	856.4906	856.4906	856.4906
PGIVHVPY	896.4831	449.2488	896.4756	896.4756	896.4756
KPNSIPDYNT	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.5349	1148.5349	1148.5349
ADLLGNFVSFQ	1167.519	584.7668	1167.556	1167.556	1167.556
AGKAVPL	0	328.2224	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
AGIPMQIPL	938.4547	470.2346	938.5259	938.5259	938.5259
VDEIIVYV	948.4571	475.2358	948.5168	948.5168	948.5168
GWSRQLAPN	1027.4547	514.7346	1027.5199	1027.5199	1027.5199
MVEAELDLTP	1116.5488	559.2817	1116.5372	1116.5372	1116.5372
LDLMQDVENK	1204.6033	603.3089	1204.5646	1204.5646	1204.5646
KEFAALGIVEEN	1318.6373	660.3259	1318.6769	1318.6769	1318.6769
PVHLTV	664.4259	333.2202	664.3908	664.3908	664.3908
ISVAGLAGGL	856.4455	429.23	856.5018	856.5018	856.5018
DLPVLVTH	892.5347	447.2746	892.5018	892.5018	892.5018
QSLPDLIL	896.4831	449.2488	896.4855	896.4855	896.4855
PLMEPAEIAE	1098.5261	550.2703	1098.5267	1098.5267	1098.5267
PLMEPAEIAE	1098.5261	550.2703	1098.5267	1098.5267	1098.5267
AEILADPEYE	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.5237	1148.5237	1148.5237
AVPAKGI	0	328.2231	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
LPIQMPIGA	938.4525	470.2335	938.5259	938.5259	938.5259
ETPFVDEL	948.4725	475.2435	948.444	948.444	948.444
GIANNGIQSV	971.4333	486.7239	971.5036	971.5036	971.5036
DAAVDAGINYI	1120.5667	561.2906	1120.54	1120.54	1120.54
AGNVPN	0	571.3042	570.2762	570.2762	570.2762

PAGMDVNDLNK	1204.6033	603.3089	1204.5394	1204.5394	1204.5394
IMII	488.3576	245.1861	488.3033	488.3033	488.3033
LSNNLPLS	856.4313	429.2229	856.4655	856.4655	856.4655
DLPVLVTH	892.5347	447.2746	892.5018	892.5018	892.5018
LDPAICGLARA	1098.5261	550.2703	1098.5856	1098.5856	1098.5856
LLFSIGGIVPS	1101.5531	551.7838	1101.6434	1101.6434	1101.6434
ALPGGTYKNT	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.619	1148.619	1148.619
GLASPSGSLFDDPSKVSQV	1905.865	636.2956	1905.932	1905.932	1905.932
QNIGLAEEQLES	1312.6077	657.3111	1312.6146	1312.6146	1312.6146
AVPAKGI	0	328.2226	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
ATPSLPLIQ	938.4525	470.2335	938.5437	938.5437	938.5437
AGNVPN	1140.5667	571.2906	570.2762	570.2762	570.2762
VAVHPNDDVNQ	1206.593	604.3038	1206.5629	1206.5629	1206.5629
DPAICGLARAIGE	1300.6029	651.3087	1300.6445	1300.6445	1300.6445
PAAPAAPNPGMGGMM	1368.6157	685.3151	1368.5989	1368.5989	1368.5989
KSDPFE	0	722.3135	721.3282	721.3282	721.3282
DFFP	524.2619	263.1382	524.2271	524.2271	524.2271
LPVILLIP	892.5347	447.2746	892.5997	892.5997	892.5997
LNAHPQLN	906.4521	454.2333	906.4559	906.4559	906.4559
NATAILIGLG	942.4609	472.2377	942.5386	942.5386	942.5386
ALQAVGAQLP	966.4703	484.2424	966.5498	966.5498	966.5498
LGSSISQLAH	1098.5261	550.2703	1098.5669	1098.5669	1098.5669
ALPGGTYKNT	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.619	1148.619	1148.619
TGPVSWDVEDDPTDEVTAKIESLDV 0		919.1669	3672.6592	3672.6592	3672.6592
AGKAVPL	0	328.2231	654.4064	654.4064	654.4064
GAKLSYALDV	0	346.1966	1035.5601	1035.5601	1035.5601
MLNFQVPQ	976.4745	489.2445	976.4688	976.4688	976.4688
GIGPETADYV	1020.4487	511.2316	1020.4764	1020.4764	1020.4764
INESTAHNSE	1100.551	551.2828	1100.4734	1100.4734	1100.4734
AGNVPN	1140.5667	571.2906	570.2762	570.2762	570.2762
AKNIGMGFASTA	1166.5219	584.2682	1166.5754	1166.5754	1166.5754
APGLAVMPILANE	1310.6207	656.3176	1310.6904	1310.6904	1310.6904
FIEI	520.2737	261.1441	520.2897	520.2897	520.2897
QCTWTT	721.3113	361.6629	721.2741	721.2741	721.2741
SPGQLAGLE	870.4441	436.2293	870.4447	870.4447	870.4447
HQGQLPEV	906.4521	454.2333	906.4559	906.4559	906.4559
VAMGLGQGLP	942.4609	472.2377	942.4844	942.4844	942.4844
AVQALVAPAQ	966.4703	484.2424	966.5498	966.5498	966.5498
IITGVGMGGGV	991.5059	496.7602	991.5009	991.5009	991.5009
LSRLNTIGEM	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.5859	1148.5859	1148.5859
TSNGTVGFTGGDITIDNGD	1840.8651	921.4398	1840.7963	1840.7963	1840.7963
GIAPGAVA	654.4299	328.2222	654.3701	654.3701	654.3701
LDVNNIRNPVEV	0	346.1963	1380.7361	1380.7361	1380.7361
LNGPGAVDFM	1020.4487	511.2316	1020.4586	1020.4586	1020.4586
AASDIITKGHE	1140.5667	571.2906	1140.5775	1140.5775	1140.5775
TTGANEMGDPSVFT	0	722.3123	1442.5872	1442.5872	1442.5872
GPALATLIEAMHYDEIFGTLGDD	2464.0969	822.3729	2464.1467	2464.1467	2464.1467

GLEHVGIM	870.4421	436.2283	870.4269	870.4269	870.4269
DLDHFAPV	912.4579	457.2362	912.4341	912.4341	912.4341
ENDVNQNS	918.1659	460.0902	918.3679	918.3679	918.3679
AQLASASQPA	942.4609	472.2377	942.4771	942.4771	942.4771
ELFVNLIM	977.4723	489.7434	977.5256	977.5256	977.5256
ALLVGLGPGPDP	1120.5469	561.2807	1120.6128	1120.6128	1120.6128
QDLLHTATHN	1148.5516	575.2831	1148.5575	1148.5575	1148.5575
QAPLIMMSQNR	1303.6171	652.8158	1303.6377	1303.6377	1303.6377
DYFI	556.3255	279.17	556.2533	556.2533	556.2533
LLTVPL	654.4299	328.2222	654.4316	654.4316	654.4316
QGKAAQSSNF	1020.4493	511.2319	1020.4512	1020.4512	1020.4512
AGIVPGFYTIDIP	1377.6772	689.8459	1377.718	1377.718	1377.718
NENPTNFTDVEEAAMSPAN	0	722.312	2163.9016	2163.9016	2163.9016
GENGIILGV	870.4421	436.2283	870.4811	870.4811	870.4811
LSAALAGVIP	910.4729	456.2437	910.5488	910.5488	910.5488
DVAFGLENL	977.4679	489.7412	977.4706	977.4706	977.4706
ALLVGLGPGPDP	1120.5469	561.2807	1120.6128	1120.6128	1120.6128
SDQPMSVQEL	1148.5385	575.2765	1148.502	1148.502	1148.502
LMTVDL	0	346.1975	690.3622	690.3622	690.3622
FNDVRIIN	990.5521	496.2833	990.5134	990.5134	990.5134
PGAVAQTLHQ	1020.4525	511.2335	1020.5352	1020.5352	1020.5352
MNPSGTVLEPPY	1303.618	652.8163	1303.6118	1303.6118	1303.6118
ALANPVYDLEDIVQQ	0	844.4349	1686.8464	1686.8464	1686.8464
AGIQPRDV	870.4421	436.2283	870.4559	870.4559	870.4559
AGASAVLLIV	912.4979	457.2562	912.5644	912.5644	912.5644
EGIGNEVYP	976.4745	489.2445	976.4502	976.4502	976.4502
ALITPTIFGNA	1116.5491	559.2818	1116.6179	1116.6179	1116.6179
GGSIROPSSFN	1148.5441	575.2793	1148.5575	1148.5575	1148.5575
EDLNFHVNSE	1202.4288	602.2217	1202.5204	1202.5204	1202.5204
DIVMDV	0	346.1942	690.3258	690.3258	690.3258
DVAVGSQV	773.4387	387.7266	773.3919	773.3919	773.3919
QDDLSVEAL	988.4863	495.2504	988.4713	988.4713	988.4713
NNPKVVLPHS	1103.6295	552.822	1103.6088	1103.6088	1103.6088
KDPEVDQTMLL	1303.618	652.8163	1303.6329	1303.6329	1303.6329
IEPALEN	0	785.3638	784.3967	784.3967	784.3967
ELQKAQQ	0	844.437	843.445	843.445	843.445
DFFP	524.2599	263.1372	524.2271	524.2271	524.2271
EKEYIGGVCLNV	1323.6277	442.2165	1323.6381	1323.6381	1323.6381
AVIALSVVAE	970.5367	486.2756	970.5699	970.5699	970.5699
DDIDVLDSLI	1116.5491	559.2818	1116.5551	1116.5551	1116.5551
EDQSDALGLTT	1148.5383	575.2764	1148.5197	1148.5197	1148.5197
GLIGPLAFLVF	1161.6083	581.8114	1161.6798	1161.6798	1161.6798
SDQPFE	0	722.3191	721.2919	721.2919	721.2919
LVRNAS	0	330.2378	658.3762	658.3762	658.3762
DGVIIGVP	0	385.243	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
GIPTGISGI	813.3927	407.7036	813.4596	813.4596	813.4596
LAPQIYAAMVYSPS	1510.6895	756.352	1510.7378	1510.7378	1510.7378

HGELDFLIGQNPET	0	785.3635	1568.7471	1568.7471	1568.7471
NPKFPEL	0	844.4345	843.449	843.449	843.449
ADPAVAAGVNS	970.5367	486.2756	970.472	970.472	970.472
LVREVIQH	992.4871	497.2508	992.5767	992.5767	992.5767
GMLLPVAIQD	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.5583	1087.5583	1087.5583
IVSQFIGLGDT	1148.5391	575.2768	1148.6078	1148.6078	1148.6078
LASGLLGIGSGAF	1161.6083	581.8114	1161.6394	1161.6394	1161.6394
AQAMSKS	0	722.3338	721.3429	721.3429	721.3429
MDIMSGE	0	798.3191	797.2935	797.2935	797.2935
ALAAKDIRIEAPI	0	346.1965	1380.7976	1380.7976	1380.7976
IFVSTGV	721.313	361.6638	721.4011	721.4011	721.4011
TAGIVGLP	768.4739	385.2442	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
DLVLMDEP	930.4734	466.244	930.4368	930.4368	930.4368
IDYTDAPGPQ	1091.5193	546.7669	1091.4772	1091.4772	1091.4772
VAGIDYLPQ	974.4635	488.239	974.5073	974.5073	974.5073
GIPTVEHLK	992.4871	497.2508	992.5655	992.5655	992.5655
DGAMLMIQI	1006.4944	504.2545	1006.4827	1006.4827	1006.4827
QGIAGLITPVP	1047.5139	524.7642	1047.5964	1047.5964	1047.5964
SAIGGGLSQLW	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.5662	1087.5662	1087.5662
LPNAPQRP GAL	1148.5388	575.2767	1148.6302	1148.6302	1148.6302
LASGLLGIGSGAF	1161.6083	581.8114	1161.6394	1161.6394	1161.6394
APKNYAVPYK	1166.6136	584.3141	1166.5972	1166.5972	1166.5972
PNVPV	524.2599	263.1372	524.2958	524.2958	524.2958
VEVNRINNV DL	0	346.196	1380.7361	1380.7361	1380.7361
DGVIIGVP	768.4739	385.2442	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
LTGALGDPAV	912.4979	457.2562	912.4916	912.4916	912.4916
DKPGANPNHV	1047.5139	524.7642	1047.5098	1047.5098	1047.5098
HNAVLQGPLGA	1091.5193	546.7669	1091.5724	1091.5724	1091.5724
PQSDEF	0	722.3164	721.2919	721.2919	721.2919
GLVAFGVL	774.3841	388.1993	774.464	774.464	774.464
AGLMMPLGAI	1004.4943	503.2544	1004.5035	1004.5035	1004.5035
GDVVGVGGTMTG	0	525.2259	1048.486	1048.486	1048.486
GMLLPVAIQD	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.5583	1087.5583	1087.5583
LNPAFAIIIAG	1115.5575	558.786	1115.6227	1115.6227	1115.6227
AGERPVIMVGD	1142.5247	572.2696	1142.5754	1142.5754	1142.5754
CYTIGAAIIPGA	1148.5388	575.2767	1148.59	1148.59	1148.59
EMAVPK	1346.6854	674.35	673.3469	673.3469	673.3469
AAELAVPV	0	769.4766	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
DGVIIGVP	768.4739	385.2442	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
AHGPADIHAY	1050.494	526.2543	1050.4883	1050.4883	1050.4883
GAHDTVAIAPH	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.541	1087.541	1087.541
LTKAEEVDAL	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.576	1087.576	1087.576
AAVVPADGTIY	1091.5193	546.7669	1091.5499	1091.5499	1091.5499
ADANGEHEIF	1101.5569	551.7857	1101.4727	1101.4727	1101.4727
AGVMGGLT	0	705.3147	704.3527	704.3527	704.3527
AHGSTLRAMIKYLEHISDTGIDGVEVA	0	867.4416	3465.7385	3465.7385	3465.7385
IGMSIGVV	774.3766	388.1956	774.431	774.431	774.431

APVSMGPLGAL	1011.4671	506.7408	1011.5423	1011.5423	1011.5423
TAVVGNLYGTG	1050.494	526.2543	1050.5345	1050.5345	1050.5345
GPIGALMTTAW	1148.5388	575.2767	1148.5536	1148.5536	1148.5536
NLAGGAGDGGTSSGI	1233.5681	617.7913	1233.5474	1233.5474	1233.5474
VGIPHVAGSVAVNK	1346.6854	674.35	1346.7671	1346.7671	1346.7671
LGIGAVIGTGIFILPGTVAALKAGP	0	769.4781	2305.3774	2305.3774	2305.3774
ENYPGFKSILGPDIAKEMYESSTQFG/0		836.3958	3341.5439	3341.5439	3341.5439
DGVIIGVP	768.4739	385.2442	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
EFPNFPK	878.4405	440.2275	878.4174	878.4174	878.4174
AGDKIDDSII	1045.4913	523.7529	1045.5292	1045.5292	1045.5292
VQAPLTKAAH	1050.494	526.2543	1050.5822	1050.5822	1050.5822
AKMTVDLGVMM	1063.4911	532.7528	1063.5405	1063.5405	1063.5405
AHAGASSNFVQ	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.5046	1087.5046	1087.5046
QDGADQTPAAD	1087.5259	544.7702	1087.4418	1087.4418	1087.4418
VPQNPLPAPQ	1091.5193	546.7669	1091.5612	1091.5612	1091.5612
GIAVMSNSAIMG	1149.54	575.7773	1149.5522	1149.5522	1149.5522
NQIQSGLATEIAVTYQEPVEIVDAVPC0		768.4001	3069.5757	3069.5757	3069.5757
ATANQ	0	504.2422	503.234	503.234	503.234
NEDQDLVV	1045.4913	523.7529	1045.4564	1045.4564	1045.4564
APEFAGKNAF	1050.494	526.2543	1050.5134	1050.5134	1050.5134
VAGPEGLEGHAP	1148.5388	575.2767	1148.5461	1148.5461	1148.5461
VGIPHVAGSVAVNK	1346.6854	674.35	1346.7671	1346.7671	1346.7671
DSGSIVAG	0	705.3147	704.3341	704.3341	704.3341
MMEPSK	0	722.3089	721.3139	721.3139	721.3139
VVDAIGVP	0	769.4763	768.4382	768.4382	768.4382
AMSLAQFVLPFIVAAQPNAQ	0	1058.576	2115.1187	2115.1187	2115.1187
ITVALVGP	768.4739	385.2442	768.4745	768.4745	768.4745
KDIQQQMAALTFTDEGPE	0	506.2371	2020.9412	2020.9412	2020.9412
AVSEPK	0	630.3161	629.3384	629.3384	629.3384
AAFAADQTPSELQ	1347.6895	674.852	1347.6306	1347.6306	1347.6306
FIVELP	0	717.3701	716.4109	716.4109	716.4109
SGPGALVAVGYMDPGNWSTSITGGC0		744.3419	2973.3604	2973.3604	2973.3604
AVLAIGIPSNARVNGIMYPIIDL	0	880.152	2637.4312	2637.4312	2637.4312
MLKINYPK	1006.5083	504.2614	1006.5521	1006.5521	1006.5521
KPHCDALPNGAQAPT	0	507.2094	1518.7249	1518.7249	1518.7249
ALVQDKIGAH	1050.494	526.2543	1050.5822	1050.5822	1050.5822
VGGSQTIGANA	1087.5255	544.77	1087.5509	1087.5509	1087.5509
GLIGENGAGFIT	1148.5388	575.2767	1148.5714	1148.5714	1148.5714
PGILGYIMGAPL	1200.5739	601.2942	1200.6577	1200.6577	1200.6577
AAIAGIP	0	612.3263	611.3643	611.3643	611.3643
DAIYAL	0	665.3085	664.3432	664.3432	664.3432
VGIPHVAGSVAVNK	1346.6854	674.35	1346.7671	1346.7671	1346.7671
VENGADVMKQVNEP	0	766.3446	1530.6871	1530.6871	1530.6871
IGAAVIRASCP	1056.5343	529.2744	1056.575	1056.575	1056.575
GDIVPA	0	571.2682	570.3013	570.3013	570.3013
GAKGHL	0	582.3198	581.3286	581.3286	581.3286
KTLNEVAKALTPQVE	0	585.3213	1752.9622	1752.9622	1752.9622

PNGTTVVQPRPEEVPAPT	0	630.3211	1887.969	1887.969	1887.969
TFVQGASIEFSADGPLRAPY	0	709.3459	2125.0481	2125.0481	2125.0481
CQNNHLYASVAMA	0	711.2505	1420.6228	1420.6228	1420.6228
MEATPIG	0	718.3568	717.3367	717.3367	717.3367
KSDPFE	0	722.3128	721.3282	721.3282	721.3282
TLGVLSSVVGICMDV	1548.7083	775.3614	1548.7892	1548.7892	1548.7892
VAAIIV	584.3161	293.1653	584.3898	584.3898	584.3898
AVPGPSQPAAP	1006.5083	504.2614	1006.5084	1006.5084	1006.5084
TCLLLIDGAAV	1087.5255	544.77	1087.5947	1087.5947	1087.5947
GLLESPNPIP	1148.5388	575.2767	1148.6078	1148.6078	1148.6078
ANLGNVDQVTV	1200.5739	601.2942	1200.5986	1200.5986	1200.5986
TPAGGTQPPNPAV	1222.5682	612.2914	1222.583	1222.583	1222.583
AGNAADV	0	617.3058	616.2817	616.2817	616.2817
ASAASYALSNAAGSYAIANDVNSGVGN	0	665.3121	2657.2568	2657.2568	2657.2568
AAKTGMLANSVVD	1346.6854	674.35	1346.6864	1346.6864	1346.6864
AATDMKRVFDADTYWDSIEDFDEPQ	0	766.3463	3061.3289	3061.3289	3061.3289
DYIF	556.3249	279.1697	556.2533	556.2533	556.2533
AHGLA	0	468.2473	467.2492	467.2492	467.2492
TLSNGILIGVA	1056.5343	529.2744	1056.6179	1056.6179	1056.6179
FPYE	0	555.2402	554.2377	554.2377	554.2377
VAAVPE	0	585.3219	584.317	584.317	584.317
EVNPMLAGIGFVVGLEV	0	587.3276	1758.9226	1758.9226	1758.9226
VLRESESQKMQTVPVGT	0	630.3224	1887.9724	1887.9724	1887.9724
VEDQVNAAVSLYN	0	711.2541	1420.6835	1420.6835	1420.6835
ADEALEA	0	718.3562	717.3181	717.3181	717.3181
MAQPKNFDAFYEQGMTANT	0	722.3104	2163.9241	2163.9241	2163.9241
APVLAVIVMVA	0	399.2586	1194.741	1194.741	1194.741
DPVEIQEN	0	472.2013	942.4294	942.4294	942.4294
AEQARQHPQ	1063.5281	532.7713	1063.5159	1063.5159	1063.5159
AYHDGAVGIQG	1086.5083	544.2614	1086.5094	1086.5094	1086.5094
LNLNELHLE	1093.5299	547.7722	1093.5768	1093.5768	1093.5768
NAPIYPQQSQQAQK	0	577.2916	1728.8431	1728.8431	1728.8431
DAVNATTIGGGPL	1200.5739	601.2942	1200.5986	1200.5986	1200.5986
EVYDPNEVIE	0	604.2936	1206.5292	1206.5292	1206.5292
ANAGTLGSNPDSTDPHETTGPQESQI	0	766.3462	3061.3384	3061.3384	3061.3384
YTAMAGAIGAGGLGALAYN	0	879.4494	1756.8455	1756.8455	1756.8455
FMIF	556.3249	279.1697	556.2719	556.2719	556.2719
DGGIMFNGGN	0	491.2122	980.4022	980.4022	980.4022
PTQPAVAVKP	1006.5083	504.2614	1006.5811	1006.5811	1006.5811
GIGLACVYFL	1054.4879	528.2512	1054.5521	1054.5521	1054.5521
QGGSLFFPYQ	0	555.2433	1108.4713	1108.4713	1108.4713
GLRAGVGLAAPQ	0	555.3095	1108.6353	1108.6353	1108.6353
VAAVPE	0	585.324	584.317	584.317	584.317
GSLEPQ	0	630.3202	629.3021	629.3021	629.3021
GMSAAIPTNELSASS	0	718.356	1434.666	1434.666	1434.666
DTSPNSTVSSQAESGAMMVESNEQ	0	722.3127	2885.1814	2885.1814	2885.1814
IGTGLGQIIRGTVLVP	0	399.2587	1592.9614	1592.9614	1592.9614

QSSGAANTNQKVEP	0	472.2034	1413.6372	1413.6372	1413.6372
FIDLQNVQ	0	489.2316	976.4866	976.4866	976.4866
AASSANGTNGNGFPNNNNASS	0	492.206	1964.8209	1964.8209	1964.8209
ARVPAAQPVR	1063.5265	532.7705	1063.6251	1063.6251	1063.6251
LGGGIPEMICS	1091.5217	546.7681	1091.4991	1091.4991	1091.4991
EVYDPNEVIE	0	604.2962	1206.5292	1206.5292	1206.5292
SVGLDYLI	0	879.4508	878.4749	878.4749	878.4749
FEGNEFEDVNGWFPQ	0	908.4002	1814.7424	1814.7424	1814.7424
VSAGADIAPRV	1054.4877	528.2511	1054.5771	1054.5771	1054.5771
IIGTIGEFYP	0	555.3073	1108.5804	1108.5804	1108.5804
DQSFQEVSLP	1148.5259	575.2702	1148.5349	1148.5349	1148.5349
QPVILVSPLLPEDIQQINHA	0	585.3217	2337.2581	2337.2581	2337.2581
AVDGIPI	0	684.35	683.3854	683.3854	683.3854
SSTSTSAASTATSSST	0	717.2917	1432.6166	1432.6166	1432.6166
QPDASNEAPGDEPT	0	722.3126	1442.5797	1442.5797	1442.5797
NQPAEISQ	0	886.4117	885.4192	885.4192	885.4192
AGDIKAVYNGLNLPVLSPP	0	485.2723	1937.0623	1937.0623	1937.0623
IMDLMLPQ	0	489.2329	976.4609	976.4609	976.4609
IMDVVGLPSF	0	547.2942	1092.5525	1092.5525	1092.5525
GDGLSMIGGTTI	0	561.2947	1120.5435	1120.5435	1120.5435
LSDWNFSYQ	1159.3893	580.7019	1159.4822	1159.4822	1159.4822
DVENK	0	604.297	603.2864	603.2864	603.2864
GAHAYQNHQTP	1222.5682	612.2914	1222.548	1222.548	1222.548
GIGEDYITVNLDPNQSLYYATVAGVIG	0	747.3701	2985.4607	2985.4607	2985.4607
GPAVGARYIEDEMFVETPTNLPRGGF	0	879.4497	3513.7715	3513.7715	3513.7715
EVYDPNEVIE	0	1207.5811	1206.5292	1206.5292	1206.5292
EPLNPTVV	867.3945	434.7045	867.4702	867.4702	867.4702
VSGPLMIM	878.4483	440.2314	878.4241	878.4241	878.4241
PTQPAVAVKP	1006.5083	504.2614	1006.5811	1006.5811	1006.5811
PGGDNIGPRPI	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.5673	1107.5673	1107.5673
ADVVANVQTDN	1144.5062	573.2604	1144.536	1144.536	1144.536
DIQAAIA	0	701.3404	700.3755	700.3755	700.3755
DPDAEIESDPEVETESEPEVEIDSEP	0	722.3121	2885.1985	2885.1985	2885.1985
NQPAEISQ	0	886.411	885.4192	885.4192	885.4192
CTSFKDAAYWQASKVSFGSGHDNDT	0	908.3968	2722.1606	2722.1606	2722.1606
AAALSPADNVGDGVMIVHNGKAQY	2398.1274	1200.071	2398.1587	2398.1587	2398.1587
EVLFLDEP	0	489.2309	976.4753	976.4753	976.4753
PAGKATPAPPV	1004.5249	503.2697	1004.5655	1004.5655	1004.5655
EAQIQTIVPQ	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.5924	1107.5924	1107.5924
EADLYHLPLP	1148.5259	575.2702	1148.5867	1148.5867	1148.5867
AGDQVPADAVVLEATNLA	0	585.3133	1752.8894	1752.8894	1752.8894
DVENK	0	604.2953	603.2864	603.2864	603.2864
TDASDES	0	724.3103	723.2559	723.2559	723.2559
KSASQSASQAQTNQNA	0	747.3651	1492.6754	1492.6754	1492.6754
RGLSGVETHVSYVSE	0	810.381	1618.795	1618.795	1618.795
AGDVPTTSFVD	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.5084	1107.5084	1107.5084
NLVNLMYEP	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.5271	1107.5271	1107.5271

ADVVGDDDLVQ	1144.5062	573.2604	1144.5248	1144.5248	1144.5248
ESDTDAAANNAGT	0	619.2656	1236.4742	1236.4742	1236.4742
GIGLGNIIDEETD	0	673.3368	1344.6409	1344.6409	1344.6409
AAIPGIANMLAAPR	0	683.3667	1364.7599	1364.7599	1364.7599
PNTNEF	0	722.3142	721.2919	721.2919	721.2919
NQPAEISQ	0	886.4091	885.4192	885.4192	885.4192
VATLVMVILIVFAYEVFLSDPSISGIKGO		906.2711	3621.0183	3621.0183	3621.0183
IHGPFANI	924.4763	463.2454	924.4818	924.4818	924.4818
DILFIDEI	0	489.2526	976.5117	976.5117	976.5117
TYDYARLLAESKPLMNLGM	0	547.2868	2185.0911	2185.0911	2185.0911
DSIIFHLPII	1150.5532	576.2839	1150.6387	1150.6387	1150.6387
EVYDPNEVIE	0	604.294	1206.5292	1206.5292	1206.5292
GVGPEGI	0	628.3261	627.3228	627.3228	627.3228
DPDNRRRCMNWQPDEQ	0	635.2782	1902.7737	1902.7737	1902.7737
TDASDES	0	724.3108	723.2559	723.2559	723.2559
NFGDI	564.3361	283.1753	564.2544	564.2544	564.2544
LPVDYFP	849.3849	425.6997	849.4272	849.4272	849.4272
ISIP	0	429.2637	428.2635	428.2635	428.2635
AGDVPTTSFVD	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.5084	1107.5084	1107.5084
KPGGPLPADKE	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.5924	1107.5924	1107.5924
EGGLYPHFLL	1144.5062	573.2604	1144.5917	1144.5917	1144.5917
INDGILYSSVFH	1363.5969	682.8057	1363.6772	1363.6772	1363.6772
ADGSPANDSGKDAAPA	0	722.3113	1442.6273	1442.6273	1442.6273
GEHLSEMPGVKITTSW	0	886.4176	1770.8611	1770.8611	1770.8611
NANMFTEVPFDVKTRAGKIALSNEVV0		906.2729	3620.8032	3620.8032	3620.8032
FINQ	520.2314	261.123	520.2645	520.2645	520.2645
PSDPNVPDVPT	0	380.1804	1137.519	1137.519	1137.519
CALMNILF	924.4759	463.2452	924.4449	924.4449	924.4449
PIGPV	0	482.2927	481.29	481.29	481.29
LGNGIGAGLAAGF	1132.5463	567.2804	1132.5876	1132.5876	1132.5876
PYNLSLFLPL	1150.5532	576.2839	1150.5911	1150.5911	1150.5911
ADIQKANVPGNAG	0	628.3281	1254.6205	1254.6205	1254.6205
TDASDES	0	724.3117	723.2559	723.2559	723.2559
SVEVGAPL	0	771.378	770.4174	770.4174	770.4174
GAYTRGLLLLAIFLI	0	409.244	1632.9967	1632.9967	1632.9967
DKLDSRIGQ	0	516.2615	1030.5408	1030.5408	1030.5408
GLGENDDFIQ	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.472	1107.472	1107.472
GAAVLAVVLQPF	1200.6017	601.3081	1200.6754	1200.6754	1200.6754
GPADPDHMGKKT	0	635.2783	1268.5819	1268.5819	1268.5819
VAGLGNGGMISLPY	1363.5969	682.8057	1363.6805	1363.6805	1363.6805
PNEDLVKGQEVTL	1440.6543	721.3344	1440.746	1440.746	1440.746
ADMGNFALALDEPQ	0	746.3479	1490.6711	1490.6711	1490.6711
EGTSK	520.2314	261.123	520.2493	520.2493	520.2493
FSISVLLM	924.4792	463.2469	924.499	924.499	924.499
AAFLDFVANK	1094.6095	548.312	1094.576	1094.576	1094.576
LPHMLETTIP	1150.5509	576.2827	1150.6056	1150.6056	1150.6056
ADIQKANVPGNAG	0	628.3271	1254.6205	1254.6205	1254.6205

GIITPPT	0	698.401	697.4011	697.4011	697.4011
DGIIDGATVNAPGKVD	0	771.3797	1540.7733	1540.7733	1540.7733
FLTLFVGGFI	0	279.1707	1112.6271	1112.6271	1112.6271
GGMNILAY	837.4021	419.7083	837.4055	837.4055	837.4055
IELPNFPK	972.5011	487.2578	972.528	972.528	972.528
DQGDLWIQG	0	516.2585	1030.4719	1030.4719	1030.4719
EETLLDYPQ	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.4972	1107.4972	1107.4972
AVAVGIGVADAQQ	1198.6267	600.3206	1198.6194	1198.6194	1198.6194
VVWGIPIGLLGYAAASGTPF	2003.9875	669.0031	2004.072	2004.072	2004.072
HGQSDTVTALQQR	1440.6543	721.3344	1440.6957	1440.6957	1440.6957
AGNEGDAI	0	746.3512	745.3242	745.3242	745.3242
AATPLPL	681.3487	341.6816	681.4061	681.4061	681.4061
HLPLAQED	922.4601	462.2373	922.4396	922.4396	922.4396
AGGNGQ	0	503.1907	502.2136	502.2136	502.2136
SLVHDIGPNK	1094.6121	548.3133	1094.572	1094.572	1094.572
HIPIP	0	576.3481	575.3431	575.3431	575.3431
ADIQKANVPGNAG	0	628.3257	1254.6205	1254.6205	1254.6205
ITLGLAQIMPAGLP	0	698.4046	1394.7843	1394.7843	1394.7843
QMRRAWCLLNIVTQAAGTPECVLIRGI	0	775.3917	3097.5874	3097.5874	3097.5874
LSIGMTIT	0	279.1679	834.4521	834.4521	834.4521
DQGPLH	666.3457	334.1801	666.2973	666.2973	666.2973
ELVQAGMPE	972.5029	487.2587	972.4586	972.4586	972.4586
PNDEVANCFV	1107.5321	554.7733	1107.4542	1107.4542	1107.4542
EDYVYDEVE	1159.3867	580.7006	1159.4557	1159.4557	1159.4557
ALGAATSVIGAVIG	1198.6267	600.3206	1198.6921	1198.6921	1198.6921
IGGAPDPVDGQYRP	1440.6543	721.3344	1440.6997	1440.6997	1440.6997
EDTEGVP	0	746.3514	745.313	745.313	745.313
LLNIPI	681.3487	341.6816	681.4425	681.4425	681.4425
LFSLALLF	922.4623	462.2384	922.5528	922.5528	922.5528
ADRLGLPGIN	1024.4927	513.2536	1024.5665	1024.5665	1024.5665
PTTDIVTVPI	0	528.2951	1054.5911	1054.5911	1054.5911
FIAVDTVFLA	1094.6118	548.3132	1094.6012	1094.6012	1094.6012
HIPIP	0	576.3476	575.3431	575.3431	575.3431
DNGSGGPIYALP	1159.3867	580.7006	1159.5509	1159.5509	1159.5509
ADIQKANVPGNAG	0	628.3254	1254.6205	1254.6205	1254.6205
ANSDAGGQAGQAEQ	1302.5791	652.2968	1302.5436	1302.5436	1302.5436
LLGPTGNPVPYVPA	0	698.4021	1394.7445	1394.7445	1394.7445
AVHDFDSF	0	469.2012	936.3978	936.3978	936.3978
ITGAVGGMGTK	990.511	496.2628	990.5168	990.5168	990.5168
KLVDPLVV	996.4983	499.2564	996.5856	996.5856	996.5856
IGGTVVAVIVGV	1082.6029	542.3087	1082.6699	1082.6699	1082.6699
DFDYMNLNQ	1159.3867	580.7006	1159.4492	1159.4492	1159.4492
AATPQF	0	635.2828	634.2963	634.2963	634.2963
LPGNQTGFLWFAALNIIE	2003.9875	669.0031	2004.0356	2004.0356	2004.0356
HGQSDTVTALQQR	1440.6521	721.3333	1440.6957	1440.6957	1440.6957
DNQPEAPYWFPK	1492.6903	747.3524	1492.651	1492.651	1492.651
DIIPII	0	342.2376	682.4265	682.4265	682.4265

DPIHLNTI	922.4623	462.2384	922.476	922.476	922.476
HDGNPIEPQ	1006.5073	504.2609	1006.4356	1006.4356	1006.4356
APVNRGVELA	1024.4927	513.2536	1024.5665	1024.5665	1024.5665
NEISKDKVFN	1142.5801	572.2973	1142.5931	1142.5931	1142.5931
HIPIP	0	576.3471	575.3431	575.3431	575.3431
GQDGAGIQDLPDA	1256.6215	629.318	1256.5521	1256.5521	1256.5521
SNADLEAAGTNLQ	1302.5791	652.2968	1302.6052	1302.6052	1302.6052
AVYPPQ	0	674.3448	673.3435	673.3435	673.3435
AVLPMPA	0	698.4028	697.3833	697.3833	697.3833
ENVQLQLF	990.511	496.2628	990.5022	990.5022	990.5022
LGPMANFAHV	1055.4905	528.7525	1055.5222	1055.5222	1055.5222
GLGISLLVAAGL	1082.6029	542.3087	1082.6699	1082.6699	1082.6699
DEATITPEDE	1118.5363	560.2754	1118.4615	1118.4615	1118.4615
AGPDFE	0	635.2811	634.2598	634.2598	634.2598
DAVQRGQRNAPSALPILTP	2003.9875	669.0031	2004.0752	2004.0752	2004.0752
VVTMIGCVAPNPPQ	1440.6521	721.3333	1440.7104	1440.7104	1440.7104
CIAANIPVVP	0	997.5009	996.5314	996.5314	996.5314
DMGNFALA	837.4225	419.7185	837.3691	837.3691	837.3691
YIAISIE	920.4886	461.2516	920.5219	920.5219	920.5219
AEANGT	0	562.2613	561.2394	561.2394	561.2394
IPDYQPGHLL	1152.5826	577.2986	1152.5815	1152.5815	1152.5815
NTAIQESLSNAAQ	0	674.3472	1346.6313	1346.6313	1346.6313
NEPQEMLRQAQI	1456.6857	729.3501	1456.698	1456.698	1456.698
GDGVINAP	0	742.3847	741.3657	741.3657	741.3657
CNVMVLPY	980.4792	491.2469	980.446	980.446	980.446
LVPVGGTGPKS	1010.5149	506.2647	1010.576	1010.576	1010.576
AEDYHNQQV	1105.3834	553.699	1105.42	1105.42	1105.42
GLPNVVRGIMAD	1240.6729	621.3437	1240.6598	1240.6598	1240.6598
DAGDPIINDLL	1270.572	636.2933	1270.5929	1270.5929	1270.5929
DQALPDDENLALQ	1440.6517	721.3331	1440.6732	1440.6732	1440.6732
QPTKPVEPT	0	997.5032	996.5128	996.5128	996.5128
FMIF	556.3246	279.1696	556.2719	556.2719	556.2719
DDAPLGGPGP	837.4271	419.7208	837.3868	837.3868	837.3868
LRSNGLAR	885.4925	443.7535	885.5145	885.5145	885.5145
AGDFLANVD	920.4886	461.2516	920.424	920.424	920.424
EIPLKALSPQ	1094.6118	548.3132	1094.6335	1094.6335	1094.6335
FSLISYTLPL	1152.5826	577.2986	1152.6431	1152.6431	1152.6431
DIDHVDLDPQ	1278.5682	640.2914	1278.6093	1278.6093	1278.6093
GAPVSMGPLGALNV	1281.6033	641.8089	1281.675	1281.675	1281.675
DAPVIVE	0	742.3915	741.3909	741.3909	741.3909
NIGVPVVV	0	812.4423	811.4803	811.4803	811.4803
NKALYIPY	980.4792	491.2469	980.5331	980.5331	980.5331
DKFNDKNE	1010.5149	506.2647	1010.4193	1010.4193	1010.4193
DAPISGLVQGV	1054.4874	528.251	1054.5659	1054.5659	1054.5659
FDEAAEFDY	1105.3834	553.699	1105.4241	1105.4241	1105.4241
ETFNIYDEIK	1270.572	636.2933	1270.6082	1270.6082	1270.6082
LPGSTMFEIIGP	1276.6337	639.3241	1276.601	1276.601	1276.601

GWPSAKLYPNPTT	1446.6594	724.337	1446.7144	1446.7144	1446.7144
DTQPLQASH	0	997.5018	996.4512	996.4512	996.4512
DYIF	556.3246	279.1696	556.2533	556.2533	556.2533
ESGFDGII	836.4239	419.2192	836.3916	836.3916	836.3916
GADLPTSLAV	942.4925	472.2535	942.5022	942.5022	942.5022
IGTIGDKFDI	1077.4708	539.7427	1077.5707	1077.5707	1077.5707
LANVPVQEPQ	1094.6118	548.3132	1094.5608	1094.5608	1094.5608
LGVMIALTSSSGGS	1278.5682	640.2914	1278.6489	1278.6489	1278.6489
LEDNLHSVSAV	1281.6033	641.8089	1281.6565	1281.6565	1281.6565
DPAVIVE	0	742.3914	741.3909	741.3909	741.3909
ANPVDVGVEIVTTSVLGAYKGAKF	0	812.4464	2434.3108	2434.3108	2434.3108
PAPAPTHPLP	996.4983	499.2564	996.5392	996.5392	996.5392
SPDDIHNKE	1054.4874	528.251	1054.4567	1054.4567	1054.4567
QQVYGEILPPQ	1270.572	636.2933	1270.6558	1270.6558	1270.6558
ATIRIDGDSATAS	1276.6337	639.3241	1276.6259	1276.6259	1276.6259
GHAGLFTSLNDLTVFTEM	1952.9506	651.9908	1952.9189	1952.9189	1952.9189
GGAHEGGKGPSVYDT	1446.6594	724.337	1446.6376	1446.6376	1446.6376
GGAADNAAGAIGAGILN	1454.6875	728.351	1454.7114	1454.7114	1454.7114
DYIF	556.3246	279.1696	556.2533	556.2533	556.2533
DVGAEFLART	1077.4708	539.7427	1077.5455	1077.5455	1077.5455
IISAYVWLM	1094.6118	548.3132	1094.5835	1094.5835	1094.5835
LFFSPYVTPI	1182.644	592.3293	1182.6324	1182.6324	1182.6324
AIPQPAGDTASDE	1270.572	636.2933	1270.5677	1270.5677	1270.5677
DPGDAPVMSLFD	1278.5682	640.2914	1278.5438	1278.5438	1278.5438
LLQIGANECQEV	1281.6033	641.8089	1281.6565	1281.6565	1281.6565
GAGVKIHM	0	812.4456	811.4374	811.4374	811.4374
GAGLINVPL	852.4355	427.225	852.5069	852.5069	852.5069
AVKGKYPT	862.425	432.2198	862.4913	862.4913	862.4913
VLLMIPFIMS	1178.5457	590.2801	1178.6443	1178.6443	1178.6443
NIKAYRKDVT	1206.6903	604.3524	1206.6721	1206.6721	1206.6721
ADADGKLIFNAH	1270.572	636.2933	1270.6306	1270.6306	1270.6306
ARGGQFRHELNY	1446.6594	724.337	1446.7117	1446.7117	1446.7117
TPEVPKTPQ	0	997.4979	996.5128	996.5128	996.5128
ELADVPPV	820.3805	411.1975	820.433	820.433	820.433
VTGAAQVAAT	887.4149	444.7147	887.4713	887.4713	887.4713
VGSDMFGIPR	1077.4708	539.7427	1077.5277	1077.5277	1077.5277
AMPREGQLVHI	1249.5886	625.8016	1249.6602	1249.6602	1249.6602
ETPGSIHEGGELG	1281.6033	641.8089	1281.5837	1281.5837	1281.5837
FGGAPII	0	674.3486	673.3799	673.3799	673.3799
DVIVVDPP	852.4069	427.2107	852.4593	852.4593	852.4593
ELSVALLI	856.4481	429.2313	856.527	856.527	856.527
GLYVPVAF	0	433.243	864.4745	864.4745	864.4745
QASAAIVVIPT	1051.5742	526.7944	1051.5913	1051.5913	1051.5913
EPQVDIAVPDP	1178.5457	590.2801	1178.5819	1178.5819	1178.5819
DEEFNQIINFKYSEQ	0	635.2815	1902.8635	1902.8635	1902.8635
GVVAVVAAG	0	742.4037	741.4385	741.4385	741.4385
VDLVVPLV	0	853.5702	852.532	852.532	852.532

DAPPILPV	820.3833	411.1989	820.4695	820.4695	820.4695
LSGQQQLGQ	887.4149	444.7147	887.4349	887.4349	887.4349
VPIVLQNM	912.4943	457.2544	912.5103	912.5103	912.5103
IMGFVEPF	980.4785	491.2465	980.4677	980.4677	980.4677
DEYNSLIKP	1077.4708	539.7427	1077.5342	1077.5342	1077.5342
GAPIPGV	0	610.3513	609.3486	609.3486	609.3486
AAGIMATQPTVVA	1228.5851	615.2998	1228.6486	1228.6486	1228.6486
DFEQP	0	636.2657	635.2439	635.2439	635.2439
DEVNVV	0	674.3441	673.3282	673.3282	673.3282
DVIVVDPP	852.4069	427.2107	852.4593	852.4593	852.4593
NASPGVLPV	852.4069	427.2107	852.4705	852.4705	852.4705
GIMMGIFP	0	433.2437	864.4238	864.4238	864.4238
DKIMPFEP	975.4957	488.7551	975.4736	975.4736	975.4736
DPTDPILQILPQG	1423.6503	712.8324	1423.7083	1423.7083	1423.7083
GIGAAICGVVAVLMPI	0	742.4063	1482.8302	1482.8302	1482.8302
LADPDILILDEATSSVDT	1886.9569	944.4857	1886.936	1886.936	1886.936
CKEQAGSV	820.3833	411.1989	820.3749	820.3749	820.3749
GHIFMIPV	912.4843	457.2494	912.4891	912.4891	912.4891
IPFFSMIL	982.4841	492.2493	982.5198	982.5198	982.5198
GAPIPGV	0	610.3507	609.3486	609.3486	609.3486
VGVGILG	0	614.3454	613.3799	613.3799	613.3799
DEFEP	0	636.2658	635.2439	635.2439	635.2439
FGGAPII	0	674.346	673.3799	673.3799	673.3799
DPIKHIDGAASGVVP	0	738.3963	1474.778	1474.778	1474.778
ELDPEPIDDLLEELQM	0	909.4142	1816.7925	1816.7925	1816.7925
HSSGNELGAMMALVADATL	1886.9569	944.4857	1886.8866	1886.8866	1886.8866
DPSQVLPV	854.4209	428.2177	854.4385	854.4385	854.4385
ITIEPDIP	912.4825	457.2485	912.4804	912.4804	912.4804
DEIIIGSVMPLVPGVPLT	0	463.252	1849.0271	1849.0271	1849.0271
FINPINDGA	975.4957	488.7551	975.4662	975.4662	975.4662
IDARALSPADN	1141.3783	571.6964	1141.5728	1141.5728	1141.5728
DGQIPE	0	658.3371	657.297	657.297	657.297
GRDVGLVALQRGTATRGFGATL	0	739.425	2215.2185	2215.2185	2215.2185
APNLVDVQ	0	856.4347	855.4338	855.4338	855.4338
AVLLAQEIDNLVSKDYP	1886.9569	944.4857	1886.9989	1886.9989	1886.9989
FGRFVPV	820.3833	411.1989	820.4595	820.4595	820.4595
DPIEIVEV	912.4825	457.2485	912.4804	912.4804	912.4804
ESEFDPLF	982.4841	492.2493	982.4284	982.4284	982.4284
EDEFP	0	636.264	635.2439	635.2439	635.2439
AEAAPSMPPESEPLAEIKAP	1952.9506	651.9908	1952.9401	1952.9401	1952.9401
GLVLLDNIVSPE	1310.7083	656.3614	1310.7081	1310.7081	1310.7081
DEPLLAGHVETIGLQKAVV	1987.9915	663.6711	1988.0942	1988.0942	1988.0942
AVNGKSV	0	674.3424	673.3759	673.3759	673.3759
DQDAAINPAGCVIQUIPEEEGVQCI	0	909.4131	2725.2576	2725.2576	2725.2576
LGLNVLDIGLEPDIVHGL	1886.9569	944.4857	1887.0353	1887.0353	1887.0353
DLLVIF	718.3923	360.2034	718.4265	718.4265	718.4265
LLVNGQPVNRRQTYQ	0	440.2494	1756.922	1756.922	1756.922

DLFLGINGQ	975.4957	488.7551	975.5026	975.5026	975.5026
ITANSASLIPIQ	1114.5459	558.2802	1114.587	1114.587	1114.587
DQIPDGYMAFP	0	635.2966	1268.5383	1268.5383	1268.5383
LNRGLL	0	686.3898	685.4123	685.4123	685.4123
KSSAKNAPIAKNPSSQ	0	814.4479	1626.8689	1626.8689	1626.8689
LTPGQLVE	0	856.434	855.4702	855.4702	855.4702
SPSPKPVIRQYKGLGEM	1886.9569	944.4857	1886.9924	1886.9924	1886.9924
GIVGASMI	0	374.2248	746.3997	746.3997	746.3997
NTPQAYQ	820.3833	411.1989	820.3715	820.3715	820.3715
APGVSEQLL	912.4795	457.247	912.4916	912.4916	912.4916
GKILDEVPI	982.4841	492.2493	982.5699	982.5699	982.5699
DEFEP	0	636.2654	635.2439	635.2439	635.2439
IPVRADSRSRF	1302.7747	652.3946	1302.7157	1302.7157	1302.7157
VAPNQEIPDQGQ	1310.7054	656.36	1310.6102	1310.6102	1310.6102
EDELGV	0	661.3175	660.2966	660.2966	660.2966
IMVNPL	685.3889	343.7017	685.3833	685.3833	685.3833
AAIAYPVIPTVVYGVPO	0	440.2476	1756.9763	1756.9763	1756.9763
DLALPASVAG	912.4799	457.2472	912.4916	912.4916	912.4916
ILFYPNLP	975.4957	488.7551	975.543	975.543	975.543
NEPEF	0	635.2958	634.2598	634.2598	634.2598
GPTGWFLDGPQ	0	644.2996	1286.6295	1286.6295	1286.6295
LIRADTVPLIPP	1303.7789	652.8967	1303.7864	1303.7864	1303.7864
GPQIQRELLSDY	1418.6816	710.3481	1418.7041	1418.7041	1418.7041
KSSAKNAPIAKNPSSQ	0	814.4465	1626.8689	1626.8689	1626.8689
LTPGQLVE	0	856.4354	855.4702	855.4702	855.4702
ILMAGGILLIVL	0	409.2801	1224.788	1224.788	1224.788
MLYTVPMI	982.4841	492.2493	982.4868	982.4868	982.4868
EDEFPP	0	636.2655	635.2439	635.2439	635.2439
VPLVPQ	1302.7747	652.3946	651.3956	651.3956	651.3956
VVPTS SVSPTPD	1313.613	657.8138	1313.6715	1313.6715	1313.6715
EDELGV	0	661.3198	660.2966	660.2966	660.2966
KDFPEQ	0	763.3265	762.3548	762.3548	762.3548
PAGLTAVPGP	0	440.248	878.4861	878.4861	878.4861
AHPMAIGDGIGT	1154.5813	578.2979	1154.5391	1154.5391	1154.5391
DIPLM	0	588.3453	587.2989	587.2989	587.2989
MLADLAVNDADAFKVLVDT	0	674.3488	2020.0187	2020.0187	2020.0187
KSQLNIINELPT	0	686.3907	1370.7294	1370.7294	1370.7294
GAPFFKKEQIREI	1561.8145	781.9145	1561.8617	1561.8617	1561.8617
GSALSTRQPLLCVVWSILLYILFYNGVT	0	814.4505	3253.7937	3253.7937	3253.7937
LTPGQLVE	0	856.4323	855.4702	855.4702	855.4702
PVAGFEAQYLAQLLTHQSSAAIAYPVI	0	1142.375	4565.4575	4565.4575	4565.4575
DVVISKVP	855.4308	428.7227	855.5066	855.5066	855.5066
AVQGLDATD	0	445.1961	888.4189	888.4189	888.4189
FSMILMPI	982.4841	492.2493	982.4868	982.4868	982.4868
PEGDALSGGPL	1027.4779	514.7462	1027.4822	1027.4822	1027.4822
APQPNDVISR	1096.5024	549.2585	1096.5513	1096.5513	1096.5513
ENTIDLSLPK	1110.5701	556.2923	1110.592	1110.592	1110.592

FEPMP	0	636.2644	635.2625	635.2625	635.2625
VPLVPQ	1302.7747	652.3946	651.3956	651.3956	651.3956
VSIAPGCAMGLANALGYIGMG	0	661.3182	1980.9471	1980.9471	1980.9471
DQFPEQ	0	763.3257	762.3184	762.3184	762.3184
IIVQGRQ	813.4449	407.7297	813.4708	813.4708	813.4708
IPVVPLPGA	877.4423	439.7284	877.5273	877.5273	877.5273
ESMIFPTV	922.4613	462.2379	922.447	922.447	922.447
DTLATIQVP	956.4783	479.2464	956.5179	956.5179	956.5179
ILGGVLSTAQF	0	553.3289	1104.6179	1104.6179	1104.6179
IEGSFLDMIP	1120.5576	561.2861	1120.5475	1120.5475	1120.5475
EAVMTVQGSVPAVVEGSSPQ	1952.9503	651.9907	1952.9513	1952.9513	1952.9513
PENVNPEEIDEYL	0	781.3357	1560.6831	1560.6831	1560.6831
AGDISVELLPSSIAQK	0	814.4432	1626.8828	1626.8828	1626.8828
IAPISLASTNFNSFMV	0	856.4333	1710.8651	1710.8651	1710.8651
DVVISKVP	855.4308	428.7227	855.5066	855.5066	855.5066
EEETVSV	0	445.1882	888.4077	888.4077	888.4077
YIYNQGP	982.4841	492.2493	982.476	982.476	982.476
PEIYVLPNEP	1268.5992	635.3069	1268.6653	1268.6653	1268.6653
IVPVASQKLSIANMAITPT	1952.9503	651.9907	1953.0969	1953.0969	1953.0969
FGGAPII	0	674.341	673.3799	673.3799	673.3799
ADYLGNLMLNVAGPGA	1477.676	739.8453	1477.6871	1477.6871	1477.6871
MVTLLQNDPYAPE	0	746.3594	1490.6963	1490.6963	1490.6963
KDFPEQ	0	763.3274	762.3548	762.3548	762.3548
GLVGGAADL	0	772.412	771.4127	771.4127	771.4127
DPGGVGLEIT	956.4783	479.2464	956.4815	956.4815	956.4815
AVIGLA	0	543.3051	542.3428	542.3428	542.3428
IPNPL	0	553.332	552.3271	552.3271	552.3271
AVVVQPDNSPAFSA	1416.6611	709.3378	1416.6885	1416.6885	1416.6885
ADVGLLGFPSVGKST	1446.7379	724.3762	1446.7719	1446.7719	1446.7719
KSPDDL	0	821.3769	820.3967	820.3967	820.3967
ADLAHMDHERAYTAI	1712.8198	857.4172	1712.7941	1712.7941	1712.7941
AGGLANGEVGTQM	0	445.1902	1332.598	1332.598	1332.598
LWVPEGKE	956.4783	479.2464	956.4967	956.4967	956.4967
AIGSALTGSGTY	1096.5024	549.2585	1096.54	1096.54	1096.54
EAHYRNGGGH	1096.5024	549.2585	1096.4799	1096.4799	1096.4799
AGVPLGAAKAAQ	1110.5701	556.2923	1110.6033	1110.6033	1110.6033
YINYVPQEPF	1268.5992	635.3069	1268.6078	1268.6078	1268.6078
GADAVLE	0	674.3466	673.3282	673.3282	673.3282
VPAFPDT	0	746.3649	745.3647	745.3647	745.3647
DQFPEQ	0	763.3269	762.3184	762.3184	762.3184
KVKPNQL	825.4939	413.7542	825.5073	825.5073	825.5073
AGVIGLSLYLMSNNQLIVPAP	0	543.3107	2169.1868	2169.1868	2169.1868
INPMLPLAGY	1104.5609	553.2877	1104.5525	1104.5525	1104.5525
FPIMTANMPQ	1148.5525	575.2835	1148.5359	1148.5359	1148.5359
LDPYIDLLT	1208.5836	605.2991	1208.5999	1208.5999	1208.5999
RPEMAILDEID	1300.6246	651.3196	1300.6333	1300.6333	1300.6333
AGINIMGFTKDF	1312.6107	657.3126	1312.6486	1312.6486	1312.6486

LGDGLVNSPIINR	1446.7379	724.3762	1446.7231	1446.7231	1446.7231
MPFISYTYNVMPF	0	821.3785	1640.7255	1640.7255	1640.7255
DPDVDLDT	0	445.1892	888.3713	888.3713	888.3713
PIYNFSAGP	980.4756	491.2451	980.4603	980.4603	980.4603
AGCATAKSSSSQ	1096.5024	549.2585	1096.4819	1096.4819	1096.4819
FDEEFNQIIN	1268.5992	635.3069	1268.5562	1268.5562	1268.5562
FGGAPII	0	674.3452	673.3799	673.3799	673.3799
NVPQGNV	0	727.392	726.366	726.366	726.366
PGLMAGANVTTFEPS	0	746.3623	1490.7075	1490.7075	1490.7075
LVPVNDP	0	753.444	752.4069	752.4069	752.4069
ILFIPDYLP	1202.6245	602.3195	1202.6587	1202.6587	1202.6587
EEIFLEDGIVV	1261.6362	631.8254	1261.6442	1261.6442	1261.6442
PAGVPVATMAIGDA	1268.5992	635.3069	1268.6434	1268.6434	1268.6434
NNFNRLIEAIP	1300.6246	651.3196	1300.6775	1300.6775	1300.6775
GPTAPQPERPAVP	1316.6362	659.3254	1316.6725	1316.6725	1316.6725
AMQPIMM	0	821.3878	820.3646	820.3646	820.3646
VAEDGSVTKIAPAQVQLGE	1926.91	964.4623	1926.9899	1926.9899	1926.9899
PEKISGSP	813.4265	407.7205	813.4232	813.4232	813.4232
PINLLHGH	876.4389	439.2267	876.5069	876.5069	876.5069
KAASDSGNNSYNSTSSST	0	445.189	1776.7399	1776.7399	1776.7399
QGSLNNKHS	966.4568	484.2357	966.4519	966.4519	966.4519
PSPKGSTNASPGV	1198.5651	600.2898	1198.583	1198.583	1198.583
KPNTLYLNPPP	1268.6021	635.3083	1268.6765	1268.6765	1268.6765
IDSTTKDPVMGSVVVNVED	0	674.3446	2019.967	2019.967	2019.967
NVPQGNV	0	727.3945	726.366	726.366	726.366
EEIPAPGVDEI	0	390.1857	1167.5659	1167.5659	1167.5659
DFSDVLIHTVMEP	0	394.1952	1572.7494	1572.7494	1572.7494
LVAGGSLLVDYIM	1252.7069	627.3607	1252.6373	1252.6373	1252.6373
AIVQSTIHAGASD	1268.6021	635.3083	1268.6361	1268.6361	1268.6361
QPQRDIAIVDAGQALFSQ	1956.0316	653.0178	1956.0065	1956.0065	1956.0065
AVMIPFNQNFAAIRAVV	1973.0359	658.6859	1973.092	1973.092	1973.092
NPAPVAAPSEPKEVKEAKTEAK	0	764.4241	2290.2168	2290.2168	2290.2168
GLDTPPELLAGLSRLEPSFNTLPP	0	813.4299	2437.2742	2437.2742	2437.2742
PQSVNFE	0	821.3865	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
IDPLMGMT	876.4389	439.2267	876.4085	876.4085	876.4085
AGETLGIIGI	942.4431	472.2288	942.5386	942.5386	942.5386
PAVRNLPRNF	1198.5651	600.2898	1198.6571	1198.6571	1198.6571
LVASAGASVAKADP	1255.5975	628.806	1255.6772	1255.6772	1255.6772
YSVAILMVNVVFTGSVL	1952.95	651.9906	1953.0646	1953.0646	1953.0646
FPPKW	0	674.3454	673.3588	673.3588	673.3588
HSGTLDPNVDGVLPIGIGNATKVVQF	0	727.3951	2905.5371	2905.5371	2905.5371
VDGPATAPLQQNWILMDGSECYKG/0	0	927.4698	3705.835	3705.835	3705.835
KDDVYN	752.4393	377.2269	752.3341	752.3341	752.3341
EIPAALKN	854.4373	428.2259	854.4861	854.4861	854.4861
FQAILPSIIP	1097.5551	549.7848	1097.6484	1097.6484	1097.6484
PTAPEV	0	613.2759	612.3119	612.3119	612.3119
RGVAASDIDDLL	1244.5908	623.3027	1244.6249	1244.6249	1244.6249

DEPVQPNAPNTPDVPITPG	1973.0359	658.6859	1972.9377	1972.9377	1972.9377
NPAPVAAPSEPKEVKEAKTEAK	0	764.4247	2290.2168	2290.2168	2290.2168
GLDSVPPE	0	813.428	812.3916	812.3916	812.3916
PQSVNFE	0	821.3789	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
QFLNLE	745.3649	373.6897	745.3647	745.3647	745.3647
DAQPDFE	820.3809	411.1977	820.3239	820.3239	820.3239
PINLLLHG	876.4389	439.2267	876.5069	876.5069	876.5069
AGETLGIIGI	942.4431	472.2288	942.5386	942.5386	942.5386
VPMIMFEQF	1172.5745	587.2945	1172.5247	1172.5247	1172.5247
DTPDMEIQKQGHGALVNT	1952.95	651.9906	1952.9261	1952.9261	1952.9261
IMTGVSSGGSNPKV	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.6656	1348.6656	1348.6656
ESLSATA	0	678.3378	677.3232	677.3232	677.3232
DDAIVNVVLKPDYKMFKA	0	727.3887	2179.1235	2179.1235	2179.1235
SLIPVVVFN	0	937.5244	936.5644	936.5644	936.5644
PSAIVAGLFGP	1027.4769	514.7457	1027.5702	1027.5702	1027.5702
DLPLSVPEKT	1097.5551	549.7848	1097.5968	1097.5968	1097.5968
EAPAEV	0	613.2807	612.2755	612.2755	612.2755
LEDSVNIDDQIYFPPT	1865.91	622.9773	1865.8571	1865.8571	1865.8571
ATVTLGSLVAPMS	1261.6255	631.82	1261.6588	1261.6588	1261.6588
AVLPILDINGYKLSNPTL	1956.0316	653.0178	1956.0931	1956.0931	1956.0931
RKGFYGVVTRTPVANEPLP	1973.0359	658.6859	1973.0483	1973.0483	1973.0483
PIVELPLP	876.4389	439.2267	876.532	876.532	876.532
PEVGTTKAPE	1027.4769	514.7457	1027.5186	1027.5186	1027.5186
GKLPEITVTD	1172.5745	587.2945	1172.6289	1172.6289	1172.6289
GGHAWLNSLGLPQ	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.6888	1348.6888	1348.6888
GIVAVPSVTNVLHAA	1446.7377	724.3761	1446.8195	1446.8195	1446.8195
PQSVNFE	0	821.3786	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
PGLGAATIGATQLTAVEQPA	1865.9128	933.9637	1865.9735	1865.9735	1865.9735
KEALPSVPP	0	937.5255	936.528	936.528	936.528
DCAFIKAMPPEIM	0	489.2297	1464.6815	1464.6815	1464.6815
HWFGIILAV	1054.5127	528.2636	1054.5964	1054.5964	1054.5964
LSTLQGDVAEAP	1200.5907	601.3026	1200.5874	1200.5874	1200.5874
EIPKTLPGGHTL	1261.6255	631.82	1261.703	1261.703	1261.703
PQLFTQQLIPL	1297.7067	649.8606	1297.7281	1297.7281	1297.7281
ATAFHTFIGEFDFPSQP	1952.95	651.9906	1952.8945	1952.8945	1952.8945
VPEDLFVYEAPVSLAVIL	1973.0359	658.6859	1973.0762	1973.0762	1973.0762
GSAQSIMMGIPI	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.6731	1348.6731	1348.6731
RHPAQFQ	0	883.4771	882.446	882.446	882.446
PIVELPLP	876.4389	439.2267	876.532	876.532	876.532
FIAGSAGASISNPAA	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.6624	1348.6624	1348.6624
LLHRPDPLMEP	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.6809	1348.6809	1348.6809
EPVAHE	0	681.3173	680.3129	680.3129	680.3129
ETTGPEGPKGPQSPETTGPQSP	0	821.3769	2461.1245	2461.1245	2461.1245
NDEVPNH	0	824.3396	823.3461	823.3461	823.3461
LKELGKVALKRPN	0	371.2238	1480.9089	1480.9089	1480.9089
LRYLNP	0	388.2507	774.4388	774.4388	774.4388
EVQQQVVEH	1095.4783	548.7464	1095.5197	1095.5197	1095.5197

IEIAVYNIEPH	1297.7067	649.8606	1297.6554	1297.6554	1297.6554
DRRFVFDLDFSIVPDL	1952.95	651.9906	1952.9996	1952.9996	1952.9996
TAQIAGQTVKVGKASVAPT	1973.0359	658.6859	1973.0946	1973.0946	1973.0946
LTIAINGSGTGIDLVRPQN	2052.0166	685.0128	2052.1216	2052.1216	2052.1216
AIVLVAILDVVGGDTGFTN	0	937.5278	1873.0197	1873.0197	1873.0197
AGDEPQAVATVAHFVETLG	1910.9141	956.4643	1910.9374	1910.9374	1910.9374
KNLPIQNNVP	1136.6631	379.895	1136.619	1136.619	1136.619
PPIIALLAAGVV	0	416.2816	1245.806	1245.806	1245.806
DPLELLPLQQP	1261.6255	631.82	1261.6918	1261.6918	1261.6918
LGGIDGLVHISEISYERV	1956.0316	653.0178	1956.0316	1956.0316	1956.0316
GGHAWLNSLGLPQ	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.6888	1348.6888	1348.6888
PGEEAKVSAVEAMGIKFKPKAIRDGEIO		906.2718	3620.8508	3620.8508	3620.8508
GAPVLAVSGH	0	907.5441	906.4923	906.4923	906.4923
QQNIVEAASSKEIQQVYNA	2231.1294	1116.572	2231.0706	2231.0706	2231.0706
LAVTSTNLVVLVVP	0	371.2256	1480.8977	1480.8977	1480.8977
SAAIIVMA	0	388.2537	774.431	774.431	774.431
DNQVVISH	910.433	456.2238	910.4509	910.4509	910.4509
QPLPLELV	924.5616	463.2881	924.5168	924.5168	924.5168
QVGSQEQNSH	1095.4783	548.7464	1095.4581	1095.4581	1095.4581
GVILFTAPILASFSAAVAPP	1973.0359	658.6859	1973.0874	1973.0874	1973.0874
VEPESETDFDVPESDSE	0	681.259	2040.7808	2040.7808	2040.7808
ILPVIIALVQYGANYLYN	2052.0171	685.013	2052.1296	2052.1296	2052.1296
AAFPFAQAARDAQP	1461.6829	731.8487	1461.6888	1461.6888	1461.6888
AASPN	0	230.1124	458.2125	458.2125	458.2125
HAFEHA	0	356.2158	710.3136	710.3136	710.3136
VPKNLES	786.4243	394.2194	786.4124	786.4124	786.4124
WTKVGLK	0	416.2826	830.5014	830.5014	830.5014
AGNLGPLAQP	0	485.2562	968.4927	968.4927	968.4927
NNPKVVLPHS	1103.5697	552.7921	1103.6088	1103.6088	1103.6088
GNIVQSGSPVDIY	1348.6333	675.3239	1348.651	1348.651	1348.651
RTREDAHPDGIQHFSNFLP	0	746.3555	2236.0774	2236.0774	2236.0774
VPEPASATASIITEVPAGLLSTGLDA	0	846.4373	2536.3271	2536.3271	2536.3271
VDLANKLAAPISRN	0	371.2261	1480.8362	1480.8362	1480.8362
IHSNAPLNTALQLSA	0	388.2535	1548.826	1548.826	1548.826
EPEV	0	455.2108	454.2064	454.2064	454.2064
DPLELLPL	0	455.2821	908.5219	908.5219	908.5219
DNLPGVGLV	924.5616	463.2881	924.528	924.528	924.528
DIDI	0	475.2195	474.2326	474.2326	474.2326
DLQAGQFTES	1095.4783	548.7464	1095.472	1095.472	1095.472
VLPDGAVLHQG	1104.5713	553.2929	1104.5928	1104.5928	1104.5928
ILPVIIALVQYGANYLYN	2052.0154	685.0124	2052.1296	2052.1296	2052.1296
LYATKGAFE	998.5883	500.3014	998.5073	998.5073	998.5073
APIPQ	0	525.2633	524.2958	524.2958	524.2958
AMRAPE	0	674.3424	673.3217	673.3217	673.3217
DKRVVARHNYENVIPED	2053.0205	685.3474	2053.0342	2053.0342	2053.0342
ATAGSVVSANADEVAT	1461.6829	731.8487	1461.6947	1461.6947	1461.6947
ENVPLVQ	0	799.4339	798.4124	798.4124	798.4124

IVQANEF	0	821.3784	820.3967	820.3967	820.3967
NPELKQTYLHSDHLTPLGTLYNRGDG	0	846.4391	3381.7139	3381.7139	3381.7139
LPSDNPIT	0	856.4293	855.4338	855.4338	855.4338
PLGKLEP	752.4443	377.2294	752.4432	752.4432	752.4432
EPEV	0	455.2129	454.2064	454.2064	454.2064
ELLPLDLP	0	455.2831	908.5219	908.5219	908.5219
AGNIV	0	473.2941	472.2646	472.2646	472.2646
NPKFPELNK	1085.5079	543.7612	1085.5869	1085.5869	1085.5869
ELAAHYLPL	1104.5713	553.2929	1104.5968	1104.5968	1104.5968
ALPPLT	0	654.3804	653.3748	653.3748	653.3748
LLTGVGSSFLAIGP	0	666.3759	1330.7496	1330.7496	1330.7496
IEGGYAGANMFIAGGVSGPIGAAFE	0	670.0828	2676.2529	2676.2529	2676.2529
LVPTRSQHLDPTQFRNQ	2052.0168	685.0129	2052.05	2052.05	2052.05
AGLEQLQQL	998.5883	500.3014	998.5397	998.5397	998.5397
LVPVP	0	524.3392	523.337	523.337	523.337
APIPQ	0	525.2649	524.2958	524.2958	524.2958
QPGPQ	0	527.2669	526.2387	526.2387	526.2387
VGSVNAQ	0	674.3464	673.3395	673.3395	673.3395
MINSGDIIGVSVADA	1461.6829	731.8487	1461.7021	1461.7021	1461.7021
EDFPQSV	0	821.3793	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
VDDNPLLA	0	856.4357	855.4338	855.4338	855.4338
LSAPRPL	752.4443	377.2294	752.4545	752.4545	752.4545
LLVIPLLP	0	439.2872	876.6048	876.6048	876.6048
EPEV	0	455.21	454.2064	454.2064	454.2064
IVENGISPLVIKAVQPLV	0	473.293	1889.1238	1889.1238	1889.1238
NLNYPYPI	1008.5911	505.3028	1008.4916	1008.4916	1008.4916
PIGIE	0	528.3318	527.2955	527.2955	527.2955
KQYDKDVPL	1104.5713	553.2929	1104.5815	1104.5815	1104.5815
PPPEAS	0	597.2842	596.2806	596.2806	596.2806
DPLITKNSLKYFVGISKN	2052.0168	685.0129	2052.1255	2052.1255	2052.1255
ITGH	0	427.2509	426.2227	426.2227	426.2227
LVRQENRS	1000.5613	501.2879	1000.5414	1000.5414	1000.5414
APIPQ	0	525.2642	524.2958	524.2958	524.2958
FDQQPPQPL	1085.5079	543.7612	1085.5029	1085.5029	1085.5029
ALAGVMGGLTSEVEP	1429.644	715.8293	1429.7123	1429.7123	1429.7123
NPDILAMTATPIPR	0	755.3875	1508.8021	1508.8021	1508.8021
QNGNFNPRKLGSLDNPKNLATQTAF	0	773.3956	3089.5278	3089.5278	3089.5278
QVALPNLG	0	812.4084	811.444	811.444	811.444
EDFPQSV	0	821.3805	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
PIVELPLP	0	439.2896	876.532	876.532	876.532
EVLNPDLP	1008.5927	505.3036	1008.5491	1008.5491	1008.5491
HGAPIVGPISV	1102.561	552.2878	1102.6135	1102.6135	1102.6135
GPGIDILYDAA	1103.5691	552.7918	1103.5499	1103.5499	1103.5499
NQPVVQLPEK	1152.6494	577.332	1152.6027	1152.6027	1152.6027
EPAAPI	0	597.284	596.317	596.317	596.317
HANDFFRQNFTAMLKPRWSLTP	0	670.0831	2676.3384	2676.3384	2676.3384
AVPAAASVGFEDIEA	1445.6843	723.8494	1445.7039	1445.7039	1445.7039

PAVQPIP	736.3735	369.194	736.4119	736.4119	736.4119
TVPVLAGP	752.4443	377.2294	752.4432	752.4432	752.4432
PALSSSFKTFISPVKP	0	427.2516	1704.9451	1704.9451	1704.9451
SYLPPL	0	689.4272	688.3796	688.3796	688.3796
ASLPVPQ	0	753.4446	752.4069	752.4069	752.4069
NSIVNPI	0	757.3938	756.4018	756.4018	756.4018
GANIGAILGQGAAEEY	1532.7249	767.3697	1532.7471	1532.7471	1532.7471
EDFPQSV	0	821.3789	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
DALEFDQGPLFGLLQL	1775.843	888.9288	1775.8982	1775.8982	1775.8982
LLVIPLLP	0	439.2898	876.6048	876.6048	876.6048
LPNDPLPI	0	440.2443	878.4749	878.4749	878.4749
ATADLVIALG	0	472.2694	942.5386	942.5386	942.5386
LVDLVKALE	998.5883	500.3014	998.6012	998.6012	998.6012
GGIYNYLPI	1008.5927	505.3036	1008.528	1008.528	1008.528
VGTL DANLDNA	1102.561	552.2878	1102.5143	1102.5143	1102.5143
VDFNVPVKNG	1103.5691	552.7918	1103.5612	1103.5612	1103.5612
GHPEYGMTAGVDATTGPL	0	597.283	1788.7988	1788.7988	1788.7988
PIGIVYIDGDKEQ	1445.6843	723.8494	1445.7402	1445.7402	1445.7402
PVPAVPQ	0	739.4283	738.3912	738.3912	738.3912
DGAKHLL	752.4443	377.2294	752.4181	752.4181	752.4181
ATAGMLETD	907.4917	454.7531	907.3957	907.3957	907.3957
PGGNGTTVKPKNGS	0	477.2245	1428.6844	1428.6844	1428.6844
NEMVVSDFNANAIR	0	527.2416	1578.7461	1578.7461	1578.7461
GLMPLN	0	644.3382	643.3363	643.3363	643.3363
EAEAGSE	0	674.2446	673.2555	673.2555	673.2555
EDFPQSV	0	821.3792	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603
DKDLAPVSAIPADQLP	1648.7825	825.3985	1648.8672	1648.8672	1648.8672
GLAAPFIDHSSIATAHMDQVSTYM	0	860.4044	2578.1831	2578.1831	2578.1831
QKSQGIGIL	0	472.2728	942.5498	942.5498	942.5498
LIEMQLPE	972.5249	487.2697	972.4838	972.4838	972.4838
HDIKVYQP	998.5883	500.3014	998.5186	998.5186	998.5186
VDSVADVVKAT	1102.561	552.2878	1102.587	1102.587	1102.587
GKMLQDIDGGA	1103.5691	552.7918	1103.5281	1103.5281	1103.5281
PGMALPHDIDPL	1274.6189	638.3167	1274.6329	1274.6329	1274.6329
VAPSILSADPANLM	1429.6381	715.8263	1429.7123	1429.7123	1429.7123
AVQFTTQEHAQGL	1429.6381	715.8263	1429.6837	1429.6837	1429.6837
MNASTGAGGQIAPVIFN	1647.7847	824.8996	1647.7926	1647.7926	1647.7926
KTFNFP	752.4443	377.2294	752.3857	752.3857	752.3857
DLNPAII	754.3841	378.1993	754.4225	754.4225	754.4225
PGIYIPGF	862.5363	432.2754	862.4589	862.4589	862.4589
FATVQGTAN	907.4917	454.7531	907.4399	907.4399	907.4399
EPEKFIDGY	1096.4641	549.2393	1096.5077	1096.5077	1096.5077
EVPMLFPKDSREPT	0	588.2962	1761.8607	1761.8607	1761.8607
IMGPLGG	0	644.3308	643.3363	643.3363	643.3363
QDNVSE	0	674.2471	673.2555	673.2555	673.2555
DILAPNP	0	755.3882	754.3861	754.3861	754.3861
EDFPQSV	0	821.3787	820.3603	820.3603	820.3603

EATAQTADA	858.3893	430.2019	858.3719	858.3719	858.3719
GPAVLPQPV	876.4827	439.2486	876.5069	876.5069	876.5069
EGDGIVVAAI	0	472.2708	942.5022	942.5022	942.5022
LIEMQLPE	972.5249	487.2697	972.4838	972.4838	972.4838
PTDLNMLPV	998.5883	500.3014	998.5107	998.5107	998.5107
HGKAGAAGEIGH	1103.5691	552.7918	1103.5472	1103.5472	1103.5472
ATTPGNWLIGL	1199.5377	600.7761	1199.6187	1199.6187	1199.6187
FTVLPL	0	689.4298	688.416	688.416	688.416
LQQGPEIESNSNL	1429.6381	715.8263	1429.6572	1429.6572	1429.6572
AIDSKISDWYAVAPI	1647.7847	824.8996	1647.8508	1647.8508	1647.8508
VYDLMI	752.4443	377.2294	752.3779	752.3779	752.3779
ELVILLACLVLLSN	0	455.2427	1816.9679	1816.9679	1816.9679
PKPDGTLPT	924.4651	463.2398	924.4916	924.4916	924.4916
PIGVIAAFLV	998.5883	500.3014	998.6165	998.6165	998.6165
EEPQQTQQK	1096.4601	549.2373	1096.5149	1096.5149	1096.5149
DAILDDANEVGVSI	1429.6381	715.8263	1429.6936	1429.6936	1429.6936
KNPGIDNVLADKLP	0	755.3951	1508.8198	1508.8198	1508.8198
GHEINGIEGIRIEP	1532.7249	767.3697	1532.7947	1532.7947	1532.7947
GSVMNPNDHPHGGGEGKAPIGHPSIO		821.3791	2461.1194	2461.1194	2461.1194
LLIGMNLGLLAV	0	415.2502	1242.7257	1242.7257	1242.7257
DLADAGVKA	858.3893	430.2019	858.4447	858.4447	858.4447
YVGIIVVT	862.5363	432.2754	862.5164	862.5164	862.5164
PPMINQIQY	1103.5691	552.7918	1103.5321	1103.5321	1103.5321
LTGSVGTGADKRD	1275.6368	638.8257	1275.6418	1275.6418	1275.6418
HLPLIP	0	689.4294	688.4272	688.4272	688.4272
NEQNVKDIVEQL	1429.6381	715.8263	1429.6936	1429.6936	1429.6936
DIFDDM	754.3841	378.1993	754.2844	754.2844	754.2844
ELLVPVPE	876.4825	439.2485	876.4957	876.4957	876.4957
LSEEVKGAS	0	460.3087	918.4658	918.4658	918.4658
GNPLQHIF	924.4651	463.2398	924.4818	924.4818	924.4818
GANEIVLSGGG	972.5249	487.2697	972.4876	972.4876	972.4876
AHFLYPNQP	1085.5143	543.7644	1085.5294	1085.5294	1085.5294
QEPTGPEEPL	1096.4601	549.2373	1096.4924	1096.4924	1096.4924
DVSPLQ	0	658.3511	657.3334	657.3334	657.3334
LGIALCLNPIIMYI	1561.7661	781.8903	1561.8612	1561.8612	1561.8612
ITAIPAIP	794.4159	398.2152	794.4902	794.4902	794.4902
AMLVPADL	0	415.2526	828.4415	828.4415	828.4415
NPALHIQA	862.5363	432.2754	862.4661	862.4661	862.4661
QDFWVDQYAADELIP	0	453.2061	1808.8257	1808.8257	1808.8257
LPDNPLRYT	1104.5715	553.293	1104.5452	1104.5452	1104.5452
HLPLIP	0	689.4322	688.4272	688.4272	688.4272
GIAGDTIQVYMPGVGGG	0	796.3746	1590.7712	1590.7712	1590.7712
TVLTMIKN	0	460.3088	918.5208	918.5208	918.5208
TLFATLIF	924.4651	463.2398	924.532	924.532	924.532
AGPAVLSFL	972.5249	487.2697	972.5644	972.5644	972.5644
EDEQKNTDH	1096.4601	549.2373	1096.4421	1096.4421	1096.4421
VVPPF	0	558.3226	557.3214	557.3214	557.3214

PGFPPLS	0	617.322	616.3221	616.3221	616.3221
GPMQALVKAMPL	1255.6663	628.8404	1255.6669	1255.6669	1255.6669
IWPAFPMPTPLIG	0	728.3927	1454.7632	1454.7632	1454.7632
PLNNSLP	0	755.3903	754.3861	754.3861	754.3861
TLHPDNKKYASK	0	351.1987	1400.7412	1400.7412	1400.7412
ITAIPAIP	794.4159	398.2152	794.4902	794.4902	794.4902
PFVAADPI	0	415.2511	828.4382	828.4382	828.4382
ATSGVSATVA	862.5363	432.2754	862.4396	862.4396	862.4396
GELVPGGPIS	924.4651	463.2398	924.4916	924.4916	924.4916
NIMTKTVAPL	1102.561	552.2878	1102.6056	1102.6056	1102.6056
PAGGTQPPN	0	838.4385	837.3981	837.3981	837.3981
ALVPSILGAI	968.5129	485.2637	968.5906	968.5906	968.5906
VVPPF	0	558.3253	557.3214	557.3214	557.3214
ACPGALVIGTPVS	1165.6252	583.8199	1165.6343	1165.6343	1165.6343
PLGPPL	0	609.3343	608.3533	608.3533	608.3533
GILNISAMWEP	1230.6665	616.3405	1230.5955	1230.5955	1230.5955
GPEDIT	0	631.3391	630.2861	630.2861	630.2861
AMLPEV	0	659.3359	658.336	658.336	658.336
IPNDSPL	0	755.387	754.3861	754.3861	754.3861
GPVSIQPAEFCKFY	0	793.3965	1584.7646	1584.7646	1584.7646
PDVAPTPT	0	813.4309	812.3916	812.3916	812.3916
GFFTKISAFLSAI	0	351.1986	1400.7704	1400.7704	1400.7704
GRENFP	0	360.1898	718.3398	718.3398	718.3398
VWLPAPI	794.4159	398.2152	794.4691	794.4691	794.4691
EIFELVN	862.5363	432.2754	862.4437	862.4437	862.4437
FSFGPLIP	876.4825	439.2485	876.4745	876.4745	876.4745
INPPL	0	553.3292	552.3271	552.3271	552.3271
HLPLIP	0	689.427	688.4272	688.4272	688.4272
LYLNPEIEQDPQ	0	730.3522	1458.6879	1458.6879	1458.6879
GNEIPAIGFGTFQIPN	1674.8721	838.4433	1674.8253	1674.8253	1674.8253
PGAYSNTLT	938.4828	470.2487	938.4345	938.4345	938.4345
VPVPF	0	558.3271	557.3214	557.3214	557.3214
PLGPPL	0	609.3376	608.3533	608.3533	608.3533
DLSMPPGESGLI	1230.6665	616.3405	1230.5802	1230.5802	1230.5802
GPFIPT	0	631.3423	630.3377	630.3377	630.3377
LTGGISQLLFNH	1298.7135	650.364	1298.6982	1298.6982	1298.6982
APEDID	0	659.3346	658.281	658.281	658.281
ILDLATPA	0	813.4328	812.4644	812.4644	812.4644
IPGGSGNDFARGGLMATD	0	868.399	1734.7996	1734.7996	1734.7996
TGSNPPF	0	360.1886	718.3286	718.3286	718.3286
QGVVISLP	794.4159	398.2152	794.4538	794.4538	794.4538
PIVELPLP	876.4825	439.2485	876.532	876.532	876.532
LPLTKPVPT	964.5544	483.2845	964.5957	964.5957	964.5957
LPDWIPGLI	0	512.2831	1022.5801	1022.5801	1022.5801
INPPL	0	553.328	552.3271	552.3271	552.3271
PNDVVQLGAPLREPMVLATHR	0	597.3184	2385.2476	2385.2476	2385.2476
DLPPEAESDTQRIHPLSLISALQYRVDI	4621.022	771.1776	4621.2534	4621.2534	4621.2534

FPLPIGTMPLLGISMG	1674.8721	838.4433	1674.8724	1674.8724	1674.8724
IMPGATIGKN	1000.5165	501.2655	1000.5375	1000.5375	1000.5375
GYPPTVREI	0	516.295	1030.5448	1030.5448	1030.5448
VVPPF	0	558.3249	557.3214	557.3214	557.3214
LPPGLP	0	609.3351	608.3533	608.3533	608.3533
ISDWYAVAPI	1230.6665	616.3405	1230.6284	1230.6284	1230.6284
GPEDIT	0	631.3411	630.2861	630.2861	630.2861
APVETLPFEAVDYWNELLTIIDWSRQI	4621.0215	661.1532	4621.2266	4621.2266	4621.2266
PVNLWFDNIGGLVG	1499.7211	750.8678	1499.7772	1499.7772	1499.7772
IPVAVTPT	0	813.4298	812.4644	812.4644	812.4644
EIGNIEHG	0	868.3973	867.4086	867.4086	867.4086
LGTHLPNVD	964.5544	483.2845	964.4978	964.4978	964.4978
EENPLDQTQFINE	0	521.2521	1560.7307	1560.7307	1560.7307
YPFIAHVIK	0	544.3266	1086.6226	1086.6226	1086.6226
AGVGHL	0	553.3276	552.302	552.302	552.302
ADVPPV	0	597.3162	596.317	596.317	596.317
VAVIVGLELSRP	1251.7173	626.8659	1251.7551	1251.7551	1251.7551
TKVRPIFYFAG	1298.7135	650.364	1298.7023	1298.7023	1298.7023
GPLKSIQNIIVDMRFG	1674.8721	838.4433	1674.8763	1674.8763	1674.8763
ASALLMAIYFNGM	0	355.1833	1416.6781	1416.6781	1416.6781
DFLPVIML	946.5385	474.2765	946.5198	946.5198	946.5198
GDNVIVINAS	1000.5171	501.2658	1000.5189	1000.5189	1000.5189
ATAGSQVIRE	0	516.2975	1030.5408	1030.5408	1030.5408
VVPPF	0	558.3236	557.3214	557.3214	557.3214
NINGPLTGSTMI	0	609.3336	1216.6122	1216.6122	1216.6122
PDINPVA	0	725.3774	724.3755	724.3755	724.3755
IPWVIGFLGDPPSLV	0	813.4271	1624.8865	1624.8865	1624.8865
DHAPTLNT	0	868.3974	867.4086	867.4086	867.4086
LPDYGFNDGR	0	404.1308	1209.5415	1209.5415	1209.5415
LPPSQNPVP	964.5544	483.2845	964.4866	964.4866	964.4866
APGGNLQRGGHNSVYIGAAGAD	0	521.2523	2081.0039	2081.0039	2081.0039
SSTAAT	0	537.2226	536.2442	536.2442	536.2442
ATKMSVPAVAI	0	544.328	1086.6107	1086.6107	1086.6107
NSAAQGPLSGLLG	1183.5463	592.7804	1183.6198	1183.6198	1183.6198
LIDGLPRILNK	1251.7173	626.8659	1251.7551	1251.7551	1251.7551
DLMEPFG	0	808.3833	807.3473	807.3473	807.3473
NGLGRINLPFIEGIM	1674.8721	838.4433	1674.8763	1674.8763	1674.8763
ALSQSGF	0	355.183	708.3442	708.3442	708.3442
QQNQNNQQN	1000.5167	501.2656	1000.4323	1000.4323	1000.4323
GPKQPTAVKRLGKGQSCQVN	0	516.2982	2061.1443	2061.1443	2061.1443
DLFRRVQKITKEQDIPPF	0	558.3237	2229.2271	2229.2271	2229.2271
ATLALIRAAGTPIVGPSA	0	560.3218	1677.9778	1677.9778	1677.9778
GLMVIGLVGLLG	0	571.3341	1140.6941	1140.6941	1140.6941
KVDGHAV	0	725.3757	724.3868	724.3868	724.3868
KYYGNGVTCGKHSCSVDWGKATTC	4621.022	771.1776	4620.9976	4620.9976	4620.9976
GGCEPCGGQ	0	404.1313	806.2687	806.2687	806.2687
IAGEVAPGPL	938.4828	470.2487	938.5073	938.5073	938.5073

DKFMKSPL	964.5544	483.2845	964.5052	964.5052	964.5052
APGGNLQRGGHNSVYIGAAGAD	0	521.2536	2081.0039	2081.0039	2081.0039
DIVPQNPLPA	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.5659	1078.5659	1078.5659
NKAFQQRVP	0	544.3285	1086.5934	1086.5934	1086.5934
DVSPIA	0	601.3299	600.3119	600.3119	600.3119
LLDAATTAIPGPL	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7074	1251.7074	1251.7074
NPDLPI	0	668.3572	667.3541	667.3541	667.3541
IVPQNPLP	876.4825	439.2485	876.5069	876.5069	876.5069
PLNFVIPF	946.5463	474.2804	946.5164	946.5164	946.5164
YGLKQPVLVSPL	0	476.3028	1425.8595	1425.8595	1425.8595
GADDIQVHM	1000.5167	501.2656	1000.4284	1000.4284	1000.4284
AGTIRIKKNGPRRTEPLP	0	516.2976	2061.1807	2061.1807	2061.1807
VVPPF	0	558.3242	557.3214	557.3214	557.3214
GPMIGL	0	587.3143	586.3149	586.3149	586.3149
DGRYKTIKNF	1240.649	621.3318	1240.6564	1240.6564	1240.6564
PLEEPKPLVTTTGDSSQQDGNTQY	0	652.0744	2604.2192	2604.2192	2604.2192
MPVEPF	0	751.3622	750.3258	750.3258	750.3258
GGATILWVENDWVP	0	404.1304	1612.7886	1612.7886	1612.7886
NQTSNITVFFVTHDLP	0	459.277	1832.8945	1832.8945	1832.8945
KLTVKTHP	964.5544	483.2845	964.5706	964.5706	964.5706
PLDVNVPVI	964.5544	483.2845	964.5593	964.5593	964.5593
DLVGT	0	504.3336	503.2591	503.2591	503.2591
DVSPIA	0	601.3295	600.3119	600.3119	600.3119
DLPPNL	0	668.3577	667.3541	667.3541	667.3541
DLNPPAP	0	739.3907	738.3548	738.3548	738.3548
LNPPPP	649.3407	325.6776	649.3435	649.3435	649.3435
NPPI	0	440.2471	439.2431	439.2431	439.2431
LAGEPLPLAA	0	476.3034	950.5437	950.5437	950.5437
DAVPI	0	514.283	513.2798	513.2798	513.2798
ENLFVVPED	1060.5875	531.301	1060.5077	1060.5077	1060.5077
GPMGLL	0	587.3164	586.3149	586.3149	586.3149
VVAVVGTIDPGLP	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7074	1251.7074	1251.7074
FIFIP	0	636.3319	635.3683	635.3683	635.3683
MPVEPF	0	751.3605	750.3258	750.3258	750.3258
IDPNEVLELQLGNKF	0	865.4644	1728.8934	1728.8934	1728.8934
EQAITMASA	920.4523	461.2334	920.4273	920.4273	920.4273
ILGGKSFPF	964.5544	483.2845	964.5382	964.5382	964.5382
DKFMKSPL	964.5544	483.2845	964.5052	964.5052	964.5052
IYAAM	0	504.3325	503.2777	503.2777	503.2777
RAVLPTVQPV	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.6499	1078.6499	1078.6499
AWRGNMGDMII	1132.5106	567.2626	1132.5336	1132.5336	1132.5336
DVSPIA	0	601.3257	600.3119	600.3119	600.3119
LLDAATTAIPGPL	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7074	1251.7074	1251.7074
DLPPNL	0	668.3579	667.3541	667.3541	667.3541
ITGLEKVNAG	0	1001.52	1000.5553	1000.5553	1000.5553
IRGFKEMA	0	476.304	950.5008	950.5008	950.5008
ADVPI	0	514.2847	513.2798	513.2798	513.2798

DKIFVPDDI	1060.5875	531.301	1060.5441	1060.5441	1060.5441
DEIDDVSGDYI	1239.3513	620.6829	1239.5143	1239.5143	1239.5143
DIEYP	0	636.3356	635.2803	635.2803	635.2803
QPVDLPLAELLT	1307.6991	654.8568	1307.7336	1307.7336	1307.7336
DEPEL	0	717.2881	716.2864	716.2864	716.2864
MPVEPF	0	751.3619	750.3258	750.3258	750.3258
DFQPVF	0	753.3668	752.3381	752.3381	752.3381
EAFQSEP	919.4499	460.7322	919.4287	919.4287	919.4287
LPPSQNPVP	964.5544	483.2845	964.4866	964.4866	964.4866
ALVIGMIGVP	1000.5167	501.2656	1000.5627	1000.5627	1000.5627
GILVLPSPVP	0	504.3365	1006.6426	1006.6426	1006.6426
PVGLYGGQLSA	1061.5897	531.8021	1061.5393	1061.5393	1061.5393
VKHGDNLIAI	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.6135	1078.6135	1078.6135
EVLGDRQLPII	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7186	1251.7186	1251.7186
PKVDLPSPLYDVVADLMM	0	668.3537	2002.0155	2002.0155	2002.0155
IDPNEVLELQLGNKF	0	865.4686	1728.8934	1728.8934	1728.8934
LTGLLTGCHS	0	1001.521	1000.5012	1000.5012	1000.5012
ESRTFVPL	947.5421	474.7783	947.5076	947.5076	947.5076
IPVLLGIIGG	0	476.3032	950.6165	950.6165	950.6165
ADVPI	0	514.2831	513.2798	513.2798	513.2798
FITPGVGIGSN	1060.5875	531.301	1060.5553	1060.5553	1060.5553
DAWMYNDPDN	1239.3513	620.6829	1239.4502	1239.4502	1239.4502
DIEYP	0	636.3339	635.2803	635.2803	635.2803
NNPVVDPTNPNQ	1307.6991	654.8568	1307.6106	1307.6106	1307.6106
QPVYPF	0	751.3587	750.3588	750.3588	750.3588
VSVGLPGL	0	757.4035	756.4382	756.4382	756.4382
DPAVMDDPVNTQLAIV	0	857.4134	1712.8291	1712.8291	1712.8291
CLNIYGHT	919.4499	460.7322	919.4222	919.4222	919.4222
DKFMKSP	964.5544	483.2845	964.5052	964.5052	964.5052
IVVPQNALLP	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.6387	1078.6387	1078.6387
GAFVRSKLN	0	560.32	1118.656	1118.656	1118.656
LGLVPNLPMGLI	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7261	1251.7261	1251.7261
DFFDVGTEVEIL	0	692.335	1382.6605	1382.6605	1382.6605
ITGLEKVNAG	0	1001.516	1000.5553	1000.5553	1000.5553
AKVLSDIQST	1060.5875	531.301	1060.5764	1060.5764	1060.5764
EIGLVQLSALLKKVNNESTN	0	543.2957	2169.2004	2169.2004	2169.2004
ICDECAQVMND	1239.3513	620.6829	1239.457	1239.457	1239.457
FIFIP	0	636.3327	635.3683	635.3683	635.3683
SLIAGLDVDKYD	1307.6991	654.8568	1307.6609	1307.6609	1307.6609
VELTYENNYIPM	1500.739	751.3768	1500.6807	1500.6807	1500.6807
FLASAYPMYVPIN	1500.739	751.3768	1500.7323	1500.7323	1500.7323
APDDL PANLDLSVVD	1552.6787	777.3466	1552.7621	1552.7621	1552.7621
GPMGHLNP	0	838.4359	837.3803	837.3803	837.3803
LNLPVLSPP	964.5547	483.2846	964.5593	964.5593	964.5593
IDMLDRLR	0	516.2972	1030.5593	1030.5593	1030.5593
ESSSFLHGUV	1060.5875	531.301	1060.5189	1060.5189	1060.5189
LDNPLPLIA	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.5911	1078.5911	1078.5911

VKVVKEMSSI	0	560.3241	1118.637	1118.637	1118.637
LDEMQLVGLVN	1132.5106	567.2626	1132.5435	1132.5435	1132.5435
AATTAATKEAKL	0	588.3521	1174.6558	1174.6558	1174.6558
AVMPNIVLLIGL	1251.7177	626.8661	1251.7625	1251.7625	1251.7625
ANKYIAYAGAPLGFMMIPF	0	692.3442	2074.042	2074.042	2074.042
DNGAHVLVVDAAAPFGREG	0	920.4537	1838.8911	1838.8911	1838.8911
KIIEVLEGT	1000.5167	501.2656	1000.5804	1000.5804	1000.5804
ESRTRLIQQNARR	0	543.2972	1626.9026	1626.9026	1626.9026
DNAFNRIPLF	1206.6553	604.3349	1206.6033	1206.6033	1206.6033
DRPLVQSNVSSDKPQIPQQLK	0	609.3338	2433.2976	2433.2976	2433.2976
DAWMYNDPDN	1239.3513	620.6829	1239.4502	1239.4502	1239.4502
ATLEAVLQSKQLP	1396.7335	699.374	1396.7926	1396.7926	1396.7926
DPAPSAIGNYVAILP	0	757.4005	1512.7823	1512.7823	1512.7823
VAPMPLV	0	758.4026	757.4044	757.4044	757.4044
ILGLNVMDIGLEPDIIVDELSKMOV	0	838.4384	2512.3169	2512.3169	2512.3169
RIGQGIFMN	1034.5747	518.2946	1034.5331	1034.5331	1034.5331
ISLMALSPIT	1060.5875	531.301	1060.5839	1060.5839	1060.5839
DNGGVPLVLPV	1078.5961	540.3053	1078.6023	1078.6023	1078.6023
KQNKVRFSD	1120.5929	561.3037	1120.5989	1120.5989	1120.5989
KNGDLYITPI	1132.5106	567.2626	1132.6128	1132.6128	1132.6128
TAGNLI	0	588.3544	587.3279	587.3279	587.3279
DAAQQAHEVIN	1194.5457	598.2801	1194.5629	1194.5629	1194.5629
IGPEPE	0	641.3236	640.3068	640.3068	640.3068
ANKYIAYAGAPLGFMMIPF	0	692.3438	2074.042	2074.042	2074.042
DLDADSIDFVEFVLEL	0	920.4523	1838.8826	1838.8826	1838.8826
PPQQMAQPEGP	0	399.1992	1194.5339	1194.5339	1194.5339
ITLFLAIILPGNRVLPF	0	475.2847	1897.144	1897.144	1897.144
AGCAVL	0	533.3011	532.2679	532.2679	532.2679
DGKGPQKQNEL	0	543.2968	1084.5513	1084.5513	1084.5513
AASKMVDLLGGGG	0	588.2928	1174.6016	1174.6016	1174.6016
GLGIGDQQNAFVVPT	1514.8088	758.4117	1514.7729	1514.7729	1514.7729
DIIGLIPMVDGTQRF	0	838.4358	1674.8651	1674.8651	1674.8651
FPGIPVGFIP	0	1059.578	1058.5801	1058.5801	1058.5801
PIIFVSAKDTEEDIINGLGI	0	1072.582	2143.1414	2143.1414	2143.1414
DDLDP	0	344.1765	686.3123	686.3123	686.3123
VEFSDNT	0	406.1604	810.3395	810.3395	810.3395
APVVLMEGAH	0	512.2822	1022.5219	1022.5219	1022.5219
ISLMALSPIT	1060.5873	531.3009	1060.5839	1060.5839	1060.5839
FGLDVGPAASVT	1061.4789	531.7467	1061.5393	1061.5393	1061.5393
KKQONLYTIEWVVTG	0	560.323	1677.9091	1677.9091	1677.9091
QGCAMLEAQYADNIRNLAQH	0	562.269	2245.0369	2245.0369	2245.0369
LDEIDFVPFL	1206.6534	604.334	1206.6172	1206.6172	1206.6172
LLEDAVPMKHKH	0	641.3225	1280.6798	1280.6798	1280.6798
AFSGHKMFGPT	0	399.199	1194.5492	1194.5492	1194.5492
VAPSEIVQELSA	0	415.2289	1242.6344	1242.6344	1242.6344
DVNLLPLKP	1007.5594	504.787	1007.6015	1007.6015	1007.6015
ATASKAVLIHQVTVKPEYSK	0	543.2996	2169.2158	2169.2158	2169.2158

DNLPP	1108.6049	555.3097	554.27	554.27	554.27
AASKMVDLLGGGG	0	588.2975	1174.6016	1174.6016	1174.6016
LMALLVMPSSMPLI	1514.8088	758.4117	1514.8274	1514.8274	1514.8274
DDIFELKPSQKMIGILLAA	0	1059.5811	2117.1443	2117.1443	2117.1443
PEGLPASTSVV	0	1072.583	1071.5448	1071.5448	1071.5448
YLPNLKDE	1006.5881	504.3013	1006.4971	1006.4971	1006.4971
IMLGTFSLSA	1038.6389	520.3267	1038.542	1038.542	1038.542
AFSINMGIIIP	1061.4789	531.7467	1061.558	1061.558	1061.558
KIPVELVSKLYLQL	0	548.3587	1642.007	1642.007	1642.007
LFNDSIVRVG	0	560.3232	1118.6084	1118.6084	1118.6084
EVKGASIPDLAST	0	635.3324	1268.6613	1268.6613	1268.6613
DLLESLVPLAP	1280.6527	641.3336	1280.6864	1280.6864	1280.6864
DPAIPNGNQDVYH	1438.6389	720.3267	1438.6477	1438.6477	1438.6477
KIPILNQLTARFK	0	779.4583	1556.9403	1556.9403	1556.9403
LDKRSIPHGDFIINGETPALLQVIMKLL	0	1032.578	4126.2979	4126.2979	4126.2979
NVVEPIVPN	1007.5594	504.787	1007.5287	1007.5287	1007.5287
PQLWVGVALGGSLVGCNIGL	0	525.2807	2097.1292	2097.1292	2097.1292
NDYVDQVLP	1061.4789	531.7467	1061.5029	1061.5029	1061.5029
ARLVQIALP	1080.6011	541.3078	1080.6655	1080.6655	1080.6655
DVPLEVVNQP	1108.6049	555.3097	1108.5764	1108.5764	1108.5764
PFDLP	0	588.2968	587.2955	587.2955	587.2955
DLFIPFFPTI	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6482	1208.6482	1208.6482
EMPGPRYLANVAVV	1514.8088	758.4117	1514.7915	1514.7915	1514.7915
MLSNIPNL	0	902.4492	901.4579	901.4579	901.4579
SSSLEKKDN	1006.5881	504.3013	1006.4931	1006.4931	1006.4931
LEQALNGHSA	1038.6389	520.3267	1038.5094	1038.5094	1038.5094
GQPSISEQDT	1061.4789	531.7467	1061.4513	1061.4513	1061.4513
NDYVDQVLP	1061.4789	531.7467	1061.5029	1061.5029	1061.5029
ELPKRIALVG	0	548.3596	1094.6812	1094.6812	1094.6812
LHAPTP	0	635.3326	634.3439	634.3439	634.3439
PLGVEEDEPALP	1280.6527	641.3336	1280.6136	1280.6136	1280.6136
VIVPPIAA	0	779.4598	778.4953	778.4953	778.4953
APVIPDDATTWIFTPQNDSNVHQDA	0	1145.037	4576.167	4576.167	4576.167
TKIVVPAALP	1007.5594	504.787	1007.6379	1007.6379	1007.6379
LLLRANVAFSAPNTS	0	525.2845	1572.8624	1572.8624	1572.8624
EAAGVITYEE	1080.597	541.3058	1080.4976	1080.4976	1080.4976
PVVDasLYVF	1108.6049	555.3097	1108.5804	1108.5804	1108.5804
AFIDQMIQKLRNDV	0	564.3554	1689.8872	1689.8872	1689.8872
IPFLCFYPLP	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6304	1208.6304	1208.6304
DIPGLI	0	627.3439	626.364	626.364	626.364
DAGGLIAQRHQH	1301.5819	651.7982	1301.6589	1301.6589	1301.6589
GWVVFNAVIDIIG	1514.8088	758.4117	1514.8497	1514.8497	1514.8497
AQLQMATDIVINGKVQRPSVCNATE	0	896.1373	2685.3579	2685.3579	2685.3579
EIKSAYPEA	1006.5881	504.3013	1006.4971	1006.4971	1006.4971
AIVLVIVLVT	1038.6389	520.3267	1038.7053	1038.7053	1038.7053
TIPICIGEIP	0	528.2895	1054.5732	1054.5732	1054.5732
SHGEGVIVALN	0	548.3602	1094.572	1094.572	1094.572

RDFPLSALTPDTAKSLAT	0	635.3342	1903.0051	1903.0051	1903.0051
DLDILAPVQPSI	1280.6527	641.3336	1280.6864	1280.6864	1280.6864
LNLVIVVEQRVAGM	0	779.4525	1556.8596	1556.8596	1556.8596
AYDIVQILLDANAEEAL	0	902.4563	1802.9302	1802.9302	1802.9302
EVIIVAHDL	1007.5594	504.787	1007.5651	1007.5651	1007.5651
PKELGTQELLQNDAFVAQP	0	525.2802	2097.0742	2097.0742	2097.0742
QSDVLLPKIP	1108.6049	555.3097	1108.6492	1108.6492	1108.6492
QNVSKELNKN	0	587.3137	1172.615	1172.615	1172.615
IPFLCFYPLP	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6304	1208.6304	1208.6304
DIGLPL	0	627.3449	626.364	626.364	626.364
LVEEIQDKSLQ	1301.5819	651.7982	1301.6715	1301.6715	1301.6715
VTADLPEV	0	859.4415	858.4335	858.4335	858.4335
IGTGVGGAUV	828.4353	415.2249	828.4705	828.4705	828.4705
IDDAAAITFA	1006.5881	504.3013	1006.4971	1006.4971	1006.4971
AGTQTGTFR	0	520.3292	1038.5094	1038.5094	1038.5094
ATNAVGFLL	0	560.3258	1118.6335	1118.6335	1118.6335
DLPHHTKSGLI	1216.6627	609.3386	1216.6564	1216.6564	1216.6564
LISLCS	0	635.3362	634.336	634.336	634.336
EQTAPDASSSGSHSSDESSNSSSSSSS	0	885.3765	3537.437	3537.437	3537.437
FKTGT	552.2195	277.117	552.2908	552.2908	552.2908
MPAAG	0	446.1897	445.1995	445.1995	445.1995
TLPYLFLLYAFPFKENQN	0	587.3223	2345.2461	2345.2461	2345.2461
AGKAIKADQPLP	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6765	1208.6765	1208.6765
DIPGLI	0	627.3428	626.364	626.364	626.364
RVAQMALKIRYPHAKL	0	632.3778	1894.1088	1894.1088	1894.1088
VELGNVLAGLIVKQTPENQVILDK	0	648.3718	2589.4741	2589.4741	2589.4741
DTTVVMPDEAPQ	1301.5819	651.7982	1301.5809	1301.5809	1301.5809
IPIVVPQ	0	765.4824	764.4796	764.4796	764.4796
CEVIN	0	543.2929	542.27	542.27	542.27
DKNSWPAKY	1108.6049	555.3097	1108.5189	1108.5189	1108.5189
PGALIPMALPSIAVNTN	0	560.3216	1677.9124	1677.9124	1677.9124
IPGKVNTVYNP	1216.6627	609.3386	1216.6451	1216.6451	1216.6451
ATAGIAAG	0	631.3474	630.3337	630.3337	630.3337
ESPRF	0	635.3359	634.3075	634.3075	634.3075
PKNEDEPG	0	885.3793	884.3876	884.3876	884.3876
KFGDS	552.2195	277.117	552.2544	552.2544	552.2544
IDAGA	0	446.1905	445.2173	445.2173	445.2173
AGGVGLNAIQIAKYLGAEVATTASA	0	587.3249	2345.259	2345.259	2345.259
HGQNNRRKIS	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6487	1208.6487	1208.6487
IEAVVGTEGPYD	0	625.2805	1248.5874	1248.5874	1248.5874
AGKGPREPYLIQLPLRS	0	632.3816	1894.0789	1894.0789	1894.0789
EIKGTIASATAIRQSIQR	0	648.3765	1942.0959	1942.0959	1942.0959
IDQIFWWSAH	1301.5819	651.7982	1301.6193	1301.6193	1301.6193
IPIVVPQ	0	765.4826	764.4796	764.4796	764.4796
EDVSMPLPN	1000.4953	501.2549	1000.4536	1000.4536	1000.4536
ILIQLVGLGGP	1078.5991	540.3068	1078.675	1078.675	1078.675
KPTESPDAIGA	0	543.2961	1084.54	1084.54	1084.54

ANGAGKTTLMR	0	560.3221	1118.5867	1118.5867	1118.5867
VSPDVIIIGASFL	1216.6627	609.3386	1216.6703	1216.6703	1216.6703
ESPRF	0	635.333	634.3075	634.3075	634.3075
LLAQNLLDNGHP	0	653.3559	1304.6725	1304.6725	1304.6725
LNIKPNLFIHLNR	1590.8524	796.4335	1590.9358	1590.9358	1590.9358
SLPIQLPIP	0	978.5511	977.5797	977.5797	977.5797
GNTPT	488.2411	245.1278	488.2231	488.2231	488.2231
AGNVLN	0	587.3234	586.3075	586.3075	586.3075
VIEITHQQNK	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6514	1208.6514	1208.6514
EGIDL	0	625.2767	624.3119	624.3119	624.3119
AGKGTQA	0	632.3805	631.3289	631.3289	631.3289
VLALAGQKLHCDQILQLITMLAPT	0	648.371	2589.4387	2589.4387	2589.4387
EPILDENLDISIVNAGDGSQHPHQ	0	652.0753	2604.2305	2604.2305	2604.2305
KPVGIVVQFGGQTAINLAKP	0	680.3922	2038.1462	2038.1462	2038.1462
IPIVVPQ	0	765.4774	764.4796	764.4796	764.4796
PGGNTGAEGQN	1000.4953	501.2549	1000.421	1000.421	1000.421
RAKFAKKMN	0	547.325	1092.6226	1092.6226	1092.6226
GNPLILNRKLPNSSR	0	560.32	1677.9639	1677.9639	1677.9639
LLNALRFAVYIVVVT	0	564.3544	1690.0182	1690.0182	1690.0182
DPIYFYVPR	1184.6396	593.3271	1184.5867	1184.5867	1184.5867
QNRLLGLPPI	1215.6609	608.8377	1215.7339	1215.7339	1215.7339
IISCA	0	635.3357	634.2996	634.2996	634.2996
QNPLAKALNWIVALFVNVFRSIP	0	653.3543	2609.437	2609.437	2609.437
LNIKPNLFIHLNR	1590.8524	796.4335	1590.9358	1590.9358	1590.9358
RAQALIPRILNPNMIFS	0	978.5514	1955.0663	1955.0663	1955.0663
GNTPT	488.2411	245.1278	488.2231	488.2231	488.2231
ILVLGH	0	326.2065	650.4116	650.4116	650.4116
EVAAG	0	446.1936	445.2173	445.2173	445.2173
PDALAPEVTGGL	1138.5958	570.3052	1138.587	1138.587	1138.587
VIKEDPGGVQK	0	585.2841	1168.6451	1168.6451	1168.6451
DIGHYRSLVN	0	587.3229	1172.5939	1172.5939	1172.5939
DNPVGVPLVLSA	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.6765	1208.6765	1208.6765
ALLAFDYAIHQ	1260.6373	631.3259	1260.6503	1260.6503	1260.6503
DEPVVQQMLSKSDDLANKGDTDT	0	652.0738	2604.2224	2604.2224	2604.2224
QVPAEPIP	977.55	489.7823	977.5182	977.5182	977.5182
AGRKPFVNP	1000.4953	501.2549	1000.5454	1000.5454	1000.5454
IVNMA	0	547.3299	546.2836	546.2836	546.2836
SAAQGPLSGLLGG	0	564.3567	1126.5983	1126.5983	1126.5983
IIYSA	0	566.3613	565.3112	565.3112	565.3112
KTPVIISGDKK	1184.6396	593.3271	1184.7129	1184.7129	1184.7129
LCQALTATPSLP	1214.6525	608.3335	1214.6217	1214.6217	1214.6217
MLNVVQPLPLP	1235.6681	618.8413	1235.6948	1235.6948	1235.6948
DVVIKELPLED	0	635.3344	1268.6864	1268.6864	1268.6864
QSPQPL	0	653.3573	652.3068	652.3068	652.3068
RAIPELQQAL	1138.5958	570.3052	1138.6346	1138.6346	1138.6346
NELNEEQGHV	0	585.282	1168.4996	1168.4996	1168.4996
KIDALRAVPIGG	1208.7227	605.3686	1208.7241	1208.7241	1208.7241

PLDFQDMQWN	0	647.2996	1292.5496	1292.5496	1292.5496
EPILDENLDISIVNAGDGSQHPSPQ	0	652.0745	2604.2305	2604.2305	2604.2305
SAQEDNLNLAQDTQLDSQAF	2206.8994	1104.457	2206.9978	2206.9978	2206.9978
GIIGVLALGGLVKDMA	0	547.3289	1638.9742	1638.9742	1638.9742
PRVEAARIADERPPN	0	564.3561	1689.8911	1689.8911	1689.8911
QPGAIWTTGT	0	565.7735	1129.5768	1129.5768	1129.5768
EMIERAGSGHP	0	592.3836	1182.5452	1182.5452	1182.5452
EAL AHL	0	653.3491	652.3544	652.3544	652.3544
AIMSVSSLTASISFE	1557.7417	520.2545	1557.7596	1557.7596	1557.7596
PDANKLLLVP	1079.5767	540.7956	1079.6227	1079.6227	1079.6227
DENIPIPANR	1138.5958	570.3052	1138.5619	1138.5619	1138.5619
LPFMQAIFSTAAMSGMQWLIPVV	0	635.3307	2537.2886	2537.2886	2537.2886
ASTNTTAANIATAS	0	647.2962	1292.6208	1292.6208	1292.6208
SDYIVAILGTILFLYGGQ	0	648.3716	1942.0452	1942.0452	1942.0452
DGMGQPIAVNNAAITVVAMPDLTV/	0	652.0713	2604.304	2604.304	2604.304
PQAAVLGMLTNPSAYN	0	867.4329	1732.8455	1732.8455	1732.8455
IEFTNVPY	982.5447	492.2796	982.4648	982.4648	982.4648
AFVGGIVPAPI	1055.5419	528.7782	1055.6016	1055.6016	1055.6016
AVKIKILMKAAGFFC	0	547.3302	1638.9353	1638.9353	1638.9353
DVRDMFLIP	1104.5513	553.2829	1104.5637	1104.5637	1104.5637
LVLGGQGRAGVT	0	564.3541	1126.6459	1126.6459	1126.6459
DPAALSVPADLATPADTQ	0	585.2816	1752.8418	1752.8418	1752.8418
DAGGFVLGLPKN	1186.5989	594.3067	1186.6346	1186.6346	1186.6346
ANAPTVVLYFNP	0	653.3243	1304.6765	1304.6765	1304.6765
GQRIQVRIGNEI	0	692.3993	1382.7631	1382.7631	1382.7631
VIADRLGNI	969.4881	485.7513	969.5607	969.5607	969.5607
IVNVLATGGGPFVFGEE	1557.7417	520.2545	1557.8038	1557.8038	1557.8038
DILMSLDEP	1047.5361	524.7753	1047.4794	1047.4794	1047.4794
PFGPIVFLMAGI	1260.6377	631.3261	1260.6941	1260.6941	1260.6941
IMGAVACSVSVP	1261.6123	631.8134	1261.6046	1261.6046	1261.6046
GYKQKTAQIAQNLQRPV	0	648.3746	1942.0748	1942.0748	1942.0748
TAAAAPTGTAFLLLTAVLL	0	676.4025	2026.2078	2026.2078	2026.2078
PVDPKEHMTPGIG	0	697.3535	1392.6708	1392.6708	1392.6708
LNLNVVHGI	0	978.5449	977.5658	977.5658	977.5658
AGGGKGAN	630.3434	316.179	630.3085	630.3085	630.3085
IVANQVNPSI	1055.5419	528.7782	1055.5499	1055.5499	1055.5499
LVNPDNVPVL	1079.5767	540.7956	1079.5863	1079.5863	1079.5863
KNAKRSYKVN	0	604.3471	1206.6833	1206.6833	1206.6833
GPANISDFENRLMGKLSALVIESQ	0	652.0756	2604.3218	2604.3218	2604.3218
LEPHAS	0	653.3305	652.3181	652.3181	652.3181
HGEDDAPAEQGEQ	1310.3812	656.1979	1310.5011	1310.5011	1310.5011
LIEKEKDKINGP	0	692.3996	1382.777	1382.777	1382.777
MITTGSSVIP	988.4811	495.2478	988.4899	988.4899	988.4899
IQEQAKLENGGLKE	1557.7417	520.2545	1557.7886	1557.7886	1557.7886
IPVPILGMPLNP	1260.6377	631.3261	1260.7152	1260.7152	1260.7152
IMGCPALTGYLND	1261.6123	631.8134	1261.6013	1261.6013	1261.6013
ATAGIGANLYLAK	1261.6123	631.8134	1261.703	1261.703	1261.703

HIVINSVNLETG	0	648.3765	1294.6881	1294.6881	1294.6881
QNHNNMQGLVHKAETDGG	0	669.3014	2004.8596	2004.8596	2004.8596
AFLSGIVLSFFLAISCLL	0	676.4052	2026.1577	2026.1577	2026.1577
AEDKTIPNLSYVGP	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.7457	1503.7457	1503.7457
KLNANPVP	0	852.4749	851.4865	851.4865	851.4865
AGGVGTGI	630.3434	316.179	630.3337	630.3337	630.3337
PGIKDVVESL	1055.5419	528.7782	1055.5863	1055.5863	1055.5863
VEPDVFFLD	1079.5767	540.7956	1079.5176	1079.5176	1079.5176
EYGLFEALET	1170.6001	586.3073	1170.5444	1170.5444	1170.5444
GPKQNELINFIEPTLVYRGII	0	604.347	2413.3369	2413.3369	2413.3369
VDFANAGWGAIP	1216.5942	609.3044	1216.5876	1216.5876	1216.5876
ATLTSSA	0	650.379	649.3282	649.3282	649.3282
ELIVGLTDGPEAYILGFIGLQNDY	0	653.3336	2609.3264	2609.3264	2609.3264
EIIPRRNFEIP	0	692.3975	1382.7671	1382.7671	1382.7671
TGANIADN	0	776.3403	775.3348	775.3348	775.3348
DMLMGALIP	975.5016	488.7581	975.4769	975.4769	975.4769
GGAPPNYVNT	988.4811	495.2478	988.4614	988.4614	988.4614
PFIVVPQVLT	1111.5823	556.7984	1111.6642	1111.6642	1111.6642
DIGSNIARKM	1216.5942	609.3044	1216.6598	1216.6598	1216.6598
EPDGLNMMVRT	1261.6123	631.8134	1261.5795	1261.5795	1261.5795
AGLFGANITSALQ	1261.6123	631.8134	1261.6666	1261.6666	1261.6666
HKAVLVLGSTDR	0	648.3766	1294.7357	1294.7357	1294.7357
IKPAIERVIAQN	0	676.4054	1350.7983	1350.7983	1350.7983
AEDKTIPNLSYVGP	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.7457	1503.7457	1503.7457
AILPKNVDIDLVPV	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
PEIAPKLPE	1024.5543	513.2844	1024.5441	1024.5441	1024.5441
TPKFPNPGN	1099.5632	550.7889	1099.5298	1099.5298	1099.5298
LLEKVRTLGRRKPYTDFRGG	0	591.3527	2361.3394	2361.3394	2361.3394
MIPILLFLPM	1186.5989	594.3067	1186.6858	1186.6858	1186.6858
IFGGPGG	0	604.3465	603.3016	603.3016	603.3016
EPDIILLDEAT	1227.6187	614.8166	1227.6234	1227.6234	1227.6234
NVLKY	0	636.4094	635.3643	635.3643	635.3643
EIVLVADTTEDT	0	653.33	1304.6348	1304.6348	1304.6348
ASYAGYVGKYYF	0	776.3406	1550.7081	1550.7081	1550.7081
LMYPLGP	0	790.4041	789.4095	789.4095	789.4095
DAIEVPAI	826.4181	414.2163	826.4437	826.4437	826.4437
APPLV	0	496.2743	495.3057	495.3057	495.3057
TPLFPPKNVV	1111.5823	556.7984	1111.6277	1111.6277	1111.6277
EHIIP	0	608.3819	607.3329	607.3329	607.3329
DLVFDVLQSL	1260.6359	631.3252	1260.6965	1260.6965	1260.6965
GHAVVLQNEGQILRPAIQ	0	648.3732	1942.0748	1942.0748	1942.0748
AILPKNVDIDLVPV	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
QPKSVQAAPGPAGILA	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8409	1503.8409	1503.8409
DILVNQPKLDRHI	0	781.4543	1560.8624	1560.8624	1560.8624
SNSAIMGSIP	0	976.5008	975.4695	975.4695	975.4695
PEGAESKESTTKPE	0	373.169	1488.6943	1488.6943	1488.6943
IILVGPMVVPN	1099.5632	550.7889	1099.5947	1099.5947	1099.5947

GNAIPEIKRLA	0	591.3553	1180.6927	1180.6927	1180.6927
LPEAEKLAGMP	1186.5989	594.3067	1186.5903	1186.5903	1186.5903
EQAALQGTPTLTIRNPQ	0	613.336	1836.9694	1836.9694	1836.9694
SSSLKPLNPQSN	0	636.4121	1270.6517	1270.6517	1270.6517
KTKAPQISTLEAVIVLLVVGIMSA	0	653.3978	2609.5442	2609.5442	2609.5442
SDHAYLA	0	776.3415	775.3501	775.3501	775.3501
LFENGPL	0	790.4042	789.3909	789.3909	789.3909
MIIGAPLI	826.4181	414.2163	826.4987	826.4987	826.4987
PAPIV	0	496.2729	495.3057	495.3057	495.3057
DFFPIDIF	0	507.2579	1012.4906	1012.4906	1012.4906
NNLLKQPYGTLSDGQRRRVD	0	583.3168	2329.2251	2329.2251	2329.2251
ILGDPIHLNTIVGIIILIGSVF	0	608.3822	2429.4661	2429.4661	2429.4661
IMGALALVGAGTGM	1260.6359	631.3252	1260.657	1260.657	1260.657
AILPKNVDIDLVPV	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
AILPKNVDIDLVPV	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
GGIVGAVAGVHRVLQE	0	781.4561	1560.8737	1560.8737	1560.8737
PEGAESKESTTKPE	0	373.1706	1488.6943	1488.6943	1488.6943
VEDVSMPLPN	1099.5632	550.7889	1099.522	1099.522	1099.522
HWPEFNLPN	1153.4799	577.7472	1153.5193	1153.5193	1153.5193
QAEAVLQRKVG	0	591.3525	1180.6564	1180.6564	1180.6564
EDQIESLRPT	1186.5989	594.3067	1186.583	1186.583	1186.583
LLGVLLMLMWVVGILDTDGQHLI	0	613.3358	2449.3477	2449.3477	2449.3477
RIPRLRHNL	0	636.4121	1270.7734	1270.7734	1270.7734
ENNITVVPIPIVI	0	653.3961	1304.734	1304.734	1304.734
PASAVSSAAQSTSSTAASEAPSASTS	0	776.3387	2326.0408	2326.0408	2326.0408
GGGTPT	488.2352	245.1249	488.2231	488.2231	488.2231
FPPPKLL	826.4181	414.2163	826.4953	826.4953	826.4953
LGMPAFFYWLFTKLFT	0	496.2708	1981.0212	1981.0212	1981.0212
EALYVWLNGH	1200.6096	601.3121	1200.5928	1200.5928	1200.5928
LVLILLSRKYPKGHAD	0	608.3815	1822.0829	1822.0829	1822.0829
ATATTR	0	675.3728	674.3824	674.3824	674.3824
GAGTSYHAGLVGKKLLERFA	0	692.4005	2074.1323	2074.1323	2074.1323
AGLGAALVGVTAGMGIGG	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.7865	1470.7865	1470.7865
IMLLLVVITLFRM	0	781.4576	1560.95	1560.95	1560.95
IGLMKN	674.3693	338.1919	674.3785	674.3785	674.3785
QSIHINQAEP	1095.5901	548.8023	1095.5448	1095.5448	1095.5448
GGDILTLADEP	1099.5632	550.7889	1099.5397	1099.5397	1099.5397
APSMALPAGVML	1156.5701	579.2923	1156.5984	1156.5984	1156.5984
WRGQFYAPM	1170.5999	586.3072	1170.5281	1170.5281	1170.5281
DIFNLVKKNP	1186.5989	594.3067	1186.671	1186.671	1186.671
EEPDE	0	618.2523	617.2181	617.2181	617.2181
IINQLPDTFFGL	0	697.3538	1392.7289	1392.7289	1392.7289
ATAKKMA	0	720.4291	719.4	719.4	719.4
FPPE	488.2352	245.1249	488.2271	488.2271	488.2271
LFVMPSGPKPP	1200.6096	601.3121	1200.6213	1200.6213	1200.6213
AGQIMR	0	675.3751	674.3534	674.3534	674.3534
KNKKAVFVISPQWFVRK	0	692.4027	2074.2205	2074.2205	2074.2205

DAPGVNASVMPGSEFLLGRAQTAFD	0	713.3309	2849.3291	2849.3291	2849.3291
ENAVIPAKLLNLPP	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.8446	1470.8446	1470.8446
AGIVVLVVTEVDKY	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.8549	1503.8549	1503.8549
KPDISGENLPAGRH	1503.8169	752.9157	1503.7794	1503.7794	1503.7794
IEPLIQSDKVPPLL	0	781.4547	1560.9127	1560.9127	1560.9127
VLAEDPID	0	871.4653	870.4335	870.4335	870.4335
EQAGVPLVGPSANTSGKPSPT	0	499.2694	1993.0116	1993.0116	1993.0116
FPLPLPQVV	1024.5543	513.2844	1024.5957	1024.5957	1024.5957
IAAKMHNDAN	1083.5939	542.8042	1083.5132	1083.5132	1083.5132
IVFPIAMVPN	1099.5632	550.7889	1099.61	1099.61	1099.61
DLNLPEVSGTL	1156.5701	579.2923	1156.5975	1156.5975	1156.5975
FLAFVPHMPI	1170.5999	586.3072	1170.626	1170.626	1170.626
EEPDE	0	618.2519	617.2181	617.2181	617.2181
AGSATKN	0	648.3745	647.3239	647.3239	647.3239
KQNQLEPFYVQ	0	697.3551	1392.7037	1392.7037	1392.7037
PGVAELKQRLKKIHADVTR	0	720.4311	2158.2698	2158.2698	2158.2698
DILPLMITEG	1100.5653	551.2899	1100.5787	1100.5787	1100.5787
PVVLQGGQLQH	1134.525	568.2698	1134.6033	1134.6033	1134.6033
QLIEDGVTENT	1200.6096	601.3121	1200.551	1200.551	1200.551
AGTGFVAITDGPR	0	631.349	1260.6462	1260.6462	1260.6462
LSLLILGDPIHL	0	652.4045	1302.7911	1302.7911	1302.7911
IFTTDPQSITFVYVRLDAGNITVK	0	675.3751	2697.4377	2697.4377	2697.4377
PGKKLPGRMGNKT	0	692.4026	1382.7816	1382.7816	1382.7816
VPVVKPTTEVATQS	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.793	1470.793	1470.793
ENIGMNIGLLP	1170.5999	586.3072	1170.5955	1170.5955	1170.5955
EEPDE	0	618.2556	617.2181	617.2181	617.2181
CILLPQNPLSR	0	635.3769	1268.691	1268.691	1268.691
TESLNFVFNPSIAPGTAF	0	643.3066	1926.9364	1926.9364	1926.9364
AGTPKQVERSRLSLTGQYLAGKKS	0	648.3762	2589.4351	2589.4351	2589.4351
LPPPPPPPPPPPP	1311.7097	656.8621	1311.7227	1311.7227	1311.7227
IKAIYNNLTLPP	1356.791	679.4028	1356.7653	1356.7653	1356.7653
LCPEITVFLQCDWLRWSRLYACA	0	697.3548	2785.3542	2785.3542	2785.3542
AEISKKRVIKGPN	0	720.4316	1438.8619	1438.8619	1438.8619
FPIILPILT	1025.5551	513.7848	1025.6525	1025.6525	1025.6525
DIIPLYKQI	1101.5659	551.7902	1101.6434	1101.6434	1101.6434
GTMVMLQLFLSSVTGRKEA	0	652.4087	1954.0016	1954.0016	1954.0016
PGAIDAHISGNFF	0	673.3323	1344.6462	1344.6462	1344.6462
QLQKLINEENLKTAAARKTNAEN	0	675.3729	2697.4409	2697.4409	2697.4409
GVRQRRNVQDR	0	692.3986	1382.7604	1382.7604	1382.7604
NVPGAVPKTSTDALT	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.7566	1470.7566	1470.7566
ASAAQNIRPED	1170.5999	586.3072	1170.5629	1170.5629	1170.5629
EEPFP	0	618.2538	617.2697	617.2697	617.2697
LQIKPVMDVDPLGHLRPVQKVR	0	635.3806	2537.4629	2537.4629	2537.4629
NPLSNNLPLSIE	1311.7097	656.8621	1311.6558	1311.6558	1311.6558
PLVNFLLAGLAGGV	1356.791	679.4028	1356.7653	1356.7653	1356.7653
LAQDVINSIPEFN	1459.6749	730.8447	1459.7195	1459.7195	1459.7195
IGPTVLSVATVPDLNTP	0	855.4818	1708.9247	1708.9247	1708.9247

DILLGTQMIAGLDFPEVTLVGVLNAI	0	871.4824	3481.863	3481.863	3481.863
NNGGQVFRWVRDELFTTESQTARAN	0	1051.519	3151.5183	3151.5183	3151.5183
DIIPLYKQI	1101.5659	551.7902	1101.6434	1101.6434	1101.6434
TTDYLVLPGPP	1187.5819	594.7982	1187.6074	1187.6074	1187.6074
AHFLGV	0	643.3076	642.3489	642.3489	642.3489
ISSTQIRQKISHGHSVRYLVPEA	0	652.4076	2605.4089	2605.4089	2605.4089
DPVSKQ	0	673.3337	672.3442	672.3442	672.3442
LPGALQIMLSNGVVVGSVAAVGLNLI	0	692.3986	2765.5513	2765.5513	2765.5513
IVVVIVVYVQMP	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.8884	1470.8884	1470.8884
AGTPLTVNPDVLEEPT	0	827.3969	1652.8145	1652.8145	1652.8145
GPNLAEY	762.4231	382.2188	762.3548	762.3548	762.3548
DDLHATIGPL	1050.5187	526.2666	1050.5345	1050.5345	1050.5345
VVYPVPVGTGP	1083.5939	542.8042	1083.5964	1083.5964	1083.5964
FLPVAFYML	1198.6306	600.3226	1198.646	1198.646	1198.646
EEFPF	0	618.2515	617.2697	617.2697	617.2697
MILISLPSAVL	0	635.3797	1268.7778	1268.7778	1268.7778
GAPANLGTGVATGGIPELLTDKALK	0	648.375	2589.4741	2589.4741	2589.4741
NPLSNNLPLSIE	1311.7097	656.8621	1311.6558	1311.6558	1311.6558
LAVLAIVLVLSGCS	1356.791	679.4028	1356.8051	1356.8051	1356.8051
GGPLYKKYVAVTT	0	780.4505	1558.8395	1558.8395	1558.8395
LMDVKN	718.3949	360.2047	718.3683	718.3683	718.3683
FFVVQN	752.4481	377.2313	752.3857	752.3857	752.3857
ILGIASYFAYPWGYLFGAATVIL	0	631.3495	2521.3298	2521.3298	2521.3298
DPGFPL	0	645.3105	644.317	644.317	644.317
QLGIKTAPYVTI	0	652.4066	1302.7548	1302.7548	1302.7548
LVVNVINGNSDLAQ	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.7678	1470.7678	1470.7678
ESLWAQRSPNTDA	1473.6869	737.8507	1473.6848	1473.6848	1473.6848
ESPKIGVVKRSKIS	0	764.4539	1526.9144	1526.9144	1526.9144
KNVVKKLRKESHK	0	399.2435	1592.9839	1592.9839	1592.9839
MPEVVVAADGP	1083.5939	542.8042	1083.5271	1083.5271	1083.5271
MEDPLPLYP	1105.5363	553.7754	1105.5001	1105.5001	1105.5001
DFILPQNPM	1105.5363	553.7754	1105.5114	1105.5114	1105.5114
PGTPEQPETPE	1180.4827	591.2486	1180.5248	1180.5248	1180.5248
EEFPF	0	618.2508	617.2697	617.2697	617.2697
KFTLLMLLNFSLIITAFIITEP	0	635.377	2537.4583	2537.4583	2537.4583
PAPTKEV	0	741.379	740.4069	740.4069	740.4069
LDDAIHSTVVENLS	0	757.3529	1512.7307	1512.7307	1512.7307
ATFVTKN	0	780.4515	779.4177	779.4177	779.4177
KATNATN	718.3949	360.2047	718.361	718.361	718.361
HTALRR	752.4481	377.2313	752.4406	752.4406	752.4406
ITGY	0	453.3034	452.2271	452.2271	452.2271
VTLAAPVGSVGVLLYNLVG	0	652.4048	1954.1503	1954.1503	1954.1503
DISAFPSDPRRL	1372.6417	687.3281	1372.71	1372.71	1372.71
ALMAPLYHKALR	0	692.4007	1382.7856	1382.7856	1382.7856
GGLGDIIIRGTNATN	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.7791	1470.7791	1470.7791
AQSSVASATKPAQAQA	1473.6869	737.8507	1473.7423	1473.7423	1473.7423
ASKTVTSA	0	764.457	763.4076	763.4076	763.4076

VEGIDLPF	0	889.4744	888.4593	888.4593	888.4593
PDSIDRPDILTADIH	0	420.1231	1676.8369	1676.8369	1676.8369
IAATGQLTVPN	1083.5939	542.8042	1083.5924	1083.5924	1083.5924
EDGAVTQPLIL	1170.5999	586.3072	1170.6132	1170.6132	1170.6132
EEFPF	0	618.253	617.2697	617.2697	617.2697
QDPNLADK DANQ	1328.613	665.3138	1328.5845	1328.5845	1328.5845
RENPLNTDANTGI	1429.6663	715.8404	1429.6797	1429.6797	1429.6797
APSQIIQDP IVSPT	0	741.3794	1480.7773	1480.7773	1480.7773
ADPDINI	0	757.3523	756.3654	756.3654	756.3654
GPLGSGYSVMSFVFRIGLLILL	0	780.4509	2338.3123	2338.3123	2338.3123
LEKQSN	718.3949	360.2047	718.3497	718.3497	718.3497
QQHVQN	752.4481	377.2313	752.3566	752.3566	752.3566
GSGHPGLP	763.4225	382.7185	763.3613	763.3613	763.3613
IVKVDYPK	960.5961	481.3053	960.5644	960.5644	960.5644
APQYTKPNTKAVKKMQKN	0	692.4002	2074.1357	2074.1357	2074.1357
PASLVLP	0	696.4304	695.4218	695.4218	695.4218
PLDVNVPVIYVEN	1470.8379	736.4262	1470.7606	1470.7606	1470.7606
IIAALAQKRIQFR	0	764.4568	1526.9409	1526.9409	1526.9409
FIVMLGPI	0	889.4768	888.5143	888.5143	888.5143
GYGLRN	678.4011	340.2078	678.3449	678.3449	678.3449
DPALPNGAS	840.4941	421.2543	840.3978	840.3978	840.3978
FSIISLL	0	453.3006	904.5634	904.5634	904.5634
YVNRDYL	942.3887	472.2016	942.4447	942.4447	942.4447
AYEVDGHAENALIPLVALM	0	507.2565	2025.0242	2025.0242	2025.0242
VQDSTIPLLNH	0	627.3408	1252.6299	1252.6299	1252.6299
PLDFPL	0	701.3868	700.3796	700.3796	700.3796
DLIIQKAAKPGIKPFKKLY	0	724.4607	2170.3242	2170.3242	2170.3242
ILLALGN	712.4531	357.2338	712.4483	712.4483	712.4483
NPIP	0	440.2447	439.2431	439.2431	439.2431
PIVVLMLVLPK	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.7039	1123.7039	1123.7039
GPAFRAEDSHTRHAAEFWMVEP	0	661.3216	2641.2131	2641.2131	2641.2131
KAAIVHELPGGQN	0	675.372	1348.71	1348.71	1348.71
CLADLPVNKD VW	1372.6417	687.3281	1372.6697	1372.6697	1372.6697
PGGHLLV	0	692.3975	691.4017	691.4017	691.4017
PGTPVLI	0	696.4325	695.4218	695.4218	695.4218
VEGIDLPF	0	889.475	888.4593	888.4593	888.4593
TTAAASSA	678.4011	340.2078	678.3184	678.3184	678.3184
DTAGVIFTLDTTCA	1426.5619	476.5279	1426.665	1426.665	1426.665
EEDEP	0	618.2526	617.2181	617.2181	617.2181
IDPGLP	0	627.3431	626.3275	626.3275	626.3275
NLQKCAIGDVLN	0	701.3872	1400.7334	1400.7334	1400.7334
ILKPTGKLVTIAGH	0	724.461	1446.8922	1446.8922	1446.8922
GPTAPQPERPAVPGP	1470.8353	736.4249	1470.7467	1470.7467	1470.7467
IPERLL	0	740.4526	739.4592	739.4592	739.4592
SIRKPI	712.4531	357.2338	712.4595	712.4595	712.4595
AFRKQN	762.4203	382.2174	762.4137	762.4137	762.4137
AGKLYVN	763.4225	382.7185	763.4229	763.4229	763.4229

IVTVFDM	823.4733	412.7439	823.415	823.415	823.415
EVAVEIVP	0	436.2405	870.4698	870.4698	870.4698
AQQIMGDSPSNPL	1372.6417	687.3281	1372.6293	1372.6293	1372.6293
KVPSATLVHKRGV	0	696.4327	1390.8408	1390.8408	1390.8408
PGTTGPNGPETTGPE	1426.5593	714.2869	1426.6212	1426.6212	1426.6212
KNERIGKVDLME	1430.6705	716.3425	1430.7551	1430.7551	1430.7551
FIVMLGPI	0	889.4739	888.5143	888.5143	888.5143
GHNKHS	678.4011	340.2078	678.3198	678.3198	678.3198
TPDQPELPEV	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.5397	1123.5397	1123.5397
ASTHENNAPLAP	0	611.2975	1220.5786	1220.5786	1220.5786
IIMASSVLLGGLL	1285.6719	643.8432	1285.7679	1285.7679	1285.7679
PTPVSTVSTPVVAE	0	692.3964	1382.7294	1382.7294	1382.7294
LTQLFIGKTTDAINYPPIP	0	701.3853	2101.146	2101.146	2101.146
DAPIVPL	0	724.4633	723.4167	723.4167	723.4167
EALEVNVYGGGVLAV	1470.8329	736.4237	1470.7719	1470.7719	1470.7719
AKGQNPAIKQLLNGVSHMIPFVVVG(0		780.4508	3117.7524	3117.7524	3117.7524
RLGLSKILERYRQVDTKRLYALLNRR	0	808.4767	3229.8999	3229.8999	3229.8999
TANKESN	762.4203	382.2174	762.3508	762.3508	762.3508
QNYSQAS	796.4719	399.2432	796.3351	796.3351	796.3351
FIVMLGPI	888.4703	445.2424	888.5143	888.5143	888.5143
IPKAINDIPV	1079.5773	540.7959	1079.6227	1079.6227	1079.6227
KPTLPSDCAGQIK	1372.6417	687.3281	1372.702	1372.702	1372.702
EVDGHH	0	693.2408	692.2878	692.2878	692.2878
LILGLTLLAGHFAQRIGIPAVVGQLLV	0	696.4314	2781.6997	2781.6997	2781.6997
ENESPVLVAAMQESVDVQPAALG	0	785.4035	2353.1472	2353.1472	2353.1472
AQRAGVAE	0	801.3775	800.4141	800.4141	800.4141
ATGKGFALFALLVGLGP	0	824.4791	1646.9396	1646.9396	1646.9396
LNDYEKTIDVY	0	344.1783	1372.6398	1372.6398	1372.6398
GPKVGLVR	824.5051	413.2598	824.5232	824.5232	824.5232
EPKVMGGLP	942.3887	472.2016	942.4844	942.4844	942.4844
MIPIMIVIMPI	1285.6719	643.8432	1285.7212	1285.7212	1285.7212
DEIKESIQPD	1285.6719	643.8432	1285.6401	1285.6401	1285.6401
LDPLAVHDLLAL	0	653.3957	1304.734	1304.734	1304.734
NFYLVAGLNPLLI	0	780.454	1558.9124	1558.9124	1558.9124
EIVPKNISIDIPLKVLMMVVVT	0	808.4825	2422.3909	2422.3909	2422.3909
TANKESN	762.4203	382.2174	762.3508	762.3508	762.3508
DLLRPAI	796.4719	399.2432	796.4807	796.4807	796.4807
ANRIGALIV	925.4875	463.751	925.5709	925.5709	925.5709
VVSGMLFPVVV	1145.5975	573.806	1145.6519	1145.6519	1145.6519
ILDLPFTFDDI	1176.5299	589.2722	1176.5914	1176.5914	1176.5914
DEVMAE	0	693.2413	692.2687	692.2687	692.2687
VASPGGVFDQKALLPATIVSSARQQK	0	696.4323	2781.5137	2781.5137	2781.5137
AFREVTEVDAVHV	1470.8319	736.4232	1470.7467	1470.7467	1470.7467
GLKIFGENPEYFR	0	785.4048	1568.7987	1568.7987	1568.7987
DPTQQITDLKAQLD	0	801.3808	1600.7944	1600.7944	1600.7944
LDDPEV	0	344.1783	686.3123	686.3123	686.3123
NAGTAFLS	779.4471	390.7308	779.3813	779.3813	779.3813

EQPTKPVE	0	472.2351	942.4658	942.4658	942.4658
PTDPILQILP	1105.6057	553.8101	1105.6383	1105.6383	1105.6383
IISLLEPEPFL	1285.6719	643.8432	1285.7169	1285.7169	1285.7169
IIMASSVLLGGLL	1285.6719	643.8432	1285.7679	1285.7679	1285.7679
PLLANQPVVIPI	0	653.3952	1304.7704	1304.7704	1304.7704
KLHPFV	0	740.4596	739.4381	739.4381	739.4381
LLAAVLLMGYTHVKTIMLLPIL	0	808.4769	2422.446	2422.446	2422.446
GYVLTGN	722.4261	362.2203	722.3599	722.3599	722.3599
AKMQQAS	762.4203	382.2174	762.3694	762.3694	762.3694
LILIYTGL	0	453.3055	904.5634	904.5634	904.5634
ISEVLANAYR	1135.5061	568.7603	1135.5873	1135.5873	1135.5873
VPTEVPGTSLF	1145.5975	573.806	1145.5968	1145.5968	1145.5968
ATGAVPPQMQTI	1212.6425	607.3285	1212.6173	1212.6173	1212.6173
SGVEAQC	0	693.2383	692.28	692.28	692.28
EDRPISIFKNGKVMMLYNIP	0	745.4059	2233.1929	2233.1929	2233.1929
IPISIEP	0	768.4855	767.4429	767.4429	767.4429
LDDPEV	0	344.1786	686.3123	686.3123	686.3123
SAQQQNVFVPAAVSMVYT	0	472.2325	1884.8928	1884.8928	1884.8928
GPGNPNDLPAE	1079.5817	540.7981	1079.4884	1079.4884	1079.4884
NQPLKPDIPT	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.576	1123.576	1123.576
TNVAGVMKAAPDL	1285.6719	643.8432	1285.67	1285.67	1285.67
LDPLAVHDLAL	0	653.3948	1304.734	1304.734	1304.734
PLAAAIKTIVEKAF	0	736.4279	1470.881	1470.881	1470.881
VPRGNVV	0	740.4581	739.4341	739.4341	739.4341
IEPLIQSDKVPPLL	0	781.4519	1560.9127	1560.9127	1560.9127
TAAVLPPAVPMAFDVPMLSAVGVGL	0	868.5055	3469.9697	3469.9697	3469.9697
YGKNQCN	722.4261	362.2203	722.3348	722.3348	722.3348
LPAGTVIS	756.4785	379.2465	756.4382	756.4382	756.4382
KVVDPNN	784.5101	393.2623	784.4079	784.4079	784.4079
GYKTPKGT	850.4737	426.2441	850.4549	850.4549	850.4549
KNNGLTIT	860.3653	431.1899	860.4603	860.4603	860.4603
DAVSPQVPAPN	1135.5061	568.7603	1135.5509	1135.5509	1135.5509
DINLIKRVKN	1212.6425	607.3285	1212.719	1212.719	1212.719
LPDKAIDLIDEAAKIRIDAAEKQSKR	0	745.4104	2977.656	2977.656	2977.656
LPVSGGDIDPHNVDA	0	761.3863	1520.7107	1520.7107	1520.7107
GLIAKTAIRALPLDTVKSILPI	0	768.4874	2302.4353	2302.4353	2302.4353
ASWNQTT	806.4467	404.2306	806.3559	806.3559	806.3559
ATVVPGALP	823.4727	412.7436	823.4803	823.4803	823.4803
STVLVDAAEP	1000.5603	501.2874	1000.5077	1000.5077	1000.5077
EPESEIELDVEP	0	701.3243	1400.6195	1400.6195	1400.6195
LEENVEVIKITAN	0	736.4267	1470.793	1470.793	1470.793
TRLKKNLDLHKN	0	740.4601	1478.8682	1478.8682	1478.8682
PVFWSYVPEILPL	0	780.4488	1558.8435	1558.8435	1558.8435
DVPGLLIAA	0	868.5072	867.5066	867.5066	867.5066
AAPITHN	722.4261	362.2203	722.3712	722.3712	722.3712
NKKQNIP	840.4991	421.2568	840.4818	840.4818	840.4818
ASTAQATT	850.4737	426.2441	850.4032	850.4032	850.4032

VVQIVNVV	868.5265	435.2705	868.5382	868.5382	868.5382
DAVSPQVPAPN	1135.5061	568.7603	1135.5509	1135.5509	1135.5509
NVVVDTDQTAK	1188.4253	595.2199	1188.5986	1188.5986	1188.5986
QATKSEAKPAKTANIQNVISELQRVTL 0		745.4118	2977.6196	2977.6196	2977.6196
PKVISQP	0	768.486	767.4542	767.4542	767.4542
GALLDAPQMVIPPLLR	0	852.5021	1702.9803	1702.9803	1702.9803
ELQAYAI	806.4467	404.2306	806.4174	806.4174	806.4174
NLLLPHN	845.4523	423.7334	845.4647	845.4647	845.4647
TIQKVVPIPE	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.6489	1123.6489	1123.6489
KVHQLVQTYQEV	1471.7107	736.8626	1471.7671	1471.7671	1471.7671
KVRHHIGMIFQN	0	740.455	1478.7928	1478.7928	1478.7928
EMKKNPPKIIKPGP	0	824.4788	1646.9542	1646.9542	1646.9542
FGDLSGVGVAFKACALLEEVPEEFLC 0		829.4327	3313.6831	3313.6831	3313.6831
VVKMYVC	840.4991	421.2568	840.4238	840.4238	840.4238
SSAKGAVGAN	860.3639	431.1892	860.4352	860.4352	860.4352
DAVSPQVPAPN	1135.5061	568.7603	1135.5509	1135.5509	1135.5509
MPEVPITAIPA	1137.5143	569.7644	1137.6104	1137.6104	1137.6104
ALDTALTVLEPQ	1269.6489	635.8317	1269.6816	1269.6816	1269.6816
NIPVDNQIPLHK	1389.7437	695.8791	1389.714	1389.714	1389.714
TILGMGLSGVANQGCDIGGFDGPLP{ 0		845.4073	2533.1829	2533.1829	2533.1829
ATAMRSQALPFKVKR	0	852.5045	1702.9664	1702.9664	1702.9664
ATNQQFV	806.4467	404.2306	806.3923	806.3923	806.3923
PTQKGIII	868.5279	435.2712	868.5382	868.5382	868.5382
EIAGTWDIP	1000.5603	501.2874	1000.4866	1000.4866	1000.4866
ALDTALTVLEPQ	1269.6489	635.8317	1269.6816	1269.6816	1269.6816
LLVGIMFGLLPP	1284.7695	643.392	1284.7516	1284.7516	1284.7516
EVFSTVV	0	780.446	779.4065	779.4065	779.4065
AGNHLAKN	0	824.478	823.4301	823.4301	823.4301
LINTTDIQIFEQQP	1658.8336	830.4241	1658.8516	1658.8516	1658.8516
FVKQQN	762.4185	382.2165	762.4025	762.4025	762.4025
QGNNVPR	766.4521	384.2333	766.3722	766.3722	766.3722
GGVLVFI	800.5049	401.2597	800.4796	800.4796	800.4796
NKKQNIP	840.4991	421.2568	840.4818	840.4818	840.4818
IVIPKTN	0	784.4835	783.4854	783.4854	783.4854
IVALLGLN	0	812.5104	811.5167	811.5167	811.5167
IVAASLARLLKNRGLKVTIQKFD	0	852.5057	2554.5322	2554.5322	2554.5322
YGQNVLN	806.4467	404.2306	806.3923	806.3923	806.3923
DLTLPLAS	828.5381	415.2763	828.4593	828.4593	828.4593
ATLQGYEL	894.4971	448.2558	894.4335	894.4335	894.4335
KRPVWMI	928.5522	465.2834	928.5317	928.5317	928.5317
GVLTMIVSIL	1044.5857	523.3001	1044.6252	1044.6252	1044.6252
ITQQVLPVPL	1123.6207	562.8176	1123.6489	1123.6489	1123.6489
IPVVQVDLANFA	1284.7695	643.392	1284.7078	1284.7078	1284.7078
LVLGHKN	0	780.4515	779.4654	779.4654	779.4654
NKANSIKGLVSRPDYVKPDYNLDALVIO		789.439	3153.6936	3153.6936	3153.6936
GPTLAGALPKIIDGPWIKWNPLN	0	824.4774	2470.3735	2470.3735	2470.3735
GKTESN	762.4185	382.2165	762.3872	762.3872	762.3872

AVRNGHN	766.4521	384.2333	766.3834	766.3834	766.3834
EAITSAIP	800.5049	401.2597	800.428	800.428	800.428
FAGEPKAS	805.4599	403.7372	805.397	805.397	805.397
ELTHTGVR	911.5225	456.7685	911.4825	911.4825	911.4825
AAGMSIGMLVI	1061.6102	531.8124	1061.5613	1061.5613	1061.5613
ALEQRAKQDNP	1269.6489	635.8317	1269.6313	1269.6313	1269.6313
KTIPLWSQGLE	1271.5917	636.8031	1271.6761	1271.6761	1271.6761
QAALRKVTALGIGKAA	0	784.4858	1566.9569	1566.9569	1566.9569
DPAKVGLL	0	812.5149	811.4803	811.4803	811.4803
IIMSGVLP	828.5381	415.2763	828.4779	828.4779	828.4779
GKYKNKN	850.4715	426.243	850.4661	850.4661	850.4661
NKTYTKN	867.4987	434.7566	867.445	867.445	867.445
LAPEASIAN	884.5249	443.2697	884.4603	884.4603	884.4603
AGGGKGANQAV	928.5522	465.2834	928.4727	928.4727	928.4727
PTQIFKGVVG	1044.5857	523.3001	1044.5968	1044.5968	1044.5968
RAVLPTVQPV	1078.6375	540.326	1078.6499	1078.6499	1078.6499
DMINNMISYQLN	1471.7107	736.8626	1471.6323	1471.6323	1471.6323
GRLLDTPVFGTSVV	0	780.45	1558.8719	1558.8719	1558.8719
ALVGSFICIVLSLRS	0	789.4349	1576.9011	1576.9011	1576.9011
HGNLVGGN	766.4521	384.2333	766.3722	766.3722	766.3722
ITDGAVLP	800.5049	401.2597	800.428	800.428	800.428
FGYLFLM	889.4775	445.746	889.4408	889.4408	889.4408
LEKQVLAL	912.5535	457.284	912.5644	912.5644	912.5644
AVGMILLIRLPI	1194.6581	598.3363	1194.7522	1194.7522	1194.7522
ILSNDADSIPEP	1269.6489	635.8317	1269.6089	1269.6089	1269.6089
ITVGYDAIEYE	1271.5917	636.8031	1271.5922	1271.5922	1271.5922
DLVVLPE	0	784.4841	783.4378	783.4378	783.4378
IDPYLKRHDLKII	0	812.5121	1622.9508	1622.9508	1622.9508
IEGHARVVVDGRRKIS	0	896.5293	1791.0227	1791.0227	1791.0227
AGSSRRKFV	850.4715	426.243	850.4661	850.4661	850.4661
PGVDEIKAG	884.5249	443.2697	884.4603	884.4603	884.4603
NEGHQYGT	904.3889	453.2017	904.3675	904.3675	904.3675
DLPPRKGf	928.5522	465.2834	928.5131	928.5131	928.5131
GPISDAIFIP	1044.5857	523.3001	1044.5492	1044.5492	1044.5492
DNGGVPLVLPV	1078.6375	540.326	1078.6023	1078.6023	1078.6023
ELTQLASELRHVLLN	0	868.5051	1734.9629	1734.9629	1734.9629
FIEIEQDIGRKAFSALYRDLITFDCKLKC	0	873.4599	3489.833	3489.833	3489.833
GPTADTPRV	912.5535	457.284	912.4665	912.4665	912.4665
GLRTAGAEIMA	1088.6091	545.3118	1088.5648	1088.5648	1088.5648
LPVPRPHPNP	1122.6615	562.338	1122.6298	1122.6298	1122.6298
GLISVILGIGIL	1166.6891	584.3518	1166.7638	1166.7638	1166.7638
EPATGKILAEED	1271.5917	636.8031	1271.6245	1271.6245	1271.6245
ASLSDIVPRPSTLIV	0	784.4811	1566.8981	1566.8981	1566.8981
IPVVLNKN	0	896.5337	895.5491	895.5491	895.5491
GKYKNKN	850.4715	426.243	850.4661	850.4661	850.4661
LAPEASIAN	884.5249	443.2697	884.4603	884.4603	884.4603
PGGNLQRGGHN	1105.6356	553.8251	1105.5377	1105.5377	1105.5377

LFKYLAKHN	1132.6375	567.326	1132.6393	1132.6393	1132.6393
ECLPTANIPYPGA	0	673.3093	1344.6384	1344.6384	1344.6384
IDLGIAGVKAGIVKWPSTIR	0	742.4406	2224.2766	2224.2766	2224.2766
GPALNPARDLGPRLVHAILPIKH	0	824.4748	2470.4285	2470.4285	2470.4285
TANKILIDSMTLLFR	0	868.5047	1734.9702	1734.9702	1734.9702
ELNKQKN	0	873.4565	872.4716	872.4716	872.4716
ASASSVKSA	806.4459	404.2302	806.4134	806.4134	806.4134
GMYTLLGG	810.4767	406.2456	810.3946	810.3946	810.3946
ALAMAAVAK	844.5305	423.2725	844.4841	844.4841	844.4841
FINQNKPI	972.5746	487.2946	972.5392	972.5392	972.5392
DYIPLLMP	992.4518	497.2332	992.4889	992.4889	992.4889
QNTAKKNKSA	1088.6091	545.3118	1088.5939	1088.5939	1088.5939
LPKNVDIDL	1122.6615	562.338	1122.6284	1122.6284	1122.6284
LISEPPLQVLP	1220.6703	611.3424	1220.7017	1220.7017	1220.7017
IFPMPLAQAGSY	1293.7051	647.8598	1293.6427	1293.6427	1293.6427
IIGLIGEN	0	828.5091	827.4753	827.4753	827.4753
GAQVVTGGY	850.4715	426.243	850.4185	850.4185	850.4185
KQGKSGLR	872.5611	437.2878	872.5192	872.5192	872.5192
DLIEKNPG	884.5249	443.2697	884.4603	884.4603	884.4603
KTTQEILP	928.5495	465.282	928.5229	928.5229	928.5229
NPKNQKN	938.5207	470.2676	938.4934	938.4934	938.4934
IVGLFILVE	1001.5475	501.781	1001.6161	1001.6161	1001.6161
ELKKHLPN	1105.6356	553.8251	1105.6608	1105.6608	1105.6608
FPLLYTA	0	824.4769	823.448	823.448	823.448
LPVRGAKVPAPKAPAK	1711.9735	856.994	1712.0461	1712.0461	1712.0461
QVLVKTNRQQDLDP	0	868.4989	1734.9629	1734.9629	1734.9629
HGNPMQK	810.4767	406.2456	810.3807	810.3807	810.3807
APSAKKLM	844.5305	423.2725	844.4841	844.4841	844.4841
FINQLFN	894.4958	448.2552	894.46	894.46	894.46
AGPGIILSFV	972.5746	487.2946	972.5644	972.5644	972.5644
QTGAGKSTLLN	1088.6091	545.3118	1088.5826	1088.5826	1088.5826
PLEKIVVDNP	1122.6615	562.338	1122.6284	1122.6284	1122.6284
LISEPPLQVLP	1220.6703	611.3424	1220.7017	1220.7017	1220.7017
MIPLKNL	0	828.5106	827.4939	827.4939	827.4939
PALILISLGYFLSMQ	0	833.4604	1664.9211	1664.9211	1664.9211
EVHTEPL	823.4727	412.7436	823.4076	823.4076	823.4076
INVSLSL	872.5611	437.2878	872.5331	872.5331	872.5331
QIGKAGNKN	911.5245	456.7695	911.4825	911.4825	911.4825
QIGKAGNKN	928.5495	465.282	928.509	928.509	928.509
PTKDKKGLA	956.5797	479.2971	956.5655	956.5655	956.5655
KLQEITGETN	1132.6323	567.3234	1132.5612	1132.5612	1132.5612
EILRPIDIQPI	1321.7148	661.8647	1321.7605	1321.7605	1321.7605
LIQGMLNVVQPLPL	1550.8182	776.4164	1550.8741	1550.8741	1550.8741
KAHQQLKQAPQLDHA	1711.9735	856.994	1711.9117	1711.9117	1711.9117
HGNPMQK	810.4767	406.2456	810.3807	810.3807	810.3807
TKGAGNQGI	844.5305	423.2725	844.4403	844.4403	844.4403
EIQNKYT	894.4958	448.2552	894.4447	894.4447	894.4447

QMKIPVVVLN	1122.6615	562.338	1122.6471	1122.6471	1122.6471
TATHAVQRR	1166.6888	584.3517	1166.6268	1166.6268	1166.6268
IGRLIDLPSI	1210.7133	606.3639	1210.6921	1210.6921	1210.6921
LISEPPLQVLP	1220.6703	611.3424	1220.7017	1220.7017	1220.7017
DILQLLN	0	828.5086	827.4753	827.4753	827.4753
LLDKLKALRPDVQKDQ	0	940.5578	1879.0891	1879.0891	1879.0891
AINAQNPAN	911.5245	456.7695	911.4461	911.4461	911.4461
ELGIEIKK	928.5495	465.282	928.5593	928.5593	928.5593
GPKVTPTKN	956.5797	479.2971	956.5291	956.5291	956.5291
QSAKEMRKR	1132.6323	567.3234	1132.6135	1132.6135	1132.6135
EIAYVREN	1149.6609	575.8377	1149.5779	1149.5779	1149.5779
DIVQAYINKN	1176.6603	589.3374	1176.6139	1176.6139	1176.6139
GNAALKITVPIPE	1321.7148	661.8647	1321.7605	1321.7605	1321.7605
DILHMIVANNVVDQIKGMVFRSDRTIO		917.4813	3665.8958	3665.8958	3665.8958
GAILKPL	0	356.2504	710.4691	710.4691	710.4691
ATQTTTATT	894.4958	448.2552	894.4294	894.4294	894.4294
DLEDNKFL	992.4518	497.2332	992.4815	992.4815	992.4815
KNVKPLGVSEP	1166.6888	584.3517	1166.6659	1166.6659	1166.6659
KVIEKRDHVA	1193.6873	597.8509	1193.6881	1193.6881	1193.6881
LPIIEANELEA	1210.7133	606.3639	1210.6445	1210.6445	1210.6445
TPQAGRVPQKLPLQI	0	824.4727	1646.9355	1646.9355	1646.9355
AVLFILPGIVGIVHVLFG	0	940.5599	1879.1335	1879.1335	1879.1335
SRIANHAS	854.5027	428.2586	854.4359	854.4359	854.4359
LWAGGVRN	871.5293	436.7719	871.4664	871.4664	871.4664
NALAIVTGM	888.5567	445.2856	888.4739	888.4739	888.4739
EIAALADLP	911.5245	456.7695	911.4964	911.4964	911.4964
QIGKAGNKN	928.5495	465.282	928.509	928.509	928.509
LPAGYRVQN	1016.6001	509.3073	1016.5403	1016.5403	1016.5403
QSAKEMRKR	1132.6323	567.3234	1132.6135	1132.6135	1132.6135
LTGVLFGLAIF	1149.6609	575.8377	1149.6798	1149.6798	1149.6798
LDAPQMVIPPLL	1321.7148	661.8647	1321.7316	1321.7316	1321.7316
QNDQITDELYSLI	1550.8182	776.4164	1550.7465	1550.7465	1550.7465
GYKKRVT	850.4733	426.2439	850.5025	850.5025	850.5025
ILAEQRR	884.5229	443.2687	884.5192	884.5192	884.5192
SIAVASSFGG	894.4958	448.2552	894.4447	894.4447	894.4447
GIISITGVAS	916.5867	459.3006	916.5229	916.5229	916.5229
FIDELFLP	992.4518	497.2332	992.5219	992.5219	992.5219
QDSKQPLPVR	1166.6888	584.3517	1166.6407	1166.6407	1166.6407
TQGVINLAEGIP	1210.7133	606.3639	1210.6558	1210.6558	1210.6558
EDPIQAQPVLP	1222.6869	612.3507	1222.6082	1222.6082	1222.6082
KNNIFLQLPTFVFNLLQVSAILA	0	868.5022	2602.4888	2602.4888	2602.4888
TYNKKAM	854.5027	428.2586	854.432	854.432	854.432
AIEGSRVAS	888.5567	445.2856	888.4665	888.4665	888.4665
NKKSDPHN	938.5231	470.2688	938.457	938.457	938.457
VVKKSGQPN	955.5491	478.7818	955.5451	955.5451	955.5451
AAKVTVVAGAS	972.5757	487.2951	972.5604	972.5604	972.5604
KNVFEGQRR	1132.6323	567.3234	1132.6101	1132.6101	1132.6101

KNKFAEQLSL	1176.6609	589.3377	1176.6503	1176.6503	1176.6503
VVKKSGQPNKNG	1254.7395	628.377	1254.7045	1254.7045	1254.7045
GRLSAAHVWLAIGFLIVVLIVGPTL	0	872.5362	2614.5728	2614.5728	2614.5728
TAHPIHFPLPPFTLIGATTRAGLLSA	0	900.566	2698.4958	2698.4958	2698.4958
DYIPLLMP	992.4518	497.2332	992.4889	992.4889	992.4889
LQQQATQIA	1000.6045	501.3095	1000.5189	1000.5189	1000.5189
AKFRKIVR	1016.6001	509.3073	1016.6607	1016.6607	1016.6607
QDSKQPLPVR	1166.6888	584.3517	1166.6407	1166.6407	1166.6407
PTKSKSSKFAN	1193.6873	597.8509	1193.6404	1193.6404	1193.6404
AQAAGVRTILNP	1210.7133	606.3639	1210.667	1210.667	1210.667
DNPKKYL	0	877.4897	876.4705	876.4705	876.4705
DRRHTGN	854.5027	428.2586	854.4107	854.4107	854.4107
INVASRVN	871.5293	436.7719	871.4875	871.4875	871.4875
NKGNSKGGK	888.5567	445.2856	888.4777	888.4777	888.4777
FINQFISA	938.5231	470.2688	938.4861	938.4861	938.4861
DTNQVVAPI	955.5491	478.7818	955.4974	955.4974	955.4974
VQAAQAGNKS	972.5757	487.2951	972.4988	972.4988	972.4988
GDSSFVIGKGN	1176.6609	589.3377	1176.5775	1176.5775	1176.5775
KIADLKQQQLA	1254.7393	628.3769	1254.7296	1254.7296	1254.7296
PLLVNHA	0	763.4249	762.4388	762.4388	762.4388
GPQGTAVLKGK	0	984.5812	983.54	983.54	983.54
NLPYPVKF	977.5317	489.7731	977.5222	977.5222	977.5222
FLDINPYP	993.4365	497.7255	993.4808	993.4808	993.4808
PGRKGIFIN	1000.6045	501.3095	1000.5818	1000.5818	1000.5818
EIQKVYRMQ	1193.6873	597.8509	1193.6227	1193.6227	1193.6227
LTQQIQEKSH	1210.7133	606.3639	1210.6306	1210.6306	1210.6306
DNLKIPVVIIP	1220.6841	611.3493	1220.738	1220.738	1220.738
TIQKVVPIPEV	1222.6869	612.3507	1222.7173	1222.7173	1222.7173
LEPIMLLVRR	1238.7377	620.3761	1238.7533	1238.7533	1238.7533
QEPVIGVP	0	821.432	820.433	820.433	820.433
IVPEVFGN	874.3448	438.1797	874.4437	874.4437	874.4437
HTGQGVVKGK	938.5231	470.2688	938.4934	938.4934	938.4934
KNQPVLGN	955.5491	478.7818	955.5087	955.5087	955.5087
LGQVGAMIAGG	972.5757	487.2951	972.5062	972.5062	972.5062
ENSQATVLVT	1060.6261	531.3203	1060.54	1060.54	1060.54
DIIVPIPVVH	1100.6171	551.3158	1100.6594	1100.6594	1100.6594
GDSSFVIGKGN	1176.6609	589.3377	1176.5775	1176.5775	1176.5775
ASAGQKGILPNTV	1254.7393	628.3769	1254.6932	1254.6932	1254.6932
EIKKPLKDSN	1298.7668	650.3907	1298.7559	1298.7559	1298.7559
TPMQSGAASIGNSLQNIIGGALAGTG/0		843.4124	3369.6582	3369.6582	3369.6582
THASNVLGT	898.5275	450.271	898.4509	898.4509	898.4509
HGNALAHTI	932.5818	467.2982	932.4828	932.4828	932.4828
PVIGVP	0	581.3575	580.3585	580.3585	580.3585
DGATKTTSTAKN	1193.6873	597.8509	1193.5887	1193.5887	1193.5887
FDRAYKANKV	1210.7133	606.3639	1210.6459	1210.6459	1210.6459
DEVYQQVKGR	1220.6857	611.3501	1220.615	1220.615	1220.615
EMQLVTPVKVI	1237.7114	619.863	1237.7104	1237.7104	1237.7104

KSAATSSKSAAVSA	1264.7139	633.3642	1264.6624	1264.6624	1264.6624
TIESIAALV	0	916.557	915.5277	915.5277	915.5277
PDLASFPE	874.3448	438.1797	874.4072	874.4072	874.4072
LTINLGLFA	960.6121	481.3133	960.5644	960.5644	960.5644
KRNGVRIM	972.5757	487.2951	972.5651	972.5651	972.5651
VPLVKKYRV	1100.6171	551.3158	1100.707	1100.707	1100.707
VVKYQDSAGNP	1176.6609	589.3377	1176.5775	1176.5775	1176.5775
ASAGQKGILPNTV	1254.7393	628.3769	1254.6932	1254.6932	1254.6932
AFRKTLLGLGHS	1298.7668	650.3907	1298.7458	1298.7458	1298.7458
YGSVIGNSMSAQRFEPADIRE	0	843.4116	2527.2014	2527.2014	2527.2014
FGRQFGLP	0	921.5119	920.4868	920.4868	920.4868
MTKIPEL	0	944.5886	943.5413	943.5413	943.5413
GHNTISISA	898.5275	450.271	898.4509	898.4509	898.4509
KESIAKKI	915.5543	458.7844	915.5753	915.5753	915.5753
TGAIAAVIAF	932.5818	467.2982	932.5331	932.5331	932.5331
GHNPANQFV	982.5469	492.2807	982.4621	982.4621	982.4621
EDVPVSIKN	999.5731	500.7938	999.5237	999.5237	999.5237
GAIKKMQKN	1016.6005	509.3075	1016.5801	1016.5801	1016.5801
TPKQHKKIKN	1220.6857	611.3501	1220.7354	1220.7354	1220.7354
EDPIQAQPVLP	1237.7114	619.863	1237.619	1237.619	1237.619
KSAATSSKSAAVSA	1264.7139	633.3642	1264.6624	1264.6624	1264.6624
QEPVIGVP	0	821.4354	820.433	820.433	820.433
QGGSLALASKN	1044.6312	523.3229	1044.5564	1044.5564	1044.5564
PVINVTETMPDGKSY	1649.8898	550.9705	1649.7971	1649.7971	1649.7971
GAALQPAPIPK	1190.7003	596.3574	1190.7023	1190.7023	1190.7023
ASAGQKGILPNTV	1254.7393	628.3769	1254.6932	1254.6932	1254.6932
KNQVTIPKTVR	1298.7646	650.3896	1298.7671	1298.7671	1298.7671
NQNAILALLLN	1308.7395	655.377	1308.7765	1308.7765	1308.7765
AIMAVDALKKRGGA	1342.7915	672.403	1342.7755	1342.7755	1342.7755
LPKALSNTFGTDGGVV	1575.8347	788.9246	1575.8145	1575.8145	1575.8145
LIVAQNKN	898.5275	450.271	898.5236	898.5236	898.5236
DIRKDVGN	915.5543	458.7844	915.4774	915.4774	915.4774
QGLAAYTLP	932.5818	467.2982	932.4967	932.4967	932.4967
FLTPQQFC	982.5469	492.2807	982.4583	982.4583	982.4583
GYPPNAILVG	999.5731	500.7938	999.5389	999.5389	999.5389
ELTAQLQKS	1016.6005	509.3075	1016.5502	1016.5502	1016.5502
KPSLADFAMKN	1220.6857	611.3501	1220.6223	1220.6223	1220.6223
LFVMPSGPKPPN	1282.7623	642.3884	1282.6744	1282.6744	1282.6744
GANGAGKSSF	894.4958	448.2552	894.4196	894.4196	894.4196
IPMIVIMI	928.5509	465.2827	928.549	928.549	928.549
GGQDVIVQKRVG	1254.7393	628.3769	1254.7045	1254.7045	1254.7045
YGLSAKSLGQN	1264.7126	633.3636	1264.6775	1264.6775	1264.6775
NAGKITGIIPNGA	1281.7395	641.877	1281.7041	1281.7041	1281.7041
DVLIVRGASQQN	1298.7646	650.3896	1298.6942	1298.6942	1298.6942
IDSKYPFSQPK	1308.7399	655.3772	1308.6714	1308.6714	1308.6714
HGKVASMLKKSAS	1342.7915	672.403	1342.7391	1342.7391	1342.7391
LVNIGEVLIDPQDI	1649.8868	825.9507	1649.924	1649.924	1649.924

GPKNLMPNP	982.5469	492.2807	982.4906	982.4906	982.4906
FLDINPYP	993.4363	497.7254	993.4808	993.4808	993.4808
ELKQIQQI	999.5731	500.7938	999.5601	999.5601	999.5601
GPKFAPVKS	1016.6005	509.3075	1016.5655	1016.5655	1016.5655
ATIIGPLGGLPP	1104.6356	553.3251	1104.6543	1104.6543	1104.6543
TTKGAGSPGILGY	1220.6857	611.3501	1220.6401	1220.6401	1220.6401
DSNLILQIPPPQ	1237.7114	619.863	1237.6554	1237.6554	1237.6554
NIPEAILPEVKP	1319.7349	660.8747	1319.7336	1319.7336	1319.7336
GKPNTLYLNPPP	1325.7683	663.8914	1325.698	1325.698	1325.698
IVEEVIPAVKPD	1420.7844	711.3995	1420.8177	1420.8177	1420.8177
GYRAVHKI	942.5527	472.2836	942.5399	942.5399	942.5399
VNRLTTVTG	959.5787	480.7966	959.54	959.54	959.54
NKKMAVSSL	976.6053	489.3099	976.5375	976.5375	976.5375
NKQVIQKCLR	1254.7393	628.3769	1254.7772	1254.7772	1254.7772
KSAATSSKSAVSA	1264.7126	633.3636	1264.6624	1264.6624	1264.6624
NAGKITGIIPNGA	1281.7395	641.877	1281.7041	1281.7041	1281.7041
ATADPLRVIGSSI	1298.7646	650.3896	1298.7194	1298.7194	1298.7194
RSSSIHTISSLR	1342.7915	672.403	1342.7317	1342.7317	1342.7317
ELVSHPGG	0	795.4183	794.3923	794.3923	794.3923
LMNHDPPIVFALANPV	1649.8868	825.9507	1649.86	1649.86	1649.86
DLQMEDQD	993.4363	497.7254	993.3597	993.3597	993.3597
GPAEDVQRGV	1026.5748	514.2947	1026.5094	1026.5094	1026.5094
LEKMGKVTR	1060.6245	531.3195	1060.6063	1060.6063	1060.6063
LAREVDQFQ	1104.6356	553.3251	1104.5564	1104.5564	1104.5564
LSERLTKNVASS	1303.717	652.8658	1303.7096	1303.7096	1303.7096
DKVIKALAIQP	1308.7399	655.3772	1308.7653	1308.7653	1308.7653
NIPEAILPEVKP	1319.7349	660.8747	1319.7336	1319.7336	1319.7336
IEYFAYRPLR	1326.7932	664.4039	1326.7085	1326.7085	1326.7085
GQNNTLRKVTGT	1386.8167	694.4156	1386.7579	1386.7579	1386.7579
IDQNPILPAVVIL	1420.7844	711.3995	1420.8177	1420.8177	1420.8177
ELPGGLETQ	942.5527	472.2836	942.4658	942.4658	942.4658
HGSALLYSL	959.5787	480.7966	959.5076	959.5076	959.5076
VYAPVQTL	976.6053	489.3099	976.5229	976.5229	976.5229
IDDDVLIGAN	1043.6001	522.8073	1043.5135	1043.5135	1043.5135
VVGKQVLSAAM	1264.7126	633.3636	1264.6849	1264.6849	1264.6849
KRSSLSYKAS	1281.7395	641.877	1281.7153	1281.7153	1281.7153
GVSSIVPLQSQAI	1298.7646	650.3896	1298.7081	1298.7081	1298.7081
EAVARKQKGN	1342.7925	672.4035	1342.7317	1342.7317	1342.7317
ELVSHPGG	0	795.4165	794.3923	794.3923	794.3923
LVNIGEVILDPQDI	1649.8868	825.9507	1649.924	1649.924	1649.924
FLDINPYP	993.4363	497.7254	993.4808	993.4808	993.4808
QQLQKVVT	1026.5748	514.2947	1026.5709	1026.5709	1026.5709
ELKNGAFVIA	1060.6245	531.3195	1060.5917	1060.5917	1060.5917
QTKDRLFNEL	1308.7399	655.3772	1308.6561	1308.6561	1308.6561
GVTGLVLSGAIK	1325.7671	663.8908	1325.8282	1325.8282	1325.8282
QSLLMVDHSPK	1352.764	677.3893	1352.7123	1352.7123	1352.7123
ELQGADALVITAGI	1369.7915	685.903	1369.7452	1369.7452	1369.7452

TDSLVERKKRR	1386.8167	694.4156	1386.8055	1386.8055	1386.8055
IDQNPILPAVVIL	1420.7844	711.3995	1420.8177	1420.8177	1420.8177
LVNIGEVILIDPQDI	1649.8868	825.9507	1649.924	1649.924	1649.924
ELVFIFPI	976.6053	489.3099	976.5634	976.5634	976.5634
FITGTFIVF	1043.6001	522.8073	1043.5692	1043.5692	1043.5692
GIYMSIGLPLSD	1264.7126	633.3636	1264.6373	1264.6373	1264.6373
RSSFYVIGAGPL	1281.7395	641.877	1281.6718	1281.6718	1281.6718
VGSIGHDLGKAFV	1298.7646	650.3896	1298.6982	1298.6982	1298.6982
LSLTLENEIRR	1342.7925	672.4035	1342.7568	1342.7568	1342.7568
IVNTNENPQDGF	1362.6569	682.3357	1362.6052	1362.6052	1362.6052
IVLISGIVVYVMER	1589.8633	795.9389	1589.9215	1589.9215	1589.9215
PVVVILMIPVMAFGT	1617.8978	809.9562	1617.8875	1617.8875	1617.8875
LAVIDIIGGNTGLPNAL	1649.8868	825.9507	1649.9352	1649.9352	1649.9352
FLDINPYP	993.4363	497.7254	993.4808	993.4808	993.4808
PPNKFRRLL	1026.5748	514.2947	1026.6086	1026.6086	1026.6086
SSKGAQIEKN	1060.6245	531.3195	1060.5513	1060.5513	1060.5513
PIIMIPVIPQ	1162.6635	582.339	1162.6783	1162.6783	1162.6783
GPKKLDQHHHL	1308.7399	655.3772	1308.7051	1308.7051	1308.7051
AGKGGGLAVGIQNNQ	1325.7671	663.8908	1325.7052	1325.7052	1325.7052
GANSGAGLSLIYAPG	1347.7462	674.8804	1347.667	1347.667	1347.667
AATKSGHLEQLKA	1352.764	677.3893	1352.7412	1352.7412	1352.7412
VVKKSQHIHSPQ	1386.8167	694.4156	1386.7732	1386.7732	1386.7732
DMIARVATAKSIR	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.8027	1430.8027	1430.8027
LDAPPLTNF	986.5804	494.2975	986.5073	986.5073	986.5073
HKSATYAIGG	1003.6078	502.8112	1003.5087	1003.5087	1003.5087
LPSVPIAMP	1020.6311	511.3228	1020.5678	1020.5678	1020.5678
IIDLQAGQFT	1104.6505	553.3325	1104.5815	1104.5815	1104.5815
EATLPQSNLVL	1298.7646	650.3896	1298.6718	1298.6718	1298.6718
ATGNALVIPMLIM	1342.7925	672.4035	1342.7352	1342.7352	1342.7352
GVTITANSASLIPQ	1370.8195	686.417	1370.7406	1370.7406	1370.7406
IQKGDRLPPTQK	1396.7897	699.4021	1396.7675	1396.7675	1396.7675
DLPVPAGVLFPHRGQ	1617.8978	809.9562	1617.8627	1617.8627	1617.8627
ELNIKLLDTHN	1308.7411	437.2543	1308.7037	1308.7037	1308.7037
KENEKYFN	1070.5999	536.3072	1070.5033	1070.5033	1070.5033
GGSVIMSVNAGP	1087.6265	544.8205	1087.5332	1087.5332	1087.5332
EDYVTAKGALNK	1308.7399	655.3772	1308.6561	1308.6561	1308.6561
PGRPRLFQVEQ	1325.7671	663.8908	1325.7205	1325.7205	1325.7205
ATNTAKTALATANT	1347.7462	674.8804	1347.6995	1347.6995	1347.6995
IDPQRDGLGNIR	1352.7659	677.3902	1352.7161	1352.7161	1352.7161
SDAIRKQLGLEAS	1386.8173	694.4159	1386.7467	1386.7467	1386.7467
PLRPEGVPQGLHN	1413.8207	707.9176	1413.7365	1413.7365	1413.7365
MLIAIVLASGLIM	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.8241	1430.8241	1430.8241
LDAPPLTNF	986.5804	494.2975	986.5073	986.5073	986.5073
IEWSVGRGTG	1003.6078	502.8112	1003.5087	1003.5087	1003.5087
PALVLLQPGN	1020.6311	511.3228	1020.5968	1020.5968	1020.5968
TAASKKTIQAS	1104.6505	553.3325	1104.6139	1104.6139	1104.6139
DNLKIPVVIIP	1236.7039	619.3592	1236.7329	1236.7329	1236.7329

DTLVNAQVKVTR	1342.7925	672.4035	1342.7568	1342.7568	1342.7568
AQKNALLQKSLR	1369.7915	685.903	1369.8042	1369.8042	1369.8042
NKQASAPKNPKTN	1396.7897	699.4021	1396.7423	1396.7423	1396.7423
FIVVVPIVMTLIQF	1617.8978	809.9562	1617.9568	1617.9568	1617.9568
PNGRWSGEQIDDYN	1649.5948	825.8047	1649.707	1649.707	1649.707
EVFSQKKAQARL	1403.8536	468.9585	1403.7885	1403.7885	1403.7885
QVRQGKPGVC	1070.5999	536.3072	1070.5656	1070.5656	1070.5656
ATGGQKQVEAV	1087.6265	544.8205	1087.5509	1087.5509	1087.5509
VVKLSKSHQR	1308.7399	655.3772	1308.799	1308.799	1308.799
LERRQAISQPGA	1325.7671	663.8908	1325.7052	1325.7052	1325.7052
GVSMVFNKSKTR	1352.7659	677.3902	1352.7235	1352.7235	1352.7235
MNKKRVAGAALASA	1386.8173	694.4159	1386.7766	1386.7766	1386.7766
DKSKEKILDNIK	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.7981	1430.7981	1430.7981
GAGGAGKAIIAALDYG	1474.869	738.4418	1474.778	1474.778	1474.778
ATANFIVNALPLTP	1440.8218	481.2812	1440.7976	1440.7976	1440.7976
TPKALYTDI	1020.6311	511.3228	1020.5491	1020.5491	1020.5491
SRVARVEAAF	1104.6505	553.3325	1104.604	1104.604	1104.604
GYPTGQKRLNLP	1342.7925	672.4035	1342.7357	1342.7357	1342.7357
KKNKKLQQQID	1369.7915	685.903	1369.8042	1369.8042	1369.8042
IDAPLGSNHLLLN	1391.7731	696.8938	1391.7408	1391.7408	1391.7408
ATEPAIPYALAAPL	1396.7897	699.4021	1396.7603	1396.7603	1396.7603
LEELKAKTKDQI	1414.8429	708.4287	1414.8031	1414.8031	1414.8031
AADLGEVDNTPDSEAF	1649.5948	825.8047	1649.7057	1649.7057	1649.7057
DKKDLPPYP	974.4433	488.2289	974.5073	974.5073	974.5073
FHKHEIVR	1064.6566	533.3356	1064.5879	1064.5879	1064.5879
NKFNSIVRSSSN	1352.7659	677.3902	1352.6685	1352.6685	1352.6685
ELKKAGQLGTVDE	1386.8173	694.4159	1386.7355	1386.7355	1386.7355
DDVLAVLILSLMI	1413.8203	707.9174	1413.8153	1413.8153	1413.8153
KNQKKQLRYLP	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.8358	1430.8358	1430.8358
GPGDVNFVYDELI	1436.6881	719.3513	1436.6824	1436.6824	1436.6824
ELKTAIQKLTMSPI	1474.869	738.4418	1474.8065	1474.8065	1474.8065
LPVPAGVLFPHRGQ	1502.8984	752.4565	1502.8358	1502.8358	1502.8358
ILSLNMVGAN	1030.6036	516.3091	1030.5481	1030.5481	1030.5481
AATFLAEPQN	1060.6259	531.3202	1060.5189	1060.5189	1060.5189
TTTALVVAAGVPVT	1369.7915	685.903	1369.7817	1369.7817	1369.7817
ENLPDKLIPQLI	1391.7731	696.8938	1391.8024	1391.8024	1391.8024
IQKGDRLPPTQK	1396.7893	699.4019	1396.7675	1396.7675	1396.7675
LDLHKDVSTVLSLSD	1440.8154	721.415	1440.746	1440.746	1440.746
ALVKVVKEMSSII	1458.8702	730.4424	1458.848	1458.848	1458.848
TPIKTSLTAQANLP	1470.8317	736.4231	1470.793	1470.793	1470.793
VPGDPDGWPTPEWTP	1649.5948	825.8047	1649.7362	1649.7362	1649.7362
DQDGRMIFVVPR	1447.8708	483.6309	1447.7242	1447.7242	1447.7242
ELKQLDAGVKYASA	1491.9022	498.308	1491.7933	1491.7933	1491.7933
MAVLFQRGK	1064.6566	533.3356	1064.5801	1064.5801	1064.5801
YGKNKKLVTV	1148.6793	575.3469	1148.6918	1148.6918	1148.6918
NAIRQIVVKRR	1352.7659	677.3902	1352.8364	1352.8364	1352.8364
PALVLLQPGNGPIV	1386.8173	694.4159	1386.8235	1386.8235	1386.8235

AGGLDLKSITVVQN	1413.8203	707.9174	1413.7827	1413.7827	1413.7827
TDNKTIKAKRGS	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.8206	1430.8206	1430.8206
QKCISYRTRKPL	1474.869	738.4418	1474.8079	1474.8079	1474.8079
DTNQVVVNIN	1114.6259	558.3202	1114.5619	1114.5619	1114.5619
ERAAALMQKN	1131.6533	566.8339	1131.5707	1131.5707	1131.5707
QAGEVVTVKGPKGT	1369.7915	685.903	1369.7565	1369.7565	1369.7565
DKMKKDGFTTVK	1396.7893	699.4019	1396.7384	1396.7384	1396.7384
ATIGGMSTGMVGIKN	1435.795	718.9048	1435.7163	1435.7163	1435.7163
NPTPKTVDSLMLK	1458.8702	730.4424	1458.7753	1458.7753	1458.7753
KSATSRGAGVSLGII	1518.8923	760.4534	1518.8188	1518.8188	1518.8188
QSEAPTDTYEGGRSAV	1649.5948	825.8047	1649.7169	1649.7169	1649.7169
ITGVKTFEELPTN	1447.8708	483.6309	1447.7559	1447.7559	1447.7559
DLASARRRLRGTN	1484.8452	495.9557	1484.8284	1484.8284	1484.8284
PNLKQNPAAL	1064.6566	533.3356	1064.5979	1064.5979	1064.5979
PLLAWITDF	1074.6257	538.3201	1074.575	1074.575	1074.575
KRATTKNIAF	1148.6793	575.3469	1148.6666	1148.6666	1148.6666
VSALLGITEPALFG	1386.8173	694.4159	1386.7759	1386.7759	1386.7759
AALDTALKKIEKN	1413.8203	707.9174	1413.8191	1413.8191	1413.8191
HIVLAGHSQGGVVAS	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.7631	1430.7631	1430.7631
KDIVAPVGKLGEDT	1440.8143	721.4144	1440.7823	1440.7823	1440.7823
TQTTSKIVLAGLEN	1474.869	738.4418	1474.7878	1474.7878	1474.7878
ARTRTPNGIEIQN	1484.8452	495.9557	1484.7695	1484.7695	1484.7695
EIKQIGQNCFR	1491.8969	498.3062	1491.7616	1491.7616	1491.7616
IIEALLAHKPVVGTDVAGIQ	2043.1224	682.0481	2043.1729	2043.1729	2043.1729
QKSAKRAVAVALR	1396.7893	699.4019	1396.8627	1396.8627	1396.8627
YNAKAIVNGDSIAT	1435.795	718.9048	1435.7307	1435.7307	1435.7307
IEKATKLSEQALK	1457.8445	729.9295	1457.8453	1457.8453	1457.8453
QTPLEFRQLNTR	1501.8708	751.9427	1501.8002	1501.8002	1501.8002
GTVIHNIELKPGKGG	1518.8923	760.4534	1518.8518	1518.8518	1518.8518
DQLYAATKGPKEK	1447.8708	483.6309	1447.7671	1447.7671	1447.7671
LIRGIEPYAG	1087.5826	544.7986	1087.6025	1087.6025	1087.6025
DKVNKKATKAPGSA	1413.8203	707.9174	1413.7939	1413.7939	1413.7939
TKGKHHLNGKQAL	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.8107	1430.8107	1430.8107
DLFSKQKSRGFE	1440.8143	721.4144	1440.7361	1440.7361	1440.7361
GPKAGNPKRINKVP	1474.869	738.4418	1474.8733	1474.8733	1474.8733
ASAYKVGADLQKLEA	1562.9205	782.4675	1562.8304	1562.8304	1562.8304
AGNKRRTRSITPE	1484.8452	495.9557	1484.8171	1484.8171	1484.8171
ATVMIFLTILSGAR	1491.8969	498.3062	1491.8483	1491.8483	1491.8483
GSVSKYKGPKESNR	1535.9257	512.9825	1535.8057	1535.8057	1535.8057
DKTIPKPLVV	1108.6826	555.3486	1108.6855	1108.6855	1108.6855
LMGLTFIVNYIN	1396.7893	699.4019	1396.7424	1396.7424	1396.7424
ARVLPDLASFPE	1444.6588	723.3367	1444.7198	1444.7198	1444.7198
KTGKTALAIIDTILN	1457.8445	729.9295	1457.8453	1457.8453	1457.8453
TPKDVVLRVYRAS	1502.8983	752.4564	1502.8569	1502.8569	1502.8569
VFEGQNLVEKSLR	1518.8923	760.4534	1518.8042	1518.8042	1518.8042
TPKQVARSRSLTG	1528.87	510.6306	1528.8685	1528.8685	1528.8685
GVQSRQGSRSHAVLV	1579.9473	527.6564	1579.8542	1579.8542	1579.8542

GAQGATRVSTTG	1104.6503	553.3324	1104.5524	1104.5524	1104.5524
PLMALPIEVPN	1192.7004	597.3575	1192.6526	1192.6526	1192.6526
LVNQLPWSYALK	1430.8433	716.4289	1430.7922	1430.7922	1430.7922
TYVNDKVYGKRV	1440.8143	721.4144	1440.7725	1440.7725	1440.7725
AKSKKQTINKMQA	1474.869	738.4418	1474.829	1474.829	1474.829
SNFKSLSKSLKKN	1479.821	740.9178	1479.8409	1479.8409	1479.8409
NKKSIIKTSNEVT	1562.9193	782.4669	1562.8628	1562.8628	1562.8628
VYAASKSIEALQGR	1491.8969	498.3062	1491.8046	1491.8046	1491.8046
GPQLMKAVFAERSI	1545.8954	516.3057	1545.8337	1545.8337	1545.8337
TKTQEVVKED	1175.6763	588.8454	1175.6034	1175.6034	1175.6034
IGNGTDVAIDSADV	1444.6588	723.3367	1444.7046	1444.7046	1444.7046
DILLAESGLKMIR	1457.8445	729.9295	1457.8276	1457.8276	1457.8276
HGASSAKFKAGLKLA	1484.843	743.4288	1484.8463	1484.8463	1484.8463
ELTAQGKKMANTVL	1502.8983	752.4564	1502.8126	1502.8126	1502.8126
QLSGKFQDIKREA	1518.8947	760.4546	1518.8154	1518.8154	1518.8154
KLAKGPKFAPVKS	1440.816	481.2793	1440.8817	1440.8817	1440.8817
KSDESLQVIARR	1528.87	510.6306	1528.8685	1528.8685	1528.8685
ARQIVVKELKPV	1535.9221	512.9813	1535.9512	1535.9512	1535.9512
EDTIKTPHSVIGGN	1579.9473	527.6564	1579.8206	1579.8206	1579.8206
TPWAVQAIPP	1192.7004	597.3575	1192.624	1192.624	1192.624
ISDVLKGTDKSIAQ	1474.869	738.4418	1474.7878	1474.7878	1474.7878
AIDKAMIKLDGTPN	1501.8685	751.9415	1501.781	1501.781	1501.781
ELVLIGIRVGSHDR	1562.9193	782.4669	1562.8893	1562.8893	1562.8893
RVKVGKATDIIHAA	1606.9459	804.4802	1606.9155	1606.9155	1606.9155
GSALIGNMIGIGLIMS	1545.8954	516.3057	1545.8259	1545.8259	1545.8259
SLFRNRMIANRVP	1572.8979	525.3066	1572.8671	1572.8671	1572.8671
GIILEPLAEGFAGR	1457.8445	729.9295	1457.7878	1457.7878	1457.7878
GYTGKHSQQRVP	1484.843	743.4288	1484.7848	1484.7848	1484.7848
GTVIHNIELKPGKGG	1518.8947	760.4546	1518.8518	1518.8518	1518.8518
VTVISAGLQSFQMS	1523.8475	762.931	1523.7654	1523.7654	1523.7654
SSKSGSLGTIVVLKD	1546.9244	774.4695	1546.8567	1546.8567	1546.8567
AFRQVSGQLLYT	1528.87	510.6306	1528.8038	1528.8038	1528.8038
AATSKTAVKKTITTK	1535.9221	512.9813	1535.8883	1535.8883	1535.8883
PGKIKTFSQMFALL	1579.948	527.6566	1579.8796	1579.8796	1579.8796
DAQARLARVAPGKGTN	1623.9739	542.3319	1623.8805	1623.8805	1623.8805
DPIKHIDGAASGVVP	1474.869	738.4418	1474.778	1474.778	1474.778
AASGLTIREKTGTPT	1501.8685	751.9415	1501.8101	1501.8101	1501.8101
AAKALDLGYHWRE	1528.8667	765.4406	1528.7787	1528.7787	1528.7787
ALDKAIQYMAKRR	1562.9205	782.4675	1562.8715	1562.8715	1562.8715
DAGQSLLPKDSKIH	1606.9459	804.4802	1606.8679	1606.8679	1606.8679
HGASSAKFKAGLKLA	1484.8435	495.9551	1484.8463	1484.8463	1484.8463
GKTVVKSGQPNKNG	1540.8795	514.6338	1540.8685	1540.8685	1540.8685
LNSRWIFLGKPNQ	1572.8979	525.3066	1572.8413	1572.8413	1572.8413
IEIGRTHVQAN	1236.7261	619.3703	1236.6575	1236.6575	1236.6575
RAVLPTVQPVVQQLKEPA	2085.1343	696.052	2085.231	2085.231	2085.231
QLAKASQIFASNKN	1518.8947	760.4546	1518.8154	1518.8154	1518.8154
KGGLAVGIQNNQLVN	1523.8475	762.931	1523.842	1523.842	1523.842

ISGVGETKGNFVKN	1545.8906	773.9526	1545.8151	1545.8151	1545.8151
VVNKYHKDLKAS	1528.8694	510.6304	1528.8726	1528.8726	1528.8726
GPKVKKKKKVLGV	1535.9221	512.9813	1536.0603	1536.0603	1536.0603
DLNHSGTKVIGVVGAN	1579.948	527.6566	1579.8318	1579.8318	1579.8318
HTQISGPKALVQGRV	1589.9214	530.9811	1589.9001	1589.9001	1589.9001
DQLRRLSPLTLLSL	1623.9739	542.3319	1623.9672	1623.9672	1623.9672
IDEQPAVIRRIEEKYL	1971.0931	658.0383	1971.079	1971.079	1971.079
IVAMLFALALGAIIV	1501.8685	751.9415	1501.8942	1501.8942	1501.8942
GYKKREKMRPDR	1562.9205	782.4675	1562.8463	1562.8463	1562.8463
GPQNPVAYHIVGDKI	1606.9459	804.4802	1606.8468	1606.8468	1606.8468
ELSLSMNTGTDGDPVP	1631.5883	816.8014	1631.7349	1631.7349	1631.7349
GVVAGVTLNKSQAQN	1484.8435	495.9551	1484.8311	1484.8311	1484.8311
DNPLTQGGKFLQAL	1572.8979	525.3066	1572.8148	1572.8148	1572.8148
LFNFRKHGIDEKN	1616.9198	539.9805	1616.8423	1616.8423	1616.8423
IPVNALKAIVFAGNKL	1668.0022	557.008	1667.9974	1667.9974	1667.9974
RAVLPTVQPVVQQLLEPA	2085.1343	696.052	2085.231	2085.231	2085.231
GVPQSLITESVYAR	1518.8947	760.4546	1518.8042	1518.8042	1518.8042
QKVPSPTLVHHRGV	1545.8906	773.9526	1545.8992	1545.8992	1545.8992
KAQAETIIAQLPHT	1590.9482	796.4814	1590.8729	1590.8729	1590.8729
EILPIKGQRANLVAE	1650.9713	826.4929	1650.9304	1650.9304	1650.9304
PGKNQPHVSVGVVNV	1545.8959	516.3059	1545.8263	1545.8263	1545.8263
EIAGRQKRRKLLL	1579.948	527.6566	1579.9999	1579.9999	1579.9999
HGKKLAEMADRRVN	1623.9735	542.3318	1623.8628	1623.8628	1623.8628
AYAGTRIPTLDEVVQLLI	1971.0931	658.0383	1971.1041	1971.1041	1971.1041
LDNWTDLDIHN	1354.6293	678.3219	1354.6154	1354.6154	1354.6154
EIQGLEQGATLSQGV	1528.8667	765.4406	1528.7733	1528.7733	1528.7733
VVKKWDLSKVVSF	1562.9205	782.4675	1562.9185	1562.9185	1562.9185
VYRALRYKLPQAN	1590.9482	796.4814	1590.8994	1590.8994	1590.8994
SIMCRVKEGGSLKTV	1606.9447	804.4796	1606.8535	1606.8535	1606.8535
TQTELSERIGKRR	1572.8962	525.306	1572.8696	1572.8696	1572.8696
FIGHNQMPLDIQTA	1584.8995	529.3071	1584.7606	1584.7606	1584.7606
EIKRKKSESISSP	1616.9198	539.9805	1616.9098	1616.9098	1616.9098
INRAGLIHGADFEKK	1668.0022	557.008	1667.9108	1667.9108	1667.9108
VGCLIQGMNLNVVQPLPLPF	2085.1343	696.052	2085.1003	2085.1003	2085.1003
GISPVRPQPQKVVGG	1518.8947	760.4546	1518.8518	1518.8518	1518.8518
LEKKQVVKSGAVFN	1545.8906	773.9526	1545.8878	1545.8878	1545.8878
TLEEYGPKGLLAFM	1567.8746	784.9446	1567.7957	1567.7957	1567.7957
QLADLPAGAQQVAKGTP	1650.9713	826.4929	1650.894	1650.894	1650.894
EKLLDEDAIKNQN	1528.8694	510.6304	1528.7733	1528.7733	1528.7733
FKVFTAKGAKVKTR	1579.948	527.6566	1579.9562	1579.9562	1579.9562
ARKVVISVPTTVLQN	1623.9735	542.3318	1623.9672	1623.9672	1623.9672
GIGIIAQLAKY	1258.7133	630.3639	1258.7649	1258.7649	1258.7649
QVELLQKYLQQLIIN	1971.0931	658.0383	1971.1405	1971.1405	1971.1405
NPQVQAYADKYG	1354.6293	678.3219	1354.6041	1354.6041	1354.6041
IKAQPPGKKLQRLS	1562.9205	782.4675	1562.962	1562.962	1562.962
QVAKGNEPLTKVVKN	1606.9447	804.4796	1606.9043	1606.9043	1606.9043
GYKPGKDVAIAVDVAA	1572.8962	525.306	1572.8512	1572.8512	1572.8512

DIIVKIHQGQKSPQ	1589.9214	530.9811	1589.8889	1589.8889	1589.8889
FAKKRNPDTGKLEN	1616.9198	539.9805	1616.8634	1616.8634	1616.8634
TTIVHFPSLAVELKN	1668.0022	557.008	1667.9247	1667.9247	1667.9247
IEKIQEIQKNAREN	1712.0256	571.6825	1711.9218	1711.9218	1711.9218
QMVPDLKVKVAFDKEPIL	2085.1343	696.052	2085.1543	2085.1543	2085.1543
FMPLFLLIPIMIST	1634.972	818.4933	1634.918	1634.918	1634.918
GPKQPTAVKRLGKGQS	1650.9713	826.4929	1650.9529	1650.9529	1650.9529
KGTANYRGSTLKVTSL	1694.9945	848.5045	1694.9315	1694.9315	1694.9315
QVAKGNEPLTKVVKN	1623.9735	542.3318	1623.9308	1623.9308	1623.9308
ELQDQNLTYPPRR	1628.925	543.9823	1628.827	1628.827	1628.827
VGSKIASVLANTDTVDA	1660.9457	554.6558	1660.8519	1660.8519	1660.8519
EIERNPSLISKRSQN	1752.0256	585.0158	1751.9279	1751.9279	1751.9279
EKPLGLKAGFGKR	1562.9205	782.4675	1562.8933	1562.8933	1562.8933
SRSQTAATRSSKTAR	1606.9447	804.4796	1606.85	1606.85	1606.85
NLPAQQAGSSIMPGKI	1611.8978	806.9562	1611.8291	1611.8291	1611.8291
KNVYNVTVSVLRGKAS	1634.972	818.4933	1634.9104	1634.9104	1634.9104
HAEISPTLNLTERTESAFPVEW	2510.3579	837.7932	2510.2805	2510.2805	2510.2805
FIEI	520.3	261.1573	520.2897	520.2897	520.2897
AFRKAVAVAKRNDGA	1572.8962	525.306	1572.8849	1572.8849	1572.8849
LPPAINPMLP	1061.5667	531.7906	1061.5944	1061.5944	1061.5944
FDQLNTEILLQKR	1616.9198	539.9805	1616.8885	1616.8885	1616.8885
SQVAADIVQQIRLIN	1667.9989	557.0069	1667.9207	1667.9207	1667.9207
RATELGAIKKRNELN	1712.0256	571.6825	1711.9694	1711.9694	1711.9694
MLVGAAVAVNLSEANGKI	1756.0496	586.3571	1755.9553	1755.9553	1755.9553
AGLIAGRRGGESNGYI	1589.9222	795.9684	1589.8274	1589.8274	1589.8274
GSVFGPQPATLLPIR	1650.9713	826.4929	1650.9457	1650.9457	1650.9457
IHWGPRTIDLILF	1694.9945	848.5045	1694.9144	1694.9144	1694.9144
PGKQDDAVAVLALKEA	1623.9735	542.3318	1623.8832	1623.8832	1623.8832
NQCLVKVNPAGADITY	1633.9465	545.6561	1633.8134	1633.8134	1633.8134
AKSKAQANQVMKMOV	1660.9457	554.6558	1660.8752	1660.8752	1660.8752
LEHGRYDKNWNKN	1672.9515	558.6578	1672.807	1672.807	1672.807
ELGYQVKSVKTKEV	1606.9447	804.4796	1606.8931	1606.8931	1606.8931
FPGIPVGFIPVPIVLQNMGIFLAA	2510.3579	837.7932	2510.4011	2510.4011	2510.4011
NKVLNIFQNGLPPII	1678.9973	840.5059	1678.9771	1678.9771	1678.9771
LMPDPRPIHPAIGQVV	1739.0197	870.5171	1738.9552	1738.9552	1738.9552
AFKRHATSKITSRA	1572.8962	525.306	1572.8849	1572.8849	1572.8849
EQFMTPPVN	1061.5667	531.7906	1061.4852	1061.4852	1061.4852
THSPTSVVVLQIDPD	1606.9491	536.657	1606.8202	1606.8202	1606.8202
YTELEIQGKNAQHS	1616.9198	539.9805	1616.7794	1616.7794	1616.7794
AGRTRWQGKRPTVR	1667.9989	557.0069	1667.9445	1667.9445	1667.9445
LEAQKDSLSETFSKP	1704.9706	569.3308	1704.8934	1704.8934	1704.8934
TILSVGVQPNVLAENA	1712.0251	571.6823	1711.8992	1711.8992	1711.8992
SKGPVINELAKRHHGGG	1756.0496	586.3571	1755.9492	1755.9492	1755.9492
SIINWLPQKLKRR	1650.9713	826.4929	1651.0046	1651.0046	1651.0046
GPGSTLLVVGPKGTIRGV	1694.9977	848.5061	1694.9679	1694.9679	1694.9679
NDGPNPVSPASVIKSH	1633.9465	545.6561	1633.806	1633.806	1633.806
AYNQANSSLQVKQPN	1660.9457	554.6558	1660.8169	1660.8169	1660.8169

FIPAIAGLDFSPIIAL	1672.9515	558.6578	1672.944	1672.944	1672.944
GPQNPVAYHIVGDKI	1606.9447	804.4796	1606.8468	1606.8468	1606.8468
LIPLSIVAFSANGLVSVVEVLALVA	2510.3579	837.7932	2510.4612	2510.4612	2510.4612
ELSQHRQLIFVPGR	1678.9973	840.5059	1678.9268	1678.9268	1678.9268
GPKQNIIDDALATAIAK	1739.0197	870.5171	1738.9465	1738.9465	1738.9465
EMIE	520.2999	261.1572	520.2203	520.2203	520.2203
ITMDNPMLK	1061.5667	531.7906	1061.5249	1061.5249	1061.5249
DPLRYLQSPSFGVK	1605.9204	536.3141	1605.8514	1605.8514	1605.8514
LTVSKVVYHQNATSA	1616.9198	539.9805	1616.8522	1616.8522	1616.8522
RSAIDVGRDVGLVALQ	1667.9989	557.0069	1667.9319	1667.9319	1667.9319
AKVKQLLTAACKAKTN	1712.0251	571.6823	1712.0673	1712.0673	1712.0673
AGEIGFAQGVQRKVLAL	1756.0496	586.3571	1755.9995	1755.9995	1755.9995
LDNNRDLIEKNSSKNE	1888.1287	630.3835	1887.9286	1887.9286	1887.9286
AGRGIGAVNSVPTGIVLA	1650.9713	826.4929	1650.9417	1650.9417	1650.9417
GASRALQGGKGPCKLEIN	1694.9977	848.5061	1694.9427	1694.9427	1694.9427
DKSLETPTAIKKAFL	1660.9457	554.6558	1660.9399	1660.9399	1660.9399
KAMEKTDLKKMLSR	1677.9706	560.3308	1677.927	1677.927	1677.927
EFVQLKKHADHLPR	1716.9768	573.3329	1716.9424	1716.9424	1716.9424
TELHHVGAKEVPKAPGM	1800.0765	601.0328	1799.9352	1799.9352	1799.9352
PIMIVIMPISWLWNLIL	2184.2019	729.0746	2184.209	2184.209	2184.209
HRHAAQVGCLIQGMLNVVQPLPL	2510.3579	837.7932	2510.325	2510.325	2510.325
LIVPQKLGYPITSVV	1739.0197	870.5171	1739.0597	1739.0597	1739.0597
GPKNVQRGRAIAMDR	1667.9989	557.0069	1667.9001	1667.9001	1667.9001
GGTAGSSKVFGRLEFSKGG	1712.0251	571.6823	1711.9005	1711.9005	1711.9005
AVNVIDAAEGVHDVMLP	1748.9998	584.0072	1748.8767	1748.8767	1748.8767
AEELEPLIYVRSKP	1756.0497	586.3572	1755.9771	1755.9771	1755.9771
PDLNECEAAVTAA	1302.4868	652.2507	1302.5762	1302.5762	1302.5762
TQPQKIEVNLAPGKQ	1650.9713	826.4929	1650.894	1650.894	1650.894
PGQRIQVRIGNEITN	1694.9977	848.5061	1694.9064	1694.9064	1694.9064
QNVVKNPNAQGKTQKMI	1783.0453	892.5299	1782.9774	1782.9774	1782.9774
LTVGVVVLGYEKAATL	1660.9457	554.6558	1660.9763	1660.9763	1660.9763
ARFKGSWTVPKETR	1677.9706	560.3308	1677.8951	1677.8951	1677.8951
PVGWKFSTRVALDE	1704.9701	569.3306	1704.8835	1704.8835	1704.8835
FARLGTAGGIVMLVALI	1800.0765	601.0328	1800.0696	1800.0696	1800.0696
GYGLTESYKKN	1258.7197	630.3671	1258.6194	1258.6194	1258.6194
DLLDQPIEDLLATAVKFAV	2070.157	691.0596	2070.1248	2070.1248	2070.1248
IDQDEIREKVNEILDKNN	2184.2019	729.0746	2184.1023	2184.1023	2184.1023
MLILGIPPLALTGAVFGG	1739.0206	870.5176	1739.0055	1739.0055	1739.0055
FAGHRGGVVGAIATMGVI	1712.0251	571.6823	1711.9192	1711.9192	1711.9192
AHEARVALIPGSSFGPGG	1721.9971	575.0063	1721.8849	1721.8849	1721.8849
YVLAVEFTDKATKGKS	1756.0497	586.3572	1755.9407	1755.9407	1755.9407
AVPVNSAKSLKYLVSPPR	1844.0995	615.7071	1844.052	1844.052	1844.052
HTSYVSNQPLGT	1302.4833	652.2489	1302.6205	1302.6205	1302.6205
IIGTIALVPQNIITMV	1694.9977	848.5061	1695.0005	1695.0005	1695.0005
LISVPKGNLVAASNRS	1783.0459	892.5302	1783.0316	1783.0316	1783.0316
YGQRLNIDFHSSLR	1704.9701	569.3306	1704.8696	1704.8696	1704.8696
GGQQQRVGIARALMQH	1748.9961	584.006	1748.9216	1748.9216	1748.9216

AVLNELETPKHHQER	1800.0765	601.0328	1799.9279	1799.9279	1799.9279
SAAAAGLPILLAYPGMLAH	1836.0798	613.0339	1835.9968	1835.9968	1835.9968
DLGADKTKPIVDMILDRGN	2070.157	691.0596	2070.0779	2070.0779	2070.0779
ADHRIVELLVPVPEDPKQN	2184.2019	729.0746	2184.1538	2184.1538	2184.1538
IIANIINIPVAIIYQ	1739.0206	870.5176	1739.0233	1739.0233	1739.0233
KNSAGIISPWLSKRR	1712.0251	571.6823	1711.9846	1711.9846	1711.9846
TLEDDTLARYNGALLG	1721.9971	575.0063	1721.8472	1721.8472	1721.8472
IQKPLKTGNVLETLAM	1756.0497	586.3572	1755.9805	1755.9805	1755.9805
AVRQGILIGHNIEKPTV	1844.0995	615.7071	1844.0632	1844.0632	1844.0632
IPLSIVAFSANGLVSVVEVLALVAVI	2609.4268	870.8162	2609.5295	2609.5295	2609.5295
GGDVTGSGGLGLIIQRAGR	1783.0459	892.5302	1782.9701	1782.9701	1782.9701
ILLQPDGLLAIALSLR	1704.9701	569.3306	1705.0502	1705.0502	1705.0502
DGGRGGDVILKVDPLR	1739.0253	580.6824	1738.9326	1738.9326	1738.9326
PTQKERFYPFVAGIP	1748.9961	584.006	1748.925	1748.925	1748.925
TPRLVVVSPKTTISVAV	1766.02	589.6806	1766.0665	1766.0665	1766.0665
LFLSLYIVGLIVVVPVG	1800.0765	601.0328	1800.1165	1800.1165	1800.1165
LSQKLSLKSFMNNLASG	1837.0471	613.3563	1836.9768	1836.9768	1836.9768
VQNLLNNTVQHVDNGKLFM	2184.2019	729.0746	2184.0999	2184.0999	2184.0999
LGMHKAYARIPKNQN	1756.0497	586.3572	1755.9203	1755.9203	1755.9203
GNKRVVIIGGGYVGTLE	1828.0984	610.3734	1828.0206	1828.0206	1828.0206
EVKYNVRPNKKFVLE	1844.0995	615.7071	1844.0309	1844.0309	1844.0309
NLILAVGVGLVKTTPDISGSGIPQI	2609.4268	870.8162	2609.468	2609.468	2609.468
EPVANSQSIELIARNYPKQDLPK	2609.4268	870.8162	2609.3813	2609.3813	2609.3813
KNRDVIGTFKLNAPPN	1783.0459	892.5302	1782.9741	1782.9741	1782.9741
ADAPVEFDALDFRQR	1748.9961	584.006	1748.8481	1748.8481	1748.8481
LVSALVIALVVIIFAIL	1766.02	589.6806	1766.1685	1766.1685	1766.1685
ARGWLIFIVPKERES	1800.0765	601.0328	1800.0046	1800.0046	1800.0046
AVKKSVKLKAKQPQPAT	1837.0471	613.3563	1837.1149	1837.1149	1837.1149
QTGEGLNDMWRNILLE	1888.129	630.3836	1887.9149	1887.9149	1887.9149
MITPLILNKSETLLFATVNGAP	2342.3662	781.796	2342.292	2342.292	2342.292
DPTPVSTVSTP	1115.4851	558.7498	1115.5347	1115.5347	1115.5347
QRVAIARALAGDPDVII	1793.0233	598.6817	1793.016	1793.016	1793.016
KNVQLKDGVIYILNVNK	1844.0995	615.7071	1844.052	1844.052	1844.052
LPLEQQSIIISLLVILGEAFSTPLL	2609.4268	870.8162	2609.4932	2609.4932	2609.4932
KNRDVIGTFKLNAPPN	1783.0459	892.5302	1782.9741	1782.9741	1782.9741
FILGIVLASTMLILIPN	1827.0731	914.5438	1827.0944	1827.0944	1827.0944
LDPATLAIADLQLADLP	1748.9961	584.006	1748.9561	1748.9561	1748.9561
SSISKVKRLSALRQAR	1800.0765	601.0328	1800.0693	1800.0693	1800.0693
APDAALASVASAIIIVLGGQ	1836.0796	613.0338	1836.0356	1836.0356	1836.0356
ITTLRGKKSLSVTKTTLE	1888.1287	630.3835	1888.1357	1888.1357	1888.1357
KNEKKRTDGRSLTSVT	1932.1516	645.0578	1932.0752	1932.0752	1932.0752
KTGKYYHHQNDFKRLSKLN	2342.3662	781.796	2342.2607	2342.2607	2342.2607
TSILNPGDEVLIPTPI	1677.9701	560.3306	1677.9189	1677.9189	1677.9189
LVITEEPALKDLKNLP	1793.0233	598.6817	1793.0187	1793.0187	1793.0187
QLQHGEKFKLSIFLR	1844.0995	615.7071	1844.0309	1844.0309	1844.0309
FGSLGVPTPWAVQAIPP	1866.0448	623.0222	1865.9675	1865.9675	1865.9675
HDQLITYKTSKGAIQFLDQPLP	2609.4268	870.8162	2609.3853	2609.3853	2609.3853

ANVKTRRSEETVLPIN	1827.0731	914.5438	1826.985	1826.985	1826.985
EIDKPDVNINKLAPNN	1793.0233	598.6817	1792.9319	1792.9319	1792.9319
FKKDNYKTLIAGGIPAT	1836.0796	613.0338	1836.0145	1836.0145	1836.0145
DLDKIVIGGGISSQPLLI	1837.0481	613.3566	1837.056	1837.056	1837.056
TRGIGLFNAVTEQKIQN	1888.1287	630.3835	1888.0166	1888.0166	1888.0166
ATLPKNLRSTMEDLAKAQELN	2342.3662	781.796	2342.2263	2342.2263	2342.2263
LPVFFATQPAHLFARGG	1844.0995	615.7071	1843.9734	1843.9734	1843.9734
DLKSGDTVSLPN	1244.7202	623.3674	1244.6249	1244.6249	1244.6249
QVNVAMGFLALLGAIFGPV	1932.152	645.0579	1932.0543	1932.0543	1932.0543
GPIIAFILFLMPMYAIHKSPK	2386.3896	796.4705	2386.3308	2386.3308	2386.3308
KTGKPALETVYTIHAGG	1871.0955	936.555	1871.0153	1871.0153	1871.0153
FMYTGPFLP	1087.5228	544.7687	1087.5049	1087.5049	1087.5049
DTVYMERET	1142.5673	572.2909	1142.4913	1142.4913	1142.4913
HGLAALHVRIQHTRGTA	1837.0481	613.3566	1837.0183	1837.0183	1837.0183
QKKLDATHDSMKGKGN	1837.0481	613.3566	1836.9153	1836.9153	1836.9153
ILWRTMAQHGVHVGLGN	1888.1287	630.3835	1887.989	1887.989	1887.989
APVQVIYDDPL	1244.707	623.3608	1244.6289	1244.6289	1244.6289
DVIMMKLHGLKIKGDAI	1881.0748	628.0322	1881.058	1881.058	1881.058
IIAAITIGVLCILTLVSYG	1932.152	645.0579	1932.137	1932.137	1932.137
DVALRRPEFAGSGTAVII	1871.0955	936.555	1871.0265	1871.0265	1871.0265
FMYTGPFLP	1087.5228	544.7687	1087.5049	1087.5049	1087.5049
LDNYFPKMV	1142.5673	572.2909	1142.5317	1142.5317	1142.5317
GGCAIGSRPIDLHLKGLN	1836.0796	613.0338	1835.9677	1835.9677	1835.9677
GPRELVGGKAILPFIHG	1888.1287	630.3835	1888.1047	1888.1047	1888.1047
EEGPEGNEAIEPAPN	1551.6201	776.8173	1551.6689	1551.6689	1551.6689
ELKIGTERQVRKLFQKQNR	2430.4177	811.1465	2430.3342	2430.3342	2430.3342
SFLLHRPDPL	1193.5858	597.8002	1193.6556	1193.6556	1193.6556
GLHLKGTVNPPP	1244.707	623.3608	1244.6877	1244.6877	1244.6877
FALSLFPLDQIAPVCSI	1932.152	645.0579	1932.0431	1932.0431	1932.0431
EAATAIATSKAKREEASSR	1976.1771	659.733	1976.0287	1976.0287	1976.0287
EVMPKPVYQPLI	1428.8226	715.4186	1428.7687	1428.7687	1428.7687
MEEPLPLP	1087.5228	544.7687	1087.526	1087.526	1087.526
VEDEFDYL	1141.4447	571.7296	1141.5179	1141.5179	1141.5179
VEALIAAGDKPNVAIKTIARRN	2447.4404	612.8674	2447.4336	2447.4336	2447.4336
VEYDFHLSVHSATVLDG	1888.1287	630.3835	1887.9003	1887.9003	1887.9003
FFRPLIAAGGE	0	295.1416	1176.6292	1176.6292	1176.6292
PNNNILIVKYG	1244.7129	623.3637	1244.6765	1244.6765	1244.6765
FLRDPKILMLDEATASL	1932.152	645.0579	1932.0391	1932.0391	1932.0391
DSKKTNTQKVTKATVTPS	1976.1771	659.733	1976.0902	1976.0902	1976.0902
GGMPVILLNKSFTFDSYKTSDF	2447.4404	612.8674	2447.2407	2447.2407	2447.2407
DNMETALKNAADGRDIR	1889.1281	630.7166	1888.9061	1888.9061	1888.9061
FARGGIELL	974.5881	488.3013	974.5549	974.5549	974.5549
GLHLKGTVNPPP	1244.7129	623.3637	1244.6877	1244.6877	1244.6877
TKTTYKPNGLVAAVKGKSN	1976.1771	659.733	1976.1055	1976.1055	1976.1055
IAANQDGTQVVAHKSQKP	2020.2056	674.4091	2020.0702	2020.0702	2020.0702
GKLADNSSKDPE	1259.744	630.8793	1259.5994	1259.5994	1259.5994
HNVGKIPPLSVMSGT	1535.7529	768.8837	1535.813	1535.813	1535.813

KTIPIIIIEATNILMEAGPRLDYR	0	876.5071	2626.4517	2626.4517	2626.4517
TGAAFVIRNKLHRVAKRRI	2447.4434	612.8681	2447.4714	2447.4714	2447.4714
SSIMPGKINPVIPEVVNQV	2020.2056	674.4091	2020.1027	2020.1027	2020.1027
DPAVPVSDQPL	1136.4905	569.2525	1136.5714	1136.5714	1136.5714
ILGISLMADQAE	1259.744	630.8793	1259.6432	1259.6432	1259.6432
CIVDFKVVPTVTT	1535.7529	768.8837	1535.7905	1535.7905	1535.7905
GGNANAKQTFSTMSFNGKPIMT	0	613.0536	2448.1565	2448.1565	2448.1565
PIPGSPMVSLN	1127.5535	564.784	1127.5532	1127.5532	1127.5532
DVVPSIQHGNA	1136.4905	569.2525	1136.5461	1136.5461	1136.5461
SIRAGKTAADDARLALFYLVSPN	0	613.0523	2448.3125	2448.3125	2448.3125
DFFFQP	800.2769	401.1457	800.3381	800.3381	800.3381
KNLPYP	0	747.3653	746.3963	746.3963	746.3963
RGTPLMVQLMLVY	1535.7511	768.8828	1535.8204	1535.8204	1535.8204
DLPYLPLPE	1087.5233	544.7689	1087.5437	1087.5437	1087.5437
ACNVTVLPYTATTEILNLDPDG	0	613.0525	2448.1731	2448.1731	2448.1731
ETLIPLIIPFP	1267.7527	634.8836	1267.7428	1267.7428	1267.7428
DMYLYP	800.2769	401.1457	800.3415	800.3415	800.3415
NIRHALPFVDQIKF	0	429.2645	1712.9363	1712.9363	1712.9363
NTLPYP	0	747.365	746.3599	746.3599	746.3599
VQSPTLDANIVMIH	1536.7552	769.3849	1536.797	1536.797	1536.797
KENMEVQVTLYKGEVLGIDLP	0	792.4201	2374.2454	2374.2454	2374.2454
DFKT	0	510.2848	509.2486	509.2486	509.2486
APREFLPQM	1087.5233	544.7689	1087.5485	1087.5485	1087.5485
MGGIGLAPVIIIISVLIGT	0	613.0503	1836.1158	1836.1158	1836.1158
LVGGALGALLFNVLVLP	1453.806	727.9103	1453.8545	1453.8545	1453.8545
DLGDLEPVKKSNF	0	366.199	1460.7511	1460.7511	1460.7511
DISGEALP	800.2769	401.1457	800.3916	800.3916	800.3916
TMGADRYLSLH	0	632.299	1262.6078	1262.6078	1262.6078
DLHELEFGGVEGAY	1534.6165	768.3155	1534.694	1534.694	1534.694
ISSLIGISIEGQSANSSQQIEDTA	0	613.0503	2448.1868	2448.1868	2448.1868
RSKRMVETLGSIVADFIIEPDE	0	631.0617	2520.2529	2520.2529	2520.2529
REETPGDFSNPEYNVEPG	2035.7994	1018.907	2035.876	2035.876	2035.876
TNWIMH	800.2769	401.1457	800.364	800.364	800.364
DNGFGYDPLFYVE	1534.6165	768.3155	1534.6616	1534.6616	1534.6616
GLRIDNPVVKKPDILP	1772.9647	887.4896	1773.0513	1773.0513	1773.0513
DVVPSIQHGNA	1136.4923	569.2534	1136.5461	1136.5461	1136.5461
EPAKLVQYLANVDLPTA	1842.0923	615.038	1841.9775	1841.9775	1841.9775
DVDLEIESEPEP	0	686.2914	1370.6089	1370.6089	1370.6089
VAENIVSSEDATMGADLEW	2035.7994	1018.907	2035.9044	2035.9044	2035.9044
ESQAGQLPYP	1088.5099	545.2622	1088.5138	1088.5138	1088.5138
DDYIETGIPLDADV	1534.6165	768.3155	1534.7039	1534.7039	1534.7039
PKGVKAPTLDPT	1222.582	612.2983	1222.6921	1222.6921	1222.6921
GPEVNYEPNSFDGPTEER	2035.8075	1018.911	2035.876	2035.876	2035.876
FPNMEEPLP	1088.5099	545.2622	1088.4849	1088.4849	1088.4849
IMDQQP	0	747.3639	746.3269	746.3269	746.3269
EASKEKRLCGC	1222.5798	612.2972	1222.5798	1222.5798	1222.5798
APREFLPQM	1088.5101	545.2623	1088.5325	1088.5325	1088.5325

AILPGPTGVPVPYV	1410.7019	706.3582	1410.7759	1410.7759	1410.7759
GPEVNYEPNSFDGPTTEER	2035.8075	1018.911	2035.876	2035.876	2035.876
INPIGEVNRKGTL	1410.7019	706.3582	1410.7831	1410.7831	1410.7831
PAVSISTSASPAESAATSSTSQ	2035.8075	1018.911	2035.9546	2035.9546	2035.9546
PAVSISTSASPAESAATSSTSQ	2035.8118	679.6112	2035.9546	2035.9546	2035.9546
QPEKMDLDIVYEDDDVI	2035.8118	679.6112	2035.9296	2035.9296	2035.9296
SLFFGDCPIDNQ	1354.6105	678.3125	1354.5863	1354.5863	1354.5863
IDPRQTAWDP	1197.5563	599.7854	1197.5779	1197.5779	1197.5779
NLWNAVRDLP	1197.5563	599.7854	1197.6143	1197.6143	1197.6143
EDPIQAQPVLP	1432.7474	717.381	1432.7562	1432.7562	1432.7562
LEVMPKPVYQPL	1460.7417	731.3781	1460.7585	1460.7585	1460.7585
GLGNIGPAGGLP	1021.6041	511.8093	1021.5557	1021.5557	1021.5557
DRQMPKVP	1197.5563	599.7854	1197.6539	1197.6539	1197.6539
DNGHLDEFGIYTP	0	493.2397	1476.6521	1476.6521	1476.6521
HTIIVVRAN	1021.6041	511.8093	1021.6033	1021.6033	1021.6033
EPNWLVLVRTVMPLGLSYI	2199.3574	550.8466	2199.2126	2199.2126	2199.2126
HAMAHVYGLDANNFAMGGLMEAE	0	613.0509	2448.0662	2448.0662	2448.0662
EASFSDFAKECHF	0	380.1563	1516.6293	1516.6293	1516.6293
EDPIQAQPVLP	1432.7474	717.381	1432.7562	1432.7562	1432.7562
IPFT	0	493.2387	492.2584	492.2584	492.2584
GLGNIGPAGGLP	1021.6041	511.8093	1021.5557	1021.5557	1021.5557
KQQQLVKTVVYSPTKDFS	2111.3054	528.8336	2111.1262	2111.1262	2111.1262
GSGTGIDLVRPQLQPHANL	2199.3574	550.8466	2199.176	2199.176	2199.176
RMEATTTAVPTGSNKSGE	0	613.0511	1835.8683	1835.8683	1835.8683
AGGPSYHA	0	380.1551	758.3348	758.3348	758.3348
KPDQPNFQLFKEWLTYAMPAADIPLC	0	821.4065	3281.6221	3281.6221	3281.6221
EPNKLKPL	1052.546	527.2803	1052.623	1052.623	1052.623
ACNVTVLPYTATTEILNLDPDG	0	613.0511	2448.1731	2448.1731	2448.1731
LDSPADEP	0	843.3897	842.3658	842.3658	842.3658
SHDTLSQGYDT	1222.5829	612.2987	1222.5103	1222.5103	1222.5103
PNNKPN	0	683.3532	682.3398	682.3398	682.3398
AACIAANIP	0	843.3919	842.432	842.432	842.432
ASSLGSTQNMVE	1222.5836	612.2991	1222.5499	1222.5499	1222.5499
DLKPNP	0	683.3544	682.365	682.365	682.365
AACIAANIP	0	843.3915	842.432	842.432	842.432
AACIAANIP	0	843.3923	842.432	842.432	842.432
KSTLLNHLVNKKVAITG	1835.3955	612.8058	1835.0992	1835.0992	1835.0992
VPVIAMSMMKSLLL	1531.8167	766.9156	1531.854	1531.854	1531.854
CLPLLIQFPVFAAL	1559.8082	780.9114	1559.8785	1559.8785	1559.8785
PINDFSEPLTWRDQDTER	0	740.339	2218.0291	2218.0291	2218.0291
VPVIAMSMMKSLLL	1531.8167	766.9156	1531.854	1531.854	1531.854
GGDPANLP	0	740.3396	739.3501	739.3501	739.3501
VPVIAMSMMKSLLL	1531.8167	766.9156	1531.854	1531.854	1531.854
PIDDAKTEGVLPNL	1480.7263	741.3704	1480.7773	1480.7773	1480.7773
RFWV	606.5489	304.2817	606.3278	606.3278	606.3278
IIPLKVEVEP	1151.6118	576.8132	1151.6802	1151.6802	1151.6802
DKPDQSGATDIEFVN	1634.6499	818.3322	1634.7424	1634.7424	1634.7424

ILVQMPLPPQ	1151.6121	576.8133	1151.626	1151.626	1151.626
QTDAPTALDAPV	0	400.2023	1197.5878	1197.5878	1197.5878
GPGGPLAVFGDALE	1298.6306	650.3226	1298.6506	1298.6506	1298.6506
HPAKPHQQPIP	1249.6669	625.8407	1249.6567	1249.6567	1249.6567
ADADDLDVPGAPK	1298.6306	650.3226	1298.599	1298.599	1298.599
VLSPDLAVGVALP	1249.6647	625.8396	1249.7281	1249.7281	1249.7281
QTATDELVPPIN	1296.6135	649.314	1296.6561	1296.6561	1296.6561
PIELSEPLP	1082.5334	542.274	1082.5496	1082.5496	1082.5496
VPGINENLPKGP	1249.5673	625.7909	1249.6666	1249.6666	1249.6666
PGEPSAPGTPDQP	1248.5544	625.2845	1248.5623	1248.5623	1248.5623
NPAQGVAPVNIDMF	1488.7703	745.3924	1488.6919	1488.6919	1488.6919
DPKSPIITMLVLY	1488.77	745.3923	1488.8262	1488.8262	1488.8262
NPAQGVAPVNIDMF	1488.7699	745.3922	1488.6919	1488.6919	1488.6919
NPAQGVAPVNIDMF	1488.7699	745.3922	1488.6919	1488.6919	1488.6919
NPAQGVAPVNIDMF	1488.7697	745.3921	1488.6919	1488.6919	1488.6919
DVPQGLPNVV	1036.5359	519.2752	1036.5553	1036.5553	1036.5553
TLGATGLPNGH	1036.5359	519.2752	1036.5302	1036.5302	1036.5302
DVPQGLPNVV	1036.5355	519.275	1036.5553	1036.5553	1036.5553
DVPQGLPNVV	1036.5355	519.275	1036.5553	1036.5553	1036.5553
HAKLLGFKHPVTGDLLTFEAPLP	2500.0325	626.0154	2500.3843	2500.3843	2500.3843
LIVNPIDPDDPSKPGTGGTNNLGPL	2500.0325	626.0154	2500.281	2500.281	2500.281
NNYLSTITKLQ	1293.7861	647.9003	1293.6929	1293.6929	1293.6929
LMLVIRQLRISQNDMSKFPLP	2499.5369	625.8915	2499.3706	2499.3706	2499.3706
DLPTFDDIDDENM	1538.5819	770.2982	1538.6083	1538.6083	1538.6083
GVRTPVANEPLP	1249.759	625.8868	1249.6666	1249.6666	1249.6666
IHECRPCVVGDTNP	1538.5819	770.2982	1538.697	1538.697	1538.697
GEPVQEGKIY	1118.4796	560.2471	1118.5608	1118.5608	1118.5608
EADPEEGPLY	1118.4796	560.2471	1118.4768	1118.4768	1118.4768
ISEVPLADMI	1118.4796	560.2471	1118.553	1118.553	1118.553
AGGPIP	0	511.2725	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
IPYALAAPLP	1024.6677	513.3411	1024.5957	1024.5957	1024.5957
AGGPIP	0	511.2729	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
AGGPIP	0	511.2725	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
MMTQLLPMT	0	533.2544	1064.5068	1064.5068	1064.5068
DIVQQLPLP	1022.5175	512.266	1022.5648	1022.5648	1022.5648
MMTQLLPMT	0	533.2513	1064.5068	1064.5068	1064.5068
RQNLVSPPLP	1022.5175	512.266	1022.5873	1022.5873	1022.5873
AINPARDLGP	1022.5175	512.266	1022.5509	1022.5509	1022.5509
PIHPMDEIGG	0	533.2521	1064.4961	1064.4961	1064.4961
IPIPLTWLA	1022.5175	512.266	1022.6165	1022.6165	1022.6165
DIRIEAPIP	1022.5175	512.266	1022.576	1022.576	1022.576
AGGPIP	0	511.272	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
AGGPIP	0	511.2725	510.2802	510.2802	510.2802
APRVVEGKQVLENI	1550.9698	776.4922	1550.8781	1550.8781	1550.8781
LKAKAQAALQANATALK	1639.0222	820.5184	1638.9781	1638.9781	1638.9781
TPKNKGRLLISAVVTSL	1683.0482	842.5314	1683.0043	1683.0043	1683.0043
LFNKKLAKQDFR	1506.9417	754.4781	1506.8671	1506.8671	1506.8671

ENLLVSELLSVSHR	1594.9958	798.5052	1594.8679	1594.8679	1594.8679
EIKKVVNAGRLFIGP	1727.0719	864.5432	1726.9883	1726.9883	1726.9883
ITVGQVRPDRVRR	1550.9698	776.4922	1550.9117	1550.9117	1550.9117
TQTKRQRLISALPK	1639.0222	820.5184	1638.9894	1638.9894	1638.9894
DIKQKVEQNGKKIGV	1683.0482	842.5314	1682.9679	1682.9679	1682.9679
KNSKATDRKNAVALKK	1771.0975	886.556	1771.0428	1771.0428	1771.0428
ELDTGTLIALKQRR	1594.9958	798.5052	1594.9155	1594.9155	1594.9155
NKKRRAEKLGIQSTV	1727.0719	864.5432	1727.0166	1727.0166	1727.0166
VGYRAQLQGKLVLSVG	1815.123	908.5688	1815.073	1815.073	1815.073
KKIEVINIHVRKGTLE	1876.1782	626.4	1876.1259	1876.1259	1876.1259
NDKTKIIHQHKVD	1550.9698	776.4922	1550.8781	1550.8781	1550.8781
LKAKAQAALQNAATALK	1639.0222	820.5184	1638.9781	1638.9781	1638.9781
AIAKAIALIKQTSDLQ	1683.0482	842.5314	1682.993	1682.993	1682.993
SAKALKLGAKFKASSAGH	1771.0975	886.556	1771.0105	1771.0105	1771.0105
EVRQKLGLDNF	0	440.2723	1317.7041	1317.7041	1317.7041
GTVVVLKNKPITVDI	1594.9958	798.5052	1594.9658	1594.9658	1594.9658
ASKADLQLDLGQISRL	1727.0719	864.5432	1726.9578	1726.9578	1726.9578
LELINKFDKILLIEN	1815.123	908.5688	1815.0393	1815.0393	1815.0393
KNKKLFPVIAGILQA	1639.0222	820.5184	1639.0186	1639.0186	1639.0186
ALKKQQATIQAQVKQ	1683.0482	842.5314	1683.0043	1683.0043	1683.0043
TAALTAALKNLSIEAATL	1771.0975	886.556	1771.0092	1771.0092	1771.0092
NKFIKMAKN	1092.7014	547.358	1092.6113	1092.6113	1092.6113
KNELQIVLQP	1180.7533	591.3839	1180.6815	1180.6815	1180.6815
ELSVTQLMQLLRQTPLFNKKLAK	0	900.5779	2698.5569	2698.5569	2698.5569
YVLTGQA	0	376.2574	750.3912	750.3912	750.3912
IRVLLPPNK	1048.6766	525.3456	1048.6757	1048.6757	1048.6757
VSIHTRIGVR	1136.7273	569.3709	1136.6779	1136.6779	1136.6779
TKGARVPPNSVV	1224.7772	613.3959	1224.6826	1224.6826	1224.6826
TPQAGRVPQKLPLQIIFSTRKDNSH	0	944.6068	2830.5566	2830.5566	2830.5566
QLTPAGQA	0	393.2829	784.4079	784.4079	784.4079
AHLVGNLPKNAK	0	421.3137	1260.7302	1260.7302	1260.7302
PPKLSVASFI	1057.6606	529.8376	1057.6172	1057.6172	1057.6172
PRVLAILASGP	1092.7014	547.358	1092.6655	1092.6655	1092.6655
KGGPDVLIIVRGA	1180.7533	591.3839	1180.6927	1180.6927	1180.6927
GPGLILTQLSTLG	1268.8004	635.4075	1268.734	1268.734	1268.734
ITYVGAK	0	376.2566	750.4276	750.4276	750.4276
PQAALARVRR	1136.7273	569.3709	1136.6891	1136.6891	1136.6891
AASRSIRVFKTADLKALVNK	2187.3235	730.1151	2187.2852	2187.2852	2187.2852
IDKAMIKLDGTPNK	1542.9359	772.4752	1542.844	1542.844	1542.844
ARWLTIQFINQNK	1630.9879	816.5012	1630.8944	1630.8944	1630.8944
FTLGDIIIGDSLKSDSK	1723.0355	862.525	1722.8676	1722.8676	1722.8676
NKVLFIANS LAPNTKLA	1813.1024	907.5585	1813.0461	1813.0461	1813.0461
QYTGAIRGAK	0	393.281	1176.6615	1176.6615	1176.6615
TITPAPKN	0	421.3106	840.4705	840.4705	840.4705
GHDAIVVFI	969.6125	485.8135	969.5284	969.5284	969.5284
KEKTVKKN	973.6457	487.8301	973.592	973.592	973.592
GSIVYQTNK	1008.6817	505.3481	1008.524	1008.524	1008.524

QNKRHQSR	1052.7073	527.3609	1052.5587	1052.5587	1052.5587
GLKNVGELTK	1057.6606	529.8376	1057.6132	1057.6132	1057.6132
NKFIKMAKN	1092.7014	547.358	1092.6113	1092.6113	1092.6113
GKITGIIGPNGA	1096.7336	549.3741	1096.624	1096.624	1096.624
ITILRIKNGN	1140.7579	571.3862	1140.6979	1140.6979	1140.6979
RRLVPNRFQ	1184.7841	593.3993	1184.6891	1184.6891	1184.6891
QNDDLQSKNELHHKQLQN	2188.3208	730.4475	2188.062	2188.062	2188.062
ATPGAILLVKHKTVT	1547.9325	774.9735	1547.9399	1547.9399	1547.9399
LGYKELIARTRTPN	1630.9879	816.5012	1630.9155	1630.9155	1630.9155
FLPILLGFSATKRFGG	1723.0355	862.525	1722.9821	1722.9821	1722.9821
GDQALLRLDQIKTTNK	1813.0955	907.555	1813.0057	1813.0057	1813.0057
LPNDPSNLARALQLLAAQKLITLKKN	0	948.633	2842.6755	2842.6755	2842.6755
IPTLGLGFI	929.6158	465.8152	929.5586	929.5586	929.5586
EVKYKGKN	964.6565	483.3355	964.5342	964.5342	964.5342
GTSKILNKN	973.6457	487.8301	973.5557	973.5557	973.5557
FILMLFIL	1008.6817	505.3481	1008.6082	1008.6082	1008.6082
LLLTWFI	1017.6697	509.8421	1017.6263	1017.6263	1017.6263
INVSLPRVR	1052.7073	527.3609	1052.6455	1052.6455	1052.6455
AVVTRNVPKN	1096.7336	549.3741	1096.6353	1096.6353	1096.6353
LFPVIAGILQA	1140.7579	571.3862	1140.6907	1140.6907	1140.6907
IAKKGDYYHLVKN	1547.9325	774.9735	1547.8461	1547.8461	1547.8461
IPLLEDPHVLDIKN	1630.9879	816.5012	1630.8931	1630.8931	1630.8931
ILYIISNNFQKLF	1725.0377	863.5261	1724.9866	1724.9866	1724.9866
IGRAGSFASIVLRQPKN	1813.0955	907.555	1813.0322	1813.0322	1813.0322
LMLFILFI	1008.6817	505.3481	1008.6082	1008.6082	1008.6082
QNKRHQSR	1052.7073	527.3609	1052.5587	1052.5587	1052.5587
IPGDVIK	0	371.3242	740.4432	740.4432	740.4432
KSHKNVIVTR	1180.7521	591.3833	1180.704	1180.704	1180.704
PLGRLSTVVASILR	0	371.3243	1480.9089	1480.9089	1480.9089
PPKQSKRR	1092.7039	547.3592	1092.6516	1092.6516	1092.6516
VGRPGAIVGRVG	1136.7283	569.3714	1136.6779	1136.6779	1136.6779
TKGARVPPNSVV	1224.7793	613.3969	1224.6826	1224.6826	1224.6826
INFAVFPQN	1048.6766	525.3456	1048.5342	1048.5342	1048.5342
ILIVILVASAG	1180.7521	591.3833	1180.7795	1180.7795	1180.7795
QKALFIIFGG	1092.7039	547.3592	1092.6332	1092.6332	1092.6332
VRAPNGVVIVN	1136.7283	569.3714	1136.6666	1136.6666	1136.6666
EALERAKPKID	1268.8066	635.4106	1268.7089	1268.7089	1268.7089
YTGLMIRR	1008.6819	505.3482	1008.5539	1008.5539	1008.5539
NKSKAYTKN	1052.7083	527.3614	1052.5614	1052.5614	1052.5614
PLQSSILGGII	1096.7345	549.3745	1096.6492	1096.6492	1096.6492
ALLKPAIRF	1140.7596	571.3871	1140.7383	1140.7383	1140.7383
IPLKGKTQN	1013.6413	507.8279	1013.5869	1013.5869	1013.5869
ILKRLSNLERHVFGAQLDNNQN	2578.5293	860.517	2578.3728	2578.3728	2578.3728
ILPHPLNLAHLLSLEQQTVGIHHN	2709.605	904.2089	2709.4714	2709.4714	2709.4714
IRIEPPTI	1008.6819	505.3482	1008.5968	1008.5968	1008.5968
ALPLSLQGVR	1052.7083	527.3614	1052.6343	1052.6343	1052.6343
ILPIALVGGASLIFGVSPMEALF	2314.3564	772.4594	2314.301	2314.301	2314.301

FWVFSGLAIVGLVAGLNV TAPSASA	2446.4487	816.4902	2446.3259	2446.3259	2446.3259
LDPASGKASM	0	326.1473	975.4695	975.4695	975.4695
ATLDDMRGYDFAMKILNGVYKSA	2578.5293	860.517	2578.2559	2578.2559	2578.2559
NDEHGF	0	360.1301	718.2559	718.2559	718.2559
LPNNHG	0	326.1476	650.3136	650.3136	650.3136
LFAKLRNLTPTLFGQ	1718.0853	573.7024	1717.9879	1717.9879	1717.9879
EIQIPASKVPAPFKPGKA	1762.1112	588.3777	1762.0142	1762.0142	1762.0142
LFLAQAYGIHLTLGHQI	1894.1932	632.405	1894.0465	1894.0465	1894.0465
KVVYQVKAQEMATAIK	1806.137	603.0529	1806.0073	1806.0073	1806.0073
LKSRKALIKLLKKLQA	1850.1637	617.7285	1850.2557	1850.2557	1850.2557
AATMQKNADPLVVAP	1524.9563	763.4854	1524.797	1524.797	1524.797
AAVDLKKVIENKKN	1568.9801	785.4973	1568.925	1568.925	1568.925
KKRRKAIVQLSEDS	1657.0299	829.5222	1656.9635	1656.9635	1656.9635
KMIKEFKPDVVLGTGG	1718.0853	573.7024	1717.9437	1717.9437	1717.9437
KKSHQRPIIQVKVDS	1762.1112	588.3777	1762.0214	1762.0214	1762.0214
AKKVRESLSRVVKN	1613.0081	807.5113	1612.9736	1612.9736	1612.9736
NKLREKFEPTKAKL	1701.0569	851.5357	1700.9938	1700.9938	1700.9938
AGAVLPGIAFYGLIALLM	1789.1095	895.562	1789.0212	1789.0212	1789.0212
ADVNFVVKKFKVKTVR	1850.1637	617.7285	1850.0778	1850.0778	1850.0778
ITEAVVTKTLPRVRRR	1894.1932	632.405	1894.1588	1894.1588	1894.1588
IQNLLQLRKREA	1480.9309	741.4727	1480.8838	1480.8838	1480.8838
IVSYGFSLRKSIR	1524.9563	763.4854	1524.8777	1524.8777	1524.8777
ISLGLTKLLALWQGG	1568.9801	785.4973	1568.929	1568.929	1568.929
AMNWKNAKAAIKRR	1657.0299	829.5222	1656.9358	1656.9358	1656.9358
RLAKKSTQINVVFKN	1745.0845	873.5495	1745.0311	1745.0311	1745.0311
FLAKLAMSALTALKSPK	1718.0853	573.7024	1718.0165	1718.0165	1718.0165
EKSQKGVVDVKYGRR	1762.1112	588.3777	1761.985	1761.985	1761.985
NVFALLLVAFKAASKTN	1806.137	603.0529	1806.0404	1806.0404	1806.0404
RLGPKSIRKLGIVREN	1938.2168	647.0795	1938.1487	1938.1487	1938.1487
ALQATKLPKSPGN	1436.9033	719.4589	1436.8351	1436.8351	1436.8351
HGASSAKFKAGLKLAK	1613.0081	807.5113	1612.9413	1612.9413	1612.9413
EIKTPFLIKQLAETA	1701.0569	851.5357	1700.9713	1700.9713	1700.9713
LLGLVSILFFLNKKNM	1850.1637	617.7285	1850.074	1850.074	1850.074
GLIEGLKIRROKAEKGV	1894.1932	632.405	1894.1476	1894.1476	1894.1476
PTGLLLVGWLIGWG	1480.9309	741.4727	1480.8442	1480.8442	1480.8442
EPAVKAEVQRLKSA	1524.9563	763.4854	1524.8624	1524.8624	1524.8624
LKKQSLRRTQRR	1568.9801	785.4973	1568.97	1568.97	1568.97
SSRKALEKLRLNEI	1657.0299	829.5222	1656.9523	1656.9523	1656.9523
FLKQKDLADLKR	1745.0845	873.5495	1744.9948	1744.9948	1744.9948
KMIKEFKPDVVLGTGG	1718.0853	573.7024	1717.9437	1717.9437	1717.9437
LSGLKAEYGQKRGTVR	1762.1112	588.3777	1761.985	1761.985	1761.985
ELQKHAARDKVKK	1806.137	603.0529	1806.0952	1806.0952	1806.0952
LEKVIPGNPQLL	1392.8779	697.4462	1392.7976	1392.7976	1392.7976
EILFLKFSIKLS	1436.9033	719.4589	1436.8643	1436.8643	1436.8643
IFNKIAAILDRF	1490.9041	746.4593	1490.861	1490.861	1490.861
LEKIFKNQPQK	1613.0081	807.5113	1612.9664	1612.9664	1612.9664
IFKVAENGLVKKLEN	1701.0569	851.5357	1700.9825	1700.9825	1700.9825

ELLISSKLPGRH	1348.8519	675.4332	1348.7827	1348.7827	1348.7827
LSRKKKFPDAIY	1480.9309	741.4727	1480.8402	1480.8402	1480.8402
IVSYGFSLRKSIR	1524.9563	763.4854	1524.8777	1524.8777	1524.8777
LQHEKAAAALIGVALP	1529.9077	765.9611	1529.8929	1529.8929	1529.8929
EIKQQLGKVITANQ	1568.9801	785.4973	1568.8885	1568.8885	1568.8885
IFILSIFQVFFNS	1573.9341	787.9743	1573.8545	1573.8545	1573.8545
AMNWKNAKAAAIKRR	1657.0299	829.5222	1656.9358	1656.9358	1656.9358
NQQFLNLFQLLLRV	1745.0845	873.5495	1744.9988	1744.9988	1744.9988
EAGVKTILNPAPAI	1392.8779	697.4462	1392.7976	1392.7976	1392.7976
HSKQLLNKIQTQ	1436.9033	719.4589	1436.8099	1436.8099	1436.8099
LIGADLMLKLHHS	1446.8743	724.4444	1446.8018	1446.8018	1446.8018
IINMASIAGLIGISN	1485.8831	743.9488	1485.8225	1485.8225	1485.8225
APNICVNGFIFLAI	1490.9	746.4573	1490.7955	1490.7955	1490.7955
GKILPRRVGTSAKN	1613.0081	807.5113	1612.9373	1612.9373	1612.9373
NQKIQRDLEGFIKI	1701.0569	851.5357	1700.9574	1700.9574	1700.9574
IFALPAMFKIAK	1348.8519	675.4332	1348.7941	1348.7941	1348.7941
LQQRVRSISMPK	1441.8567	721.9356	1441.8187	1441.8187	1441.8187
ELGVPVIALSQLSR	1480.9309	741.4727	1480.8613	1480.8613	1480.8613
KNIRKPNGAKPGFV	1524.9563	763.4854	1524.8889	1524.8889	1524.8889
SRQERKIALKVIQ	1568.9801	785.4973	1568.9363	1568.9363	1568.9363
TSAAKVGTIRVLKAATA	1657.0299	829.5222	1656.9886	1656.9886	1656.9886
PTKPVNAPRPRGR	1304.8251	653.4198	1304.7313	1304.7313	1304.7313
KNVIAAHGNSLR	1392.8779	697.4462	1392.7837	1392.7837	1392.7837
KNKQVLVSLKKN	1397.8331	699.9238	1397.8718	1397.8718	1397.8718
PVQIIAGTELTPAK	1436.9033	719.4589	1436.8239	1436.8239	1436.8239
LFNGALGALLGLGLSA	1485.8831	743.9488	1485.8555	1485.8555	1485.8555
ALVVLIVVLLGWYR	1613.0081	807.5113	1613.0068	1613.0068	1613.0068
SGSGKVSIE	990.6763	496.3454	990.5345	990.5345	990.5345
KLVTTLPQHAIE	1348.8519	675.4332	1348.7715	1348.7715	1348.7715
GLGVGTGLILAAGNRI	1480.9309	741.4727	1480.8726	1480.8726	1480.8726
VVQKIENVASLEKI	1568.9801	785.4973	1568.9138	1568.9138	1568.9138
LNLLKVKGIGPKSA	1436.9033	719.4589	1436.9078	1436.9078	1436.9078
EIADSSQKN	990.6763	496.3454	990.4618	990.4618	990.4618
IALLSAPL	0	399.3529	796.5059	796.5059	796.5059
LNLIKPQILI	1164.7601	583.3873	1164.7482	1164.7482	1164.7482
MVIAAVVTGLIL	1198.7675	600.391	1198.736	1198.736	1198.736
ILVGQIPIMLL	1208.7794	605.397	1208.7566	1208.7566	1208.7566
MNVGKIKITKGN	1286.8182	644.4164	1286.7017	1286.7017	1286.7017
EKLAPALKAH	1076.6959	539.3552	1076.6343	1076.6343	1076.6343
RTLQGPITLI	1110.7136	556.3641	1110.6761	1110.6761	1110.6761
IQPAAIEKGTK	1154.7389	578.3767	1154.6659	1154.6659	1154.6659
KGVVFKVNKAQN	1330.8457	666.4301	1330.7721	1330.7721	1330.7721
FLAADKIVF	1022.6605	512.3375	1022.5801	1022.5801	1022.5801
PYLLLLKSA	1066.6873	534.3509	1066.6063	1066.6063	1066.6063
ATKRRRSQKP	1198.7675	600.391	1198.7258	1198.7258	1198.7258
TYKNNLPAIPL	1242.7921	622.4033	1242.6973	1242.6973	1242.6973
IYLPPIIAGAM	1286.8182	644.4164	1286.7672	1286.7672	1286.7672

DKQKIIADYQA	1291.7727	646.8936	1291.6772	1291.6772	1291.6772
LFGKGTAKAS	978.6353	490.3249	978.5498	978.5498	978.5498
LIRVVRNEL	1110.7136	556.3641	1110.6874	1110.6874	1110.6874
LLGVRNQNEL	1154.7389	578.3767	1154.6407	1154.6407	1154.6407
LKTAMLREKA	1159.6959	580.8552	1159.6747	1159.6747	1159.6747
QIIQKARAYN	1203.7247	602.8696	1203.6724	1203.6724	1203.6724
IFHILYEINS	1247.7487	624.8816	1247.655	1247.655	1247.655
FARNQFLK	1022.6605	512.3375	1022.5662	1022.5662	1022.5662
KNPKPNQKN	1066.6873	534.3509	1066.5884	1066.5884	1066.5884
LGAENGLLAKS	1071.6406	536.8276	1071.5924	1071.5924	1071.5924
EKLAPALKAH	1076.6735	539.344	1076.6343	1076.6343	1076.6343
KIELPEPIR	1093.6879	547.8512	1093.6495	1093.6495	1093.6495
LFAAIIIIQN	1115.6681	558.8413	1115.6591	1115.6591	1115.6591
LMLKNYNLL	1120.6947	561.3546	1120.6315	1120.6315	1120.6315
IIVNMPNLKTG	1198.7675	600.391	1198.6744	1198.6744	1198.6744
TPKQHKKI	978.6353	490.3249	978.5975	978.5975	978.5975
IMMIAGIHV	983.5898	492.8022	983.5296	983.5296	983.5296
TATTKKTAAN	1005.6346	503.8246	1005.5455	1005.5455	1005.5455
AIGIVEAIGSV	1027.6161	514.8153	1027.5913	1027.5913	1027.5913
AVLYALASLL	1032.6396	517.3271	1032.6219	1032.6219	1032.6219
IIIVITHNQ	1049.6605	525.8375	1049.6233	1049.6233	1049.6233
LYYGLSSLVG	1070.7173	536.3659	1070.5648	1070.5648	1070.5648
PYASVLHLVL	1110.7136	556.3641	1110.6437	1110.6437	1110.6437
IILIGAASRQN	1154.7389	578.3767	1154.6771	1154.6771	1154.6771
FINLVKNS	934.6109	468.3127	934.5124	934.5124	934.5124
FIAAVRSAQ	961.6091	481.8118	961.5345	961.5345	961.5345
LLSQENKAS	988.6097	495.3121	988.5189	988.5189	988.5189
HGKNVLVEK	1022.6605	512.3375	1022.5873	1022.5873	1022.5873
VVKELKPVR	1066.6873	534.3509	1066.6863	1066.6863	1066.6863
IIAAQIIKVF	1114.7417	558.3781	1114.7114	1114.7114	1114.7114
ILKNEGFIKDVEYIDDDKQGIIRVFLKY(O		918.5877	3669.9771	3669.9771	3669.9771
VRLEDQAINLMALQQPVANDFRQVI'	3694.2458	924.5687	3693.9875	3693.9875	3693.9875
PIEKVRRPALTINELVTLNPFLNFN	2907.7451	970.2556	2907.6335	2907.6335	2907.6335
IIIQYQGG	890.5833	446.2989	890.4861	890.4861	890.4861
LLRQTSLN	944.5853	473.2999	944.5291	944.5291	944.5291
LEKKGVIQ	978.6353	490.3249	978.5386	978.5386	978.5386
KLESALPLI	982.6656	492.3401	982.6063	982.6063	982.6063
HTMVPSILS	983.5898	492.8022	983.511	983.511	983.511
PVVAKIAKDS	1026.6915	514.353	1026.6073	1026.6073	1026.6073
KAAVAQNAKGKG	1070.7173	536.3659	1070.5833	1070.5833	1070.5833
VQATLNVSQRLGAFTQYMANITPIKA	3317.9827	830.5029	3317.803	3317.803	3317.803
LMNQLNYKVKAQVNRSVESIKTG	2619.5566	874.1928	2619.4167	2619.4167	2619.4167
IITTKGAGNPGLLALIKGKELSFSD	2641.5706	881.5308	2641.5054	2641.5054	2641.5054
HRVGNARI	921.6141	461.8143	921.5257	921.5257	921.5257
FINLVKNS	934.6109	468.3127	934.5124	934.5124	934.5124
ARDHTALGV	938.6423	470.3284	938.4934	938.4934	938.4934
IILLAQHS	965.6387	483.8266	965.5546	965.5546	965.5546

QALEQSKNA	987.6225	494.8185	987.4985	987.4985	987.4985
ISGILETINFKLNL	1573.9697	787.9921	1573.908	1573.908	1573.908
ALIVQKSVATISAKSATAEVNATKT	2502.5349	835.1856	2502.3904	2502.3904	2502.3904
ARKIAKIKNNLGELPGN	0	918.5907	1835.0741	1835.0741	1835.0741
KNKFVLF	894.6161	448.3153	894.5327	894.5327	894.5327
IWLGVIM	943.5953	472.8049	943.5565	943.5565	943.5565
ELIPRRIS	982.6656	492.3401	982.5923	982.5923	982.5923
PTLEGKAIKA	1026.6915	514.353	1026.6073	1026.6073	1026.6073
PTPLLEEVDRLRRLGMTARHADIN	2968.7734	743.2006	2968.6028	2968.6028	2968.6028
ALNGSPKVKETTRRKIVEAAHQGLGYVI	3317.9827	830.5029	3317.7957	3317.7957	3317.7957
KADSHLLKVMRAQIGEKIEVV	2500.5298	834.5172	2500.3948	2500.3948	2500.3948
VRYGRKFLSSGTTDLTLVHDKN	2619.5557	874.1925	2619.4133	2619.4133	2619.4133
INTPVQLIGSLFDKATIGRSYILN	2632.6055	878.5424	2632.4587	2632.4587	2632.4587
LSIALPFTLLPLVALTNDASLMKAH	2648.6172	883.8797	2648.4976	2648.4976	2648.4976
IEKQLRN	899.5695	450.792	899.5189	899.5189	899.5189
KNVIPRVN	938.6423	470.3284	938.5662	938.5662	938.5662
GPSVKYRDGKLIFDKQASKNKKATN	2792.6885	699.1794	2792.5298	2792.5298	2792.5298
LYGDKILLKGTDSA	1492.8853	747.4499	1492.8137	1492.8137	1492.8137
KFVIADEKGIPLNK	0	786.5131	1570.9083	1570.9083	1570.9083
AAKEIGGAGVISVASHI	1578.9647	790.4896	1578.8729	1578.8729	1578.8729
NLALEKDYLATGPTADTPRVGLLS	2514.519	839.1803	2514.333	2514.333	2514.333
PITLVISIETLTKMIMNLQYSIMN	2765.6934	922.905	2765.478	2765.478	2765.478
YTKRR	850.5898	426.3022	850.5137	850.5137	850.5137
IIRHNSR	894.6161	448.3153	894.5148	894.5148	894.5148
GKLLKDSLLGLLIT	1482.9137	742.4641	1482.9385	1482.9385	1482.9385
GGVTIIGDCHNDLYVQKAEGINRVKPI	2980.8086	746.2094	2980.5552	2980.5552	2980.5552
ILPQAARRTRIVFGVLGILGV	2249.3608	750.7942	2249.3735	2249.3735	2249.3735
RIVLMLGPANISDF	1544.9539	773.4842	1544.8385	1544.8385	1544.8385
GKPAQLLHPGDVVTIHPGVKHW	2385.4612	796.161	2385.3069	2385.3069	2385.3069
KAALKALHITQPTLSR	1634.0217	818.0181	1633.9628	1633.9628	1633.9628
IMGGVCFLIALILASIAPSVIWT	2500.5261	834.516	2500.4202	2500.4202	2500.4202
AKAPRSILFGQGAFLVQKNYPLTN	2632.6018	878.5412	2632.449	2632.449	2632.449
IKRWLPVPRAVVLENKG	1974.2517	659.0912	1974.1891	1974.1891	1974.1891
FSLPQINELGHN	1367.8339	684.9242	1367.6833	1367.6833	1367.6833
YGYGQKVLEAVNLRIMPNEKLTIVG	2804.7053	702.1836	2804.5259	2804.5259	2804.5259
IIEKLNLNKIKKYSTN	2117.2905	706.7708	2117.2573	2117.2573	2117.2573
RVSPFLVPNSIIN	1454.8724	728.4435	1454.8246	1454.8246	1454.8246
ANHQILLNFISIIGMIMAVLGT	2368.4529	790.4916	2368.301	2368.301	2368.301
TSILGSLPSLHMIRTWIPLAVG	2474.5271	825.8496	2474.4082	2474.4082	2474.4082
LNPDEKLLGLIQELLES	1923.1752	642.0657	1923.0565	1923.0565	1923.0565
TTILLYLILFFIAALFN	1985.2189	662.7469	1985.1642	1985.1642	1985.1642
TYTTVIQQNIRIIKNANIILYLMGTS	2980.8	746.2073	2980.6418	2980.6418	2980.6418
AKILVTTVDVPAVWVNKVALN	2249.3711	750.7976	2249.3147	2249.3147	2249.3147
APKAASSPAASDAKATKQENKSASA	2386.4814	796.5011	2386.2087	2386.2087	2386.2087
VTLSLYTGAVITGAFVAAGAVFATMA	2501.5339	834.8519	2501.324	2501.324	2501.324
VPLFGITVGKPTRKNAVKPRMPL	2518.5576	840.5265	2518.4934	2518.4934	2518.4934
LLSGSLASIVASILFLGIVGILLTQN	2611.5627	871.5282	2611.5564	2611.5564	2611.5564

ILQQSLRLDNQRIN	1710.0985	571.0401	1709.9536	1709.9536	1709.9536
IIPNLKIRTVIINKR	1791.0972	598.0397	1791.1459	1791.1459	1791.1459
INAILGVEKAAIKLATDN	1853.1489	618.7236	1853.0623	1853.0623	1853.0623
ARSLQGKNTRLIGVIFSD	1974.2517	659.0912	1974.1011	1974.1011	1974.1011
MQAKQPRVALLN	1367.8339	684.9242	1367.7708	1367.7708	1367.7708
SLPNQTYIEQLGLVLMGTVLLSLGVF	2804.699	702.182	2804.5398	2804.5398	2804.5398
LLGKFLGPFALINNVQNPY	2117.3057	706.7758	2117.1672	2117.1672	2117.1672
LKAIDTVTLSQVLSRTRGYR	2423.4556	808.8258	2423.365	2423.365	2423.365
KPGKVTVVNGDQKIEVGAPVEVPKR	2643.5825	882.2014	2643.5071	2643.5071	2643.5071
ILTRRLSKRLYAS	0	526.388	1575.9573	1575.9573	1575.9573
IINSLNFAIPALMGG	1659.0159	554.0126	1658.9066	1658.9066	1658.9066
SGNKVLWLGIGCIIVIAS	1842.1747	615.0655	1842.0437	1842.0437	1842.0437
KVPTDKRVDVMPLLAKN	1923.1752	642.0657	1923.0975	1923.0975	1923.0975
GALIGIIALIISERAVYLT	1985.2189	662.7469	1985.1925	1985.1925	1985.1925
IGEAKAVLQNLKVQQLFPAGV	2335.4038	779.4752	2335.3628	2335.3628	2335.3628
PTKTPLLQSKVQKKATAMAAEVQ	2467.4763	823.4994	2467.3833	2467.3833	2467.3833
QSEKKLQTPALTINQLVSLHPF	2474.5271	825.8496	2474.3533	2474.3533	2474.3533
IELFKQLSILFETRDDSISIKSR	2650.6362	884.5527	2650.4695	2650.4695	2650.4695
KKTTATKNVA	0	531.3459	1060.624	1060.624	1060.624
KNLKQTLQLRELN	1710.1014	571.0411	1710.0153	1710.0153	1710.0153
VFFGAPVSEGFAKQKIE	1853.1489	618.7236	1852.9723	1852.9723	1852.9723
QTTFFDTITSTLLGIFGI	1974.2517	659.0912	1974.035	1974.035	1974.035
GYASKFLSAALGLAGIGIVIKLLR	2430.5049	811.1756	2430.4727	2430.4727	2430.4727
LEKFNKPATKILKKNYYLVDS	2511.5071	838.1763	2511.4102	2511.4102	2511.4102
ATPKIKPFKRIIPMIYAYTTPN	2562.5793	855.2004	2562.4397	2562.4397	2562.4397
VVRLGNGSRILAQSESAGSKLLVGQR	2694.6606	899.2275	2694.5254	2694.5254	2694.5254
YYGKYQLSKSLLN	0	526.39	1575.8297	1575.8297	1575.8297
HQGTTRKVGTAGKALREIEAGR	2335.4038	779.4752	2335.2832	2335.2832	2335.2832
QDIYNDFKQKQTVSIKALQ	2379.4292	794.1503	2379.2798	2379.2798	2379.2798
IFNQNAIVATAIGIIIQLTTACV	2386.4814	796.5011	2386.3293	2386.3293	2386.3293
KNKLRIDNDSRLIEKLGELT	2467.4763	823.4994	2467.4121	2467.4121	2467.4121
KSAQKDFILKGDYKVSPIIVG	2518.5576	840.5265	2518.4272	2518.4272	2518.4272
LVGIPTGISGILPGNQTG	1693.0703	847.5424	1692.941	1692.941	1692.941
VVKPNKLQELLTARE	1737.0961	869.5553	1737.0149	1737.0149	1737.0149
RLTEIQNEIQELKVKTEVVIPIQ	2606.6074	869.8764	2606.4644	2606.4644	2606.4644
QNQADYITGRKAKI	1605.0161	803.5153	1604.8634	1604.8634	1604.8634
HALQGQSKLSNIIGPVETVQRGV	2430.5049	811.1756	2430.3342	2430.3342	2430.3342
HKGVVKEIADIQKAN	1649.0427	825.5286	1648.926	1648.926	1648.926
IEPYRKATIPELVNGMNAFIKA	2474.5271	825.8496	2474.3354	2474.3354	2474.3354
KNKQLKESIPLLKDNLFKELN	2511.5071	838.1763	2511.4424	2511.4424	2511.4424
VVDIKPELLAKTGHLHPNKKVLN	2562.5793	855.2004	2562.501	2562.501	2562.501
RGLKGKRADLLIRQSA	1781.119	891.5668	1781.0748	1781.0748	1781.0748
GNQRRNRNGNRQGGKN	1825.1456	913.5801	1824.9276	1824.9276	1824.9276
ILSQPVGLELANQSSWK	1869.1697	935.5921	1868.9996	1868.9996	1868.9996
FLNQELIDLSAWLAD	1747.0693	583.3637	1746.8828	1746.8828	1746.8828
YSILKRRRKKPNKIEN	1886.2003	629.7407	1886.1215	1886.1215	1886.1215
PGQVVRKTKHELVIAAAN	1930.2273	644.4164	1930.1112	1930.1112	1930.1112

ELPKHAKILVSNNV	1560.9907	781.5026	1560.8988	1560.8988	1560.8988
KSAKIKPTAKKTSTAKPGAQKTT	2386.4814	796.5011	2386.3909	2386.3909	2386.3909
VINKTDKGKYKNKN	1649.0427	825.5286	1648.926	1648.926	1648.926
IQASDLALAETKRML	1659.0127	830.5136	1658.9026	1658.9026	1658.9026
KVRSCGCLRKEKSAE	1693.0703	847.5424	1692.8763	1692.8763	1692.8763
NATKSKSATSRCGAGVSL	1737.0961	869.5553	1736.8839	1736.8839	1736.8839
DIEHSGFDLKGPAYILSL	1974.2517	659.0912	1974.0099	1974.0099	1974.0099
LFDFQLDKRVLVDVKNWR	2290.3838	764.4685	2290.2585	2290.2585	2290.2585
LITKNGIVLSDAATR	1570.9642	786.4894	1570.9043	1570.9043	1570.9043
GTVINYLGVIIIMISI	1605.0161	803.5153	1604.9211	1604.9211	1604.9211
VINKTDKGKYKNKN	1649.0427	825.5286	1648.926	1648.926	1648.926
KLKKVVEDAVDKVLD	1698.0211	850.0178	1697.9927	1697.9927	1697.9927
IISNPVFLPSVRKPSK	1781.119	891.5668	1781.0564	1781.0564	1781.0564
TPKTLTSKEINILLGVV	1825.1456	913.5801	1825.0924	1825.0924	1825.0924
VVAAPANNVFKENQLKK	1869.1697	935.5921	1869.0472	1869.0472	1869.0472
GPKIVVIGGGTGLPVILN	1703.042	568.6879	1703.0345	1703.0345	1703.0345
QYLAGKKSIPVPTERR	1842.1747	615.0655	1842.0476	1842.0476	1842.0476
IIFLAQTYSML	1482.9131	742.4638	1482.8157	1482.8157	1482.8157
IETIRRRGKYLI	1516.9655	759.49	1516.9202	1516.9202	1516.9202
IEQDHRPIKRRN	1560.9907	781.5026	1560.8597	1560.8597	1560.8597
PTKGTLYNGILVAVLG	1614.9893	808.5019	1614.9344	1614.9344	1614.9344
IITKGQKKFEIKN	1659.0127	830.5136	1659.0083	1659.0083	1659.0083
KSFGPYQAPEKQSAR	1693.0703	847.5424	1692.8584	1692.8584	1692.8584
PKVDVRAFIRQKNQ	1698.0231	850.0188	1697.9689	1697.9689	1697.9689
VGFSVAAEIPKNQIHK	1737.0961	869.5553	1736.9574	1736.9574	1736.9574
RGLSAFIKQQLR	1472.9385	737.4765	1472.8575	1472.8575	1472.8575
AVANKELTGAILTLN	1526.9381	764.4763	1526.8668	1526.8668	1526.8668
VPQSLPGSVFAVKKN	1570.9642	786.4894	1570.8719	1570.8719	1570.8719
ELVIHNPDKISRK	1605.0161	803.5153	1604.8998	1604.8998	1604.8998
HILIQPDEIKRCGK	1649.0427	825.5286	1648.9083	1648.9083	1648.9083
VQKAAPVRQASTTNNN	1698.0211	850.0178	1697.8809	1697.8809	1697.8809
VVIAKQIDERSIRR	1781.119	891.5668	1781.0636	1781.0636	1781.0636
KVVVIGDGAVGRCAVIAAK	1825.1456	913.5801	1825.0608	1825.0608	1825.0608
NDVVLQGGKRRWSVVN	1826.1515	914.083	1825.9911	1825.9911	1825.9911
LAPQPKGVTTKILGAKKLSA	2020.2894	674.4371	2020.2408	2020.2408	2020.2408
VVQNNQVGLGLGGGQ	1438.8862	720.4504	1438.7528	1438.7528	1438.7528
TPKNKGR LISAVVT	1482.9131	742.4638	1482.8882	1482.8882	1482.8882
KGFNKEIKKLAKN	1516.9655	759.49	1516.9089	1516.9089	1516.9089
SDKKLADLVKDATAS	1560.9907	781.5026	1560.8359	1560.8359	1560.8359
FHRIVMAVLLGVVI	1565.9442	783.9794	1565.948	1565.948	1565.948
NLSLAKSLSKLTVGSH	1653.999	828.0068	1653.9414	1653.9414	1653.9414
AEKEIKIWFPERN	1659.0127	830.5136	1658.8781	1658.8781	1658.8781
TPKGVYHLSFAFGKAA	1693.0703	847.5424	1692.8988	1692.8988	1692.8988
IRTKPGVGPIRELKSS	1737.0961	869.5553	1737.0261	1737.0261	1737.0261
IFFIHSQSALVVSFILVG	1976.2635	659.7618	1976.1135	1976.1135	1976.1135
IEKQASLISGWPSKVEKN	2013.2385	672.0868	2013.0895	2013.0895	2013.0895
KNQKLKILRCSKHRLSI	2064.3184	689.1134	2064.2466	2064.2466	2064.2466

FVVIFLSAYAAQGPMQALVK	2152.3657	718.4625	2152.1755	2152.1755	2152.1755
QSLFAALQRKKAL	1472.9385	737.4765	1472.8827	1472.8827	1472.8827
NKNGAKGIQRLKSN	1526.9381	764.4763	1526.8641	1526.8641	1526.8641
EIKAQPPGKKLQRL	1605.0161	803.5153	1604.9727	1604.9727	1604.9727
SQSRPKSTKFNKKN	1649.0427	825.5286	1648.9009	1648.9009	1648.9009
KGTLLENLQKRLKEVES	1871.1876	936.6011	1871.0476	1871.0476	1871.0476
KNLKPKLLEILENQN	1793.1084	598.7101	1793.0411	1793.0411	1793.0411
ERGAAKLYEFVNERR	1837.1365	613.3861	1836.9595	1836.9595	1836.9595
GLVLIVRHHNRKKRR	1881.1605	628.0608	1881.1761	1881.1761	1881.1761
NFIDAQIQLWLASKAGGG	1888.2136	630.4118	1887.9843	1887.9843	1887.9843
KYLLTQGHLPAGDSIIS	1925.1877	642.7365	1925.0623	1925.0623	1925.0623
EIKGAPMKRAIAFTDTIA	1932.2389	645.0869	1932.0503	1932.0503	1932.0503
IYAKSKLAQESLTKAKEI	2020.2894	674.4371	2020.1569	2020.1569	2020.1569
INIKYKGVVKKRLS	1516.9655	759.49	1516.9453	1516.9453	1516.9453
GPYADPKNGVKKVKKAL	1783.1361	892.5753	1783.0356	1783.0356	1783.0356
EIKHAKQIREEFWN	1827.16	914.5873	1826.9427	1826.9427	1826.9427
TTAPPFNLPRILKKAGN	1837.1365	613.3861	1837.0574	1837.0574	1837.0574
THSKANRGRKFVDVET	1844.1871	615.7363	1843.9653	1843.9653	1843.9653
AVRGKGGQIISQKGATFYG	1937.1943	646.7387	1937.0483	1937.0483	1937.0483
HGNGPQVGQINLGMNYAAE	1969.213	657.4116	1968.9113	1968.9113	1968.9113
VVQVKARKYKGLKFIEA	1976.2635	659.7618	1976.1935	1976.1935	1976.1935
RNKCRMGGKKKSHKN	1739.1099	870.5622	1739.0214	1739.0214	1739.0214
KNKVVRVLERKPFMQ	1871.1876	936.6011	1871.0928	1871.0928	1871.0928
IIVSTVVQSRLWALAM	1915.2111	958.6128	1915.0964	1915.0964	1915.0964
RVIYLNKMKRR	1959.2383	980.6264	1959.204	1959.204	1959.204
GKLVCIILPNKGAYATTLE	2003.2595	1002.637	2003.1125	2003.1125	2003.1125
IEELSRGNAYSILKR	1749.084	584.0353	1748.9421	1748.9421	1748.9421
LMLTPKVMHNGRKLKLR	1793.1084	598.7101	1793.0281	1793.0281	1793.0281
GLVLIVRHHNRKKRR	1881.1605	628.0608	1881.1761	1881.1761	1881.1761
TASTIVWRSQHRKNQCN	1925.1877	642.7365	1924.998	1924.998	1924.998
QPTVKLTRQGEYIVFGP	1932.2389	645.0869	1932.0469	1932.0469	1932.0469
IEKKETPNKYPRKPGT	2013.2385	672.0868	2013.1371	2013.1371	2013.1371
DLIAVLVIALVSLLS	1651.0544	826.5345	1651.0536	1651.0536	1651.0536
VHKWIQQOAKTQSGK	1695.0833	848.5489	1694.9216	1694.9216	1694.9216
IEKAILASDLGISPANDG	1783.1361	892.5753	1782.9364	1782.9364	1782.9364
PKGVTIGFLPVTFKPLN	1827.16	914.5873	1827.0658	1827.0658	1827.0658
GPQKGIKVVYKQKAM	1837.1365	613.3861	1837.0284	1837.0284	1837.0284
LGPQPKQALTTFLAIAER	1898.1871	633.7363	1898.0625	1898.0625	1898.0625
LAANIEQTGNLVENLEKN	1969.213	657.4116	1969.0116	1969.0116	1969.0116
LEKQMIKLNESLR	1617.0034	809.509	1616.892	1616.892	1616.892
NKKAQEFDRVRSR	1661.0297	831.5221	1660.9009	1660.9009	1660.9009
QGPLTFKQLFSRQR	1705.0581	853.5363	1704.9424	1704.9424	1704.9424
RMSIGVVYKTKKDS	1739.1099	870.5622	1738.9763	1738.9763	1738.9763
RPAITLLTKEGKNNQ	1783.1361	892.5753	1782.9952	1782.9952	1782.9952
IEKANKLANVNLFIGD	1871.1876	936.6011	1871.0516	1871.0516	1871.0516
VVKLDAYGDTLRGFSF	1915.2111	958.6128	1915.0204	1915.0204	1915.0204
ELNIKLLDTHNKRR	1749.084	584.0353	1749.001	1749.001	1749.001

GPKVHQFEVIRWIAN	1793.1084	598.7101	1792.9736	1792.9736	1792.9736
YGKTEALHGINLNLPKN	1881.1605	628.0608	1881.0109	1881.0109	1881.0109
FLNKEVPAVPLSERITL	1925.1877	642.7365	1925.0986	1925.0986	1925.0986
VVQEFLGREPMIR	1572.9783	787.4964	1572.8446	1572.8446	1572.8446
LVAIVVVPMMNIKRTV	1651.0544	826.5345	1651.0219	1651.0219	1651.0219
VVDGVKKGLLGAIPSD	1695.0833	848.5489	1694.993	1694.993	1694.993
LEDLGRRLKLERR	1766.1096	884.0621	1766.0638	1766.0638	1766.0638
CARKSLERLIGHKLG	1827.16	914.5873	1827.0302	1827.0302	1827.0302
RQQLLGQHRELAALRGN	1959.2383	980.6264	1959.0875	1959.0875	1959.0875
LGTAFAPVVYVENENQSA	1837.1365	613.3861	1836.8894	1836.8894	1836.8894
FALNSNKPLAEKIAKAVGV	1969.213	657.4116	1969.136	1969.136	1969.136
TPKQVERSRSKSLT	1528.9514	765.483	1528.8685	1528.8685	1528.8685
GKVLQHPPELLAKGGGN	1617.0034	809.509	1616.8998	1616.8998	1616.8998
ARKTPAQRHLHKLW	1661.0297	831.5221	1660.9637	1660.9637	1660.9637
LFDQNLKRTSISRK	1705.0581	853.5363	1704.9635	1704.9635	1704.9635
FVGNVVVKLIKPNRR	1739.1099	870.5622	1739.057	1739.057	1739.057
AIGTTVLALLMGSVKRP	1783.1361	892.5753	1783.0389	1783.0389	1783.0389
KAVLKAEVPSNFEAKIK	1871.1876	936.6011	1871.088	1871.088	1871.088
KELFITQPAVSQVKS	1915.2111	958.6128	1915.0779	1915.0779	1915.0779
VVKKPVPSLAFGLTI	1881.1605	628.0608	1881.1451	1881.1451	1881.1451
PGKALSGFAKKTLLK	1572.9783	787.4964	1572.9716	1572.9716	1572.9716
KREFRVIGDALAFL	1634.0313	818.0229	1633.9304	1633.9304	1633.9304
QVLGVVTQPDRKVGR	1651.0544	826.5345	1650.9529	1650.9529	1650.9529
GVKLVQNQLVTTVPSI	1695.0833	848.5489	1694.993	1694.993	1694.993
IEYGKNVRSQLFIR	1722.0823	862.0484	1721.9576	1721.9576	1721.9576
NAPGHLQRLLGKII	1749.0817	875.5481	1749.005	1749.005	1749.005
TGKAVVQAGAPLDAL	1766.1096	884.0621	1765.9574	1765.9574	1765.9574
KFVKKAIKSSITEDSI	1793.1064	897.5605	1793.0299	1793.0299	1793.0299
SKAMGLVLINKNALDKI	1827.16	914.5873	1827.0652	1827.0652	1827.0652
AKSASNKSSKAVQTTTT	1837.1365	613.3861	1836.9905	1836.9905	1836.9905
VGSKSRKRVLQDL	1484.9259	743.4702	1484.8787	1484.8787	1484.8787
NKIVPNAGIDFKTI	1528.9514	765.483	1528.8613	1528.8613	1528.8613
GPVLRVRAVSNKRR	1607.0316	804.5231	1606.9856	1606.9856	1606.9856
GKGFTTIRKGLKRR	1617.0034	809.509	1616.9951	1616.9951	1616.9951
TANKQKALALFTNLK	1661.0297	831.5221	1660.9512	1660.9512	1660.9512
PNPTPTAVKSVKLLA	1678.0579	840.0362	1678.0142	1678.0142	1678.0142
YGVIAIIIAAGAKIGY	1705.0581	853.5363	1705.0178	1705.0178	1705.0178
RGKILPRRVSGTSAKN	1739.1099	870.5622	1739.0278	1739.0278	1739.0278
SLIGPYLNGTAKLIARP	1783.1361	892.5753	1783.0356	1783.0356	1783.0356
VVTTKHSINSPVVG	1793.1084	598.7101	1792.9795	1792.9795	1792.9795
NKALNLGMKGLGIL	1440.9009	721.4577	1440.8486	1440.8486	1440.8486
FLNKRLDSIKQAN	1545.9767	773.9956	1545.8627	1545.8627	1545.8627
KASKSLVIYISYTT	1572.9783	787.4964	1572.8763	1572.8763	1572.8763
LETYNGAAKLAQRR	1590.0051	796.0098	1589.8638	1589.8638	1589.8638
VLPVGVLIARQQRR	1634.0313	818.0229	1634.0104	1634.0104	1634.0104
EELLARIRVIQRR	1651.0544	826.5345	1651.0006	1651.0006	1651.0006
VVKPTNNGKTYTFNL	1695.0833	848.5489	1694.8992	1694.8992	1694.8992

GPEGILVPNNKTKRSL	1722.0823	862.0484	1721.9788	1721.9788	1721.9788
VGVAVVNPQAAVWKAAVA	1749.0817	875.5481	1748.9938	1748.9938	1748.9938
QNVLKRSIKELSA	1484.9259	743.4702	1484.8674	1484.8674	1484.8674
GIVGVKPTYGRISR	1501.9539	751.9842	1501.8729	1501.8729	1501.8729
LTFNSLQRTKRR	1518.9777	760.4961	1518.8743	1518.8743	1518.8743
EKLLDEDAIKNQN	1528.9514	765.483	1528.7733	1528.7733	1528.7733
HQLNTMGIPKPTN	1563.0033	782.5089	1562.8239	1562.8239	1562.8239
FARLSSVKRSISTR	1607.0316	804.5231	1606.9268	1606.9268	1606.9268
ARVQQRRLFFALL	1617.0034	809.509	1616.9628	1616.9628	1616.9628
VVGAESKKGIARRFGS	1661.0297	831.5221	1660.9373	1660.9373	1660.9373
GNPLILNRKLPNSSR	1678.0579	840.0362	1677.9639	1677.9639	1677.9639
RKLMILRASLGMAFV	1705.0581	853.5363	1704.9895	1704.9895	1704.9895
GQRQRSLIKRR	1396.8745	699.4445	1396.8488	1396.8488	1396.8488
PPITNFAKIVRAN	1440.9011	721.4578	1440.8088	1440.8088	1440.8088
ELTIVFGRTKRR	1474.9536	738.4841	1474.8733	1474.8733	1474.8733
VVGPRGHSAVLLTL	1545.9767	773.9956	1545.9355	1545.9355	1545.9355
RTRARGNFRKRR	1572.9783	787.4964	1572.9298	1572.9298	1572.9298
TPSRKDVYLAKLTV	1590.0051	796.0098	1589.9141	1589.9141	1589.9141
YTMILVPLASLEATL	1634.0313	818.0229	1633.9	1633.9	1633.9
NEIDLKPNKPNQKN	1651.0544	826.5345	1650.8689	1650.8689	1650.8689
EIQSRFSERFRKL	1695.0833	848.5489	1694.9216	1694.9216	1694.9216
KKYKAELFWKNVV	1739.1099	870.5622	1738.9771	1738.9771	1738.9771
SQKANLSVGDCKIA	1457.9281	729.9713	1457.8202	1457.8202	1457.8202
GVVAGVTLNKSQAQN	1484.9259	743.4702	1484.8311	1484.8311	1484.8311
HKKPPKPOQSKRR	1501.9539	751.9842	1501.8954	1501.8954	1501.8954
TSLSSKRRIDIML	1518.9777	760.4961	1518.8552	1518.8552	1518.8552
NLTVVKTNLKNQAS	1528.9514	765.483	1528.8573	1528.8573	1528.8573
ALDKAIQYMAKRR	1563.0033	782.5089	1562.8715	1562.8715	1562.8715
GPVLRVRAVSNKRR	1607.0316	804.5231	1606.9856	1606.9856	1606.9856
GKGFTTIRKGLKRR	1617.0034	809.509	1616.9951	1616.9951	1616.9951
NKLLVRSYLRSLSL	1661.0297	831.5221	1660.9988	1660.9988	1660.9988
TPKIGRHLLANIIFL	1705.0581	853.5363	1705.0403	1705.0403	1705.0403
GLIANAGLKGKNPT	1352.8497	677.4321	1352.7776	1352.7776	1352.7776
LLGVRNQNELIE	1396.8745	699.4445	1396.7675	1396.7675	1396.7675
EIAGLSKVDARKK	1413.9003	707.9574	1413.8303	1413.8303	1413.8303
KLIYQTLKQVR	1430.9272	716.4709	1430.8973	1430.8973	1430.8973
VGILRTNKGQLSR	1440.9011	721.4578	1440.8525	1440.8525	1440.8525
KNLKKQEMVNFV	1474.9536	738.4841	1474.7966	1474.7966	1474.7966
PLLGAILKLLTSKGT	1523.9347	762.9746	1523.9651	1523.9651	1523.9651
LSKRMRALENELN	1572.9783	787.4964	1572.8406	1572.8406	1572.8406
KELPKHAKILVSNN	1590.0051	796.0098	1589.9253	1589.9253	1589.9253
SIINWLPQKLKRR	1651.0544	826.5345	1651.0046	1651.0046	1651.0046
TPNYIIRARKR	1386.8993	694.4569	1386.8208	1386.8208	1386.8208
KIAVINGVIGATFV	1457.9281	729.9713	1457.8606	1457.8606	1457.8606
NLVGSLIGNMIKIN	1484.9259	743.4702	1484.8385	1484.8385	1484.8385
GAVVMLDNRIMKR	1501.9539	751.9842	1501.8221	1501.8221	1501.8221
PGKYKSVSGIKNIE	1518.9777	760.4961	1518.8406	1518.8406	1518.8406

NLTVVKTNLKNOAS	1528.9514	765.483	1528.8573	1528.8573	1528.8573
FLNKRLDSIQAN	1545.9767	773.9956	1545.8627	1545.8627	1545.8627
QIAVVKVDPTLKPR	1563.0033	782.5089	1562.9508	1562.9508	1562.9508
YLIVARISQSNFAS	1567.9585	784.9865	1567.8358	1567.8358	1567.8358
GPVLRVRAVSNKRR	1607.0316	804.5231	1606.9856	1606.9856	1606.9856
VASIDTLVSAK	1102.7208	552.3677	1102.6234	1102.6234	1102.6234
KATKIAAAMSR	1146.7467	574.3806	1146.6543	1146.6543	1146.6543
LNVIELEKPVGV	1308.8225	655.4185	1308.7653	1308.7653	1308.7653
TLNTIKNVKVGR	1342.8752	672.4449	1342.7932	1342.7932	1342.7932
RRRLLKRRTV	1352.8497	677.4321	1352.8953	1352.8953	1352.8953
TAKLTSPSRQVPI	1396.8745	699.4445	1396.8038	1396.8038	1396.8038
TDVPLGRLSTVVAS	1413.9003	707.9574	1413.7827	1413.7827	1413.7827
GVQFSAGKIIQKR	1430.9272	716.4709	1430.8358	1430.8358	1430.8358
ASKVPAFKPGKALK	1440.9011	721.4578	1440.8817	1440.8817	1440.8817
KAMTSRQGAKNKR	1474.9536	738.4841	1474.8151	1474.8151	1474.8151
ILGTAKTLGAA	1014.6709	508.3427	1014.6074	1014.6074	1014.6074
GETKLELNR	1058.6967	530.3556	1058.572	1058.572	1058.572
GYKKVVKEN	1063.6519	532.8332	1063.6025	1063.6025	1063.6025
VRELARGAHV	1106.7518	554.3832	1106.6309	1106.6309	1106.6309
LMIIIALFSM	1150.7781	576.3963	1150.6494	1150.6494	1150.6494
SEKKMQKSL	1190.7719	596.3932	1190.6693	1190.6693	1190.6693
FINQTLKPVK	1386.8993	694.4569	1386.8235	1386.8235	1386.8235
VGSKSRKRVLQDL	1484.9259	743.4702	1484.8787	1484.8787	1484.8787
YPNKKKLLKLATC	1518.9777	760.4961	1518.8956	1518.8956	1518.8956
RAIKLRQN	0	998.6501	997.6145	997.6145	997.6145
VLPIALGLAH	1018.7015	510.358	1018.6175	1018.6175	1018.6175
IRAAKIGYK	1018.7015	510.358	1018.6287	1018.6287	1018.6287
ILPVVEQSSA	1041.6685	521.8415	1041.5707	1041.5707	1041.5707
IPKWKAHIA	1062.7261	532.3703	1062.6338	1062.6338	1062.6338
IEGSRGRRR	1085.6953	543.8549	1085.6166	1085.6166	1085.6166
ALRPNAAPF	1102.7208	552.3677	1102.5924	1102.5924	1102.5924
GFGSAPGAQVVTG	1146.7467	574.3806	1146.5669	1146.5669	1146.5669
KNKKNKSIKK	1342.8752	672.4449	1342.8772	1342.8772	1342.8772
QNDKIQPEPKTQRNK	1823.1259	912.5702	1822.965	1822.965	1822.965
SEDLILIKAPSLARAIALRQKQGGSL	0	954.6264	2860.6863	2860.6863	2860.6863
LVVITGLSGSG	1001.6739	501.8442	1001.5757	1001.5757	1001.5757
KGDKAISALI	1014.6709	508.3427	1014.6074	1014.6074	1014.6074
FIILDVFAS	1023.6572	512.8359	1023.5641	1023.5641	1023.5641
GKLICVIAVGS	1058.6967	530.3556	1058.6158	1058.6158	1058.6158
IPVTLVIGIGS	1067.6826	534.8486	1067.6591	1067.6591	1067.6591
PGQKHKQER	1106.7518	554.3832	1106.5945	1106.5945	1106.5945
GPKAGNPKRIN	1150.7781	576.3963	1150.6571	1150.6571	1150.6571
HQTSLVVTDIRKPQN	1735.0801	868.5473	1734.9376	1734.9376	1734.9376
LFKIRSDLINAVIVALM	1915.2111	958.6128	1915.1329	1915.1329	1915.1329
TPATAAKKKTVYYNQLAK	0	998.6507	1995.1154	1995.1154	1995.1154
VHIAIGIRP	974.6775	488.346	974.6025	974.6025	974.6025
HGRKVLTLGL	979.6319	490.8232	979.5927	979.5927	979.5927

FAILAGLLTT	1018.7015	510.358	1018.6063	1018.6063	1018.6063
LAIHMLFL	1045.6982	523.8564	1045.661	1045.661	1045.661
AFPLAVSLFV	1062.7261	532.3703	1062.6113	1062.6113	1062.6113
TGNRRELYIQRNK	1647.0289	824.5217	1646.8965	1646.8965	1646.8965
VSAANQVLAKGSGHKKAA	1823.1255	912.57	1823.0013	1823.0013	1823.0013
VGNVYQPVKVKLQLAGN	1826.1522	914.0834	1826.0414	1826.0414	1826.0414
GDVCLKHVEMIKKKRN	0	954.6269	1907.1139	1907.1139	1907.1139
FLKASNPLL	1001.6739	501.8442	1001.5909	1001.5909	1001.5909
KITLIWQN	1014.6709	508.3427	1014.5862	1014.5862	1014.5862
GMRFRNIM	1023.6572	512.8359	1023.5106	1023.5106	1023.5106
ILTDIAAKIPAGADGLL	1651.0544	826.5345	1650.9556	1650.9556	1650.9556
ALIPNKLNI TLKQAAQ	1735.0807	868.5476	1735.0356	1735.0356	1735.0356
RNKKRMGKKKSHKN	1739.1046	870.5596	1739.0214	1739.0214	1739.0214
KNVYNVTVL RLGKASN	1749.0801	875.5473	1748.9534	1748.9534	1748.9534
GRKTVLVF	0	919.5868	918.5651	918.5651	918.5651
WKLLPPLLGFIVAI	1917.2339	959.6242	1917.2219	1917.2219	1917.2219
NVPGAKKSY	0	963.6091	962.5186	962.5186	962.5186
TAAPADVLFA	974.6775	488.346	974.5073	974.5073	974.5073
LRQQFAMS	979.6319	490.8232	979.4909	979.4909	979.4909
LLASAVMLAM	1018.7015	510.358	1018.5555	1018.5555	1018.5555
GIIFLIGSM	1062.7261	532.3703	1062.6147	1062.6147	1062.6147
TKTSIFLKAAIEKN	1563.0033	782.5089	1562.9032	1562.9032	1562.9032
ALRSGITKYLKQNR	1647.0289	824.5217	1646.958	1646.958	1646.958
RAPRAAHKIFLERV	1663.0459	832.5302	1662.9794	1662.9794	1662.9794
AESRAQIKYDLGAKKAA	0	910.5988	1818.9952	1818.9952	1818.9952
KNKKMRKKKNKKNR	1829.1766	915.5956	1829.1257	1829.1257	1829.1257
QNKLYKSASE	1166.7747	584.3946	1166.5931	1166.5931	1166.5931
QNPKAKLAALGT	1210.7997	606.4071	1210.7034	1210.7034	1210.7034
VWGDNP LLRW N	1368.8918	685.4532	1368.6938	1368.6938	1368.6938
ATLTLKRKILEQ	1412.9172	707.4659	1412.8715	1412.8715	1412.8715
IQKHNGLLDLVRIG	1574.9939	788.5042	1574.9257	1574.9257	1574.9257
KLAEKQGANLKKPVK	1651.0544	826.5345	1651.0145	1651.0145	1651.0145
ADFVAEKKGKIFLRN	1735.0841	868.5493	1734.9781	1734.9781	1734.9781
GIAWKWKLSVRQNR	1741.1271	871.5708	1740.99	1740.99	1740.99
LTINLGLFALFIGILM	1748.097	875.0558	1748.031	1748.031	1748.031
ASQLPLPVIVHVFKNK	1917.2339	959.6242	1917.1564	1917.1564	1917.1564
RLGRILGPKN	1122.7477	562.3811	1122.6986	1122.6986	1122.6986
DLLIPDLQLKN	1280.8427	641.4286	1280.734	1280.734	1280.734
KNKVVKIKVRN	1324.8673	663.4409	1324.8667	1324.8667	1324.8667
SLPPIKGVNHARV	1386.8993	694.4569	1386.8096	1386.8096	1386.8096
IPVTGGAIKYLEAS	1417.8718	709.9432	1417.7817	1417.7817	1417.7817
KL TNK KLGTVELN	1456.9448	729.4797	1456.8613	1456.8613	1456.8613
YVKKEEIPKTLK	1474.9536	738.4841	1474.876	1474.876	1474.876
VIGIVGIIRLSLPLT	1563.0043	782.5094	1563.0123	1563.0123	1563.0123
ILPLILLGGLNLSATR	1663.0459	832.5302	1663.0397	1663.0397	1663.0397
VVALLSLMALGIVSLLTT	1829.1766	915.5956	1829.0947	1829.0947	1829.0947
VVSRLYGKTG	1078.723	540.3688	1078.6135	1078.6135	1078.6135

ESLKEKYPSL	1192.7906	597.4026	1192.6339	1192.6339	1192.6339
LFAKFIEKN	1236.8157	619.4151	1236.723	1236.723	1236.723
GLTPSAVAILFVV	1285.7955	643.905	1285.7645	1285.7645	1285.7645
PPIEDRIARLE	1307.8411	654.9278	1307.7197	1307.7197	1307.7197
VILRPVVTESSM	1329.8231	665.9188	1329.7327	1329.7327	1329.7327
KQERLLSGKLT	1368.8918	685.4532	1368.8088	1368.8088	1368.8088
GANVKLNKIELKS	1412.9172	707.4659	1412.8351	1412.8351	1412.8351
TGKISGAVIQLVNLAIG	1653.0725	827.5435	1652.9825	1652.9825	1652.9825
LNVRIKNLKSLEDTV	1741.1271	871.5708	1741.0098	1741.0098	1741.0098
APIAKNPSSQH	1148.7649	575.3897	1148.5939	1148.5939	1148.5939
QFAKIVAGGKAS	1175.7637	588.8891	1175.6663	1175.6663	1175.6663
FLKGEVAEITN	1219.7909	610.9027	1219.6449	1219.6449	1219.6449
PILLIMAVSQAS	1241.7689	621.8917	1241.7053	1241.7053	1241.7053
TPQNTLLKPVPG	1263.8148	632.9147	1263.7186	1263.7186	1263.7186
GSIRIGRGVVNPG	1280.8427	641.4286	1280.7313	1280.7313	1280.7313
TKGARVPPNSVVT	1324.8673	663.4409	1324.7463	1324.7463	1324.7463
STKKATPKIKASK	1386.8994	694.457	1386.8558	1386.8558	1386.8558
LLDPVAKVEIHNK	1474.9536	738.4841	1474.8507	1474.8507	1474.8507
HRLLYVIVAFFSV	1563.0043	782.5094	1562.8973	1562.8973	1562.8973
FLDVITNGAR	1104.739	553.3768	1104.5928	1104.5928	1104.5928
KGEVIKESD	1131.7379	566.8762	1131.6135	1131.6135	1131.6135
TAKRSMSQFV	1153.7177	577.8661	1153.5914	1153.5914	1153.5914
PTKVYIGLRI	1158.7374	580.376	1158.7125	1158.7125	1158.7125
KTIRVPKVR	1192.7906	597.4026	1192.7769	1192.7769	1192.7769
VSHLQSKKSKG	1197.7439	599.8792	1197.683	1197.683	1197.683
AGNKAKKLFQAV	1202.7665	602.3905	1202.7135	1202.7135	1202.7135
SLKRWASSKY	1224.7446	613.3796	1224.6615	1224.6615	1224.6615
VVKKAPIIEQI	1236.8157	619.4151	1236.7805	1236.7805	1236.7805
KVVAQAGRKKT	1285.7955	643.905	1285.783	1285.783	1285.783
LTLIKKRCN	1087.7126	544.8636	1087.6536	1087.6536	1087.6536
AKQKVKFVY	1109.6932	555.8539	1109.6597	1109.6597	1109.6597
QSKFIVVALQ	1114.713	558.3638	1114.6387	1114.6387	1114.6387
TALKKQSESTG	1148.7649	575.3897	1148.6038	1148.6038	1148.6038
AVRIFGLKDAS	1175.7637	588.8891	1175.6663	1175.6663	1175.6663
YGQEILKLE	1219.7909	610.9027	1219.6813	1219.6813	1219.6813
NAPIGRSKKDR	1240.843	621.4288	1240.7001	1240.7001	1240.7001
NKKLRTSPWI	1241.7689	621.8917	1241.7245	1241.7245	1241.7245
ITKCDYVVVKN	1280.8427	641.4286	1280.6798	1280.6798	1280.6798
EPGLKQALALVF	1284.8717	643.4431	1284.7441	1284.7441	1284.7441
IEKAALSQSD	1060.712	531.3633	1060.54	1060.54	1060.54
VVKKYGSKY	1070.6879	536.3512	1070.6124	1070.6124	1070.6124
TAASKTIQAS	1104.739	553.3768	1104.6139	1104.6139	1104.6139
PGELVPVDGHL	1131.7379	566.8762	1131.5924	1131.5924	1131.5924
RPIIQVKVDS	1153.7177	577.8661	1153.6819	1153.6819	1153.6819
GLSNLNANHKL	1179.7935	590.904	1179.636	1179.636	1179.636
GYKVDVGKLS	1192.7906	597.4026	1192.6451	1192.6451	1192.6451
ATVAHQTAQALS	1196.8197	599.4171	1196.615	1196.615	1196.615

NDNQNNNQNDNHQNDNQNNQNF0		1044.6899	4174.606	4174.606	4174.606
DGRTLAVQAS	1016.683	509.3488	1016.5251	1016.5251	1016.5251
EPLTKVVKN	1026.6593	514.3369	1026.6073	1026.6073	1026.6073
IAAAMSRGKAL	1087.7126	544.8636	1087.6172	1087.6172	1087.6172
SGHAKVPAKV	1091.7418	546.8782	1091.6451	1091.6451	1091.6451
LPKYSEILF	1108.7689	555.3917	1108.6168	1108.6168	1108.6168
PPLVPIRFR	1109.6932	555.8539	1109.6709	1109.6709	1109.6709
VVKAGLKVPL	1135.7675	568.891	1135.7693	1135.7693	1135.7693
HNIELKPGKGG	1148.7649	575.3897	1148.6302	1148.6302	1148.6302
SAAIPPASAQQL	1152.7925	577.4035	1152.6139	1152.6139	1152.6139
AENRNQTGFKPITDVLTSMEIEDRLY0		1000.668	3998.8804	3998.8804	3998.8804
YGQILGVRGV	1060.712	531.3633	1060.6029	1060.6029	1060.6029
ALNAGHTVLGI	1064.7439	533.3792	1064.5979	1064.5979	1064.5979
KNKKMAVSSL	1104.739	553.3768	1104.6326	1104.6326	1104.6326
PLAKAGNNK	0	912.6156	911.5189	911.5189	911.5189
VKNFIAVLAIVMVIVALV	0	956.6437	1911.1995	1911.1995	1911.1995
GPKSKIQLL	0	983.6434	982.6175	982.6175	982.6175
VPLGANLAEIYTLGFGESFSASVFADYI0		1004.698	4014.9316	4014.9316	4014.9316
DKIIVTGGNK	0	1044.694	1043.5975	1043.5975	1043.5975
GGNRNRNNSHNGRGGYSHNGRNI0		1048.724	4190.9746	4190.9746	4190.9746
VLLAPNIKPG	1020.7175	511.366	1020.6332	1020.6332	1020.6332
IRGNKVLHR	1091.7418	546.8782	1091.6676	1091.6676	1091.6676
ALPVLNGIILS	1108.7689	555.3917	1108.6855	1108.6855	1108.6855
LCILKIQSLIPIFQ	1741.1271	871.5708	1741.0576	1741.0576	1741.0576
YLSRTKK	0	895.5883	894.5287	894.5287	894.5287
GALFLRRLAANNKIPGPINLKIAAITA0		939.6172	2815.6912	2815.6912	2815.6912
QPDVAVQGGLYLAIGCSLFSVNDNREY0		960.6737	3838.7996	3838.7996	3838.7996
KIAASKAALK	0	1000.669	999.644	999.644	999.644
VPLSPWLTP	0	1009.655	1008.5644	1008.5644	1008.5644
VVKRKFVKATENAMKAATN	0	1053.681	2105.178	2105.178	2105.178
DAHLSKNQN	1025.6729	513.8437	1025.489	1025.489	1025.489
NLADGHPRVS	1064.7439	533.3792	1064.5363	1064.5363	1064.5363
VKHRRR	0	851.5628	850.5362	850.5362	850.5362
SKAQQPTSNSAQSYNQSSSYTVQQ0		912.6172	3646.6731	3646.6731	3646.6731
PIVLALYK	0	916.649	915.5793	915.5793	915.5793
KNNRIAKL	0	956.6396	955.5927	955.5927	955.5927
KLTPAQSKNAKKNELFL	0	965.6287	1929.1047	1929.1047	1929.1047
PLVMLLQMIDSDRVIFSESGVREGIISIF0		1004.701	4015.0911	4015.0911	4015.0911
KGSSNTARSSSSSNVKITNSDISNLQD0		1048.724	4191.0527	4191.0527	4191.0527
AVQAGHAINP	976.6927	489.3536	976.509	976.509	976.509
TATTSTLL	0	807.5366	806.4385	806.4385	806.4385
ELGYNRAAKLLNSAK	0	824.5657	1646.9104	1646.9104	1646.9104
KSIRKLGIVRENNK	1741.1271	871.5708	1741.0322	1741.0322	1741.0322
FNVSRVIGGLSAAALFVPTSMALAADV0		872.6234	3486.877	3486.877	3486.877
EIIAALAQKRIQFRAPAPTRSRSRQLIR0		877.5756	3506.0586	3506.0586	3506.0586
LLSIVLFIGLVLKEKI	0	899.6227	1797.1743	1797.1743	1797.1743
LVFAILAGLLSFFITSPSSFFLYLNRKTLS0		921.604	3682.0037	3682.0037	3682.0037

GMILYTHQYGIVDYMKGAVSSFIVS\0		943.6473	3770.884	3770.884	3770.884
LIGKAFDESTMYRAGYAFEQATQVYK0		960.6765	3838.8989	3838.8989	3838.8989
NLVGPDAVVALGG	1180.7173	591.3659	1180.6451	1180.6451	1180.6451
IPLLNVIGLNLSLF	0	763.5106	1524.928	1524.928	1524.928
PYQHPEKLIPKVI	1561.0715	781.543	1560.9028	1560.9028	1560.9028
KGQRDMLDYNNSLEGDIDENSHNK0		828.5971	3310.5273	3310.5273	3310.5273
RFRLEKNNKNYAKFGIRRTS	0	833.5503	2497.3779	2497.3779	2497.3779
LTKALKVTYKGTTKSA	0	855.597	1709.0087	1709.0087	1709.0087
PIVLALYK	0	916.65	915.5793	915.5793	915.5793
AAKRRKYT	0	965.6271	964.5818	964.5818	964.5818
GMGIGYTTGGDFTFPDLTTATSEALGD0		740.5419	2958.2939	2958.2939	2958.2939
SSEDDDDSTDTTSSNNDTTSSNTA	0	784.5725	2350.864	2350.864	2350.864
ELTKTKEIQVYVNRKVMITAT	0	789.5253	2365.304	2365.304	2365.304
VVPAIAKKVVKPTNNGKTYTFNLRHN0		824.5637	3293.8513	3293.8513	3293.8513
SSSAQSATTSSTASSTAASSATTTTSC0		872.6246	3486.5564	3486.5564	3486.5564
VPLWRLNKRQKGQM	0	877.5785	1752.9934	1752.9934	1752.9934
DPIAALINAFVAGMDYYQESEDQQH\0		899.6202	3594.5774	3594.5774	3594.5774
KNEDAVLAAKTSVIPKS	0	921.6048	1841.0259	1841.0259	1841.0259
TMGLDVDDDWPFIGDHRIAGLLTGG0		960.6719	3838.8586	3838.8586	3838.8586
STSSNYNDPNNQATPTPTTPSTGTGA0		696.5155	2782.2166	2782.2166	2782.2166
GAFVRSKLKRLRT	0	745.4997	1488.8889	1488.8889	1488.8889
LPVMKQL	0	828.5982	827.4939	827.4939	827.4939
NRTFLKPRVRKLQQLPQYDLAQIDNI\0		833.5529	3329.8362	3329.8362	3329.8362
ARFIKEWTKIAIMITPNIKYK	0	855.5931	2563.4712	2563.4712	2563.4712
VRPAFTMGGTGGGIAETPQQLHDITE0		916.6469	3662.8362	3662.8362	3662.8362
KALGYK	0	679.4926	678.4064	678.4064	678.4064
IPLLSYIFLAIHAPIAGIGF	0	701.4733	2101.259	2101.259	2101.259
LPVAKVN	0	740.5463	739.4592	739.4592	739.4592
EDRQVLKEGTVDYIGFSYNSNTVAA\0		767.5448	3066.457	3066.457	3066.457
VPLLKSK	0	784.5726	783.5219	783.5219	783.5219
AKLPPKGN	0	824.5637	823.4916	823.4916	823.4916
YNEIAPVSISSDDDFRKLKLSQISDSLSV0		872.6213	3486.7407	3486.7407	3486.7407
PGRTYRK	0	877.5753	876.493	876.493	876.493
SSKSSSDKLQTASEGSGVIYKKS	0	608.4658	2430.2239	2430.2239	2430.2239
KLLLYKDSYK	1269.7994	635.907	1269.7333	1269.7333	1269.7333
KITAEIKRKN	0	657.4475	1312.8191	1312.8191	1312.8191
PIGTLREVSQAVDDVTAVVEEKDAN0		696.5209	2782.4348	2782.4348	2782.4348
GSKSVTRKFRRLLADDLSENKRVVTK	0	723.5183	2889.626	2889.626	2889.626
GKIIGVWNAMVKR	0	736.514	1470.8494	1470.8494	1470.8494
ILMARKVPGSIFIGLVATALLGLITGLIK0		745.501	2977.8494	2977.8494	2977.8494
GGDDANVAVSAAQVKTGDTANSPFI0		828.5963	3310.4609	3310.4609	3310.4609
KHGQRAH	0	833.5487	832.4416	832.4416	832.4416
NQSIRLQRIV	1225.7721	613.8933	1225.7255	1225.7255	1225.7255
NGQGDGSVDLTQGNNGGANSSNC0		652.4948	2606.0825	2606.0825	2606.0825
KEMSVTYAPINIGFDYYVQSVFGS	0	679.492	2714.2937	2714.2937	2714.2937
AYNAEARAGAVSSWRAFHYGNIYLG\0		740.5462	2958.416	2958.416	2958.416
KSALEKN	0	789.5235	788.4392	788.4392	788.4392

VQAKTYYG	1042.7036	522.3591	1042.5083	1042.5083	1042.5083
VVTILEYDP	1047.7202	524.8674	1047.5488	1047.5488	1047.5488
YREVKITGK	1092.7711	547.3928	1092.6292	1092.6292	1092.6292
QKIGALGQIIGG	1136.7982	569.4064	1136.6554	1136.6554	1136.6554
QKVTKLVDYGA	1220.8169	611.4157	1220.6765	1220.6765	1220.6765
GISATVFARGYK	1268.8757	635.4451	1268.6877	1268.6877	1268.6877
MSRIPENLEIKRKDIK	0	657.4479	1969.1143	1969.1143	1969.1143
RPGVVGLIGPNGAGK	0	696.5199	1390.8044	1390.8044	1390.8044
KLENQN	0	745.4967	744.3766	744.3766	744.3766
LYVCLFFTIYSGIDYFYQ	0	564.4414	2254.0696	2254.0696	2254.0696
HARVRGKISGT	1180.8232	591.4189	1180.6788	1180.6788	1180.6788
KTRILRGAAQL	1225.7719	613.8932	1225.7618	1225.7618	1225.7618
SSVQNTAKDNQKTEPSAQDVMSNK	0	652.492	2606.2241	2606.2241	2606.2241
GPKGELT	0	701.4703	700.3755	700.3755	700.3755
LPILIALYQ	1042.7036	522.3591	1042.6427	1042.6427	1042.6427
DLPTTTATKT	1047.7202	524.8674	1047.5448	1047.5448	1047.5448
QFLGYAGSAGNVVHPQWNSERN	0	608.4673	2430.1465	2430.1465	2430.1465
PTKDKKRS	958.6667	480.3406	958.556	958.556	958.556
HRVGAVVKQN	1106.7543	554.3844	1106.6309	1106.6309	1106.6309
GVSSSSDGDDEEVEDEQDQVE	0	564.4397	2253.8516	2253.8516	2253.8516
TPKVVKKAIAP	1150.7784	576.3965	1150.7438	1150.7438	1150.7438
LIFMSATFLN	1155.7327	578.8736	1155.5999	1155.5999	1155.5999
VVINVGVSQPGVV	1194.8035	598.409	1194.6973	1194.6973	1194.6973
PVIHFGDCILECYMNNELMAHGT	0	652.49	2606.1426	2606.1426	2606.1426
IENLTKAFI	1047.7185	524.8665	1047.5964	1047.5964	1047.5964
LEKKGKVVV	1062.7277	532.3711	1062.6437	1062.6437	1062.6437
VAIKAAMKAIP	1111.707	556.8608	1111.6787	1111.6787	1111.6787
LIKMIQQLVN	1198.8342	600.4244	1198.7108	1198.7108	1198.7108
KFILEKKN	1018.7021	510.3583	1018.6175	1018.6175	1018.6175
TTHPKIIS	1023.6569	512.8357	1023.6077	1023.6077	1023.6077
QIIVQLLQM	1067.6825	534.8485	1067.6049	1067.6049	1067.6049
TSMLATKNQN	1106.7543	554.3844	1106.5391	1106.5391	1106.5391
RLVAVLDVLN	1110.7841	556.3993	1110.6761	1110.6761	1110.6761
PAIAKKVVKPT	1150.7784	576.3965	1150.7438	1150.7438	1150.7438
RRALRVGITN	1154.8091	578.4118	1154.6996	1154.6996	1154.6996
VSPIVLIAVVF	1155.7333	578.8739	1155.7267	1155.7267	1155.7267
LKLLQQQSRS	1199.7551	600.8848	1199.6986	1199.6986	1199.6986
LIGATTRAGLLSA	1242.8618	622.4382	1242.7296	1242.7296	1242.7296
RQSLQGYE	979.6302	490.8224	979.4723	979.4723	979.4723
AVLSVLAARF	1045.7023	523.8584	1045.6284	1045.6284	1045.6284
EIKKAYRR	1062.7277	532.3711	1062.6298	1062.6298	1062.6298
TYKKAPFVGG	1066.7583	534.3864	1066.5812	1066.5812	1066.5812
ITVGKLLKLSN	1071.7142	536.8644	1071.6652	1071.6652	1071.6652
TPIEVLQR	1110.7841	556.3993	1110.651	1110.651	1110.651
RQVVTIKADS	1115.7408	558.8777	1115.6299	1115.6299	1115.6299
KSGLKNRVAS	1159.7643	580.8894	1159.6674	1159.6674	1159.6674
VVRKTIKD	0	958.655	957.5971	957.5971	957.5971

EELLARIRALLRRKKREVLSDTVQL	0	1002.681	3004.7986	3004.7986	3004.7986
AFRQQKPT	974.6763	488.3454	974.5298	974.5298	974.5298
QNKFIKEL	1018.7021	510.3583	1018.5811	1018.5811	1018.5811
HAVKKLKSL	1022.7335	512.374	1022.66	1022.66	1022.66
LVALVLAIVI	1022.7335	512.374	1022.7103	1022.7103	1022.7103
IKKENIGLN	1027.6887	514.8516	1027.6025	1027.6025	1027.6025
SQHLEFKKY	1049.7324	525.8735	1049.5658	1049.5658	1049.5658
TPIEVLQR	1110.7841	556.3993	1110.651	1110.651	1110.651
NVNLLDALKR	1154.8091	578.4118	1154.6771	1154.6771	1154.6771
LLKAGQER	0	914.6296	913.5345	913.5345	913.5345
VLARAIYN	0	919.5841	918.5287	918.5287	918.5287
LITQVLHR	978.7089	490.3617	978.5975	978.5975	978.5975
GLLASVLAGAL	983.6617	492.8381	983.6015	983.6015	983.6015
VIVHVAQQI	1005.7061	503.8603	1005.5971	1005.5971	1005.5971
ILGLIISLL	1066.7583	534.3864	1066.7366	1066.7366	1066.7366
DVKRNPVMV	1071.7142	536.8644	1071.5496	1071.5496	1071.5496
AVRLITSKMA	1088.744	545.3793	1088.6376	1088.6376	1088.6376
LLKKGVGVG	0	870.6021	869.5698	869.5698	869.5698
LLLPTGRMLWVYFHLWQLPK	0	875.5582	2623.4866	2623.4866	2623.4866
ALVALLRY	0	918.662	917.5698	917.5698	917.5698
RRFPTAKITLDDIEASWAGLRPLIAAN	0	962.6858	3846.929	3846.929	3846.929
VVKASTAFI	934.6815	468.348	934.5488	934.5488	934.5488
VLDPKNPAS	939.6371	470.8258	939.5026	939.5026	939.5026
VVKKAIAPVV	1022.7335	512.374	1022.6852	1022.6852	1022.6852
TALIDLHVF	1027.6887	514.8516	1027.5702	1027.5702	1027.5702
RNRQKHKAMIKQN	0	826.5786	1650.9213	1650.9213	1650.9213
LVPFIGRGLKLKHA	0	831.534	1661.0504	1661.0504	1661.0504
KINFKLNKTKIDLATANFSDFKLDLDM	0	874.6334	3494.7869	3494.7869	3494.7869
TGTEVVRGNELVLINNTKKAIALRH	2745.7642	916.262	2745.5613	2745.5613	2745.5613
LIGGHGPLIKGSDKVGYFRKLASEIL	0	923.6153	2767.575	2767.575	2767.575
IINKLKTREKKTVNFKQQLVKETN	0	967.6407	2899.697	2899.697	2899.697
HIIASPASA	978.7089	490.3617	978.5498	978.5498	978.5498
PQLPQRVF	983.6617	492.8381	983.5552	983.5552	983.5552
AIIVTGGKQY	1048.7477	525.3811	1048.5917	1048.5917	1048.5917
VHQLIKDGAL	1092.7712	547.3929	1092.6292	1092.6292	1092.6292
LRQTPLFNKKLAKQDFRWAPDIAKEL	0	782.5509	3125.7502	3125.7502	3125.7502
LKIDASVSVSNQYPFHSESYEFPTGDVL	0	830.6105	3318.572	3318.572	3318.572
VPDSLTSQVEQITRRAFDLEKVSAVNS	0	918.6625	3670.8591	3670.8591	3670.8591
IIASNRRN	900.5687	451.2916	900.4777	900.4777	900.4777
PVIQIGRAS	939.6371	470.8258	939.5502	939.5502	939.5502
LRQVWLPV	1009.6771	505.8458	1009.6073	1009.6073	1009.6073
AYYNLALLN	1053.7026	527.8586	1053.5494	1053.5494	1053.5494
NVALQSRHSS	1097.7264	549.8705	1097.5577	1097.5577	1097.5577
AKLFDFAALLRQF	0	791.5397	1580.9078	1580.9078	1580.9078
LKLSIFSVDISAFEPQGSTFDALKSYRFI	0	874.6378	3494.7722	3494.7722	3494.7722
LLANGVAMLHPVVWKVV	0	923.6168	1845.0698	1845.0698	1845.0698
YGGILVQNTSWRNVVPSLNN	2230.4124	744.4781	2230.1494	2230.1494	2230.1494

LFIYFFQKKGIKRRVIPWLVFLFIGPI	0	835.5649	3337.9988	3337.9988	3337.9988
GITPLYVWWDINKSKLIIFRSS	0	879.5876	2635.4526	2635.4526	2635.4526
LSLMITRLFDNKKNYQRRVTLFG	2755.7004	919.5741	2755.5208	2755.5208	2755.5208
VLPVINQVE	1009.6771	505.8458	1009.5808	1009.5808	1009.5808
LSAYRATVKKQIAQLQATDQFLAH	2700.7136	901.2451	2700.4712	2700.4712	2700.4712
QQTDPDANTMVALVYQNSLKCLY	0	654.5066	2614.2407	2614.2407	2614.2407
TVLAMILIWESIGVVSSWNI	2230.4124	744.4781	2230.2073	2230.2073	2230.2073
PLGLVLWIIAVIFGL	0	812.5966	1623.0164	1623.0164	1623.0164
EIYFPYVLMKPALFLAVIAGGVGTG	2568.6396	857.2205	2568.4065	2568.4065	2568.4065
LPVELLANIIANLAA	1534.0482	768.0314	1533.9131	1533.9131	1533.9131
ASKATIEPNVL	1141.7534	571.884	1141.6343	1141.6343	1141.6343
LIANAGLKRRKNN	1310.8889	656.4517	1310.7783	1310.7783	1310.7783
EPVSQPKKKTLLRVKSPYE	2226.4478	743.1565	2226.2737	2226.2737	2226.2737
ILPGTHTSSYTSSVSNDFGGLHSFILN\0		812.5981	3246.656	3246.656	3246.656
LLANILFAAILHVTSWNAFRLA	2568.6396	857.2205	2568.4216	2568.4216	2568.4216
NQATLPAVIK	1053.7026	527.8586	1053.6183	1053.6183	1053.6183
IGGLFKELKDKQKNLL	0	615.4361	1843.0931	1843.0931	1843.0931
LVVAVVGLLANGFS	1357.9431	679.9788	1357.797	1357.797	1357.797
TQIEVIIATLVVF	1444.9961	723.5053	1444.8541	1444.8541	1444.8541
LPVREGPKIKIVEG	1534.0482	768.0314	1533.9243	1533.9243	1533.9243
KVANIGVTSNVLF	1360.9702	681.4924	1360.7715	1360.7715	1360.7715
LLLLIIALEISF	1356.9437	679.4791	1356.8633	1356.8633	1356.8633
HKKTTAKKAS	1098.7379	550.3762	1098.651	1098.651	1098.651
KPGKYKSVSGIKN	1404.9968	703.5057	1404.8088	1404.8088	1404.8088
FMEM	0	279.1575	556.2025	556.2025	556.2025
LIIRFVTLKNP	1312.9175	657.466	1312.8231	1312.8231	1312.8231
SLLRPASLLTYK	1360.973	681.4938	1360.8079	1360.8079	1360.8079
FILE	0	261.146	520.2897	520.2897	520.2897
LISVLPPS	0	413.2614	824.5007	824.5007	824.5007
PSEKKLHQM	0	279.1563	1112.5648	1112.5648	1112.5648
ILIGILVGTIAGA	1322.8314	662.423	1322.8538	1322.8538	1322.8538
LAVLAVLTFTRSA	1360.973	681.4938	1360.8079	1360.8079	1360.8079
LLLTQIVISTIW	1398.9453	700.4799	1398.8486	1398.8486	1398.8486
GVKQIAPI	0	413.2604	824.512	824.512	824.512
YTKLAWRQN	1178.8125	590.4135	1178.6196	1178.6196	1178.6196
SLLGRVPGAGIAL	1222.838	612.4263	1222.7397	1222.7397	1222.7397
YPIKGRGGKGIK	1272.9232	637.4689	1272.7666	1272.7666	1272.7666
YLRKSLRR	1090.7583	546.3864	1090.6724	1090.6724	1090.6724
ILIAIILAITS	1139.738	570.8763	1139.7529	1139.7529	1139.7529
ILIPLLIGAALK	1233.8549	617.9347	1233.8424	1233.8424	1233.8424
IIPGAAIGKLLVVG	1319.8923	660.9534	1319.854	1319.854	1319.854
TIIATAKKMA	1046.7361	524.3753	1046.6158	1046.6158	1046.6158
AGILSGDQVIVR	1226.8658	614.4402	1226.6982	1226.6982	1226.6982
GVGLSLFDKVTLTRVLN	1831.2059	916.6102	1831.0568	1831.0568	1831.0568
KIPKLVKRN	1094.7906	548.4026	1094.7288	1094.7288	1094.7288
TLLTLFYR	1138.8154	570.415	1138.675	1138.675	1138.675
NKVLKAKEAQKLHVN	1875.2333	938.6239	1875.1167	1875.1167	1875.1167

MQMALGM	0	391.2804	780.3333	780.3333	780.3333
VPTVKKSHR	1050.7659	526.3902	1050.6298	1050.6298	1050.6298
NKKAPTKSKRKTATKT	1787.1841	894.5993	1787.0741	1787.0741	1787.0741
ILAIIFYAVVRTVVIY	1836.1606	919.0876	1836.0913	1836.0913	1836.0913
SELKGQKK	0	459.2974	916.5342	916.5342	916.5342
ILLYLILF	1006.7413	504.3779	1006.6467	1006.6467	1006.6467
YLNKLM	0	391.2789	780.4204	780.4204	780.4204
VIIGAAGYKIARHVPGLR	1890.2111	946.1128	1890.1316	1890.1316	1890.1316
NSGSGKTTLAQALQ	0	459.2975	1374.7103	1374.7103	1374.7103
ASARIAGASAVLLIVAILTPVQLQAFI	2705.6826	902.9015	2705.6208	2705.6208	2705.6208
LIIMFLIILPFIAL	1629.0825	815.5485	1629.0343	1629.0343	1629.0343
PIIRAVPNRLAVIISRHYNNLGA	2572.6008	858.5409	2572.4714	2572.4714	2572.4714
LKFNFKLADKFLSLAIKW	2068.3293	1035.172	2068.1873	2068.1873	2068.1873
GNQRLFRIGAKLLGANVPDLG	2208.417	737.1463	2208.249	2208.249	2208.249
GQLKVSSIIIGLLLVLVCLVVELG	2251.4368	751.4862	2251.3589	2251.3589	2251.3589
LIVVIGVVTTWLIQEHLILAA	2300.4209	767.8143	2300.3872	2300.3872	2300.3872
NLFPHLSVLQNITLAPTQLK	2246.4824	749.8347	2246.2788	2246.2788	2246.2788
QVLKLTASATDGIGVVYVDLQ	2290.5017	764.5078	2290.2419	2290.2419	2290.2419
LLNIPRRAVNLSGWVGAAGWFTYEIL	0	770.5927	3078.6443	3078.6443	3078.6443
IIVPRVESVIFTVGT	1629.0825	815.5485	1628.9502	1628.9502	1628.9502
LAGALPTALMAIIVDLVLGALE	2163.3828	722.1349	2163.2588	2163.2588	2163.2588
SKPVTTITVTSTERIPMVLL	2185.4238	729.4819	2185.2393	2185.2393	2185.2393
LAIMQVHRRKLRALQQN	2202.4534	735.1584	2202.3008	2202.3008	2202.3008
LIQGLGYTLSSVIALVFSTI	2207.4097	736.8105	2207.2817	2207.2817	2207.2817
FIVALIIGMILIAISGGHGKKT	2251.4368	751.4862	2251.3491	2251.3491	2251.3491
IINALGTSLVTIIPGLFLLIAGS	2295.4631	766.1617	2295.3818	2295.3818	2295.3818
ILAAVLLLAVLLSPFSFGLN	2070.3774	691.1331	2070.2493	2070.2493	2070.2493
IILLAKGANKKPDEPDIQL	2075.3325	692.7848	2075.199	2075.199	2075.199
VESIRSVPINLLKAHVLLN	2114.4006	705.8075	2114.2576	2114.2576	2114.2576
IFLLGLIIDVIGMFLLWGS	2119.3591	707.4603	2119.2156	2119.2156	2119.2156
LITTLALGVALSFTNGLTLKL	2158.427	720.483	2158.2976	2158.2976	2158.2976
LTILSGTVVVPFFKRLRAF	2163.3828	722.1349	2163.2932	2163.2932	2163.2932
IIDQLPAGRKPVVTKWLKKG	2246.4824	749.8347	2246.3628	2246.3628	2246.3628
QRELSLLTLPSLRRQLDS	2124.3203	709.1141	2124.2014	2124.2014	2124.2014
PKGIENVVYLIGAFGLLTVIS	2202.4534	735.1584	2202.2664	2202.2664	2202.2664
IILFFSGVQLLSIGIIGRYV	2207.4097	736.8105	2207.3081	2207.3081	2207.3081
ALIKVVTVFVFLAVGTLTIFG	2207.4097	736.8105	2207.3333	2207.3333	2207.3333
LPNALAAPLKLGVTSILGRFNA	2251.4368	751.4862	2251.3052	2251.3052	2251.3052
AVALLKRKNVAVKQIKFTD	2141.4014	1071.708	2141.3049	2141.3049	2141.3049
ILVDQIMPKNKPSRLFK	2026.3495	676.4571	2026.1761	2026.1761	2026.1761
MLLGIIVALHILFGFLVF	2031.3091	678.1103	2031.1995	2031.1995	2031.1995
KKLNKQKIIAGLSSVALFL	2070.3774	691.1331	2070.293	2070.293	2070.293
ATLGIIIFAFSIKTLQLI	2075.3325	692.7848	2075.2646	2075.2646	2075.2646
EIQPIGSGSIDPTTKVLFVGVG	2114.4006	705.8075	2114.126	2114.126	2114.126
VQAAPGPAGILAIILTSVGGGLGI	2158.427	720.483	2158.2725	2158.2725	2158.2725
GRQLLIGLLPILQWFRLQ	2163.3828	722.1349	2163.3044	2163.3044	2163.3044
IPPLGLILKKTNINKISNQ	2119.3591	707.4603	2119.2729	2119.2729	2119.2729

TLFGGLVGTILTKILLKSP	1970.2521	986.1333	1970.218	1970.218	1970.218
ELKLAIKKVNLIATVDE	2009.3215	1005.668	2009.2136	2009.2136	2009.2136
VLLFIALLPLMIGLLYGR	2014.2775	1008.146	2014.2417	2014.2417	2014.2417
GKEIEIAASKVPAFKPGKAL	2053.3474	1027.681	2053.1936	2053.1936	2053.1936
TLQNLPIKFLAILIVSY	2058.3035	1030.1591	2058.2493	2058.2493	2058.2493
TPKIKASKKVIKLAKQTT	1982.3236	661.7818	1982.2616	1982.2616	1982.2616
LIVLVYGTATVLALLMGSGP	1987.2795	663.4338	1987.1428	1987.1428	1987.1428
TPQRRVLVEYLIQKRN	2026.3495	676.4571	2026.1799	2026.1799	2026.1799
LLKGLITKNQKVAVGVRHG	2031.3091	678.1103	2031.2317	2031.2317	2031.2317
ARYTGKLSKELQKQAQKV	2075.3325	692.7848	2075.1851	2075.1851	2075.1851
AKATQLDPIIVRILVARGF	2080.2893	694.4371	2080.2522	2080.2522	2080.2522
PGKIKTQMIAMIFLLN	2114.4006	705.8075	2114.2537	2114.2537	2114.2537
ILKILGIVAVSGLVGPFI	1921.27	961.6423	1921.238	1921.238	1921.238
KKGPFVRNIIAGLSGPRR	1965.2959	983.6552	1965.1748	1965.1748	1965.1748
TLKQADQLITERWQTL	1943.2577	648.7598	1943.0476	1943.0476	1943.0476
LLVLHEQPNKQFRAVML	2036.2644	679.7621	2036.1241	2036.1241	2036.1241
KNKKRQRRHARIRS	1833.2198	917.6172	1833.1146	1833.1146	1833.1146
KNLKPQRQNKRALQR	1877.2461	939.6303	1877.1548	1877.1548	1877.1548
AGLVKSSAVKVLGNGKLN	1882.2031	942.1088	1882.1364	1882.1364	1882.1364
AGILGLGLVLLVVTQPHGI	1926.2247	964.1196	1926.1666	1926.1666	1926.1666
RLRFLRNKPLKRGVFA	1970.2521	986.1333	1970.2167	1970.2167	1970.2167
LILKEVDGRKLAAMVVA	2009.3215	1005.668	2009.2072	2009.2072	2009.2072
ALTVRPGSLAKPADFAAVKA	1982.3236	661.7818	1982.1313	1982.1313	1982.1313
RKGRKSKVSKSNAPALNF	1987.2795	663.4338	1987.1439	1987.1439	1987.1439
GPKLVEAIRKVPAGHS	1789.1942	895.6044	1789.0033	1789.0033	1789.0033
LWSAIPVTLVIGIGSILS	1838.1729	920.0937	1838.0917	1838.0917	1838.0917
KLAKELGVPVIALSQLSR	1921.27	961.6423	1921.1725	1921.1725	1921.1725
IIGFIGGIIGLVLEATRSR	1965.2959	983.6552	1965.1411	1965.1411	1965.1411
IKIDFQQELATAIQK	1745.1682	873.5914	1744.9723	1744.9723	1744.9723
SLSNIVLVAVASLGLILL	1794.1467	898.0806	1794.123	1794.123	1794.123
TPQMRPTKGVHLVDR	1833.2198	917.6172	1833.0043	1833.0043	1833.0043
SIPSLVLFKDGKAIEKV	1843.1296	922.5721	1843.0819	1843.0819	1843.0819
LPKKISRTVPVREAR	1877.2461	939.6303	1877.1687	1877.1687	1877.1687
ELKVIHTALLIYLIIM	1882.2031	942.1088	1882.1366	1882.1366	1882.1366
LLAFVMVITASLVSHVIN	1926.2247	964.1196	1926.1012	1926.1012	1926.1012
LSQQITLLIVLMITSKGI	1970.2521	986.1333	1970.1849	1970.1849	1970.1849
AKLTKALKVTYKGTTK	1750.123	876.0688	1750.0717	1750.0717	1750.0717
KVLFHGFELFKRR	1789.1942	895.6044	1789.0515	1789.0515	1789.0515
DLLIGVSKGTIKEAEKV	1799.1029	900.5587	1799.0404	1799.0404	1799.0404
LLVRSKTIATDLSVP	1838.1729	920.0937	1838.1241	1838.1241	1838.1241
IIGSVLALLFTSLGGLNT	1887.1539	944.5842	1887.1082	1887.1082	1887.1082
VKEYVLNQIDLIPHK	1921.27	961.6423	1921.1036	1921.1036	1921.1036
KNGSRRQLKIARQLQG	1965.2959	983.6552	1965.1708	1965.1708	1965.1708
VFFLISLIVILLRR	1701.1396	851.5771	1701.1069	1701.1069	1701.1069
KLVLTKGHKQRKTVA	1706.0973	854.0559	1706.0679	1706.0679	1706.0679
KLMLDVKGAVKKPGVY	1745.1682	873.5914	1745.0273	1745.0273	1745.0273
WSLIIGVIVIIILKNT	1794.1467	898.0806	1794.1383	1794.1383	1794.1383

ELKKITHLSLKKVPTV	1833.2198	917.6172	1833.1451	1833.1451	1833.1451
KAKTTTQKALKIVKSA	1843.1296	922.5721	1843.1619	1843.1619	1843.1619
KNKLTQFALKKNKAVF	1877.2461	939.6303	1877.1251	1877.1251	1877.1251
ILGYTAAKQFNTSRIIS	1882.2031	942.1088	1882.0313	1882.0313	1882.0313
YGGVHILLILATWL	1657.1167	829.5656	1657.0219	1657.0219	1657.0219
NIIALIQSKRHGISI	1662.071	832.0428	1661.994	1661.994	1661.994
VVILAFIAAVIGIEGPN	1711.0529	856.5337	1710.9921	1710.9921	1710.9921
PTYFVLLFIALLPLM	1750.123	876.0688	1750.0143	1750.0143	1750.0143
GFTFASLIGVILIVRLA	1789.1942	895.6044	1789.0865	1789.0865	1789.0865
SVYTNFKFKIILTLL	1799.1029	900.5587	1799.0597	1799.0597	1799.0597
WGGIKALLIASSISYIF	1838.1729	920.0937	1838.0342	1838.0342	1838.0342
IILVASAGASVAKADPM	1613.0889	807.5517	1612.8859	1612.8859	1612.8859
LLPPPLLKKWNVKR	1701.1396	851.5771	1701.0818	1701.0818	1701.0818
SVLLSIGAIGALVYFAL	1706.0973	854.0559	1706.0018	1706.0018	1706.0018
EALTKFLATFKGPVHS	1745.1682	873.5914	1744.9512	1744.9512	1744.9512
KNKVVKIRVRNGIIN	1750.123	876.0688	1750.1053	1750.1053	1750.1053
LIQQSPTNFLLLAKLG	1755.0782	878.5464	1755.0294	1755.0294	1755.0294
KILQLMGIGIALVTIVL	1794.1467	898.0806	1794.1416	1794.1416	1794.1416
QIKIRVPNQKKVQVR	1833.2198	917.6172	1833.1425	1833.1425	1833.1425

Prec z

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
0

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
3
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
0

0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0

0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
0

0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
3
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0

2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2

0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
3
2
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2

0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
2

2
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2

2
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
3
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
3
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0

3
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
3
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
3
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
0
2

0
0
0
3
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
2

0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
0

0
2
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
2

2
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
3
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
2

0
0
0
0
0
2
0
3
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
3
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
3
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
3
0

3
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
3
0
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
3
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
3
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
3
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2

2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0

0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0

0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2

2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0

0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
3
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
3
2
2
0

2
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
3
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2

2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
3
2
3
0
0
2
2
0

2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2

0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
3
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
3
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2

2
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
3
3
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
3
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2

3
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
3
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
3
2
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2

2
3
3
3
0
2
3
0
2
3
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
3
0
3
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
3
2
0
0
3
2
0

0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
3
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
3
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2

2
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
0

0
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
6

2
2
0
0
0
2
0
7
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
6
0
2

2
0
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0

2
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
2

0
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0

2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
0

0
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
0

0
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2

0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
3
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
3
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
3
2
2
2
2

0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2

0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
0

0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
0
0
2
0
2
2
0
0
2
2
0

0
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
3
0
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
2
2

2
0
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
2

0
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2

2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2

2
3
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
2
3
2
2
2
3

3
2
3
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
3
2
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
2
3
3
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
2
2
2
3
3

2
3
3
3
3
3
2
3
3
2
2
2
3
3
3
2
3
3
3
2
3
2
2
2
3
3
2
3
2
2
2
3
3
2
2
2
4
3
0
2
3
3
4
3
2
2
3
3
2
2

2
2
2
2
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
4
0
0
2
0
2
4
4
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
3
2
2
2
0
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2

2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
4
4
2
4
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
0
0
0
2
0
2
2
0
2
2
0
2
0
0
2
2
2
2

2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
3
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
3
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2

2
2
3
0
2
2
2
2
4
4
3
3
3
3
2
2
4
2
0
2
3
3
2
2
2
4
3
2
3
2
3
3
3
2
4
3
2
3
3
3
3
3
3
4
3
3
3
3
3

3
3
3
3
2
4
3
3
3
3
0
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
0
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
3
0
3
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
3
2
3
2
2
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
3
3
3

3
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
3
3
3
3
3
3
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
3

0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
0
0
0
0
2
0
0
2
0
0
0
0

0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
3
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
2
2
2
2
2
0
0
0
3

